

**The Political Economy of Indigenous Governance: The Ancient Kushite
Ethiopianist Framework and Oromo Leadership in East Africa.**

by

Deribie Mekonnen Demmeksa

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Abstract

This dissertation investigates the political economy of indigenous governance in Northeast Africa. It advances an Ancient Kushite Ethiopianist framework that centred on Oromo leadership, traditions, and institutions as a foundational system of political economy. It challenges the dominance of externally derived governance models and Abyssinian-centred historiography. It demonstrates that pre-colonial African governance, such as the Gadaa governance of the Oromo, embodied coherent principles of institutional organisation, accountability, and distributive ethics that warrant complete analytical treatment within political economy rather than confinement to political and cultural anthropology. The research is qualitative, historical, and interpretive. Methodologically, it combines analyses of texts, indigenous traditions and philosophies, archival and historiographic sources, oral histories, and comparative institutional analysis. Political economy theories, including decolonial, institutional, and moral theories, guide the study. The dissertation reconstructs the Oromo governance system, the Gada system, as a constitutional republican political order. The institutional features of the Gadaa System are analysed as stabilising mechanisms of the political economy. They regulated political authority, land use, conflict resolution, environmental protection, social welfare, and resource distribution. The findings demonstrate that both the Kushite Ethiopianist framework and the Oromo governance tradition articulate political and economic logics that prioritise social cohesion, limited power, and equitable resource allocation. They directly contradict assumptions that premodern African systems lacked institutional sophistication or economic rationality. The study also demonstrates that the late 19th-century state expansion in Ethiopia produced an internal settler-colonial order in southern Ethiopia that displaced indigenous Kushite institutions and entrenched centre-periphery asymmetries through institutional separations, extractive governance,

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historiographic distortions, and the denial of the multinational nature of the empire-cum modern state. The frameworks show that governance efficiency and equity in the African context emerged from institutions that bind authority to social obligation, distribute power across communities, and enforce accountability through the communal consent of the people at the grassroots level, rather than from centralisation or coercion. The dissertation finds that Oromo marginalisation is structurally embedded in the political economy of modern Ethiopia and advances a corrective framework by linking Oromo indigenous governance to institutional stability, equity, and democratic legitimacy, thereby restoring the Oromo to their historical position as heirs to the Kushite civilizational tradition. The dissertation proposes an Oromo-led, pluralist federal order as an indigenous constitutional order, as a viable alternative to unitary nationalism and political fragmentation. This study contributes to the decolonisation of governance theory. It expands debates on institutions, state formation, and development by reframing indigenous African governance, specifically Gadaa governance, as analytically central to political economy. It integrates historically rooted African institutional principles into contemporary governance discourse. It offers both scholarly clarity and a practical pathway to legitimacy and economic governance in Ethiopia, in particular, and across the Horn of Africa, in general.

Key words: Oromo, Ethiopia, Gada system, indigenous governance, political economy, historical institutionalism, moral economy, decolonial methodology, state formation, institutional displacement, historiography, Kushite Ethiopianist.

Declaration - Signature

I declare in lieu of an oath that I have written this doctoral thesis by myself, and that I did not use other sources or resources than stated for its preparation. I declare that I have clearly indicated all direct and indirect quotations, and that this thesis has not been submitted elsewhere for examination purposes or publication.

25.10.2025. Deripie M. Demmelaga

(Date / Name)

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We, the undersigned certify on behalf of the Academic Review Board that this dissertation satisfies the scope and quality of a doctoral thesis. This dissertation, completed under the guidance of Prof Dimitrios Koumparoulis has been successfully completed in January 2026.

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List of Abbreviations

BCE	Before Common/Current Era
CE	Common/Current Era
ELF	Eritrean Liberation Front
EPLF	Eritrean People's Liberation Front
EPRDF	Ethiopian Peoples' Revolutionary Democratic Front
EPRP	Ethiopian People's Revolutionary Party
ESM	Ethiopian Students' Movement
FDRE	Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia
NNPs	Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples
OLF	Oromo Liberation Front
OPDO	Oromo People's Democratic Organization
PMAC	Provisional Military Administrative Council
SNNP	Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples
TGE	Transitional Government of Ethiopia
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization

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Dedication

This work is lovingly dedicated to my beloved mother, Bedhasie Leta Lubie—a true hero in every sense. Her life was defined by resilience, integrity, and an unwavering commitment to the transformative power of education. Though we lost her earlier this year to cancer, her spirit continues to guide and inspire us daily.

As a mostly single-handed parent, she overcame extraordinary challenges to ensure that all her children received a quality education—an achievement nothing short of remarkable for a woman raising a family in a rural town in Ethiopia. Through sheer determination and sacrifice, she witnessed five of her children graduate with distinctions and honours, some on multiple occasions and multiple degrees. Even more impressively, she saw all her daughters attain college degrees—a rare and inspiring accomplishment in her context.

Her legacy is one of courage, vision, and quiet triumph. This work is a tribute to her enduring love, her sacrifices, and the powerful example she set. May it honour her memory and reflect the values she lived by.

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Chapter 1. Introduction and Methodology

Emperor Menelik II built Modern Ethiopia during the last decades of the 19th century (Adejumobi, 2007; Boahen, 1987; Bulatovich, 1897, 1993; Bulcha, 2005; Etefa, 2012; Hassen, 1990, 2002; Jalata, 1998, 2005, 2014; Melbaa, 1988; Vaughan, 2003; Baissa, 2004; Gidada, 2016; Gnamo, 2002; Legesse, 2006; Ta'a, 2004). It was built through a protracted military conquest that expanded the kingdom of Abyssinia by about threefold and established a new non-Western colonial order in East Africa. The kingdom claimed that the conquest was a reunification of the territories over which it had lost authority centuries ago. However, the conquered nations, nationalities, and peoples (NNPs) maintain that they had never been part of the kingdom's authority, and the conquest was, in fact, colonisation. These have divided Ethiopian historiography into two main theses: reunification and colonial. This dissertation ascribes to the latter thesis. The kingdom conquered independent NNPs and tried to extend Abyssinian-centred nationalism over them. The conquest incorporated around seventy of the recognised NNPs of the Ethiopian Federation. Since then, they have struggled to preserve their identity and to compete with nationalism. One has been Oromo nationalism, an overly broad form of Ethiopian nationalism.

Oromo nationalism and Abyssinian-centred Ethiopian nationalism are competing nationalisms in East Africa. Oromo nationalism was founded on Oromo history, language, Oromummaa (Oromo national identity), the Gadaa System (republican ethos), Oromo philosophical thinking, the ancient monotheistic belief (Waaqeffannaa) in one universal God (Waaqa), the claim that the Oromo are the ancient Kush (the true ancient Ethiopia), and the struggle of the nation to do away with Abyssinian settler colonisation (since the late 19th century). Oromo nationalism draws its roots from ancient Kush, Upper Egypt. It is an ancient Kushite, multilingual, multinational, and multicultural form of Ethiopian nationalism.

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Abyssinian-centred Ethiopian nationalism, on the other hand, is based on Abyssinian history, Geez-based languages, Habasha identity, Abyssinian monarchy, and the legend of the descent of its monarchs from King Solomon of Israel, Coptic Christianity, the religiously motivated claim that modern Ethiopia is the ancient Ethiopia of the Holy Bible, and the hoopla of the unification of former territories. It is an archaic form of Abyssinian nationalism that promotes a monolingual, mononational, and monocultural perspective in a truly multilingual, multinational, and multicultural state. It is Abyssinian Ethiopian nationalism. Yusuf (2009) argues, “Just like its Ethiopian counterpart, Oromo nation/nationalism is a modern, glocal [“simultaneous interplay of ‘global’ and ‘local’ forces”] creation” (p. 301). As such, “both nationalisms are in no fundamental way different from each other in terms of their logic; both have remained to be products of social engineering that specifically began to take place in the modern era and the context of globalisation” (Yusuf, 2009, p. 302). Both nationalisms draw from the emergence of a new order in East Africa in the late 19th century. For the former, “The [Abyssinian] occupation was a formative factor in the creation of Oromo nationalism out of the traditional Oromo culture” (Erich, 1994, p. 672). In other words, Oromo nationalism is “rooted in a common language and shared modes of thought and feeling, and which has been nurtured in shared colonial-style oppression” (Baxter, 1978, p. 295). The latter also began to take root at the end of the 19th century, following the Abyssinian conquest of the Oromo and other NNPs to its south, southeast, and southwest. Since then, it has been characterised by pugnacious nationalism, in which the rest of the NNPs of modern Ethiopia have continued to be absorbed forcefully and tactfully into this Amhara-centred nationalism. It was this nationalism that has been competing with Oromo nationalism antagonistically, particularly since the late 1960s.

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Since the institutionalisation of Abyssinian settler colonialism in Oromia, Oromo nationalism has been on the rise. The late 19th century marked a turning point for the Oromo nation. It was when the kingdom of Abyssinia, the Oromo, had been overwhelmed for over four centuries, primarily by the sheer power of firearms. That was the trigger for the rebuilding of stronger Oromo nationalism. However, Oromo nationalism took a well-thought-out shape more than half a century later, starting in the 1960s, following the global movement for national self-determination of nations. The 1960s marked the formal beginning of the struggle for the rights of Ethiopia's oppressed and marginalised nations, nationalities, and peoples. It was also a period when the oppressed and marginalised nations and nationalities asserted the multinational nature of the empire.

Successive governments have attempted, but failed, to suppress Oromo nationalism. Baxter (1978) argues that Oromo nationalism "can only be repressed by an extremely ruthless, strong and efficient state" (p. 295). However, no state or regime could repress it, however ruthless and robust they may have been. Neither the political and legal suppression of Oromo nationalism by the Imperial regime of Atse Haile Selassie I, nor the brutal military suppression of the Derg regime from 1974 to 1991, nor the systemic suppression by the EPRDF regime to date could produce the desired result. Successive unfriendly regimes have tried and failed. The growing multinationalism ultimately led to the abolition of the monarchy. After 1974, the socialist regime brutally quelled the emerging multi-nationalism. This led to a devastating civil war between the state and the armed nationalist groups. The latter's victory over the former in 1991 ushered in a new dawn of multinational Ethiopia. To this effect, the new Constitution formed the Ethiopian Federation, a multinational state, in 1995. The EPRDF regime, which has stifled the federation since its formation, has oppressed

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Oromo nationalism systemically by equating its development with the disintegration of the modern Ethiopian state. Despite these attempts, Oromo nationalism has continued to thrive.

The emergent field of Oromo Studies has documented that Ethiopian Studies often overlook significant aspects of the Oromo people's history, focusing almost exclusively on the history of Abyssinians (Amhara and Tigray) and their historic kings (Jalata, 1996, p. 95). Similarly, the state-sponsored "Ethiopian History" not only dismisses the plain recorded history of the Oromo but also distorts and undermines any historical facts or events related to the Oromo and other nations that were annexed to the kingdom of Abyssinia. It has fundamentally been the history of Abyssinian kings compiled by Abyssinian "Knowledge elites" (to use Professor Asafa Jalata's expression). However, it has become the "official" history of modern, multinational Ethiopia. Jalata (1996) summarises: "The Ethiopian knowledge elites, with the support of the Ethiopian state, produced 'official' history that completely denied a historical space for the Oromo and other colonised peoples" (p. 96).

The works under Oromo Studies have neither offered a unifying nor a visionary Oromo narrative, nor provided a well-informed framework for the progress of the Oromo nation in retaining modern Ethiopia as a true ancient Ethiopia. Some of the works are more concerned with the victimisation of the Oromo by Abyssinians and their Western collaborators since the late 19th century than with the victories of the Oromo nation prior to that, or the future of the Oromo nation in the 21st century and beyond. As a result, they provide no significant details on the 16th-century triumphs of the Oromo against both Christian and Muslim powers, and offer almost no detailed analysis of why the Oromo were successful. Additionally, they provide little insight into what might have motivated the Oromo to fight in the 16th century. Additionally, they offer no historical comparative analysis of the politico-legal systems of the Kingdom of Abyssinia and the republican government of

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the Oromo under the Gadaa Constitution. There is little emphasis on the political role of the culturally integrated northern Oromo in the kingdom of Abyssinia. This might be because they have diminished the role of the Oromo in the kingdom by portraying them in a much-victimised position. Due to this positioning, the Oromo, who have suffered from aggressive assimilation projects by the kingdom of Abyssinia for a century, have received extraordinarily little attention in available works.

Furthermore, the works focus on the Oromo in Ethiopia; only a few have included the Oromo of northern Kenya. However, they have all excluded the Oromo, who had been the ruling class since the 16th century, but are presently absorbed by other cultures in the African Great Lakes region. More importantly, many scholars have devoted more attention to recounting the traditional history of what happened, particularly after the mid-19th century, than to the political history of the Oromo that may have contributed to the events, especially in the context of the war-peace relationship with the Kingdom of Abyssinia. In short, none of them is comprehensive by itself. They neither provide a thorough account of the Oromo's perspectives based on historical precedents and the Oromo's political history, nor do they offer a visionary narrative for the ancient Ethiopians, the Kushite Oromo. They are far from advocating for the Oromo nation in the way that the Oromo should cherish that they are the genuine ancient Ethiopians and progress not only to the political centre of modern Ethiopia but also towards unifying the Kushite ancient Ethiopians of the Horn of Africa.

Problem Statement and the Research Gap

Problem Statement

The political, economic, cultural, and religious domination of the Abyssinians (Amhara and Tigre) since the late 19th century has denied the rest of the nations, nationalities, and peoples (NNPs) of modern Ethiopia the sense of equality and proprietorship

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of their country. Though they are the genuine ancient Ethiopians, the failed “Ethiopian History” portrays them as if they were second-class citizens. They still endure the faint effects of such long domination and relegation to second-class citizenship. Moreover, although they have called for and constituted “rectifying historical unjust relationships” in August 1995, the TPLF/EPRDF government has taken little action in practice since then. One of the most affected nations is the Oromo nation.

Even though the Oromo are the ancient Kush, the true ancient Ethiopians, and presently constitute the single largest nation of modern Ethiopia, by virtue of which they should be at the centre in every regard, their political marginalisation has continued, and the Oromo have remained in the political periphery. This is despite efforts by interested Oromo scholars to reshape the Oromo’s social, political, cultural, philosophical, and historical narratives. Outside of the failed “Ethiopian History” and the struggling “Ethiopian” Studies, the Oromo Studies have not yet provided a complete account of progressive perspectives or a visionary narrative for the Oromo. In other words, it has not yet produced a comprehensive socio-political and historical narrative that would restore to them the honour of being true ancient Ethiopians, hence, true modern Ethiopians. Since their conquest in the late 19th century by the Kingdom of Abyssinia, the Oromo have continued to enable the Abyssinian elites, both intentionally and unintentionally, to marginalise the Oromo nation and Oromia, the largest, richest, and centrally located economic backbone of the entire country, to the political periphery. The Oromo cannot afford to be marginalised or remain in the political periphery. The recent demands of Oromo youth, politicians, and scholars reflect this sentiment. It is high time for the Oromo to find their rightful place in modern Ethiopia by initiating a chain of necessary changes, particularly in the Horn of Africa region.

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Political change in Ethiopia is evident. The Oromo nation has begun to demand a change in Ethiopia's political order. This is mainly thanks to its educated and steadfast youth (Qeerroo and Qarree of Qubee generation), devoted Abbaa Gadaas and hayyuus, and some well-informed scholars and politicians. In addition, the heightened economic marginalisation of the Oromo in recent decades, both in urban and rural districts across Oromia, has reinforced the resolve of every Oromo. The grassroots movement of the Oromo nation for justice, equality, and equitable distribution of national resources, the struggle of Oromo opposition political organisations for the political centre, and the death-defying youth movement for change in Ethiopia's political order have matured. In unison with the Oromo youth, the OPDO, within the TPLF-dominated ruling EPRDF, has initiated an internal revolution that could destabilise the EPRDF. It has become clear that no force can stop the concerted struggle. It is, therefore, high time for the Oromo to assert that they are the true ancient Ethiopians and the legitimate nation to claim the political centre in modern Ethiopia.

In addition, as the largest Kushite nation, the Oromo have the sociological legitimacy to unite and lead the brotherly Kushite nations of the Horn of Africa region. These, however, would require the transformation of the old order, which, in turn, would require a review of political history and the development of a new narrative and new strategy. The endeavour should begin with an attempt to develop a unifying and visionary narrative of the Oromo that would connect the nation's political history with its future vision. Doing so would require a critical review of the socio-political history of the Oromo in Ethiopia and the Horn of Africa region, as well as an analytical generalisation and informed action recommendations. Such a review and analytical generalisation would support the development of an enhanced socio-political and historical narrative, which in turn would facilitate the peaceful and democratic

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promotion of the Oromo nation to the political centre in modern Ethiopia and the leadership of the Kushite nations in the Horn of Africa region.

Research Gap

This study addresses a foundational omission in political economy and development theory: the systematic marginalization of indigenous African governance institutions in analyzes of state formation, institutional performance, and distributive outcomes. Dominant analytical frameworks—from institutional economics and historical political economy to mainstream governance and development paradigms—privilege externally imposed state structures, elite bargains, and colonial legacies. These perspectives often treat indigenous systems as informal, pre-modern, or normatively irrelevant, thereby explaining governance failures across Africa primarily through the lenses of path dependence, extractive institutions, or weak state capacity. Such accounts neglect the historical displacement and suppression of viable indigenous constitutional orders that once structured authority, accountability, and resource distribution.

By reconstructing the Gadaa system as a functioning republican institution embedded within the broader Kushite political economy, this dissertation challenges the prevailing assumption that legitimacy, accountability, and institutional efficiency in Africa must derive from imported or Western-derived models. It demonstrates how indigenous systems like Gadaa historically governed collective decision-making, conflict resolution, and resource allocation—roles central to statecraft and development. Their systematic erasure during colonial and internal colonial projects produced enduring centre–periphery asymmetries, particularly evident in modern Ethiopia, where the marginalization of the Oromo is reframed not as a cultural or ethnic anomaly but as an institutional consequence of internal colonial state formation.

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Mainstream development theories, despite their influence, remain analytically constrained by Eurocentric assumptions about authority and institutional legitimacy. Institutional economics, as developed by North (1990) and later Acemoglu and Robinson (2012), offers the inclusive vs. extractive institutions dichotomy, yet reduces indigenous governance to informal residuals rather than recognizing them as structured constitutional systems. Historical political economy emphasizes elite bargains and path dependence (North, Wallis, & Weingast, 2009), but often overlooks how colonial encounters dismantled precolonial republican institutions. Similarly, human development and capability approaches (Sen, 1999) prioritize agency and welfare but lack a robust account of institutional authority. Governance reform paradigms, such as those promoted by the World Bank (Kaufmann, Kraay, & Mastruzzi, 2010), emphasize participation and decentralization but abstract these values from their indigenous historical roots. Even critical postcolonial theory, while exposing dominance and subjectivity (Mbembe, 2001), rarely provides institutional alternatives grounded in African political thought.

This dissertation advances political economy theory by reinserting indigenous governance systems—specifically the Oromo Gadaa—into the analytical center of state formation and development. In doing so, it transcends externalist and ahistorical biases, offering a historically grounded framework for rethinking governance, legitimacy, and development trajectories in Africa.

Worldview and Theoretical Foundation

Researchers follow specific worldviews or paradigms when designing and conducting research (Creswell & Plano Clark, 2005, p. 21). Four worldviews guide research undertakings: postpositive, social construction, pragmatic, and advocacy (Creswell, 2009).

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Accordingly, the study is interested in advocacy for the political promotion of the Oromo nation in Ethiopia and the Horn of Africa region.

Advocacy/participatory is an emerging philosophical worldview in qualitative research (Creswell, 2009, p. 9). It is, among other things, a political and empowerment issue, involving marginalisation, hegemony, and a change-oriented approach (Creswell, 2009, p. 9; Creswell & Plano Clark, 2005, pp. 22-23). It “holds that research inquiry needs to be intertwined with politics and a political agenda. Thus, the researcher contains an action agenda for reform.” (p. 9). In addition, it addresses critical social issues “such as empowerment, inequality, oppression, domination, suppression, and alienation” (p. 9). It focuses on the needs of the marginalised or disenfranchised part of society. In summary, advocacy research, among other approaches, aims to liberate people from constraints and address critical social issues. It involves initiating emancipatory and political deliberations to effect change and entails proposing an action agenda for this change (Wilkinson, 1998, cited in Creswell, 2009, p. 10).

The theoretical foundations of the dissertation are post-colonial theory (Gandhi, 2020; Ashcroft, 2017) and indigenous political theory (Legesse, 2006). The former is relevant because modern Ethiopia was built through the settler colonial conquest of the south, east, and west by the northern Abyssinia proper. The Ethiopian state represents an internal colonial structure (Holcomb & Ibssa, 1990; Jalata, 1996, 2010). As argued by Bulcha (2016), settler colonialism refutes the myth of Ethiopian exceptionalism. That also exposes the epistemic violence of Abyssinian-centred historiography against the Kushte nations (Bulcha, 2016). The indigenous political theory is illustrated through the Gadaa System. The Gadaa system is a democratic and republican government system that features a separation of powers, checks and balances, a limited term of office, vertical and horizontal separation of powers, and

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participatory and consensus-based governance (Legesse, 2006). The Gadaa System, compared to the Western democratic political theory, not only challenges Western narratives but also validates African republican traditions as viable democratic models of governance.

Aligned with centre-periphery analysis, which investigates why and how the Oromo, as a demographic majority and geographically centred, have been marginalised in modern Ethiopia, post-colonial and indigenous political theories produce an interrogative new socio-political and historical narrative. The new narrative, the Ancient Kushit Ethiopianist Narrative, restores the Oromo to the political centre, dismantles historiographic distortions, and offers a new unifying vision for Ethiopia, in particular, and for East Africa, in general.

Research Questions

The dissertation asks three “rational questions” of “historical interpretation,” as suggested by Popper (2013, p. 473). The overall intention of the researcher was not to answer “irrational and apparently factual” questions of a historicist: “Which way are we going? What, in essence, is the part that history has destined us to play?” but to answer, “rational questions” of “historical interpretation”: “What are we to choose as our most urgent problems, how did they arise, and along what roads may we proceed to solve them?” (Popper, 2013, p. 473). Taking these broad questions into the adapted advocacy worldview, the Horn of Africa Region, the Ethiopian state, and the Oromo nation, the three main questions of the dissertation were:

1. Who are the true Ethiopians—are the Oromo the heirs of ancient Kush?
2. How did Oromo marginalisation arise through historiographical distortion and political mechanisms?
3. What new narrative is needed to provide a unifying framework for Ethiopia and the East African region?

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Propositions:

In response, the dissertation advances the following propositions:

- The Oromo are indigenous to northeast Africa and are lineal descendants of the ancient Kushites, the true Ethiopians.
- The Gadaa system represents a constitutional republican democracy that predates and rivals Western models of democracy.
- The so-called “Oromo migrations” were not nomadic invasions but liberation struggles against Abyssinian and Muslim encroachment.
- Abyssinian Ethiopia is a late political construct that appropriated the name “Ethiopia” for religious legitimacy.
- Modern Ethiopia exists because the Oromo exist: Ethiopia is because the Oromo are.

Purpose and Aims of the Study

The study’s overall purpose is to challenge the socio-political problem of marginalisation of the Oromo nation in modern Ethiopia by advocating the democratic promotion of the Oromo to the political centre. In other words, it serves as an instrument of advocacy for the Oromo nation. To do so, it illuminates and elucidates, interprets, reinterprets, analyses and synthesises, and substantiates the existing data and information about the Oromo in the available written and oral literature to inaugurate a new beginning for the Oromo nation. The new beginning would be based on a new visionary narrative encompassing all the Kushite nations. It calls for a new political order that the Oromo would lead democratically in modern Ethiopia and the Horn of Africa.

The study, however, has ancillary purposes. These include:

1. to review the socio-political history of the Oromo nation,

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2. to illustrate that the Oromo are the ancient Ethiopians,
3. to explain that modern Ethiopia is because the Oromo are,
4. to illustrate why the Oromo nation is rightful to the political centre in modern Ethiopia,
5. to develop a new narrative of the Oromo nation, and
6. Offer start-up recommendations that could help the democratic progression of the Oromo from the political periphery to the political centre in the Ethiopian federation.

The study aims to advocate the peaceful and democratic rise of the Oromo nation to the socio-political centre in modern Ethiopia, in particular, and in the Horn of Africa in general.

Methodology

Research Design and Scope

The study is a qualitative case study conducted within the framework of an advocacy worldview. Case study research “has a practical versatility in its agnostic approach whereby ‘it is not assigned to a fixed ontological, epistemological or methodological position’” (Rosenberg and Yates, 2007, as cited in Harrison, Birks, Franklin, and Mills, 2017, Para. 16). However, case study research tends to be ontologically subjective and epistemologically constructivist.

A case study is a well-established method of inquiry in the social sciences (Thomas & Myers, 2015, p.53). Modern case studies originated in the field of natural sciences. The first case study was from astronomy, whose findings won astronomer Bell Burnell and her team a Nobel Prize, and the second was from paleoanthropology (Thomas, 2012). The methodological development of the last several decades has enabled case study research to

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evolve as a pragmatic and flexible research approach, making it a methodology of choice across many disciplines (Harrison et al., 2017). It has become a method of choice for investigating and understanding complex issues across various disciplines (Harrison et al., 2017, para. 1; Kohlbacher, 2005, para. 12).

Thomas and Myers (2015) suggest that a case study must have a subject, “a ‘practical, historical unity,’” and an object, “an analytical or theoretical framework” (p. 55). The object is “the means of interpreting it [the subject] or placing it in a context” (Wieviorka, 1992, quoted in Thomas and Myers, 2015, p. 58). In addition, the case study must also have a purpose, approach, methods, and process (pp. 58–63). Alternatives are available to the researcher to make choices at every level, from ‘Subject’ to ‘Process.’ Accordingly, the present study employed a case study design, as illustrated in Figure 1.

This study focuses on the Oromo nation (subject) in the Horn of Africa, specifically in modern Ethiopia. In other words, it was the case of the Oromo nation. Because the researcher was an Oromo and was familiar with the case of the Oromo in Ethiopia, it was “a local knowledge case” (Thomas & Myers, 2015, pp. 56-57). It is a unique, holistic case study of the Oromo nation. Case studies offer the “opportunity for a holistic view of a process” (Patton and Applbaum, 2003, cited in Kohlbacher, 2005, p. 75). The study, therefore, employed a case study design.

It was a problem-driven design. The research problem focused on three areas: (1) the socio-political history of the Oromo nation, (2) the marginalisation of the Oromo in modern Ethiopia, and (3) the lack of a unifying and visionary narrative and well-founded framework for the Oromo political renaissance. To address the specific research problems, proper ‘what’ and ‘how’ questions were posed. For example: (1) What socio-political history does the Oromo nation have in the Horn of Africa region in general and in modern Ethiopia in

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particular? (2) Why and how have the Oromo been marginalised in the social, political, and historical landscapes of modern Ethiopia? (3) What should be done to bring the Oromo nation and Oromia state to the centre stage of multinational Ethiopia? Case studies are the preferred research method that asks such questions (Thomas & Myers, 2015, pp. 7-8; Yin, 2009, p. 9).

The overall aim of the study was to understand and explain the socio-political dynamics that could be beneficial for the Oromo nation in modern Ethiopia. In other words, the research problem involved understanding, explaining, drawing inferences from, and, if possible, building hypotheses or theories related to dynamics. The nature of the research problem and the research questions that drove the need to illustrate or test the theories the problem called for case study research. It required an in-depth, multidisciplinary study, which could not be achieved using other designs and methods. It is known that “the distinctive need for case studies arises out of the desire to understand complex social phenomena” (Yin, 2003, quoted in Kohlbacher, 2005, Para. 14). In case study research, “inferences about the phenomenon of interest tend to be rich, detailed, and contextualised” (Bhattacharjee, 2012, p. 93), and “the ultimate goal of the case study is to uncover patterns, determine meanings, construct conclusions and build theory” (Patton and Appelbaum, 2003, quoted in Kohlbacher, 2005, Para. 29).

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Figure 1. Overview of the design of the study

The problem also guided the choice of methodology for the case study. In the explanation and correction of the five misunderstandings of case study research, Flyvbjerg (2006) remarks: “Good social science is problem-driven and not methodology driven in the sense that it employs those methods that, for a given problematic, best help answer the research questions at hand” (p. 242). In addition, Thomas (2012) emphasises:

Progress in these instances [the first two case studies mentioned above] and myriad others rests neither on deliberate attempts to follow the scientific method nor on adherence to some set of scientific precepts, far from it. Instead, progress rests on playing with ideas and the development of an explanatory narrative via the explication of the singular. (p. 36)

Nevertheless, whether stated explicitly or not, philosophical underpinnings, methodologies, and methods are necessary to guide the inquiry’s success effectively. Case study research tends to be ontologically subjective. Epistemologically, scholars of the case

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study method place the case study in the constructivist paradigm (Baxter & Jack, 2008, p. 545). The researcher employed the ‘atheoretical/configurative-ideographic’ case study design within this paradigm. Using historical parallels and centre-periphery approaches as a framework of analysis, the case study research allows better illustrations, explanations, interpretations, and reinterpretations.

As emphasised above, case study research is an in-depth and detailed examination of a particular subject (the case) within a rich context. It is “about viewing and studying something in its completeness, looking at it from many angles and attempting to understand the interconnectedness of the elements comprising it” (Thomas & Myers, 2015, p. 15). In addition, “the researcher’s perceptions and interpretations become part of the research and as a result, a subjective and interpretive orientation flows throughout the inquiry” (Creswell, 2014, cited in Harrison et al., 2017, Para. 19).

As is true for every research design, case study research (design and method) has strengths and weaknesses. The strengths of case study research design are many: It can be used both for building new theory and for testing existing theory; it allows continuous modification of research questions during the research process as may be necessary; it captures contextual data on social, cultural, and political factors that will enable better interpretations; and it allows the inclusion of perspectives of multiple participants and analysis at various levels (Bhattacharjee, 2012, pp. 40, 93). Similarly, the weaknesses of case study research include weak internal validity, subjectivity, limited generalizability of inferences (Bhattacharjee, 2012, p. 93), an ambitious attempt to tackle a vast subject or answer too many questions (Baxter & Jack, 2008, p. 546), and a lack of structure (Thomas & Myers, 2015, p. 1). Accordingly, the study benefits from the strengths and suffers from weaknesses.

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Measures recommended by Yin (1994, pp. 33-38) helped ensure the validity and reliability of the research. For construct validity, the introductory outline specified operational measures for the concepts that constituted the case study. It did so both within and outside the traditions of “Ethiopian History,” “Ethiopian Studies,” and Oromo Studies. In addition, the researcher consulted multiple sources of evidence that form a chain of evidence over an extended period. Nevertheless, in addition to the breadth of the study’s subject, the researcher’s subjective judgments guided most of the data collection. This was partly due to the study’s partial departure from earlier traditions. The fact that the case study focused on the Oromo (the subject) for which the study’s findings would be relevant, informs the study’s external validity. Given the nature of the research, which claims no causal relationship, little emphasis may be given to the internal validity of the study (Yin, 1994, pp. 33, 35); measures have been taken to ensure the internal validity (inference) of the study. Accordingly, the researcher followed an unstructured time series for analysis and built the explanations along the chronology of major historical events. These measures have allowed better phronesis and the convergence of evidence along the process. The reliability of the study may be satisfied partly by the replicable data (information) collection procedure, the case study protocol for collecting information, and the database developed for online information.

Scholars of the case study refer to it variably as both design and method, as methodology and method, and as methodology and strategy, as well as strategy and approach. Miles (2015) treats case studies as both a method and a methodology. Others make clear distinctions: “A case study is not a method but a research strategy” (Hartley, 2004; Titscher et al., 2000, cited in Kohlbacher, 2005, Para. 16). On the other hand, Gillham (2000) and Yin (2003), as cited in (Kohlbacher, 2005, Para. 16) consider case studies as a method. Lack of “definitional clarity” and mixed use of terminology by the scholars continued to be a source

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of confusion (Harrison et al., 2017, Para. 14). Thomas and Myers (2015) argue that a case study “is not a method in itself” but a “scaffold” within which the proper methods are applied (pp. 64-65). It precisely served that in this study.

Built into the “scaffold” were methods for document analysis, text analysis, comparison, historical narration, content analysis, and explanation building. The study interwove these methods with multiple techniques of qualitative analysis and narrative construction. Techniques such as ‘questioning and surprise,’ ‘serendipity,’ ‘spirit of inquisitiveness,’ ‘generality,’ ‘canonicity, breach, and counterfactual,’ ‘narrative diachronicity,’ ‘particularity,’ ‘context-sensitivity and negotiability,’ ‘analogy,’ and ‘intentional state entailment’ (Thomas and Myers (2015), formed the very inner structure. It was, therefore, a multi-method and multi-technique case study. Considering the subject, scope, and multidisciplinary nature of the study, as well as the detail and depth involved, the case study effectively served the purpose of the study.

The study method was informed by the up-to-date and professionally researched work, “The Anatomy of the Case Study” by Thomas & Myers (2015). This first publication required the researcher to revise the approach twice and proved an essential methodological guide for the study. This research relied very much on its “anatomy.” Although Thomas (2012) discussed it earlier, it borrowed the concept of “phronesis” from the authors of “Anatomy.”

Phronesis is one of the fundamental concepts in the study. Scholars have tried to define it slightly differently. Accordingly, it is practical reasoning (Thomas, 2012), “practical wisdom on how to address and act on social problems in a particular context” (Flyvbjerg, Landman, & Schram, 2012, p. 1); “practical and experience-based knowledge” (Miles, 2015, p. 314); “a sense or a tacit skill for doing the ethically practical rather than a kind of science”

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(Flyvbjerg, 2006, p. 372); and a “judgement made based on experience and without recourse to the external guide that theory provides putatively” (Thomas & Myers, 2015, p. 48).

The understanding of phronesis has remained relatively the same since the time of Aristotle. “In Aristotle’s words,” Flyvbjerg (2006) states, “phronesis is an intellectual virtue that is ‘reasoned, and capable of action about things that are good or bad for man’” (p. 371). In the Aristotelian tradition, it is referred to as “practical knowing and judgment that is context-dependent, based on experience and developed through practice” (Miles, 2015, p. 314). Phronesis is the most important of the three virtues of Aristotle (episteme, techne, phronesis) “because it is that activity by which instrumental rationality is balanced by value-rationality” (Flyvbjerg, 2006, p. 371). This study is understood as practical reasoning — based on experience, common sense, and mind-full reflection.

Another fundamental concept is abduction. Charles S. Peirce is credited with founding the abduction paradigm, a framework that balances the competition between induction and deduction. Reichertz (2009) and Ruiz Ruiz (2009) supply detailed elaboration on abduction. Reichertz (2009) considers it “a means of inferencing,” and “a logical inference” (Para. 7). Ruiz Ruiz (2009) defines it as “an inference in which the conclusion is a hypothesis” (Para. 51). Others describe it as ‘the development of an explanatory or theoretical idea’ (Hammersley, 2007 cited in Thomas and Myers, 2015, p. 45), as “reasoning to the best explanation” (Gery Shank, n. d., quoted in Fielding and Schreier, 2001, Para. 13), and as “reverse conditional inference” (Jøsang, 2008, p. 6). Menzies (1996) proposes abduction as “a framework for knowledge-level modelling” (p. 311).

Thomas and Myers (2015) argue that a social science inquiry “uses abduction and develops phronesis” rather than relying on induction and developing a theory (p. 3).

Phronesis is “practical reasoning, craft knowledge, or tacit knowing: the ability to see the

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right thing to do in the circumstances” (p. 31). It is also compared with ‘weak theory,’ a kind of theory, “key to good case study” (p. 123). Abduction is the “development of an explanatory or theoretical idea, often resulting from close examination of a particular case” (Hammersley, 2005, quoted in Thomas and Myers, 2015, p. 45). In other words, abduction generates a theoretical idea that could be a tentative theory (p. 46). The result of abduction is, however, practical reasoning (phronesis), not a theory (p. 46): “Phronesis is about understanding and behaviour in a particular situation” (p. 48). Furthermore, social science phronesis not only connects and enriches the experiences of the researcher and the audience but also serves as a means to arrive at the “effective truth” without theorising (Flyvbjerg, Landman and Schram, 2012, p. 4).

This study did not aim to generate a strong theory, nor was it founded on a specific theory. It was an “atheoretical” case study. It was an “atheoretical/configurative-ideographic” case study, an illustrative study that does not contribute to theory (George and Bennett, 2005, cited in Thomas and Myers, 2015, p. 59). This is because it was not meant to generate theory or based on one; it was configurative because it rearranged (reconfigured) the existing ideas and understandings; it was ‘ideographic’ — “from the Greek ‘idea’ meaning (unsurprisingly) ‘idea’ or ‘private,’ and gramma meaning ‘drawing’” (Thomas & Myers, 2015, p. 20) — because it drew “a picture” of ideas in a narrative.

Because of the very nature of social inquiries and the degeneration of theory that “has come to mean almost everything,” they argue, generalising is “unattainable,” and the reliability of any theory is “unachievable” in the process of induction (Thomas & Myers, 2015, p. 47). Khan and VanWynsberghe (2008) agree: “It is far easier, and more epistemologically sound, simply to give up on the idea of generalisation” (25). They suggest that, given the inherent limitation of theory in inductive qualitative case study research, the

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recognition presumption of variability makes phronesis preferable to theory. Thus, qualitative case study research should not rely heavily on theories that are “unattainable” and offer little support for generalisation to phronesis, which is practical, tentative, malleable, and corrigible in both interpretation and analysis (Thomas & Myers, 2015, p. 48).

Phronesis can be “based on a praxis-oriented epistemology” (Flyvbjerg, Landman, and Schram, 2012, p. 6). If phronesis is “de-coupled from the inductive frame of theoretical analysis,” it can still reach validation. However, it does so “through the connections and insights it offers between another’s experience and one’s own,” not through “body of theory or generalised” because it is the experience-based judgment that does not depend on theory (Thomas and Myers, 2015, pp. 48, 49).

The object of such a case study is primarily illustrative (Thomas & Myers, 2015, p. 61). Hence, this study could be described as an ‘illustrative case study.’

The study is based on the premise that the Kushites, who are presently represented mainly by the Oromo, were the true ancient Ethiopians, the original inhabitants of Ethiopia; nonetheless, they have been marginalised socially, culturally, linguistically, and economically in modern Ethiopia. This phronesis led to the very question at the centre of the advocacy worldview: “What should we do?” Flyvbjerg (2006, p. 379). Accordingly, the first intuition would be to improve the existing state of affairs.

The phronesis was conducted through an abductive process following an extensive review of available literature. The reviews revealed vital factors. The preliminary evaluation of the relevant literature for the period preceding the formation of modern Ethiopia showed that the Oromo nation and the kingdom of Abyssinia coexisted as a republic and a monarchy, respectively, for most of their history before the 19th century. This informed the existence of a historical parallel between the Gadaa government of the Oromo and the absolute monarchy

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of the Abyssinians. To analyse the review, the researcher aptly employed ‘historical parallels’ as an analytical framework (object). The preliminary review of literature after the formation of modern Ethiopia in the late 19th century revealed that Abyssinian elites had dominated. It marginalised the largest Kushite nation in many aspects. It also stated that the marginalisation of the Oromo has been at the centre of the entire body of Oromo Studies. The reviews from this period also showed that not only has a precise centre-periphery alignment existed in modern Ethiopia since its formation, but also that several scholars of Ethiopian and Oromo studies have used it as a research tool, albeit without formal and explicit acknowledgement, in their studies. These commands selected the ‘centre-periphery approach’ as the study’s analytical framework for the period.

Following the suggestion of Creswell (2009) to use literature “sparingly” at the beginning of qualitative research unless required by its design and that “a typical practice in dissertation writing is to advance an integrative review” (pp. 28, 29), the reviewed literature was used accordingly. Both objects of the study (historical parallel and centre-periphery approach) guided, together with the study’s purpose, not only the final review of the literature but also the selection of the research design, methodological choices, analysis, and reporting.

Data Sources

This study was based on secondary information and secondary sources, except for the part originating from the researcher’s subjective experiences, analysis, and synthesis. The sources of data (information) in this study, thus, include but not limited to (a) several centuries-long records of Abyssinian chroniclers, both as direct and as reported sources in other works, and some hagiography of its Church, (b) records of European missionaries, explorers, travelers, and diplomats who have visited the Horn of Africa region and had experienced the Oromo directly or indirectly, (c) an array of academic journal in the fields of

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history, sociology, and anthropology, (d) dissertations and thesis submitted to both Ethiopian and Western universities in the relevant fields, (e) relevant books and documents, and (f) analysis, synthesis, and interpretation of the researcher, all guided by lifetime experiences.

The selection of these sources and the collection of the data (information) from them, except the last, were guided by research questions and accessibility. The source materials were accessed from multiple sources. The books were obtained through the German, Norwegian, and Dutch interlibrary book loan systems between 2012 and 2017. The researcher also accessed dissertations, theses, and journal articles in print and online through the inter-library loan systems. During the researcher's stay in the Netherlands from fall 2015 to summer 2016, the Dutch inter-library book loan system facilitated access to relevant books from that country. The researcher also accessed some antique books, dissertations, theses, peer-reviewed journals, archival documents, antique maps, and digitised books from several online libraries, university repositories, books and journal publishing companies, research foundations, and other public and private academic and non-academic institutions. Online libraries, institutional and private collections, and the online collections of the General History of Africa (GHA) of UNESCO, for example, were beneficial sources of digitised e-journals. The researcher's subjective lifetime observations and experiences, as well as analysis of the cultural and socio-political situation of the Oromo in modern Ethiopia as an informed Oromo, were also part of the information in this study, however small.

An exceedingly small part of this work's information source drew from the researcher's subjective lived experiences. Born to an honoured Oromo father and mother, everything Oromo has always been close to the researcher's heart. The researcher had lived among the Oromo in Oromia, except for a few years spent in Gondar city and abroad in Germany, the USA, and Norway. The researcher remained connected to the highly politicised

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diaspora even during those years of absence. Oromo oral literature, culture, Gadaa System, Waaqeffannaa, and worldviews informed his ordinary life experiences, from birth to adulthood and maturity. This subjective experience of the last two and a half decades also includes political experiences.

The prolonged initiative-taking in the critical review of the so-called “Ethiopian History” by the researcher inspired a similar review of the socio-political history of the Oromo nation. The researcher started having a critical view of “Ethiopian history” from history lessons in high school and undergraduate Ethiopian History courses. There were multiple issues to grapple with in “Ethiopian history.” First, it was apparent that “Ethiopian history” referred to Abyssinian history, more specifically, the history of the political power of Abyssinian kings. It offers little about the history of the other kingdoms and independent states that constitute modern Ethiopia. Second, it was an obvious extension of far-fetched and religiously motivated mythology. Fictional religious propaganda has infiltrated even the actual incidents that the chroniclers have recorded.

In most cases, it is difficult to discern facts from fiction, mainly when the supernatural intervention is reported as part of the historical account. Furthermore, it is sometimes difficult to tell if the “history” is of the Church or the state, as they were united in action and function. Third, it was full of biased interpretations of what did happen, particularly during the 19th century, when alternative disinterested sources were readily available. The interpretation has been in the Abyssinian Church and the court elites’ monopolies. Most of these elites had little regard for anything other than glorifying the person of the king they chronicled (mostly their patrons), the Church they belonged to (the provider of their livelihood), and their adopted Semitic identity (their alleged reason why they believed they were the ‘chosen’ people of oriental origin). Fourth, a few religiously misguided and self-obsessed Christian elites have

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shaped the self-perception and the history of the Abyssinian and other peoples of modern Ethiopia in the wrong direction. With such realisations, the researcher had been involved in an extensive self-motivated critical review of “Ethiopian history,” particularly during the last ten years. As more and more records by disinterested Western historians, travellers, explorers, missionaries, colonial officers, etc., on East Africa in general and on the kingdom of Abyssinian-cum-Ethiopia, in particular, became easily accessible and the “official “Ethiopian history has started to fail, a critical review of the socio-political history of the Oromo became more interesting.

Some heated discussions and debates with political opponents, former colleagues, friends, and family members during the researcher’s stays in the USA, Germany, and Norway have helped add an extra dimension to understanding the Oromo situation. However, it left the researcher to wonder how the nation that had, among others, perfected the Oromo Democracy — the Gadaa System — centuries before the formation of the USA, had remained in the twilight region of political power for so long in modern Ethiopia.

The researcher’s cultural experiences have been shaped and reshaped by the constant struggle of the Oromo to regain aspects of their cultural competence after they had been victimised for over a century in modern Ethiopia. These ‘aspects of cultural competence’ are understood by the researcher as expounded by Soujanen (1992)

. The synthesis of the researcher’s subjective experiences has contributed to the understanding and analysis of the issues. However, they are an exceedingly small part of the information used in this study.

Analytical Approach

The analysis combines thematic, comparative, and interpretive approaches. Thematic analysis is used to identify recurring patterns related to authority, legitimacy, accountability,

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decentralisation, and resource governance across historical periods. Comparative analysis examines indigenous Oromo institutions alongside Abyssinian monarchical systems and modern state structures to illuminate contrasting political-economic logics. Interpretive analysis guides the reading of historical texts, allowing for reinterpretation of dominant narratives and the recovery of suppressed institutional meanings. Historical parallels and centre–periphery analysis serve as organising frameworks, enabling the study to trace how institutional displacement produced enduring political and economic asymmetries. The overall analytical orientation is abductive, aimed at generating context-sensitive explanations and practical reasoning rather than formal theory construction.

Significance of the Study

This dissertation advances a new historiographical narrative for the Oromo: the Ancient Kushite Ethiopianist narrative. Configurative and illustrative design, the study synthesises longstanding historical and political questions within a single, coherent framework. In doing so, it lays the foundation for socio-political realignment. It demands both reinterpretation and correction of the Oromo nation’s place in modern Ethiopia.

The dissertation also claims historiographic rectification. It illuminates the progress of the Oromo nation from the “political periphery” to the “political centre” in modern Ethiopia.

It draws on historical precedents to articulate a framework for their political progression. This framework contests the entrenched Abyssinian-centred historiography that has long been marginalised. It restores the Oromo nation to its role as both heirs to and agents of the Kushite nations.

The implications are far-reaching. A revised national self-conception may shift the Oromo from viewing themselves as a forcefully annexed and systematically excluded “periphery” of the Abyssinian empire to recognising themselves as rightful Ethiopians,

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central to the making and remaking of the state. Such a shift could also mark the beginning of a renewed Oromo leadership in uniting the Cushitic peoples of the Horn of Africa, reviving the cultural and political legacies of Ancient Ethiopia. In this way, the contracted and exclusivist Abyssinian Ethiopianness could be reoriented into an inclusive Ethiopia.

The study, therefore, affirms a broader claim that the continued integration, rather than fragmentation, is the viable path for multinational states like Ethiopia. Historical integration, regardless of its origins, serves collective interests best when past wrongs are addressed, democracy is institutionalised, and integration is pursued on pluralistic and participatory terms. In Ethiopia, this would require democratic leadership by the majority nation, the Oromo, who hold a decisive position in the preservation of the state itself.

Taken together, these contributions demonstrate that the Oromo are neither marginal nor peripheral to the broader Ethiopian society. They are foundational—central to Ethiopia’s past, indispensable to its present, and vital to its future.

The significance of the study can be outlined in five dimensions:

- **Historiographical Rectification** – It dismantles the fiction of a monolithic Christian Ethiopia and restores the Oromo to their rightful place as heirs of Kush.
- **Reconceptualisation** – It reinterprets the Gadaa system not as “tribal custom” but as a constitutional democracy predating modern Europe.
- **Sociological Realignment** – It challenges Abyssinian-centred identity and defines Ethiopia as historically and culturally Cushitic.
- **Political Blueprinting** – It offers a federated, pluralist model of governance rooted in indigenous institutions.

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- Epistemic Decolonisation develops a framework for contesting hegemonic knowledge production in Africa, showing how indigenous epistemologies can inform governance.

By integrating these contributions, the dissertation demonstrates that the Oromo are not marginal but central, not peripheral but foundational.

Original Contribution to Knowledge

This dissertation makes original contributions in the form of historical rectification, reconceptualisation, sociological realignment, political blueprint, and epistemic decolonisation. It exposes the constructed nature of “Ethiopian history” as an Abyssinian-centred political project. The dissertation advances the Ancient Kushite Ethiopianist Narrative as a new and unifying historiographical paradigm. It interprets the Gadaa System as a fully-fledged deliberative republican polity. It demonstrates that the Gadaa System predates Western constitutionalism in both socio-political logic and institutional sophistication. It reclaims Ethiopia as Cushitic in its civilisational and repositions the Oromo from the political periphery to the centre of the Ethiopian state. It articulates a model for Oromo-led democratic federalism in Ethiopia and extends this vision to the Kushite commonwealth across East Africa. It models a decolonial methodology for historiography. In doing so, it demonstrates how regaining marginalised indigenous narratives can inform post-colonial political reconstruction. These contributions fill a critical gap in both Ethiopian Studies and African political thought.

Limitations of the Study

The study has limitations. First, it is based entirely on secondary information. It is an interpretation, analysis, and synthesis of readily available information. As such, it reviews research and has little input of primary data (information). Second, a few important historical

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documents and recent study findings, which could have enriched the study, were not reviewed due to access constraints. For the same reason, information that could not be freely accessed has not been incorporated or consulted by secondary sources, including information from dependable but not peer-reviewed publications. Third, the study is regressive; it refers to the past and emphasises Abyssinian-Ethiopian nationalism more than Abyssinian-Ethiopian nationalism. The former is mainly because the study's purpose dictates a thorough examination of the past, and the study method is regressive. The latter is because multinationalism adheres to the colonial thesis that the formation of modern Ethiopia in the late 19th century is the animating force behind socio-political dynamism, particularly since the establishment of the Ethiopian federation under the present Constitution in 1995.

Organisational Dissertation

The dissertation is structured into six chapters. Chapter 1: Introduction and Methodology frames the problem of Oromo marginalisation, research questions, propositions, and methodology, and defines the scope, significance, and limitations of the study. Chapter 2: Historiography and Literature Review, reviews the construction of “Ethiopian history” as an Abyssinian-centred project, contrasts it with Oromo Studies, and identifies the gap that this dissertation fills through the Ancient Kushite Ethiopianist Narrative. Chapter 3: Sociological Realignment: The Oromo as Ancient Ethiopians, presents historical, linguistic, anthropological, and oral evidence establishing the Oromo as heirs of Kush and the true Ethiopians. Introduces Gadaa as the first constitutional democracy. Chapter 4: Historiographic Rectification: The Oromo Resistance Struggles and Influence in the Kingdom of Abyssinia, 1550s-1880s reinterprets the sixteenth–to seventeenth–century “migrations” as national liberation campaigns of the Oromo and explains the reasons for their successes. It also details the Oromo influence in the Kingdom of Abyssinia during the Yejju

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Dynasty (also known as the “Era of Princes”) from the 1750s to the 1850s. Chapter 5: Colonial Conquest of the Oromo and the Making of Modern Ethiopia examines the conquest of the Oromo under Menelik II and the subsequent processes that entrenched marginalisation of the Oromo and Abyssinian domination. Chapter 6: Conclusion – Toward a New Order in East Africa: The synthesis articulates the Kushite Ethiopianist narrative and offers recommendations for Oromo-led democratic federalism and a pan-Kushite renaissance.

Summary

This chapter introduced the study and its methodology. It highlighted competing nationalism and the Oromo question in Ethiopia. It presented the problem statement, the research question, the proposition, the purpose, the significance, the contribution, and the limitations of the study. It detailed the methodologies. It presented the worldview, the theoretical foundation, the design, the methodological approach, and the sources of the data. Accordingly, the study employed an advocacy worldview, a qualitative case study inquiry, and post-colonial and indigenous political theories as its theoretical framework. Accordingly, the study employed historical parallels and a centre-periphery approach as the framework of analysis, which also served as the object of the study. Within the frameworks, it employed techniques of explanation, interpretation, and reinterpretation of the consulted historical records. The study also employed techniques such as qualitative document analysis, text analysis, comparison, historical narration, content analysis, and explanation building as its predominant methods. The chapter also listed the guiding question, the sources of information about the study and the contribution of the study. Furthermore, it outlined the dissertation and the limitations and contributions of the study.

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Chapter 2. Historiography and Literature Review

Abyssinian-Centred Ethiopian Historiography

Misguided Claim of Abyssinian Historiography

The Christian Aksumite and Zagwean kingdoms, which formed in the northern part of modern Ethiopia, had always pushed the indigenous Oromo further south through many centuries. Some of the Oromo were forced to retreat further south due to the expansion of the invasive Aksumite military kingdom. The fall of the Aksumite kingdom and the takeover of Aksum city by the so-called “pagan Queen” resulted in the immigration of its people farther south into the heartland of the Oromo. There are almost no surviving historical records of the events that occurred between the Aksumite kingdom and the formation of the Zagwean Dynasty. However, legend has it that the religious elites of the kingdom were self-exiled to remote abyssees in Tegulet, in the present North Shewa Zone of Amhara State. After the Agew came to power in present-day Northern Ethiopia in the 10th century, the Zagwean kingdom followed the expansion policy of the Aksumite Empire with similar intent and vigour. It continued to expand further south into the Oromo country. The Zagweans might have contributed to the immigration of increasingly Christian Aksumites deep into the Oromo country.

Although there are no records of historical significance for the period from 550 to 1300 CE in Abyssinia (Delebo, 2007, p. 45), several pieces of evidence strongly support two claims: First, the Oromo are an indigenous people in the Horn of Africa (East Africa) region. Semitic people who arrived from across the Red Sea set up the trading city-state of Aksum among them. Second, the Aksumite kingdom expanded at the expense of assimilation and the Semitization of the Kushite peoples, as well as the voluntary or forced movement of the

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Oromo and other Cushitic peoples to the south, north, and southwest from the present northeastern Sudan, northern Ethiopia, and Eritrea regions.

The Oromo are an ancient Ethiopian people and the largest indigenous nation in East Africa. The Oromo may have had a significant influence on the use of the collective name for the ruling groups in the political administration of the Aksumite kingdom, as well as on the apparent generational pattern of power transfer every forty years during the Zagwean Dynasty. Archaeological evidence from Northern Kenya suggests that it is highly likely the Oromo perfected their Gadaa System around 300 BCE (Legesse, 2006). Since then, they have been practising and sharing it with other nations and peoples. However, Abyssinians have long claimed preposterously that the Oromo recently arrived from the south in the present central Ethiopia region. Regarding the alleged arrival time, there are some variations. It is necessary to highlight these alleged times of the “arrival” of the Oromo and present counterarguments based on Abyssinian religious and historical records, as well as some recent research.

Aleka Taye Gebremariam (1860-1924), a renowned self-educated Abyssinian historian who has written extensively on Oromo in the history of Ethiopia based on secondary sources, emphasised that the Oromo came to the northern highland region of present Ethiopia in the 10th century (Haile, 2002, pp. 171–172; Gidada, 2016, pp. 53–54). He maintained that the Oromo arrived in the kingdom during the reign of Mera Tekle Haimanot, the first king of the Zagwean Dynasty. He was in power just before the onset of the 40 years of “Zagwean Gadaa.” Aleka Taye mentioned that there was a recorded history that the Oromo arrived in Abyssinia during the reign of Atse Yeseshaq in 1404 Eth. C., maintained by his contemporary, Atsme Giorgis, unequivocally stated that the record was incorrect. He states, “But the correct time of ascendancy (arrival) of the [Oromo] to Ethiopia [Christian kingdom]

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was during the Zagwean Dynasty during the reign of Mera Tekle Haimanot on the tenth year of his reign, ca. 938 CE” (Haile, 2002, pp. 171–172). [Translation from Amharic]

Contrary to this assertion, some Abyssinians claim that the Oromo arrived in Abyssinia in the 16th century. This claim has been at the centre of Abyssinian historiography, also known as “Ethiopian History,” regarding the history of the Oromo in Ethiopia since the early 1960s, when the study of history began at Haile Selassie I University, now Addis Ababa University. This claim heavily relies on Abba Bahrey’s account. However, Abba Bahrey’s account does not imply that the Oromo were newcomers to the region. It implies that the Oromo originated from their country south of Shewa, the Abyssinian southern frontier of the time, and took over the kingdom in a brief period of only two Gadaa genealogical generations. However, the Abyssinian kingdom’s political and religious elites continued to interpret the account instrumentally as if the Oromo had “arrived” in the region from outside. Western scholars took words and such records from these Abyssinian elites and continued to craft speculative interpretations.

The misguided Abyssinian claim about the arrival of the Oromo in the northern part of modern Ethiopia, the then-Christian Kingdom of Abyssinia, was refuted only in the 16th century by some historians. One such scholar, Mohammed Hassen (1990), dismisses the claim on three grounds: inaccurate historical premises, the incorrect assertion that all Oromo were pastoralists, and the incorrect assertion that all Oromo live in one place. This dissertation presents detailed reasons for dismissing the flawed claim in the sections that follow.

Incongruous Assertions and Contradictions

There are numerous instances of historiographical violence planted and cultivated by learned Church chroniclers over many centuries (since the 16th century) in Abyssinian

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historiography that not only deny the Oromo their history, identity, and pioneering democratic form of government but also continue to perpetuate historical injustices and deep-rooted hostility and profanity. One such historical weed is the preposterous claim that the Oromo arrived in the Abyssinian territory in the 16th century. It is primarily based on the confusing yet straightforward statement by Abba Bahrey in 1593, where he claimed that the Oromo arrived from the west, defeated the armies of the kingdom, and destroyed his country (Haile, 2006). He referenced the 16th-century Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaigns of the Oromo against the kingdom to reclaim the land it had taken from them.

The claim entered yet another period of turn and twist when Aleka Taye Gebremariam (1860–1924) alleged, without any sensible clue, that the Oromo might have migrated from Asia and Madagascar. Atse Menelik II commissioned Taye to write the history of Ethiopia in the late 1890s (Zewde, 2002, p. 68). He was one of the Abyssinian Church historians who had served German Abyssinian-Ethiopianist Eugen Mittwoch in the mid-1890s, as Abba Gorgorios had served another German scholar, Hiob Ludolf, about three centuries earlier (Zewde, 2002, p. 68). Based on his background, acquaintance with a few European Abyssinian-Ethiopianists, and the purpose of his commission to write the history of the empire that had just been built, Aleka Taye could differ neither in understanding nor in purpose from his predecessor Abyssinian dabtaras, but perpetuated the absurd claim.

Even though studies have debunked the absurd claim, its faint reverberating echo is still present in the works of those who try to use it for political and hateful purposes. It is, thus, important to briefly review some counter-historical facts and illustrate the expansion of Christian and Islamic powers in the present north-central Ethiopian region, which the Oromo inhabited, and how this expansion ultimately led to the Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaign, *duula galaa*, of the Oromo in the 16th century.

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In the Abyssinian historical records, the earliest evidence available on the first encounter between the Oromo nation and Abyssinia comes from the records of Abyssinian court historian Aleka Taye Gebremariam. Gebremariam argued that the Oromo “arrived” immediately after establishing the Zagwean Dynasty in the 10th century (Haile, 2002, pp. 171–172). However, it is unknown whether their “arrival” was in peace or for war. However, the violent encounter between the Oromo and the state-sponsored Abyssinian Church in the early 13th century is recorded clearly in the hagiography of St. Tekle Haimanot. These early encounters, which took place in the region that would become the present North Shewa Zone of Oromia State, were probably defensive on the part of the Oromo, who resisted integration into the newly formed kingdom of Abyssinia. This resistance might have held the immediate expansion of the kingdom further south.

During the early decades of the 14th century CE, the Abyssinian kingdom started to expand aggressively further south to the Oromo heartland. Donham (2002), quoting Tadesse Tamirat (1972, one of the prominent authorities on Ethiopian medieval history and a renowned scholar of Ethiopian studies, explains that during the transition of power from the Zagwean Dynasty to the “Solomonic” Dynasty, the Abyssinians were able to occupy only a small strip of land in present-day north-central Oromia (p. 21). In one of the works by Tamirat, it is clear that the Christian kingdom of Abyssinia “only occupied a long and very narrow crescent running from the southern corner of Begemdir to the upper waters of the Mugar” during 1275-1300 (Tamirat, 1972, quoted in Donham, 2002, p. 21). This indicates that the Christian kingdom expanded into most of the north-central regions, the northern part of West Shewa, and the western part of North Shewa Zones of Oromia State during the 14th and 15th centuries.

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Highly regarded and canonised documents of the Abyssinian Church have cardinally recorded that the Oromo were not only living in the central region of the present Ethiopian federation (former southern Abyssinia) before the invasion of Ahmad Ibn Ibrahim Al-Ghazi (commonly known as Ahmad Gragh in Abyssinia) in the early 16th century, but had already influenced the kingdom in many ways. Among other things, they had influenced their sovereigns' faith and character. These records included the Hagiography of St. Tekle Haimanot, Fikare Eyesus, and Dirsane Raguel. (The details of these and other evidence shall be addressed under The Place of History of Oromo in the Horn of Africa.) They have been a complementary part of the faith for centuries.

According to the hagiography of the most respected 13th-century Abyssinian Church saints, St. Tekle Haimanot, the Oromo lived in northern Shewa, around Ittisa in the Aleltu district. The region was known as Asbo before the designation was narrowed to Debre Libanos. As it is today, the region was part of the Oromo country before St. Tekle Haimanot founded the Monastery of Debre Libanos. Tekle Haimanot occupied Asbo by waging war and extensively proselytising the sedentary Yaayyaa and Galaan Oromo. Hinew (2012, p. 86) has also mentioned this extensive evangelisation by St. Tekle Haimanot, one of the main conspirators in restoring the so-called Solomonic Dynasty.

In the early 15th century, Fikare Eyesus, one of the highly regarded alleged explications of Jesus to his mother Mary, mentions the Oromo in an unprecedented manner, whereby the Christians are scared away from entering into a sexual relationship with the Oromo and some other people. It alleges that the eternal fire of hell will be the place for the souls of Christians who enter a sexual relationship with the Oromo, among others. The book was written during the reign of Atse Tewodros I (r. 1411–1414). It was published in a modern format in the 1960s, following the Abyssinian Church's separation from its Coptic "mother."

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The Church has published it several times, and it has been an authorised prayer and reflection book of the Abyssinian Orthodox Church. However, only recently has the Church tried to distance itself from some of its contents apologetically.

Gedle Raguel explains that the very reason why God allowed the invasion of Christian Abyssinia by the Islamic army of Ahmad Gragn was that Atse Libne Dengle (r. 1508–1540) had forsaken the faith and canons of the Abyssinian Church and had started to follow the Oromo “pagan” culture and system (Delebo, 1989, p. 118). This occurred a few decades before the so-called start of the Oromo migration in the mid-16th century into Abyssinian territories, which has misled some historians into wrongly believing that the Oromo came into contact with the Abyssinian kingdom for the first time in the 16th century. The fact of the matter here is that in the early 16th century, the Abyssinian Church recorded that the Christian king had adopted the Oromo faith and culture. This took place before the invasion of Ahmad Gragn in the 1520s. This record also shows how compelling the Oromo religion was and how pervasive and influential the Oromo culture and the Oromo system (Gadaa System) were in the early 16th century. The strength of the influences is evident: The Christian sovereign of the kingdom of Abyssinia, who traditionally decorated themselves as the “Lion of Judah,” “Elect of God,” and “King of Kings,” abandoned the Christian faith and adopted the Oromo culture and system long before the time Abyssinian pseudo-historians claim that the Oromo first appeared in the kingdom.

In addition, the renowned Abyssinian historian Tekletsadek Mekuria has recorded that an Oromo leader by the name of Lalo defeated an Abyssinian leader by the name of Andreas using intelligence he had received from the Oromo of central Oromia (East Shewa) during the reign of Atse Amde Tsion (r. 1314–1344) in the early 14th century (Bokku, 2011, p. 40). This indicates that the Oromo were both present and politically competitive with the

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Abyssinian kingdom and could defeat the army of one of its kings two centuries before their alleged arrival in the kingdom.

In the 14th century, military expeditions of the kingdom of Abyssinia that were led into the present central Oromia by Atse Seyfe Ared (r. 1294–1295) and Atse Amde Tsion (r. 1314–1344) forced the Oromo to move their political and religious centres from Xuqqur Midir (or Northern Booranaa) to Odaa Nabee and Dawwaaro (Gidada, 2016, p. 63). Odaa Nabee and Dawwaaro were in the present territories east and south of Addis Ababa (Finfinnee), respectively. However, this move was within the Oromo territory, and the Oromo indeed returned to their ancient centre, Odaa Nabee, in the 16th century. Odaa Nabee had been the Gadaa centre of the Oromo from 1116–194 CE (2nd–12th century) (Haile, 2001, cited in Bokku, 2011, p. 40).

Towards the end of the 15th century, during Gadaa Jibbenaa (1490–1498), the Gadaa of the fathers of Gadaa Muudanaa (1530–1538), the Oromo had crossed the Wabi River (Haile, 2002, p. 81). Wabi is a river that starts from the northeast of the Gannale River in south-central Oromia. Formerly, it was known by this name in its upper course in the territory presently inhabited by the Guragie people in the northernmost region of the SNNP State. The Oromo crossed Wabi to resist the Abyssinian expansion because, in 1525, the latter's expedition had just reached the northern shore of Lake Zway (Reclus, 1890, p. 372). Lake Zway is located approximately one hundred kilometres south of the present-day North Shewa Zone of Amhara State, along the narrow stretch of the Rift Valley. The immediate region south of Abyssinia, including the country of the Tuulamaa Oromo west of the present North Shewa Zone of Amhara State, was probably the territory of an independent section of the Oromo where the Gadaa government was in full function.

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The historical evidence that the Abyssinian historical elites have long calculatedly undermined indicates that the Oromo were not only present in central Ethiopia during the early formation of the Abyssinian kingdom in the 13th century but also consistently present during the three centuries before the invasion of Abyssinia by Ahmad Gagn. In other words, they were present in north-central modern Ethiopia at least for several centuries before the start of the offensive-defensive campaigns of the Oromo in the 16th century. As discussed earlier, the general direction of the Oromo movement in the northeast and eastern African regions was from north to south, from the south of modern Egypt to the Great African Lakes region, passing through modern Sudan, Ethiopia, and Kenya. They had established themselves in northern modern Ethiopia before the kingdom of Aksum in the first century CE, a millennium earlier than the Abyssinian kingdom. The Oromo arrived, apparently from nowhere, according to Abyssinian pseudo-historians and church elites, in the 16th century in central modern Ethiopia. However, they had been there; some had already been incorporated culturally, linguistically, and religiously into the new kingdom. In contrast, others had continued to resist the cultural and political domination of the Amhara.

Testimony of Religious Records

Paradoxically, most of the evidence that contradicts the Abyssinian claim of the late arrival of the Oromo in the region comes from the records of its church, the Coptic Orthodox Church, which had enjoyed power, privileges, and a third of the kingdom's land from the 1270s to the 1970s. Several records of the State Church, written after the 13th century, however, indicate the presence of the Oromo in the political and administrative centre of Abyssinia right from the time of the kingdom's formation. From among these records, three canonised and highly regarded records of the Abyssinian Church, for example, have documented that the Oromo were present in Abyssinia Proper during the so-called restoration

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of the Solomonic Dynasty, aka the establishment of the kingdom of Abyssinia and had already influenced at least the faith, the culture, and system (of governance) of the kingdom before the invasion of Ahmad Gragn in the early 16th century.

First, the hagiography of St. Tekle Haimanot (1215–1313), the co-founder of the Abyssinian kingdom in the late 13th century, affirms that the Oromo lived in north Shewa around the monastery of Debre Libanos before it was founded in the late 13th century. The seventh Echege of the See of Tekle Haimanot, Yohannes Kema, wrote the hagiography (according to the introduction to its 1989 Eth. C. edition) during the reign of Atse Isaac (r. 1414-1429). It was written before the misguided Abyssinian claim of the latter part of the century would emerge. The unfounded claim could not erase the founded presence of the Oromo.

Second, the alleged explanation of Jesus to his mother, Mary, by Fikare Eyesus, was written in the early 15th century. He mentions the Oromo in the context of discouraging sexual relationships between them and the Christian Abyssinians. The alleged explication was written during the reign of Atse Tewodros I (r. 1411–1414) according to የ ኢሥራቱ ምዕት የ ብዕር ምርት 1000–2000 ዓመተ ምህረት (The Ten Centuries of Literary Production: 1000–2000 Eth. C., Part One) published in September 2006.

Third, Gedle Raguel explains that God allowed the invasion of the Christian Abyssinia by Ahmad Gragn because Atse Libne Dengle (r. 1508–1540) had forsaken the faith and canons of the Abyssinian Church and had started to follow the Oromo “pagan” culture and system (Delebo 1989, p. 118). This suggests that the Oromo religion, culture, and system (likely the Gadaa System) were more attractive and perhaps the dominant culture and system in early 16th-century Abyssinia. For their culture and religion to have attained such power over the Abyssinian monarch, the Oromo must have been a thriving community in present-

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day central Ethiopia for centuries before the reign of Atse Libne Dengel, or the Abyssinians must have been a minority or a new arrival in the region.

Historical Records and Documentary Evidence

Some historical evidence suggests that the Oromo were not only present in Shewa during and after the formation of the Abyssinian kingdom, but they were also politically competitive with it, and they were able to defeat some generals of its warrior kings, such as Amde Tsiyon. Tekletsadek Mekuria, for instance, has recorded that an Oromo leader, Lalo, defeated an Abyssinian leader, Andreas, during the reign of Amde Tsion (r. 1314–1344) using intelligence he had received from the Oromo of Shewa in the early 14th century (Bokku, 2011, p. 40). Based on the account that Atse Libne Dengle had been highly influenced by Oromo religion and culture, as recorded in, for example, Gedle Raguel and Chronicle of Atse Menelik II, Mekuria further elaborates that, during the Christian–Muslim war of the early 16th century, the Oromo were able to have political influence in the Abyssinian court (Gidada, 2016, p. 55). The historical record supports this account that during the reign of Atse Libne Dengle (r. 1508–1540), Dori Tullu (an Oromo and brother of the Atse Libne Dengle’s queen mother) and Bulla Dori (the son of Dori Tullu) were Oromo Bahra Nagashs—governors of present Eritrea (Ayana, 2016). Dori (Doorii) and Tullu (Tulluu) are unmistakable, typical Oromo names. This is corroborated by the records of Francesco Alvarez, a disinterested member of the Portuguese mission that arrived in Abyssinia in 1520. In this record, it is clear that the assimilated Oromo were already part of the political establishment of the region’s governorate, which would become the modern State of Eritrea, in the early 16th century. Alvarez states:

For in our times, which was a stay of six years [1520 to 1526], there were here four Barnagais [*Bahr Negash*] [Emphasis and square bracket in the original], that is to

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say, when we arrived Dori was Barnagais; he died, and at his death, the crown came to Bulla, his son, a youth of ten or twelve years of age, by order of Prester John. (Francisco Alvarez, 1961, 1881, quoted in Etefa, 2012, p. 3)

By the beginning of the 16th century, not only had most of the northern Oromo been converted to Christianity (Reclus, 1892, p. 197), but the Galaan Oromo of Shewa had also established a marital relationship with the family of Atse Gelawdewos (r. 1540–1559). The Chief of Galaan Oromo had married the aunt of the Atse, as reported by a Portuguese eyewitness, Bermudez (Gidada, 2016). Bermudez was the leader of the Portuguese soldiers whom Atse Gelawdewos assigned to defend the kingdom’s southern frontier at Dawwaro after Ahmad Gragh’s defeat in 1543 (Jones & Monroe, 1935, pp. 86–88). Such religious conversions and marital relationships must have resulted from the long-standing coexistence of the Abyssinians and the Oromo in Shewa.

Recently, historical records have been brought to light to clarify that the Oromo have continuously inhabited the central regions of the present-day Ethiopian Federation since time immemorial. Records such as the “ታሪክ ዘጋላ” (History of the Oromo) and የ መጫ የትውልድ ሐረግ (Genealogy of Maccaa) have highlighted the suppressed history of the Oromo and asserted the presence of the Oromo in the region before the beginning of the expansion of the Abyssinian kingdom to the south, southwest, and southeast. These records have been neglected for a long time because they challenge the established Abyssinian claim of the new arrival of the Oromo in the 16th century and the foundation of “Ethiopian History” as held by Abyssinian-Ethiopianists, including both Abyssinians and some Westerners.

Furthermore, if found valid, the allegedly newly discovered historical documents and the revisionist mix of myths and history may gradually alter some aspects of the “History of Ethiopia.” Alleged ancient Geez and Suba language documents that are said to have been

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discovered by Mariras Aman Belay in Jebel Nuba (Sudan) several decades ago, and books that are written by the alleged discoverer based mainly on the discoveries, are set to change the course of history. More supporting evidence could alter the history of the Oromo and that of the Abyssinian peoples, as well as the relationship between the Cushitic Oromo and the Semitic Amhara. A controversial book by Fikre Tolossa Jiksa, entitled የአሮሞ እና የአማራ እውነተኛው የዘር ምንጭ (The True Origin of the Oromo and Amhara), written with a purposeful and artful mix of myth and history, principally based on the alleged discoveries of Aman Belay, has caught the attention of historians and ordinary people by surprise. The book's impact on historically illiterate people is immense because it appeals to their desire to support lasting peace and historical reconciliation between the two major contending nations of the federation. The book, among others, claims that the Oromo and the Amhara are descendants of the same ancestry and have been living together since ancient times. (Because historical sources do not verify some of the claims in the book, and it is a mix of myth and fragments of actual history, this researcher has refrained from quoting from the book as a statement of fact in this work, but only as information. Instead, footnotes were made from the book to highlight alternative claims and assertions when necessary.)

Furthermore, from other sources, including mainly Oromo oral chronicles, scanty archaeological and cultural evidence, and some historical references in ancient records, it is now known that the Oromo lived in the Horn of Africa region for the whole of their history and thrived as a republican form of democratic polity at least since 400 BCE. They are indigenous peoples in East and Northeast Africa. Their expansion in antiquity was from the ancient Empire of Kush (Ancient Ethiopia) from central northeast to southeast and southwest, in contradiction to the Abyssinian contention that the Oromo expanded from south to north.

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Recent Research and Revisionist Studies

Recent research challenges the foundation of the Abyssinian historiography regarding the claim that the Oromo arrived in the 16th century and “migrated” from the south. Negaso Gidada, historian and former president of the Federal Democratic Republic of Ethiopia (1995–2001), points out in his doctoral research that was published in Amharic translation as የኦሮሞ ሕዝብ ታሪክ (History of the Oromo People) in 2016 that (in addition to other stories in the “ታሪክ ዘጋገላ” and “የመጫ የትውልድ ሐረግ”) the Oromo were present in central Ethiopia before the 16th century. According to Gidada (2016, pp. 54–64), the following are historical evidence for the existence of the Oromo in the region that the Abyssinians claim was a central territory of the kingdom of Abyssinia:

1. The repeated mention of some Oromo sub-moieties, junior moieties, and clans in the historical records from the time of the Zagwean Dynasty
2. The historical record by Tadesse Tamirat states that the Yaayyaa and Galaan Oromo were inhabitants of Shewa and were converted to Christianity during the early formation of the Abyssinian kingdom
3. The similarity of Oromo clans of Jidda, Weji or wej (Waayyu), and Genz (Ganjii) mentioned in the 13th and 14th-century historical records with the Jiddaa, Waayyuu, and Ganjii clans of Sayyoo Oromo of Qeellam
4. The fact that Qorke, the alleged goddess of the Yaayyaa and Galaan Oromo who lived in Shewa in the 13th century, is the name of the month according to the Oromo calendar (also an Oromo name for a particular species of antelope), in which the Oromo have been giving thanks to Waaqa to date

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5. The mention of many districts in Shewa and Wollo having Oromo names (Masaraa, Teessoo, Goraa, Ganamo, Gombo, Ganjii, Sanyimootii, Gunnuftuu, Gandawalloo, Salgan, Baddabayii, Galeeraa, Farsoo, etc.) on 15th-century maps

6. The mention of Oromo names (Doorii, Bulaa, Anuubitaa, Waraba, and Guutaa) in the early 16th-century historical records

7. The several historical records that narrate the involvement of the [Oromo] in the Abyssinian power struggle during the reigns of Atse Be'ede Mariam (r. 1468–1478) and beyond that, including the record that, after the death of the Atse, the Oromo destroyed the tomb of the Atse at the church of Atronus Mariam (Debre Libanos) and threw away the icon images of the church.

8. Abba Bahrey's account that the Melba (Gadaa Malbaa (1522–1530)) destroyed Gegn, Angot, and Amhara had started a war campaign against Begemeder, created before Ahmad Gragn's initial victory over Atse Libne Dengle in 1527, and

9. The recorded existence of the marital relationship between the Galaan Oromo in Shewa and the Abyssinian royal family, the latter had married the aunt of Atse Gelawdewos (r. 1540–1559), which was also confirmed by the Portuguese soldier Bermudez, who saw and reported that the Chief of the Galaan, who had married the aunt of the king, was hosting Atse Gelawdewos.

Gidada (2016), therefore, rightly concludes that the Oromo, particularly the Galaan Oromo, inhabited the then main centre of the kingdom of Abyssinia, Shewa, before the 16th century.

Besides, according to the book written by yet another anti-Oromo in the early 17th century) known as “ታሪክ ዚጋላ” (History of the Oromo), Gidada (2016) asserts:

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(1) The Oromo had been living in the central regions of present-day Ethiopia during the reign of Atse Amde Tsion (r. 1314–1344) (Gidada, 2016, p. 61)

(2) The Christian Abyssinian population and the Oromo were about the same during the reign of Atse Libne Dengle (p. 62)

(3) the movement of the Oromo within the region (and transfers of their politico-religious centres) from Xuqqur or Northern Booranaa to Dawwaro and then to Odaa Nabee was to flee from the military campaigns of Atse Seyfe Ared (r. 1294–1295) and Atse Amde Tsion I (r. 1314–1344) (p. 63)

(4) The typical call to the Gadaa Assembly is, “Koottu! Koottu! Dhufee!” (Come! Come! I have come!) was in use since the 14th century in Shewa and Dawwaro (pp. 64, 243), indicating that the Oromo were organised under the Gadaa System.

Gidada concludes that the population movement of the Oromo in the present regions of Ethiopia before the 16th century was from north to south rather than from south to north. This conclusion is supported by the long-standing claim in the oral literature of sections of the Gujji and Boorana Oromo that their origin in antiquity was from northern Ethiopia, from Gojjam in the northwest and from Raayyaa in the northeast (Ayana, 2016).

Suppressed and Neglected Records

The early 17th-century manuscript that Gidada (2016) refers to is entitled *History of the Galla [The Oromo], Vision of King Libne Dengle, and the Invasion of Gragn*. It is commonly known as the *Book of Agaya*. The manuscript’s author, certain Zamalakot, knew that he was used as an instrument against the Oromo. Atsme Giorgis quotes him confessing that he was forced by Atse Zedengle (r. 1603–1604) to write the manuscript (Talfa, 1987, p. 81).

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Understandably, the manuscript falls short of being a precise reflection of Oromo history. It was prepared primarily as propaganda against the Oromo based on fragments of their history. However, it has captured some truth about the history of the Oromo, their relations to the Abyssinian kingdom, and their way of life before the 16th century. Although the author was clearly an “anti-Oromo propagandist,” most of the content of this manuscript aligns closely with the history of the Oromo as preserved in the Oromo oral chronicles (Gidada, 2016, p. 66).

The Abyssinian political, religious, and historical elites, along with their sponging Western scholars, have long ignored and suppressed this manuscript. They treated it no differently from every record that asserts the Oromo, rather than the Abyssinians, were the indigenous people of the Horn of Africa region. This is because it contradicts the narrative they wanted to promote—the paradox of the Oromo’s arrival in the Abyssinian kingdom (now Amhara and Tigray states, and parts of central Shewa in Oromia) during the 16th century.

The “Newcomers” Narrative and Its Discontentment

Some Abyssinian “historians” and chroniclers, similar to the paradox of the origin of the Oromo, portrayed in the Abyssinian historiography the protracted offensive–defensive campaigns of the Oromo in the 16th and 17th centuries to reclaim their ancestral territory as if it were an Oromo “invasion” or “migration” or colonial expansion. Abba Bahrey and early 20th-century Abyssinian pseudo-historians have excused the Abyssinian kingdom for the humiliating defeat by the Oromo, suggesting that the Oromo benefited from the invasion of the kingdom by Ahmad Grag’s army in earlier decades, which allowed them to conquer the kingdom swiftly.

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The suggestion, however, contradicts historical elements. First, the offensive-defensive struggle of the Oromo was likely a continued struggle. The Oromo must have defended themselves, including against the expansion of the earlier Aksumite and the later Abyssinian kingdoms, throughout their history of inhabiting the present northern Ethiopia. Second, the offensive-defensive struggle that Bahrey witnessed might have started in the earlier century. Based on Bahrey's record, which confirms Gadaa Muudanaa (1530-1538) is the Gadaa of the sons of Gadaa Jibbenaa (1490–1498), it is highly likely that the Gadaa-based offensive defence of the Oromo started during the Gadaa of the fathers of Gadaa Jibbenaa (1450-1458). Third, as mentioned earlier, the Oromo self-defence did start before Ahmad Gagn. It preceded the invasion of the Kingdom of Abyssinia by Ahmed Gagn in 1529. It started during Gadaa Malbaa (1522-1530). Fourth, the Oromo defended themselves against the Abyssinian Christian kingdom and the expansion of Muslim Somali, Afar, Awsa, and other peoples of the Omo region. Fifth, the Oromo defensive and offensive campaigns were not a one-time phenomenon. It lasted centuries before and after the massive, protracted wars of the sixteenth century. During these centuries, the Oromo staged battles against the Abyssinian kingdom and fought its successive kings. Sixth, most of the Oromo offensive battles of the 16th century were fought against successive Atses of the Abyssinian kingdom after the latter had regained most of the territories it had lost to Ahmad Gagn between 1529 and 1543. The suggestion, therefore, stands only for the service of self-justification for the defeats.

In addition to the suggestion for self-justification, Abyssinian-Ethiopianist “historians” have continued to present the resistance of the Oromo against Abyssinian expansion as if it started only in the 16th century. The reason is apparent: fortifying the now-discredited claim that the Oromo arrived in the 16th century. According to the records by

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Bahrey and Atsme Giorgis, the Oromo conducted highly structured and well-organised defensive and offensive campaigns against the Christian kingdom from the 1530s to the 1590s (Talfa, 1987, Haile, 2002). Abba Bahrey documented, albeit briefly, sixty years of the history of the protracted war between the Oromo and Abyssinian kingdoms, which the latter had been constantly losing (Haile, 2002) Based on Bahrey's record and chronicles of later Abyssinian Atses, Atsme Giorgis attempted to write the marginal history of the northern Oromo, who had been integrated into the kingdom in Abyssinia Proper, vis-à-vis the kingdom of Abyssinia, which spanned almost four centuries. Both writers, though about four hundred years apart, presented the coordinated and organised defence of the Oromo as if it started afresh in the early 16th century, beginning during Gadaa Malbaa (1522–1530), at the time Abyssinian political and religious elites would like everyone to believe the Oromo arrived in central Ethiopia.

The fact that the Oromo were better known to their neighbours by their lower-level lineage names, and the fact that they had no kings but elected leaders, might have contributed to the wrong perception by their historical neighbours, who tend to claim that the Oromo neither existed as a nation nor had a central government. On the contrary, however, the Oromo have always been the largest nation in the region and have had a republican form of central government that allowed for extensive decentralisation of state power in the form of a loose federation, enabling regional and local self-government for the people. These regional and local self-governments were decentralised republican governments of Oromo lineage groups, typically comprising sub-moieties and junior sub-moieties for the former, and clans for the latter. The Oromo society was politically structured along lineage lines. Settlements of the Oromo were also determined by lineages, often extrapolated lineages. All lower-level lineages have a higher level of lineage. The highest of them all is Oromo, the national name.

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The Oromo nation was politically united under the Gadaa System. The uncodified constitution of the Gadaa System was the foundation of the Oromo polity and social structure. It formed the pan-Oromo minimalist republican Gadaa system of governance. The Oromo elected leaders served for eight years, and these leaders were governed by the council they formed. They were not monarchies where absolute kings controlled the polity. The utter ignorance of how the Oromo polity functioned and the pretence that a nation exists only under the rule of an absolute monarch must have bewildered the elites of their neighbours into making such an erroneous claim.

Narrative of Conquest and Victimisation

The Abyssinian rulers, particularly after colonising most of the peoples of the present Ethiopian Federation, were engaged in a massive project of erasing the histories and the cultural identities of the colonised nations and replacing them with their myths and legends, often inculcated with miracles and wonders, that they attributed to their Christian saints and “Solomonic” kings. Additionally, the bureaucracy of the monarchy overwhelmed the people with its complex and indecipherable language. Everything, including culture, language, history, customs, way of life, local communal institutions, trades, dress, and so on, that belonged to these peoples was labelled as inferior, backward, and so on. It became candidates for spontaneous replacement with Abyssinian, particularly Amharan, equivalents. Important places of Oromo worship, such as hilltops and headstreams, were taken over by Orthodox Church buildings, and designated areas for celebrating Epiphany were established, respectively. Church building emerged everywhere: a stark reminder of Jesuit missionaries’ observation of excessive Churches and monasteries in the Abyssinian Proper in the early 17th century, repeating itself in the “colony countries. Lobo (1887[2007]) had then observed: “No country in the world is so full of churches, monasteries, and ecclesiastics as Abyssinia; it is

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not possible to sing in one church or monastery without being heard by another, and perhaps by several” (p. 38). The immensely popular annual bonfire among these people was re-branded as Christian Meskel. The Gadaa System and its political institutions were banned. The Amharic language became a lingua franca of the new Abyssinian Empire. Christianity remained the state religion; the Coptic Orthodox Church remained a State Church and an inseparable part of the state structure. In fact, in the early 20th century, the head of the Abyssinian Church was a member of Atse Menelik II’s cabinet as Minister of Education (Zewde, 2002, p. 177). Considering the historical background and the bitterness of the Church and the priesthood against the Oromo culture, language, Gadaa System, Waaqeffannaa, and other values, one can imagine the power the Church could use to victimise the Oromo identity in collaboration with the equally antagonistic state from such a position.

In this process of substituting history and the deconstructive imposition of Abyssinian culture, the Oromo, who had been considered the archenemy of the Abyssinians for at least four centuries, became the primary victim. Oromo language and their annual Thanksgiving at Lakesides (Irreessa) were banned. Through lengthy, progressive attacks and the systematic transformation of Oromo culture and traditions into Christian traditions, the Abyssinian elites altered and adapted many Oromo festivals. The stolen Oromo festivals include Taboree (an annual festival for boys), Ilillii (a yearly festival for girls), Gubaa (a New Year bonfire), and Boorantichaa (a hilltop thanksgiving). Using Calque, “a highly advanced subtle technique that WAS/icoloniserscolonisers not only to misappropriate but also to dismantle the plausibility structures of the autochthonous society” (Birbirso & Gerba, 2016, p. 115), they appropriated to themselves in the name of Tabor (also known as Debre Tabor or Buhe), Enkutatash, Meskel, and Ginbot Lideta, respectively. They also adopted traditional Oromo

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dresses like Bullukkoo, Gaabii, Kutaa, and Nafaa–nafaa (from the Oromo phrase) for a thigh dress (nafaa–nafa). These are just a few examples of the cultural, religious, and traditional elements that the Oromo have undergone. Victimisation went further up to the total formal replacement of the very name “Oromo” by the misnomer “Galla” since Galla” is a white European invention for the Native Americans (Jalata, 1998, pp. 128–129). Abyssinians invented the misnomer, most likely by misusing an Oromo word, , and gradually made it carry layers of negative connotations for denigrating the Oromo for not being Christian and for being a consistently dissenting nation. The very purpose of Abyssinian political and religious elites insisting on using “Galla” instead of “Oromo” as an official designation of the Oromo after the subjugation of the Oromo in the late 19th century was to destroy the Oromo identity and hence its history, including the history of the genocide committed by their leaders during the war of conquest. They continued to do so even after some Western social scholars, explorers, geographers, and missionaries insisted that the people call themselves Oromo, not Ilma, and should be referred to accordingly.

Under Abyssinian imperial rule, the Oromo were denied their name and forced to adopt an alien identity through the instrument of a strange name, which they were not only required to accept but also present themselves as. By the early 20th century, some Oromo communities had reluctantly accepted this name, partly because they believed that Europe would no longer recognise them with a name other than the one that had been recorded in their records. This is clear from the appeal of the Western Oromo in 1936, sent to the British Foreign Office, requesting protection by the League of Nations during the Italian invasion under this name. The thirty-three (or seventy) Oromo chiefs who established the Western Oromo Confederacy were determined to be independent of the collapsing Imperial State and expressed their desire to be protectorate under the League of Nations (Adejumobi, 2007, p.

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112; Jalata, 2005, pp. 177-178; Patrick Gilkes, 1975 and Asafa Jalata, 1994, cited in Keller, 1995, p. 626; 1998, p. 118). This was part of their aspiration to become a member of the League of Nations, “based “on self-determination (Adejumobi, 2007, p. 112), as they were not yet occupied by Italy, which had then occupied Addis Ababa (Finfinnee) in May and had overrun most of the country, forcing them to use the pejorative name involuntarily. Some Oromo individuals in Shewa were also forced to adopt this name involuntarily. Such was the result of the suppression of the Oromo’s national identity. “Successive emperors beginning with Tewodros in 1855 up to Haile Selassie, with the support of their European and American collaborators, suppressed the Oromo national identity for over a century” (Keller, 1998, p. 117; Keller, 1995).

The victimisation of the Oromo since the late 19th century provided Abyssinian elites and church historians from within, as well as foreign travellers and missionaries from without, with the opportunity to write about the Oromo under this shared identity. The Abyssinian archives of every sort and the “Ethiopian History” have consequently become repositories of such records, as they could be considered authentic by the uninformed. However, even the chronicles of Abyssinian Atses, which are “regarded everywhere in Abyssinia as the supreme and final authority for the history of the country,” are “impossible to accept as historical documents in the true sense of the word” (Budge, 1928, p. ix). In a true sense of history, Abyssinia has none but a failed, shimmering pseudo-history.

The portrayal of Oromo in Abyssinian historiography, both by pseudo-historian monks and by their modern Abyssinian-Ethiopianist successor historians, has been far from representing the historical facts about the Oromo and serving historical justice to the nation. It has remained an inter-subjective agreement among Abyssinian and a few Euro–American historians. As such, the portrayal of the Oromo has remained religiously motivated and

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guided by Abyssinian settler-colonial interests. The result is a demonstrably biased version of the Oromo's history within the history of the kingdom of Abyssinia and as part of the modern "History of Ethiopia," both of which are now declared የከሸፈ ታሪክ, or "failed history," including by Abyssinian Ethiopianist Professor Mesfin Wolde Mariam.

Nonetheless, despite its biases, the works of medieval Abyssinian monks and their 19th- and 20th-century successors have remained among the foremost written records on the Oromo. The motive of writing as such (that they wrote the history of the Oromo as the history of their enemy, both in faith and politics) has now become apparent to an average reader and every related scholarship; these works complement the modern historiography of the Oromo. It only requires dusting off the undeserving elements and bringing the historical facts to the surface. This may take only the careful and rigorous effort of brushing away the prejudices and negative attitudes of the writers and focusing on the objective facts contained in the records. The instrumental interpretations of the purposefully biased records by Ethiopianist Abyssinian writers and some of their Western copyists, who not only heavily depended on such works but also to some extent shared the same motive and sentiment to the present day, may need the excellent effort of genuine historians, particularly interested historians, to expose them in academic dialogue. After brushing away prejudices and proving the actual historical facts, the same record may reconstruct a comprehensive history of the Oromo.

The Failed Inversion of History?

The Abyssinian inversion of the history of the Oromo in the Horn of Africa has failed miserably, leaving some indignities on the elites who have tried. To invert their own migration history into the Horn of Africa, the political and religious elites of the Abyssinian kingdom fabricated the notion of Oromo migration from south to north and created an

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epicentre for the Oromo nation in south-central Ethiopia to substantiate the theory (Lata, 1998, p. 132).

For the construction of the notion that would appear plausible to the uninformed Western historians and writers who resolutely copied the contrived stories in their writings, two rather “indisputable historical facts” were brushed aside from the annals of the history of the Abyssinian empire as recorded by Abyssinian-Ethiopianists (Ethiopists). These historical facts were, first, the fact that the city-state of Aksum, the presumed historic core of the Abyssinian kingdom, “started as a settlement of immigrants from Yemen” around 100 CE, and, second, “the inexorable southward expansion of these Semitic speakers” displacing indigenous peoples, including the Oromo (Lata, 1998, p. 135). Against these two historical facts, the Abyssinian religious and political elites created the legend of the establishment of the Solomonic Dynasty by the alleged legendary son of King Solomon of Israel and the Queen of Sheba in the 9th Century BCE, and the myth of Ethiopia, the first Ethiopian. They created so many more such myths, including the absurd fable that Jesus Christ had lived in Ethiopia before the start of his ministry in Israel, which is current among the unhinged circles of the clergy of the Orthodox Tewahdo Church.

Based on such legends and myths, Abyssinians have tried to invert history. It is well documented that the kingdom of Aksum was founded by refugees from southern Arabia who acquired a preponderating influence over the people among whom they had come to dwell. Nevertheless, they have always portrayed themselves as indigenous people, inverting their historically and archaeologically verified migration from southern Arabia. By fabricating the scheme of the “arrival” of Oromo from overseas and their “migration” from south to north in the 16th century, they have attempted to project their arrival to the northeast Africa region on the indigenous peoples, mainly the Oromo. Some of the Abyssinian religious elites have

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recorded in the Abyssinian pseudo-history that the Oromo suddenly arrived in the Horn of Africa in the 16th century, destroyed the existing records that show otherwise, and gave them a derogatory new name. These records have preserved the attempted inversion of history but have failed to serve the purpose. The failed attempt was explicitly intended to vilify the Oromo nation, which they found excelling in its socio-political, religious–ritual, and organisational aspects. The attempt was a deliberate effort of Abyssinian political and church elites to transpose part of their history. Additionally, they have attempted relentlessly to transpose their unquenchable southward expansion from Aksum over the past one and a half millennia into the Oromo country by portraying the Oromo as invaders who gradually took over their territory.

However, there is no doubt that the Oromo are not only one of the indigenous peoples in the Horn of Africa but also the trunk of the flourishing tree of the region’s indigenous peoples. In addition to the historical evidence discussed above, Darrel Barte’s testimony that “The [Oromo] were a very ancient race, the indigenous stock, perhaps on which most other peoples in this part of eastern Africa have been grafted” (Bartes, 1979, quoted in Lata, 1998, p. 133) stands out as one validation.

The so-called Oromo migration/invasion/expansion of the 16th century was a national liberation movement. It was a movement of legitimate self-defence, a liberation struggle, by the little-known republican Oromo nation. The Oromo heroes and their organised groups organised themselves according to their Gadaa System and Gadaa government, reclaimed part of their ancestral territories. The expansionist Abyssinian Christian kingdom and Islamic Sultanates had taken these territories from them in the present central Ethiopia regions through gradual expansion and the settlement of military colonies, and other peoples, such as the Somali, Afar, and some Omotic and Nilotic peoples, had also expanded into the

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Oromo countries. The continued pressure from the north and east forced the Oromo to migrate further south, into central East Africa and the Great African Lakes region.

The attempted inversion of history by Abyssinian religious and political elites has failed. It has been unable to do so historically. The whole foundation of the so-called Ethiopian History had shattered. Modern Ethiopia now has a ‘failed history.’ One can only hope that it will have its history tidied by removing the weeds and cancerous biases that have been built into it over a long time by Abyssinian self-important elites, and reflect the genuine, substantiated, and validated history of the nations, nationalities, and peoples of the multinational, multilingual, multicultural modern Ethiopia.

Distortions and Epistemic Violence in Abyssinian Narratives

From Resentment to Triumph

The Abyssinians have long sought to settle in Oromo country and have been doing so, albeit marginally, both before and after the 16th century. It had been the wish of the Abyssinians to take the resource-rich land of the Oromo since the time of the Aksumite kingdom in the first half of the first millennium CE. Since then, they have continued to expand into the Oromo country and the territories of other nations. The Abyssinian kingdom also expanded south to present central Ethiopia, the heartland of the Oromo. The decisive offensive defence of the Oromo during the 16th and 17th centuries drove back the Abyssinian expansionist kingdom and restored some of their ancestral territories. The northern Oromo of Yajjuu and Walloo, who had penetrated the kingdom farther north, not only acquired military superior organisational advantages over the Abyssinian kingdom but also ruled it from the Gondar palace from the 1760s to 1855, both as kings and by enthroning puppet kings. During this period, some Oromo territories in Shewa and Gojjam were incorporated into the Abyssinian domain.

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The Abyssinian kingdom succeeded in subjugating the Oromo of modern Ethiopia only in the last decade of the 19th century. It could do so with the help of European powers and the sheer number of European firearms. This temporarily satisfied their centuries-long yearning for Oromo land. They have massively settled in the Oromo country since the second half of the 19th century as *nafxanyaa*. Their presence is evident even in most cities and towns across Oromia, particularly in fertile rural areas, where they have maintained the old clusters of dotted settlements among the communities, which they once subjugated by taking away their land.

After the Abyssinians achieved supremacy, their treatment of the Oromo was bitter and vengeful. Their ultimate target was total and absolute domination. They settled the *nafxanyaa* (resident army at the service of the kingdom), who became masters of the land and the resources of the Oromo. As a means of escaping the repression by the feudal lords, becoming a soldier was the choice of the Amhara trade. Menelik II had no problem recruiting soldiers who would become *nafxanyaa* in hundreds of thousands from the impoverished northern part of his kingdom. He did not have difficulty remunerating them as they mostly lived on the peasants for their livelihood. Hence, he had them in a considerable number. In addition, ordinary Abyssinians settled on the rich land of the Oromo, moving further south in every direction from their partly desolate mountainous region in the north. They set up urban posts following the settlement of the *nafxanyaa*. With the sheer power of European arms, the Oromo became *Gabbar* and serfs on their own land and resources. The *Nafxanyaa* system merged the triple dominance of Abyssinian Semitic nationality, Orthodox Christianity, and the Amharic language in the person of the settler *Nafxanyaa* (Tibebu, 1995, p. 180). It instituted the *nafxanyaa-gabbar*, a benighted socio-economic system of Abyssinian total

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dominance in the Oromo country, which lasted until the late 1970s. This total domination was not enough.

The Abyssinians wanted to inflict further psychological and cultural injuries on the Oromo through the instrument of literary products. They portrayed the Oromo as naïve and backward; they described the Oromo language as “devil’s tongue.” They also described the Oromo culture as backward and uncultivated, even though “[t]he Oromo were and are a people with a highly developed, sophisticated culture admired by their neighbours” (Haberland, 1992, p. 717). They treated the Oromo as pagans. They even described them as savages or primitive cattle herders, a description equally mistaken as claiming they were newcomers and had an unsophisticated culture (Haberland, 1992, p. 716). They deliberately and systematically disparaged everything about the Oromo in their writings.

The learned political and religious elites worked on literary products, while the semi-literate Nafxanyaa relentlessly promoted and imposed upon the Oromo every aspect of Abyssinian religion, culture, tradition, and the mythical Abyssinian Christian Ethiopia-wine. The apparent target was to destroy the Oromo identity (Oromummaa) by attacking the psyche, culture, language, religion, and traditions of the Oromo (Jalata, 2014) to replace it with a subservient form of Abyssinian identity that recognises the Oromo nation and the Fatherland of the Oromo.

The literary violence of the Abyssinians towards the Oromo made the latter one of Africa’s most dishonestly labelled nations. “There are few ethnic groups in Africa about whose origins and culture so much that is untrue has been written” than the Oromo (Haberland, 1963; Legesse, 1973; Cerulli, 1922, cited in Haberland, 1992, p. 197).

Abyssinian dabtaras could not help but continue recording in their religious works, as well as their politically and religiously motivated hate for the Oromo, and almost all these “untrue”

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stories about the origin and culture of the Oromo. Abba Bahrey and Atsme Giorgis, who made clear at the very beginnings of their works their aversion for the Oromo (Budge, 1928, p. 603; Tafla, 1987, p. 79), are typical examples of these dabtaras. The few Western and Arab writers who have parroted the dabtaras have only served them as an instrument to carry the defamation, recorded in their respective languages. Most of the damage to the Oromo identity (culture, language, history, socio-political system), however, was the result of actions undertaken during the two decades before and after the turn of the 20th century, during the time the Oromo lost their independence. The Abyssinians instituted a form of Amhara-Tigre settler colony in their country.

The way Abyssinian dabtaras have described the Oromo is similar to how Roman religious historians wrote about the history of the people who had defeated them. One can read today how Attila and Hannibal, along with the armies they led, are despised in both religious and secular records of the Roman Empire. The manner in which Abyssinian secular and religious records portray the Oromo of the 16th century and their Luba leaders is remarkably like that of the Roman Empire. Among others, both labelled their victors as inhumane and civilised people to compensate themselves morally and psychologically for their humiliating defeat. As history teaches us, discrediting the victors has been a traditional coping mechanism for the defeated literary societies.

The differences are that the Abyssinians succeeded in subduing their victors and institutionalised their violations. The Abyssinian political elites and pseudo-historians, known as dabtaras, had the opportunity to retaliate verbally and systematically against the Abyssinian successive defeats, the deficit of natural resources, and the arrears of progressive political ideas and philosophies. In an arduous effort to humiliate and desecrate the great Oromo nation, the Abyssinian elites created an elaborate legend and uncanny claims. This

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was, first, to help legitimise the conquest of the Oromo, and second, to lay the foundation for the Abyssinians' totalitarian dominance once the Oromo had become part of the new empire. The Abyssinian elites also used the recording of their violation of the Oromo as a coping mechanism for their defeat and realisation of the humbleness of their political ideals. By then, the Oromo nation had proved itself as the origin of not only the ideal but also the full-fledged practice of the indigenous republican democratic system (the Gadaa System) many centuries before the emergence of a Western democracy after the American Revolution (1765–1783) and the French Revolution (1789–1799) in the late 18th century.

Acrimony, Prejudice and Malevolence

Abyssinian dabtaras, who have been entrusted with the recording and maintaining of both spiritual and temporal records, have always had a credibility problem. Reclus (1892) observes that “Abyssinians are usually very indifferent to religious matters,” and that disregard for truth has been a national characteristic of the Christian Abyssinians. Most of them are “far from zealous, and extremely ignorant of their tenets, [but] rigidly observe the outward form of their religion” pp. 154, 156, 158). The cream of Abyssinians were their religious and political elites. One group among these has been the dabtaras. Reclus's observation could not be more accurate outside of this group. However, they were the ones who recorded both the spiritual and historical records of the kingdom. Modern Abyssinian dabtaras have continued the old trade, though they command almost no trustworthiness.

The dabtaras recorded most of the Oromo's written “history” before the Abyssinian monarchy's abolition, good or bad. They formed “the best instructed and most influential class of the country” (Reclus, 1892, p. 158). However, as historians, Baykadagn argues, Abyssinian official chroniclers and clerical historians (i.e., dabtaras) lack the historical methodology to write authentic history because of three reasons (Gabra-Heywat Baykadagn

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cited in Zewde, 2002, p. 142): “They overlook the important and dwell over the inconsequential. They eschew impartiality and embrace bigotry. Their style [of writing] is so confused that it only confounds the reader.” The dabtaras always had a unitary Christian outlook, pillaged with miracles, myths, and legends. Being “the most instructed,” the dabtaras recorded the “history” of Oromo, starting mainly from the 16th century and connecting it to the history of the kingdom of Abyssinia or its Church. Dabtaras first wrote the modern history of Abyssinia/Ethiopia, which has never been free from religious and political indoctrination.

The dabtaras transformed their thoughts of bitterness and vengefulness about the Oromo into their pseudo-historical writing. They, in general, viewed the people who did not adhere to their God and did not prostrate to their kings or had no Christian kings of their own outrightly as “pagan” and as an enemy both to their faith and their kingdom. The Oromo had been the primary target of this view. The ancient monotheistic religion of the Oromo, which probably predates the Abrahamic monotheism that had not only remained theologically impregnable but also had attracted some Abyssinian Christians who almost equally professed both religions—a fact that has continued to anger the Orthodox priests even to date—was the main driver of the dabtaras to attack the Oromo the most. In addition, they harboured bitterness that the non-Christian Waaqeffataa Oromo, with no master or king but organised under their elected Gadaa leaders in their republican government, had defeated their Abyssinian Christian kingdom for centuries. The Abyssinian clergy and political elites generally viewed the Oromo as the enemy of their kingdom and their Church, which, until very recently, were inseparable. These Abyssinian priests and dabtaras and their associate political elites have always been filled with revulsion against the Oromo, whom they had collectively classified as “pagan” or as Muslims. Their perceptions of the Oromo, in general,

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had been guided by thoughts of bitterness and vengefulness from the beginning of the 16th century to the end of the 19th century, when the kingdom of Abyssinia finally subjugated the Oromo. After the Abyssinian military conquest of the Oromo, Abyssinian dabtaras found no better time to turn their thoughts of bitterness and vengefulness into a literary attack against the Oromo in the form of history.

Similarly, “never in history was an Abyssinian Orthodox priest preached love, equality, respect, but hatred, ethnocentric stereotypes against ‘pagan’” (Birbirso, 2013a, p. 30). The animosity, hatred, and ethnocentrism of the priests, too, have been part and parcel of the recorded history of the Oromo in Abyssinian/Ethiopian historiography, a “historiography notoriously known for fabricating and perpetuating fairytales and legends as ‘true history’” (Birbirso, 2013a, p. 31).

If uppity Abyssinian elites could find one good reason for their hatred towards the Oromo nation since the 16th century, it could be their lowliness. The Oromo victories over both the Christian and Islamic armies, the greatness of their political, social, economic, cultural, and religious ideals, and their country’s endowment with natural resources had made the Oromo a force no one could dare to reckon with for centuries. These had instilled a profound sense of humility within Abyssinian society and a fiery hatred among its elites towards the Oromo’s self-identification with their greatness in the mid-16th century. They had to bear the self-imposed burden of hatred for three centuries. After they finally achieved total supremacy over the Oromo in the late 19th century, with the power of European firearms, the Abyssinian political and religious elites only let out the long-held bitterness of their hearts and the vengefulness of their actions on the “subject” both in shedding blood and in writing.

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In general, the history of the Oromo (or any piece of transcription for that matter), which the Abyssinian priests and dabtaras have written, has always been some accumulated thoughts of bitterness and vengefulness that finally spilt on paper: It has been a history written by the enemy. The dabtaras started to record “historical” accounts about the Oromo in the late 16th century when the Oromo had reclaimed their territories in present-day central Ethiopia through their protracted offensive-defensive campaign against the ever-expanding Abyssinian kingdom.

Collective Attitude of Abyssinian Writers

The earliest first-hand detailed historical record about the Oromo by an Abyssinian-specialised monk (dabtara) is the work of Abba Bahrey. Bahrey wrote a brief history of the Gadaa-based offensive-defensive military campaign of the Oromo (duula galaa) in order to rationalise the successive defeats of his kingdom by the Oromo over many decades and to advise his sovereign on how to defeat them. Bahrey recorded approximately seventy-one years of the history of the Duula Galaa of the Oromo (from 1522 to 1593) with a relatively lower level of violent prejudices and less blunt hostility compared to some later Abyssinian church historians. He, however, attacked the Oromo with fresh verbal vitriol and some acrimonious commentaries. He presented them as monsters. His overall personal intention was unmistakable: avenging the historic disparaging defeat of the Abyssinian kingdom at the hands of the Oromo by writing about how “bad” the Oromo were.

Bahrey was a learned but hateful and self-righteous man who considered himself a prophet. He believed that he lived to write the reality of his prophecy of the destruction of Christians and their kingdom in the hands of the people he considered pagans and cruel enemies of Christians. Though a few centuries later, disregard of truth was found to be one of the national vices of Abyssinians (Reclus, 1892, p. 154); about himself, Bahrey wrote:

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In those days, the author of this work spoke prophecy, saying: ‘I am afraid of the killer of Fasil [a Christian governor]’ because he has tasted the blood of a Christian. ... As he prophesied, it has happened because the spirit of prophecy has not departed from the priesthood. Dawwe [Jaawwii Oromo] chased away this prophet, destroyed his country of Gamo, and looted all his properties. (Haile, 2002, pp. 79–80) [Translation from Amharic]

It can be said that all of Bahrey’s successors followed his self-presentation and purpose, except with more bitterness. They continued to maintain their attitude towards the Oromo. One such work of a contemporary of Bahrey stands out. Five years after Bahrey’s work, related work appeared during the reign of Atse Zedengle (r. 1603–1604). Oromo’s legendary “history” comes from a scribe who dared to write that his Abyssinian king forced him to write blasphemously about the Oromo. In the history of Abyssinian writers, only a few were brave enough to note in their writing that they were forced by their sponsors (patrons) to write the way they wrote. The pejorative legend and systematic intrigue were recorded in the storybook “History of the Galla [the Oromo],” “Vision of King Libne Dengle,” and the “Invasion of Gagn.” It is commonly known as the Book of Agaya among the Abyssinian elites, psychologically trapped in unfounded hatred and animosity. It was named after the woman who presented the work to Atse Susenyos. The author, Zamalakot, as Atsme Giorgis quoted, confessed, “We did not write it voluntarily; Atse Zedengle compelled us to write it” (Talfa, 1987, p. 81). If Bahrey’s book was written during the reign of Atse Zedengle (r. 1603–04), as suggested by Gusarova (2009, pp. 1326, 1328), he too could have been commissioned by the Atse. Zamalakot’s work is fictional and is based on the account of the Oromo’s origin. At most, the rationalisation of the defeat of the Abyssinian kingdom at the hands of the Muslim army of Ahmad ibn Ibrahim al-Ghazi from 1527 to 1543, and in the hands of the

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Oromo from the 1530s to 1603. It was written in the same style as stories in the Bible and in the Abyssinian tradition of recording Christian “miracles.” It was hugely damaging, particularly to the Oromo people, because the book’s purpose, beyond futile rationalisation, demonised the victors and attributed to them a characteristic and origin they did not possess. The demonisation of the Oromo in the Abyssinian Empire, particularly by the Church elites, continued until the 19th century. In the early 17th century, Abyssinian elites and local chiefs, eager to adopt the democratic Gadaa government of the Oromo, failed regrettably. Since then, the political and literary elites of the Kingdom of Abyssinia have continued their academic and violent attacks on the Oromo’s superior ideals, culture, and worldviews. These attacks involved verbal violence, both orally whenever they had the opportunity and in writing, as seen in their monkish legends of the Abyssinian Church and in their pompous chronicles of the monarchs, which served to gratify their resentments. Over time, particularly during the so-called Era of Prince (1769- 18), institutionalised their inferiority and resentment of Oromo in their culture, language, religion, and pseudo–history to achieve one purpose only: rewarding themselves at the expense of the Oromo in almost all aspects of life through the fabrication of legends, myths, and pseudo-history (Chronicle) of their kings. This, however, would demonise the Oromo.

Based on Bahrey’s account and some later elaborations, in the late 19th century, Atsme Giorgis revised and rewrote the history of the Oromo, incorporating some elements of decency and objectivity. Zewde (2002) generously remarks on this work as “the most sympathetic and understanding treatment of the Oromo” (p. 131). He seems to be more impressed with specific facts and truths about the Oromo that Atsme Giorgis could not hide or withhold, and with his relative self-effacement in not attacking the Oromo, than with any damage he might have done aggressively and relentlessly to the Oromo or their history.

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Atsme Giorgis attempted to write the history of Oromo for four hundred years, including that covered by Abba Bahrey. His goals were also more elaborate. He presented them in the first paragraph of his work. According to Bairu Tafla's translation and extensive edition of his work, Atsme Giorgis wrote:

By examining the reminiscences of the old, their traditions, and heritages, we shall primarily explain how [the Oromo] came from the sea, took possession of the Ethiopian kingdom, and changed the former name of the country to their name, how after occupying the country, they drove out the Christian starting from Wabe, from Gase (from Salla) up to the Tekkaze and Tigre; how they then usurped the throne of Yekunno Amlak in Gondar for 40 years; how they declined gradually and how in the time of Atse Menelik II, they were completely subjugated. (Tafla, 1987, p. 79)

This opening was informed clearly by the attitude and trend set by Abba Bahrey. Bahrey had written a similar introduction to his History of the Oromo. Bahrey had made his intentions and attitude abundantly clear when he wrote:

I began to write the history of [the Oromo] to make known the number of their tribes, their eagerness to kill men, and their bestial manners and customs. If any man should say of me, Why has he written a history of wicked men as one writes a history of good men? I answer him, saying, Look into books, and you will see that someone has written the history of Muhammad and of the kings of the Muslims, who are enemies of our faith [Coptic Christianity]. Similarly, George Walda Amid [Al-Makin] has written the history of the foolish, legendary kings of

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Persia, such as Afridon (Feridun), and other kings of Persia, who are now called ‘Sofi’. (Bahrey, 1593, quoted in Budge, 1928, p. 603)

The fairytale legends and uncanny claims of some Abyssinian elites could not be more vivid than in the openings of the works of these two Abyssinian authors, who ventured to write the history of the Oromo, their declared enemy. In the very first opening paragraphs of their Oromo history, both authors made their goals of documenting Oromo history clear. The underlying motives and attitudes of both church historians are clear. It needs no further explanation.

Aleka [a:lɛk’a:] Taye Gebremariam (1860–1924), another Abyssinian Church historian, also attempted to write about the Oromo with the same level of ignorance and negligence as Bahrey and Atsme Giorgis have shown towards the Oromo nation. He championed the absurd claim that the Oromo arrived in Abyssinia from Asia via Madagascar and Kenya.

The works of Bahrey and Atsme Giorgis, however, differ slightly from those of others who blatantly blackmailed the Oromo in at least one way: both attempted to write their own version of Oromo history with some due diligence. They were not “forced” by their contemporary Abyssinian rulers or clerics to produce a fantasy of negativity, meek legends, and made-up stories about the Oromo, only for the consumption of political and cultural propaganda or for religious polemics. Without losing their primary intention of demonising the Oromo, they attempted to present some undeniable facts about the Oromo, even when it was painful for them to do so. Due to some undeniable facts that have been recorded, certain critical aspects of Oromo history have survived. These have remained valuable sources for the objective reconstruction of the Oromo’s history today.

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Antagonistic Discourses and Biases

Neither the Abyssinians nor the early Jesuit Catholic missionaries of the 17th century, nor the 18th- and 19th-century European visitors and missionaries, wrote about the Oromo from the Oromo perspective or presented facts about the Oromo. The first was busy with an ostentatious depiction of Abyssinian peoples and their Christian religion, as well as polemical works against the faith of the Oromo and other indigenous peoples. One of the Jesuit fathers, Fernandes, is credited with authoring several ascetic and polemical works targeting other religions of the peoples of Abyssinia and beyond, as well as for translating several Catholic liturgical books from Spanish to Amharic in the bid to convert the Atse to Catholicism. The Jesuit Catholic missionaries wrote about Oromo (for instance, Manoel de Almeida in the 1640s, Ludolf in 1681 and 1684, and J. P. Gent in 1684) with some degree of hostility towards the Oromo. The Abyssinians mainly wrote to expose all the “bad” rather than the “good” about the Oromo. Every European victory throughout the 18th and 19th centuries had objectives that hardly included writing the history of the Oromo from their perspective. They either wished to settle their resource-rich land and convert it to their religion or act as agents of the Abyssinian monarchy and its Church. Hence, they could not be free from the existing prejudices. In general, no Abyssinian or European writer has written about Oromo with an agreeable degree of objectivity.

The origin of the joint antagonism between Abyssinians and Europeans towards the Oromo could be traced to three main factors: First, the out-and-out monotheistic Oromo religion (Waaqeffannaa) was incompatible with Trinitarian Christianity. Second, the fundamental principles of Oromo worldviews were impervious to the ideal of a master–subject relationship and the divine mandate of kings. These principles include dhugaa ganamaa (primordial truth), safuu (cosmic balance, natural morals, and ethics), qixxee

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(equality of humanity), ilaa-fi-ilaamee (philosophical mode of reasoning and reflection based on the separation of facts (ilaa) and premise (ilaamee)), walabummaa and birmadumma (sovereignty and liberty of man), etc. Third, the political ideas of Oromo republicanism and the European and Abyssinian monarchies were incompatible. Therefore, the antagonism was based on worldviews, faith (religion), and politics (a form of government).

Myth of Oromo Origins and Counter-Records

Constructed Myth of Origin of the Oromo

Abyssinian writers and a few European historians who relied on Abyssinian sources have attempted to portray the Oromo nation (in their accounts of the Oromo's origin) as if it were a latecomer to the Horn of Africa region. It has been one of the paradoxical claims. The paradox appears to be an attempt to contravene the facts of the immigration of the Abyssinians from southern Arabia across the Red Sea to Africa.

The hypothesis of the fantasy that surfaced at one time or another, according to Atsme Giorgis (Tafla, 1987, pp. 50–51) and others, included:

Oromo came from equatorial Africa (Charles T. Beke, James Bruce)

Oromo came from Asia via Madagascar and Mombasa (Aleka Taye Gebremariam, 1955)

Oromo came from Egypt via Abbawi [Nile] and settled at Zigam (Gidaamii?), where Tullu Walal (Mount Walal) is located (Atsme Giorgis citing “European historians”) (Tafla, 1987, p. 309)

Oromo came from a great sea around the 10th century (a certain Abyssinian clergy, Blundell, 1922)

The Oromo descended from a Christian (Abyssinian) woman who took refuge with a provincial governor due to famine in the 14th century in Shewa. The woman gave birth to

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seven children to the slave of the governor. The children became rebels, so they were called (Oromo) (Zamalakat, Author of Book of Agaya)

Oromo may have descended from the Franks or the Portuguese (Samuel Gobat)

The Oromo were a colony of the Israelites who settled between the Indian Ocean and Bale after the period of captivity (Balthazar)

Oromo may have originally come from or through Arabia (Isenberg and Krapf)

Oromo perhaps descended from Portuguese. D'Abbadie (2007[1880]) wrote an amusing account: "One manuscript from northern Ethiopia suggests that the Oromo descended from a Portuguese who was in the service of the Atse and who was unjustly banished into the province of Bali."

None of these mistaken genealogies could make sense because the Oromo have not come from anywhere. They have been the largest indigenous Cushitic nation in the Horn of Africa. They were part of the ancient Eastern Kushites of pre-dynastic Egypt. Eastern Kushites included the Oromo, ancient Egyptians, Danakils, and Bejja (Vercoutter, 1978, p. 19). Powerful connections appear to have existed between the Oromo and ancient Egyptians, whom the former still refer to as Misr, perhaps in line with the Mizraim of the Bible (Genesis 10:6; 10:14; 1 Chronicles 1:8 [KJV]). Haberland (1992) asserts, "Notwithstanding the fanciful accounts of Amharic and European authors, who pinpoint their original home as Madagascar, Mombasa or northern Somalia, the Oromo are a true Ethiopian people" (p. 716).

Intersections of Myth and Historical Records

The Horn of Africa region is home to the Cushite peoples, who, over time, have differentiated into autonomous but linguistically and culturally related groups within the region. The Afar, Agaw, Beja, Konso, Kambata, Saho, and others, like the Oromo, have been indigenous peoples of the region. The Semitic people came to the region at a later stage. The

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two branches of Semitic groups in northeast Africa are: “the Yoktanides, or Himyarites ... mainly in the Abyssinian highlands ... –Tigre, Amhara, Bogos, and others speaking more or less corrupt dialects of the Gheez or old Himyaritic language of South Arabia” and “the Ismaelites, or Arabs proper ... chiefly in the steppe-lands west of the Nile from the Sobat confluence northwards to Dongola” (Reclus, 1892, p. 466). The earliest Yoktanides (Himyarites) who arrived in the region were probably the Agazi and Habasht people. Some other Semites from both groups are known to have migrated to the region as late as the 10th century CE following the expansion of Islam in the region. The historical fact that the Oromo are an indigenous people in the Horn of Africa, although bitter and self-defeating to Abyssinian-Ethiopianists, has been accepted by others.

Getachew Haile, one of the Abyssinian-Ethiopianist scholars who has been doing extensive harm to the Oromo by intention and dedication, has admitted that portraying the Oromo as if their origin is outside the Horn of Africa is futile (Haile, 2002, p. 100). He argues: First, because the Oromo are Cushitic language speakers, the fact that it is spoken nowhere outside of Africa exposes the allegation that the speakers of this language came from elsewhere. Second, because Afaan Oromoo is no different from the other Cushitic languages spoken in the Horn of Africa in general and the Kingdom of Abyssinia in particular, it is impossible to refer to the Oromo separately as if they had arrived in the region recently. He further explains that the language of the Oromo (Afaan Oromoo) belongs to the same Cushitic family of languages as Agewgna (the language of the Agew people of the Zagwean Dynasty), Kimantigna (the language of the Kimant people), and the language of the Somali people. In other words, the Oromo cannot be a latecomer Cushitic nation to the cradle region of the Kushites: The Oromo are as indigenous as other Cushitic language-speaking nations in the area.

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Furthermore, Haile (2002) inadvertently highlighted two other fundamental indications that support the presence of the Oromo in the region historically known as Abyssinia (Abyssinia Proper) as early as the last decades of the Aksumite kingdom. There are at least three indications: First, the Aksumite kingship was a group kingship, i.e., the names of Aksumite kings were group names, similar to the Oromo Gadaa names, and they probably ruled in the name of a victorious group. Second, the reasonably regular forty-year cycle of change of kings during the Zagwean Dynasty can only be likened to the forty-year genealogical generation (Luba) of the Gadaa System of the Oromo. Third, the Oromo and the Agew people have more in common than the Agew and the Amhara people. This suggests that the Oromo and the Agew, indigenous people of this region, might have descended from closely related or the same ancestry.

Aksumite Kingship, a Group Kingship?

Among the early Semitic people who arrived in the Horn of Africa as early as the first century CE and intermingled with the indigenous Cushitic peoples to form the “Semitized Cushites,” the kingdom of Aksum emerged with great power. After a few centuries, Aksum started to expand in every direction. In its expansion to the south and southwest, it began to engulf the Agew and force the Oromo (perhaps except the Madabay (Maddabayii?), Raayyaa, Ashangee, Asaboo Oromo) and other peoples to move further south. In this process of expansion, the Aksumites not only occupied the land of the indigenous nations but also partly inherited and adopted the political and social cultures of these peoples.

This is clear in the fact that they developed a remarkably different political system and social organisation from those that were customary at their origin in southern Arabia. A closer examination of the kingship style of the Aksumite kingdom suggests that the Gadaa

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System of the Oromo, one of the ancient peoples of the Horn of Africa, may have influenced it.

Getachew Haile (2002) notes that the naming of kings in the Aksumite kingdom was similar to the naming of Oromo leaders in the Gadaa System (pp. 100–101). According to him, in the former, the kings were addressed in plural, and the Ge'ez prefix “አለ”/ “Ella,” which in Amharic is “እነ,” followed by a plural verb, for example, “ነግሡ” in Ge'ez and “ነገሡ” in Amharic, both meaning “they reigned.” Accordingly, the naming of the king Ella Amida means the kingship of the Amidas. Haile rules out the fruitless rationalisation by his fellow Abyssinian-Ethiopianists, as if the plural verb has been used to honour the king, because he argues that such a tradition is of very recent origin. He suggests that this collective name was perhaps the name of the ruling army or class in power rather than the name of a king. This was probably similar to how the Oromo named their Gadaa after the common name of the Luba class in power. In the Oromo Gadaa System, which has been in practice since approximately 400 BCE, all Oromo who belong to the Gadaa stage are collectively known as Luba. They make up more than one-tenth of the population. All the Luba are leaders, but they elect their councillor, Abbaa Gadaas, to govern the nation centrally. The elected Abbaa Gadaas form the Gadaa government, which represents all Oromo generational and age segments, as well as all members of the five Gadaa parties, including the party in power. They rule for eight years, and their sons will come to power exactly forty years later. Gadaa Malbaa, for example, means the Gadaa of all Oromo who belong to the Malbaa party, one of the five Gadaa parties.

Similarly, Ella Amida, according to Hale, refers to the kingship of Amidas. Many kings with the prefix “Ella” ruled the Aksumite kingdom for centuries. The list of Aksumite kings between 100 and 600 CE reveals that at least twenty kings reigned with such a group

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name. Ten kings with such collective names ruled without interruption, except one king, from the year 240 to 404, for over one and a half centuries. The joint naming of the ruling class is neither an accident nor a title of honour but an indication that Aksumite rule was not governed by one person but governed by the name of a group or by a collective name of those in power.

Table 1. Aksumite Kings with Ella Prefix

<p>Ella Auda (r. 102–132), Ella Azguagua (r. 141–218), Ella Herka (r. 218–239), Ella Sagal (r. 240–242), Ella Asfeha I (r. 242–256), Ella Tzegab (r. 256–279), Ella Samara (r. 279–282), Ella Aiba (r. 282–298), Ella Eskendi (r. 298–334), Ella Tzaham I (r. 334–343), Ella San (r. 343–356), Ella Aiga (r. 356–374), Ella Amida I (r.374–404), Ella Abreha (r. 356–370), Ella Asfeha II (r. 356–370), Ella Shahel I (r. 401–402), Ella Amida (IV?) (r .475–486), Ella Asbeha (or Caleb or el-Eshaba) (r. 514–542), and Ella Sahem (Armah II or Ashama ibn Abjar) (r. 615–630).</p>
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Note. Compiled from Kelley L. Ross's list of Emperors of Ethiopia, Abyssinia.

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Though it is not possible to conclude whether the Gadaa System had existed and perhaps influenced the group rule of the Aksumite kingdom based on this indication alone, it is, however, essential to note that there existed a unique system of governance that the Aksumites inherited from the Cushitic peoples, the biggest of them the Oromo. This inherited system shares certain aspects with the Gadaa government of the Oromo. Although believed to have existed for several centuries before the formation of the Aksumite kingdom, the Gadaa

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System entered recorded history as a fully fledged democratic and egalitarian socio-political system in the 16th century.

Nonetheless, there is reasonable ground to submit that the Gadaa System of the Oromo might have influenced the Aksumite group leadership system. The submission is based on several indications. First, recent linguistic studies have shown that the Cushitic Oromo language might have influenced northeast Africa and the Mediterranean (Birbirso, 2013a, 2013b; Birbirso & Gerba, 2015, 2016). Second, the Oromo have maintained in their Gadaa System the “true zenith of democracy” that Houston asserts the Cushitic people had reached before the emergence of Egyptian civilisation at some point in their glorious ancient past (Houston, 1926 [2004], p. 15). Third, the Aksumite kingdom, a Semitic people, was established in the country of the Cushitic peoples, one of the largest of which is the Oromo nation, believed to have migrated south through the region in antiquity. Fourth, the Gadaa System of the Oromo had existed before the formation of the kingdom of Abyssinia, according to Oromo oral literature (Lata, 1998, p. 131; Bokku, 2011, p. 162). Fifth, some of the people of Tigray, for example, the Medebay, appear to be Semitized Kushite, the Matite who inhabited northeast Africa around 100 CE (Ayana, 2006), when the kingdom of Aksum was formed. Sixth, Oromo oral traditions assert that the Rayya and Azabo Oromo inhabited present northern Ethiopia before the emergence of the Aksumite kingdom. Seventh, the recent claim by Fikre Tolossa Jiksa that the Oromo were one of the nations that had constituted a glorious and mighty prehistoric kingdom in northeast Africa, including north Ethiopia, but had ancient names like Madabay, before the arrival of the Ag’azians during the rule of King Solomon (Jiksa, 2016) has some merit in the Oromo oral tradition. It also corroborates with Birbirso (2013a, 2013b), Birbirso & Gerba (2015, 2016), Ayana (2016), and Houston (1926 [2004]).

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Zagwean Kings: Gadaa Kings?

Governance by the name of a group might not have been limited to the Aksumite kingdom. Haile (2002) speculates that the Zagwean Dynasty had a similar governance system (p. 100). He substantiates the speculation that most of the kings of the Zagwean Dynasty ruled for forty years. He observes that, in the two recorded lists of the kings of the Zagwean Dynasty that exist, seven out of eleven in one list and eight out of nine in the other list ruled for forty years each (Haile, 2002, p. 101). This means that from the total period of about 354 years that the Zagwean Dynasty was in power, 280 or 320 years, respectively, were partitioned equally among the “kings.”

Taking the eleven “kings” list from Kelley L. Ross’s list seven of which reigned for forty years each (perhaps the eight out of nine may be too good to be accurate), Table 2 may give a clearer picture of the historical reality. There is no possibility that this could have happened by accident, nor could one find any other explanation than accepting that a forty-year cycle of a regular system of power transfer was in operation during the period known in Abyssinian history as the Zagwean Dynasty. However, it might have well been a very different kingdom.

However, the source and connection of this 40-year cycle of a rule need to be sought. Haile (2002) rightly sought to explain the strictly regular power transfer pattern of the Gadaa System of the Oromo. The Oromo have been the only nation that knew no system of governance other than the Gadaa governance in their recorded history. Gadaa is a system of holistic governance where, on the one hand, power is transferred from one Abbaa Gadaa (or Gadaa Class or Gadaa party) to another Abbaa Gadaa (or Gadaa Class or Gadaa party) every eight years through an election, and on the other hand, from one socially defined genealogical generation to the next every forty years by birth. Among the Oromo, even though Abbaa

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Gadaa—the one elected leader—has the least power for only eight years, every Oromo man must be forty years old to become the ruling Luba group. Besides, genealogically, every son of Oromo becomes Luba precisely forty years after his father (Legesse, 1973, 2006; Cerulli, 1922; Hallpike, 1976; Gidada, 2016; Sirna, 2012; Bokku, 2011). Based on this fixed 40-year cycle (Luba) of power transfer between the fathers' and their sons' generations, Haile (2002) suggests that the Agew probably had a system similar to the Gadaa System of the Oromo.

Table 2: Zagwean Kings, their respective years of reign

Name of the “King”	Duration in power (CE)	No. of years in power
Mara Tekle Haimanot	(r. 916–919)	3
Tatadim	(r. 919–959)	40
Jan Seiyoum	(r. 959–999)	40
German Seiyoum	(r. 999–1039)	40
St. Yemrehana Christos	(r. 1039–1079)	40
St. Harbe	(r. 1079–1119)	40
St. Gebra Maskal	(r. 1119–1159)	40
St. Na’akuto Le’ab	(r. 1159–1207)	48
Yetbarek	(r. 1207–1247)	40
Mairari	(r. 1247–1262)	15
Harbe II	(r. 1262–1270)	8

Note. Compiled from Kelley L. Ross’s list of Emperors of Ethiopia/Abyssinia. ©2013

Kelley L. Ross

This system of forty-year epochs of power, which the researcher chose to refer to as Zagwean Gadaa for convenience, may have been borrowed from the Gadaa System of the Oromo, or it could have been a rudimentary form of the Oromo Gadaa System itself. The fact that the Gadaa System had relied heavily on the 40-year generation set for a long time before the age-sets system was reintroduced suggests that there were probably connections between the forty-year rule of the Zagwean Kings and the forty-year generational empowerment of the two Gadaa generations (Generation of fathers and generation of sons). The age-set system was introduced perhaps during the mid-15th-century reformation of the Gadaa System at

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Madda Walaabuu (Dehu, 2012; Alemayehu et al., 2004, cited in Sirna, 2012, pp. 50–52) for effective military defence and to revolutionise the military recruitment, training, and combat (Legesse, 2006).

The study suggests that the Zagwean kings were probably of the “Gadaa” genealogical lineage. The Zagwean Dynasty may have been established on some rudimentary Gadaa principles left behind by the Oromo as they passed through the region during their southward migration or inspired by assimilated or Semitized Oromo communities within the Zagwean Dynasty’s dominion. It is worthwhile to bear in mind that the Aksumite kingdom that Semite peoples had built was able to Semitize the indigenous Kushites culturally and linguistically. Though it has now become clear that the Oromo inhabited the present modern Ethiopia region before the formation of the kingdom of Aksum in the 1st century CE or the emergence of the Zagwean Dynasty in the 10th century CE, some Abyssinian records make it clear that the Oromo arrived during the formative years of the Zagwean Dynasty, during the reign of Mara Tekle Haimanot in the 10th century (Haile, 2002, pp. 171–172; Gidada, 2016, pp. 53–54). If these accounts are correct, the passing or the assimilation/Semitization or “arriving” Oromo communities might have shaped the dynasty after the Gadaa System. The fact that the Zagwean Dynasty was formed during the so-called cinnamon Gadaa (the dismemberment of Gadaa) that, according to Oromo oral chronicles (argan–dhageettii), took place during the period from the 8th to the 12th century CE (Alemayehu et al. 2004 cited in Sirna, 2012), supports the suggestion.

Additionally, the fact that the Agew nation lacks a socio-political system similar to the Gadaa System supports the suggestions. The 40–year generation set, where the Gadaas of the fathers’ generation hand over generational power to the respective Gadaas of the sons, is a uniquely Oromo phenomenon. Had the Agew had a Gadaa System of their own, it would

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have been preserved in the history, culture, and way of life of the Agew. There is, however, no historical evidence to suggest that the Agew had the Gadaa System in the distant past. The now divided Agew people do not practice the Gadaa System. The Oromo nation is the only nation that created and has been practising the combination of age-set and the 40-year genealogical generation set (Gadaa System). The Zagwean kings may have adopted a 40-year generation set as the length of their kings' reigns.

The dissertation also suggests that the Gadaa System could have been practised in modern northern Ethiopia before the formation of the Kingdom of Abyssinia in the late 13th century. The mythical claim of the arrival of the Oromo into the Christian kingdom of Abyssinia (Abyssinia Proper) in the 16th century has no basis but a deliberate bookish manipulation of history by a few vengeful learned clergymen who had suffered material, religious, and psychological damages because of the victories of the Oromo during the said century and henceforth. Alternatively, it was likely a failed attempt by political and religious elites to reverse the history of immigration of Abyssinians across the Red Sea. The continued habitation of the Horn of Africa region by the Oromo as an indigenous people is asserted. It is now well known that the Oromo did not migrate to the region from anywhere; they are an indigenous people. They have inhabited the Horn of Africa, including the northern region of modern Ethiopia. According to Oromo oral literature, the Oromo have practiced the Gadaa System in the Horn of Africa region at least as early as 1000 BCE (Bokku, 2011, p. 162; Lata, 1998, p. 131), and there exists an account of historical records of Buttaa ceremonies since 851 CE, before the emergence of the Zagwean Dynasty, according to Arabic sources (Ayana, 2015). Even if the Oromo had "arrived" during the early formative years of the Zagwean Dynasty, as suggested by some Abyssinian historians (Aleka Taye quoted in Haile, 2002, pp. 171–172), it is probable that the Gadaa System of the Oromo influenced or was at work

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during the Zagwean Dynasty. Then, it would only be proper to submit that the Gadaa System of the Oromo had been practised in central Ethiopia many centuries before the emergence of the Abyssinian kingdom in the late 13th century.

Historical Turn of Events in Modern Central Ethiopia

Since their arrival on the continent of Africa, the Semitic Agazi and Habashat peoples had been expanding into present northern Ethiopia from the coastal regions of the Red Sea at the expense of the indigenous peoples, mainly the Oromo and the Agew (also spelt as Agaw) until the 16th century. Through their expansion, they either Semitized the indigenous peoples and incorporated them into the new kingdoms that they had established or displaced those who resisted the incorporation. The first such expansion may have begun in the present-day northern Ethiopia region and Eritrea's central state. Aksum expanded its political domain and adopted Christianity as its new state religion between the 4th and 6th centuries. After the long decline and final fall of Aksum in the 8th century and the intermittent rule of the non-Christian legendary Queen (known by names Yodit, Guzit, and Esato in Abyssinian legend) in Aksum, the Cushite Zagweans, who succeeded the Aksumites as Christian rulers in the 10th century, followed the same policy of expansion to the south. They expanded their kingdom even farther to the south and southwest. Similarly, the Islamic principalities established in the present-day east and central Ethiopia by some Arab elements from southern Arabia, starting around the same time, had gradually expanded in the region by converting the indigenous people. During the Zagwean rule in present-day Northern Ethiopia, the amalgamation of various peoples and languages, as discussed above, led to the formation of the Amhara identity and the development of the Amharic language. The Amhara rose to power and overthrew the Zagweans in the late 13th century. Since then, the Amhara expanded their domain and religion more than their predecessors.

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All the expansions and conversions took place at the expense of the indigenous Cushitic peoples. The most affected of them appear to be the Oromo. The displacement of the Oromo, who inhabited the region and assimilated into either the dominant Christian or Muslim identities, continued. They were forced to migrate further south. However, the continued displacement of the Oromo ended in the 16th century.

In the 16th century, the Oromo successfully defended themselves against the Christian Abyssinian kingdom and the Islamic principalities that had expanded into their territory through a gradual process that spanned centuries. The Oromo conducted successive *duula galaa*, Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaigns to reclaim their lost territories. Through these highly organised military campaigns, the Oromo checked the Islamic and Christian powers and regained much of the territory they had lost in recent centuries.

At the beginning of the 17th century, when the kingdom of Abyssinia was in a state of distress, the Oromo made a consequential political decision that would divide them. Oromo communities, who were at the forefront of the campaign against the kingdom of Abyssinia, made a radical decision to accept Atse Susenyos as their leader. The decision might have been motivated by the fact that Susenyos, a runaway Abyssinian prince whom an Oromo adopted, had become an Oromo and, hence, a Luba, according to the Gadaa System. When Susenyos became the Atse of the kingdom in the early years of the century, his Oromo followers saw him as having the character of both an Abbaa Gadaa and Atse. Hence, instead of *Mul'ataa* (Gadaa *Mul'ataa*), they followed him as the tenth Luba of the Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaign. These frontier Oromo communities soon started integrating and assimilating with the Abyssinian political, social, and cultural systems. These Oromo constitute many Oromo clans and lineages, fully assimilating into the Abyssinian identity in the present Amhara and Tigray States. Some of these northern Oromo communities, who had

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further infiltrated into the core centre of the kingdom of Abyssinia and had maintained their Oromo identity for longer, gradually became the masters of the kingdom. They effectively ruled Abyssinia Proper from the mid-18th century to the mid-19th century. Most of the Oromo, the Oromo of the present Oromia State, maintained their independence, the Gadaa System, and their republican decentralised government. Only in the Gibie region and Qellem, in southwest Oromia, would war leaders (Abbaa Duulaas) turn themselves into Mootii (Oromo monarchy) in the early 19th century without totally abandoning the Gadaa System.

Starting from the mid-19th century, the power of the northern Oromo communities began to decline, ultimately leading to the subjugation of the entire Oromo population by the end of the century. The northern Oromo started to face fierce resistance to their power from the newly crowned Abyssinian Atse, Atse Tewodros, in the 1850s. Tewodros declared war on them and attempted to expand Abyssinian territory into the Walloo and Tuulamaa (Shewa) Oromo territories to subdue the warlords and unify the fragmented territories they controlled. However, he failed. The Yajjuu, Walloo, and the Tuulamaa Oromo, who had cut off Shewa from Abyssinia Proper, prevailed. Nonetheless, his successors continued the work that Tewodros had started. The most successful of them was Atse Menelik II of Shewa, who united Abyssinians and colonised the neighbouring nations in the European colonisation style of Africa during the Scramble for Africa. The Oromo were finally defeated due to internal divisions, a lack of effective organisation, and, most importantly, the lack of modern firearms that their enemy had acquired from Europeans, who had provided them competitively. The Oromo of Ethiopia came under the total control of the Shewan-led Abyssinian settler colonisation at the end of the 19th century.

As colonised people, the history, culture, religion, and political system of the Oromo became the primary targets of the Abyssinian nation-state-building project. The project was

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based on the Amhara and Amharic languages, as well as Orthodox Christianity. The Oromo were, among others, forced to abandon their Oromo identity and adopt the Amhara identity instead. The history of the Oromo had been recorded as the “history of the enemy” starting from the time of the successive defeats of the Abyssinian kingdom in their hands in the 16th and 17th centuries (and also when they were under the lordships of the northern Oromo from the 1750s to the 1850s), was now given a reboot. Some Abyssinian elites continued to write about the Oromo full of smears and insults as part of the state propaganda to dehumanise the Oromo so that they would remain broken and under the control of the Abyssinians, who have now started to present themselves as culturally advanced and “civilised people than the Oromo. This kind of loser–victor propaganda, together with the settler-colonial mentality and its corresponding socio-political background, continued to dominate Abyssinian pseudo-history until the formal introduction of Ethiopian-centred historiography, which produced the official “Ethiopian History” beginning in the 1960s.

Even then, the tradition of overstatement of events and actions, as well as the superfluities of Abyssinian Church and court legends and stories, and the use of extensive hyperbole, which had been an integral part of the records of court chroniclers and Church historians, would prove impossible to avoid. The fact that the leading native scholars in the production (compilation) of “Ethiopian History” themselves would only be the products of the old tradition, inherited through the privilege and the opportunity to study at home or abroad, would make it harder to introduce an essence of genuine and just (fair) history. They would side with the establishment that had produced and sustained them. Even the prominent expatriate members of the “Ethiopian History” school would find themselves easily trapped in living and working for the establishment. They soon became indebted to it. They could hardly scrutinise the historical prejudices and legends that had made their way into “history,”

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but continued to echo and interpret what had been recorded in the largely propagandist Amhara-Tigre historical worldview. As the subjugated NNPs started demanding equality and justice or national self-determination of nationalities, the imperial state and the state church began to tune the narrative of the “colony countries” to “reunified territories.” This was a response to the rallying cry of the nationalist movement, but the historiographers built it into a theory. The colonial conquest of the non-Abyssinian NNPs started to be theorised as the “reunification of the former territories of Ethiopia.” “The Abyssinian conquest of the Oromo was portrayed, particularly after the 1960s, as a unification of Ethiopia” (Bulcha, 1996, p. 62). It became not only the new theme for the Abyssinian propaganda but also part of the expanded new pseudo-history of the Empire of Abyssinia-cum-modern Ethiopia.

It was based on such propagandist pseudo-historical records and highly biased socio-political backgrounds that the modernisation of Ethiopian history began in the early 1960s with the introduction of “Ethiopian History” as an academic field of learning and teaching at the then Haile Selassie I University College, now Addis Ababa University. Foreign faculty founded the university college. Professor Sven Rubenson founded the Department of History in 1962. The Department started its M.A. and PhD programs in 1980 and 1990. Through a gradual process, Ethiopians, particularly the privileged Amharans, who had spoken Amharic as a criterion for university admission, began to take over the foreign pioneers’ teaching and research. Because foreigners set the course of learning and the study of history, including the teaching and study of Abyssinian history, this was also inherited by the privileged Abyssinians, with the added interest of deep-rooting the foundation of the Ethiopian Empire’s history as the history of the victors, the Abyssinians.

Foreigners and Amhara-selected elites joined forces to remake history. They would remake it only partly in books based on existing fragments of anti-Oromo propaganda. The

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Coptic Orthodox Church (also known as the Abyssinian Orthodox Church since 1959, and sometimes referred to as Abyssinian “Tabbot Christianity“) had held the fragments and the Chronicles. The selected elites were products of the traditional education of the Church. They were protagonists of the false claim: “reunification” of ancient territories.” The imperial elites, the protagonists, have propagated the claim as a cover for the settler colonisation of more than two-thirds of the empire’s people and territory. Traditional works by Abba Bahrey, Atsme Giorgis, and Tekletsadek Mekuria, among others, have become foundational to the mainstream history of the modern Ethiopian empire state. This “history” became known simply as “Ethiopian history.”

The founders of “Ethiopian History” at Addis Ababa University published several of their works during the first two decades of teaching and studying history there. The most notable publications include *Economic History of Ethiopia, 1800–1935* *(Pankhurst, 1968); *Southern Ethiopia and the Christian Kingdom, 1508–1708* (Aregay,1971); *Priests & Politicians: Protestant & Catholic Missions in Orthodox Ethiopia (1830–1868)* (Crummey,1972); *Church and State in Ethiopia: 1270 – 1527* (Tamirat,1972); *Ancient and Medieval Ethiopian History to 1270* (Selassie,1972); *Greater Ethiopia: The Evolution of a Multiethnic Society* (Levine,1974); *Yohannes IV of Ethiopia: A Political Biography* (Sellassie,1975); *The Survival of Ethiopian Independence* (Rubenson, 1976); *The Cultural Situation in Socialist Ethiopia* (Eshete,1982); and *The Life and Times of Menelik II: Ethiopia, 1844–1913* (Marcus, 1985). These works have formed the academic foundation of “Ethiopian History” as studied and researched.

As mentioned above, this “Ethiopian History” presents the history, legends, and myths of the kingdom of Abyssinia as the official history of the multinational empire state, modern Ethiopia. Due to the absence of historical records from approximately 550 to 1300

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CE in Abyssinia (Delebo, 2007, p. 45), these works heavily relied on Abyssinian legends and religious traditions to cover the period. For the period since the formation of the Kingdom of Abyssinia, the chronicles recorded by the clergy members of the state church were copied directly as authentic sources, even though they were manifestly biased against non-Abyssinians in general and the Oromo nation in particular.

It is well known that such “historical” records based on chronicles of kings are generally full of distortions as they strive only for the service of making the kings (Emperors) appear as good (virtuous, respectable, worthy, blameless, honourable, self-sacrificing, etc.) as possible. “But in Ethiopia’s case, historical facts often stood on their head” (Bulcha, 1996, p. 62). They often invert anything uncomfortable to their enemies. Abyssinian records have no censures for their kings or peoples, but, conversely, they mainly blame the Oromo for all their transgressions. Anything excellent and advanced from other neighbouring peoples was inverted or misappropriated. Abyssinian records portray other nations as invaders, newcomers, strangers, unbelievers, and backwards, when the facts of the matter suggest otherwise. The “Ethiopian History” organisers had done little to rectify these inverted records. The academic works that subsequently followed, as well as the teaching of history in schools and universities, have been heavily dependent on the content and trends set by the works of the excessively biased ecclesiastics.

It is well known that this “Ethiopian History” has a fundamental bias against the non-Abyssinian nations, nationalities, and peoples of Ethiopia in general and against the Oromo in particular. The history of the Oromo that has been included in the later works of “Ethiopian history”, both by Abyssinians, Westerners, and even by some Oromo, had to be based on such an openly biased but deeply rooted foundation. The foreign nationals who participated in the “Ethiopian History” project served only as mouthpieces for Abyssinian political and religious

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elites, to whom they were indebted for providing all their sources. They rubber-stamped the Abyssinian elitists' (Amhara and Tigre ethnocentric historical narratives) in different languages and styles. As such, "Ethiopian History" is not what it claims to be, nor does it possess any genuine historical value, other than being largely Abyssinian ethnocentric propaganda. Some recent endeavours by some Oromo historians and political scholars to break out from the historically unjust representation of the Oromo in "Ethiopian history" seem unsuccessful, at least not yet. "Ethiopian History" has remained unfair to the least and unwritten to the best. The most disadvantaged nation in the process is the Oromo nation. Despite having had a significant part in the history of Abyssinia and the formation of the Empire State of Ethiopia, the Abyssinian "historians" and their Western counterparts were repulsed to write even the Oromo and Muslim names of some Heroes of the Battle of Adwa from recent memory. At the same time, they were keen to write Christian names of aids.

Macroscopically, such has been how the scanty history of the Oromo has been written as more than a footnote in "Ethiopian History." In this sense, there is no doubt that it was initially reported by the Abyssinians and written primarily to humiliate and desecrate the great nation that they had failed to subjugate for over 400 years, despite having continuously devastated it. The Westerners who wrote about the Oromo in the "Ethiopian History" only rewrote the recorded accounts of the Abyssinians.

Therefore, in its true sense, there is no history of the Oromo nation written with objectivity and good intention among the accounts of "Ethiopian history." However slight, any part of it that concerns the Oromo, whether Abyssinians, Westerners, or some Oromo themselves who have written it, has been devoid of either good intention, objectivity, or resourcefulness. As long as it has been moulded to fit into the Abyssinian-centred Ethiopian historiography, the existing and upcoming body of historical records about the Oromo or any

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other nation, nationality, or people of modern Ethiopia cannot be a genuine record of history. To become natural Ethiopian History, the failed “Ethiopian History” must be built on an all-encompassing foundation and jointly by all the peoples of modern Ethiopia.

Emergence of Oromo Studies

Scholars have studied and written about the Oromo. Many focused on the history of the Oromo within and outside the traditional history of the Abyssinian kingdom, which Abyssinian elites and their Western collaborators have transposed to the “official” history of modern Ethiopia, “Ethiopian History.” Others focused on the Gadaa System and its institutions. Few have conducted a comparative analysis of some aspects of the Oromo culture, institutions, and philosophies. Even fewer scholars have ventured into the cultural and religious aspects of the Oromo nation.

The emergence of Oromo Studies is attributed to the systemic and institutional biases within “Ethiopian Studies” against the Oromo. Oromo scholars could not publish about the Oromo in the *Journal of Ethiopian Studies*, which is appropriately “*Journal of Abyssinian Studies*.” One would be surprised, even upset, to find out how few and sparse Oromo-related publications are in the *Journal* in its fifty years of history. The few that have made it to the publication include the minimalist works of Abdurahaman Mohamed Korram. He published Oromo proverbs in two parts in the *Journal* (Korram, 1969, 1972). It was little more than a collection of sayings. Holcomb (1973) details the Oromo marriage tradition in Western Oromia, Wallaga. Triulzi (1975) revisited the life of the Guduruu Oromo before the Abyssinian conquest of the late 19th century. Gemeda (1992) published a review of Mohammed Hassen’s book, *The Oromo of Ethiopia: A History, 1570-1860* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1990). Yimam (1987) studied the formation of relative clauses in the Oromo language using Geez transliteration and alphabet. Berisso (2000) published his

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preliminary study on the riddles of Number Nine among the Gujji Oromo of south-central Ethiopia. These were the number of directly Oromo-related publications that have appeared in the Journal. Studies related to the politically dominant and oppressive culture, as well as the Amhara-Tigre alliance, are featured in the Journal.

The following sections provide a brief overview of the critical works related to the Oromo since the late 20th century. Overall, these works were aligned with the intellectual tenets of the emerging Oromo Studies. Only a few were shielded from the sticky influence of 'Ethiopian Studies,' while a few were produced within it.

Gada Melbaa (1988) is the first modern introductory history of the Oromo nation. Although brief, with the stated intention of serving as an introduction, the work provides an excellent overview of the social, political, and cultural history, as well as religion and the republican government (Gadaa System) of the Oromo nation, from antiquity to the late 20th century, for the average reader of Oromo origin. It also introduces the country of the Oromo and establishes them as an indigenous nation in the region. The brief and precise introductory book^[iv] could not have come at a better time, just three years before the fall of the military dictatorship in Ethiopia and the subsequent emergence of Oromia State since the mid-1980s. The Oromo were, through over a century of state propaganda, Amhara-centred unitary nation-state building, and total assimilation into the Abyssinian languages and culture. The plain and straightforward book was one of the guidebooks for the swift awakening of Oromo nationalism among the common Oromo, following intense state propaganda aimed at anaesthetising and disassociating the Oromo from their national identity. It has since been widely referred to by scholars, despite some criticism from Abyssinian historians and political elites, simply because it challenges most of their fallacious assumptions and records

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about the Oromo in the pseudo-history of the kingdom of Abyssinia, also known as “Ethiopian History.”

In the same year, Mekuria Bulcha (1988) documented the effects of the formation of the Abyssinian colonial state on the mass exodus of disadvantaged peoples from Ethiopia to the neighbouring Sudan in his book *Flight and Integration: Causes of Mass Exodus from Ethiopia and Problems of Integration in Sudan* (Uppsala, Sweden: Scandinavian Institute of African Studies). Though his research’s intent and purpose were not to write the history of the Oromo, his work has made historical records of the colonisation process and its effects from the victims’ perspective.

The first scholarly work to write the history of the Oromo nation from the Oromo perspective, using mainly the Gadaa Chronology, comes from another Oromo scholar, Mohammed Hassen. Hassen (1990) has written the most comprehensive history of the Oromo in the Gibie region in his book, *The Oromo of Ethiopia: A History, 1570-1860* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press). In this work, Hassen “analyses the profound cultural, social, economic, and religious changes that the Oromo in the region had undergone” from 1570 to 1860 (p. xiv). Hassen’s work is brief on the history of the Oromo nation and the Gadaa System of the Oromo, which was only part of the introduction. In addition, he wrote it midway between the established Abyssinian narrative (including the treatment of the Oromo as migrating pastoralists) and the emergent Oromo narrative. Nevertheless, this and his other works marked a “significant turning point in Ethiopian study,” where a history of the Oromo is written using the chronology of the Gadaa System as a “framework for analysis” (Legesse, 2006, p. xvii).

Bonnie Holcomb and Sisai Ibssa (1990), in their book *The Invention of Ethiopia: The Making of a Dependent Colonial State in Northeast Africa* (Trenton, NJ: Red Sea Press), have

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illustrated that the formation of the Empire of Abyssinia-cum-modern Ethiopia was a joint enterprise of the Abyssinians and the few but powerful European states. The Abyssinian ruling elites served as intermediaries in this joint enterprise between the conquered peoples and European strategic interests. They argue that neither the conquest of the Oromo nor the formation of modern Ethiopia could have been possible without the intervention of the European imperial powers. The work is one of the historical and analytical accounts of the conquest of the Oromo and the destruction of their identity under the collaborative forces of European imperialism and Abyssinian colonialism.

There is much correlation between the works of Bonnie Holcomb and Sisai Ibssa (1990) and Asafa Jalata (2005). The latter has elaborated on and analysed excellently the general and specific historical features of the Oromo conquest by the Kingdom of Abyssinia in the last decades of the 19th century and the subsequent developments until the beginning of the 21st century. Jalata effectively utilised the capitalist socio-economic system as a guiding theory and the penetration of the Horn of Africa by global imperialism as a methodological framework in his book *Oromia and Ethiopia: State Formation and Ethnonational Conflict, 1868-2004* (Trenton, NJ, and Asmara, Eritrea: Red Sea Press). The work presents an overarching theoretical perspective and methodological framework for the study of the colonisation of kingdoms, states, and autonomous peoples to the south, southwest, and southeast by the Kingdom of Abyssinia (Abyssinia Proper) in the late 19th century, and the formation of modern Ethiopia as a colonial state. In addition, in his earlier book, *Oromo Nationalism and the Ethiopian Discourse: The Search for Freedom and Democracy* (Asmara, Eritrea: Red Sea Press), Jalata (1998) has expounded on the overall grievances of the Oromo nation against Abyssinian domination. In addition, he painstakingly documented the emergence of Oromo nationalism in response to the policy of total

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assimilation and homogenization pursued by both imperial and socialist governments. His numerous other works have upheld the Oromo national identity, culture, social system, and Gadaa System and have continued to guide the inevitable restoration of Oromummaa.

Asmarom Legesse (1973, 2006) has conducted extensive research on the Gadaa System of the Boorana Oromo, residing in southern Ethiopia and northern Kenya. He first studied the Gadaa System in 1973 as a means of approaching the study of African societies. In his book *GADA: Three Approaches to the Study of African Societies* (New York, NY, USA: The Free Press), he has excellently expounded the inner workings of the Gadaa System of the Oromo within three intellectual traditions (case analysis, structuralism, and empiricism) and a comparative African context. As a sequel to this work, he published the full version of *Oromo Democracy: An Indigenous African Political System* (Trenton, NJ, USA, and Asmara, Eritrea: The Red Sea Press) in 2006. As *GADA* before it, *Oromo Democracy* illustrates the Oromo polity as one of traditional constitutional democracy founded on an array of democratic institutions, dual organisations, and parallel age-set and generation-set social structures. Furthermore, Legesse introduces the reinterpretation of Abyssinian records and proposes a well-educated thesis for further study of the socio-political and religious-cultural structure of the Oromo nation. These two impressive works on the Gadaa System of the Oromo, along with his other related publications on the Gadaa System, not only document the anthropological and socio-political history of the Oromo but also constitute an unrivalled knowledge base of the Gadaa System of the Oromo, written by an outsider.

Marko Bassi (2005) conducted another dedicated study of the Gadaa System of the Booranaa Oromo. He reported his anthropological field research among the Boorana Oromo in his book *Decisions in the Shade: Political and Juridical Processes among the Oromo-*

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Borana (Trenton, NJ and Asmara, Eritrea: The Red Sea Press), first published in 1996. He has compiled sufficiently detailed records of the Oromo socio-political and religious institutions, the Boorana assemblies and their procedures, as well as the juridical and political processes. He has analysed the normative and legislative spheres of the Gadaa System and the Boorana assemblies, as well as their competencies. Though his assertions about the Gadaa institutions are based on “zero days of participant observation” of Gadaa Assemblies in session (Legesse, 2006, p. xix), and hence could not reflect accurately the role of the Caffee Assembly, the legislative, executive, and judiciary roles and competencies of the Gadaa institutions and Abbaa Gadaas, his work remains one of the comprehensive field research projects on the participatory polity of Boorana Oromo.

Marco Bassi had previously published two articles on the Gadaa System: one on the political significance of the Gadaa System (Bassi, 1996), and another on the organisation of the Boorana Gadaa Council and its complexity (Bassi, 1999). The former was published in Baxter, P.T.W., Hultin, J., & Triulzi, A. (Eds.), *Being and Becoming Oromo: Historical and Anthropological Inquiries* (Uppsala, Sweden: Nordiska Afrikainstitutet and Lawrenceville, NJ: Red Sea Press). The latter was published in the *Journal of Ethiopian Studies*.

Alessandro Triulzi (1981), in his work *Salt, Gold and Legitimacy: Prelude to the History of a No-Man’s Land, Bela Shangul, Wallaga, Ethiopia (ca 1800-1898)* (Naples, Italy: Istituto Universitario Orientale), expands on the history and culture of the marginalised Oromo and Bela Shangul in southwest Ethiopia. His *Salt, Gold, and Legitimacy* was one of the original studies from that region. In his other publications, Triulzi has documented the dual organisation of Boorana and Gabbaro and the dilemma of provincial rule in West Oromia in the immediate aftermath of the Abyssinian conquest in the late 19th century.

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After publishing a preliminary study of the Oromo of Wallaga in the *Journal of Ethiopian Studies* (Bartels, 1970), Lambert Bartels (1983) focused on the cultural and religious aspects of the Maccaa Oromo in his ethnographic research published as *Oromo Religion: Myths and Rites of the Western Oromo of Ethiopia—An Attempt to Understand* (Berlin, Germany: Dietrich Reimer Verlag). His research has given more shape and form to the Oromo religion, Waaqeffannaa, and the concepts of ayyaana and safuu. According to him, the Oromo have never changed their fundamental belief in Waaqaa, even if they have confessed to Islam or Christianity. Despite primarily focusing on the Oromo religion and Abrahamic religions, his work successfully documented some Oromo social structures and the Gadaa System's intellectual prose.

Bokku (2011), in his book *Oromo Wisdom in Black Civilisation* (Finfinnee, Ethiopia: Finfinnee Printing & Publishing), written for the average reader, has illustrated the foundations, cultural, social, and political structures, as well as institutional organisations, of the Oromo. In addition, he elaborated on the 16th-century Gadaa-based offensive campaigns of the Oromo and provided an overview of the Gadaa System of the Oromo.

Tsega Etefa (2012) has elucidated the peaceful and welcoming history of the Oromo in East Africa excellently, which has contributed to the region's integration and peace, in his concise book, *Integration and Peace in East Africa: A History of the Oromo Nation* (New York, USA: Palgrave Macmillan). The book elaborates on the peaceful trading networks in East Africa, in general, and in the southwest of modern Ethiopia, in particular, as well as the historical role of the Oromo in these networks.

Focusing on the Sayyoo Oromo of Western Oromia and their 18th and 19th-century political, socio-economic, and cultural changes, Negaso Gidada (2016) studied and wrote the history of the Oromo in the mid-1980s. With his study, he successfully challenged earlier

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historical injustices of Abyssinian history that portrayed the Oromo as newcomers from the south. In his book የኦሮሞ ሕዝብ ታሪክ (ኦዲስ አበባ ፥ ኢትዮጵያ), Gidada asserts that the Oromo were neither newcomers nor did they originate from the south. They are rather indigenous nations of the region, which, over time, initially expanded from north to south through present-day central Ethiopia before expanding to the southwest of modern Ethiopia on their reverse course after the 16th-century Gadaa-based campaigns. The English version of the book was published in 2001.

In addition to the works mentioned above and many others by these researchers, numerous intellectuals have studied the Oromo culture, the Gadaa System, resistance to colonisation, the Qaalluu institution, philosophy, and the arts, among other topics. These include, but are not limited to, Darrel Bates, Jasen Clay, Karl Eric Knutsson, Gammechuu Megerssa, Abdullahi Shongolo, Haji Abbas Gnamo, Leencho Lata, Dinsa Lepisa, Herbert S. Lewis, Kuwee Kumsa, Hilarie Ann Kelly, Gollo Huqqa, John Hinnant, Joseph Van de Loo, Ulrich Braukamper, Hector Blackhurst, Lemmu Baissa, P.T.W. Baxter, and Gunther Schlee. These scholars and others have produced research outputs and contributed to the scientific and systematic development of the published body of knowledge about the Oromo. The Journal of Oromo Studies has published multi-disciplinary articles on Oromo Studies since 2000.

African Political Thoughts and Limits of Institutional Political Economy

The main theoretical argument in this dissertation is that the governance of the state fails not because institutions are absent, but instead because historically rooted moral and institutional orders are replaced by a system that is not fully backed by society, in other words, by a system that is alien to society and lacks social legitimacy (Quijano, 2000; Mignolo, 2011; Thompson, 1971; Thelen, 1999). These are decolonial political economy,

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moral political economy, and historical institutionalism theories. Together, they support the argument that African governance, its efficiency and equity, emerge from historically grounded institutions, moral regulation, and socially embedded authority, not from extractive, externally imposed governance systems.

In this argument, I would draw on decolonial political economy, historical institutionalism, and moral economy theory. First, it examines how local conquest and epistemic domination reorganize economies, state structure, and the knowledge system, including the historiography, and produce hierarchies of power that could last for a long time, but are based on extraction and dependency (Quijano, 2000; Amin, 1988). Colonial political economy rejects Western political and economic forms considered universal benchmarks. Instead, it focuses on indigenous institutions, whose stronger moral orders and established material systems and values constitute a legitimate source for decolonial political economic theory (Quijano, 2000). I wouldn't focus on inclusion in global capitalism, but on exposing how colonial rule displaced existing political economies and moralized their displacement as underdevelopment.

Under historical institutionalism, the dissertation explains and explores political economic outcomes as the product of an institutional framework through specific historical sequences, such as the colonial expansion of the Abyssinian kingdom to form the modern Ethiopian Empire, with the critical junctures such as the abolition of a monarchy, the formation of the Ethiopian Republic, and path dependence. In fact, state institutions matter. They matter because they result from rules and laws and shape incentives and power relations over time (Pierson, 2004). Historical institutionalism thus allows only slow change, which is often uneven and shaped by inherited structures rather than by abstract efficiency (North, 1990).

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In the African context, historical institutionalism theory highlights how colonial and post-colonial state formation disrupted or replaced indigenous institutions (North, 1990). In specific case of Ethiopia, it highlights how settler colonialism of the south by the north and how the entrenchment of the settler colonial bureaucracy throughout the imperial and the socialist regimes disrupted the egalitarian Republican and democratic political economy in the central Ethiopia, particularly in Oromia state and replaced it by imported bureaucracies and forms of republicanism produced long-term governance disruption which has continued until today.

Moral economy theory is about economic behavior and internalises how it is regulated by shared ethical, social norms, obligations, and expectations of justice rather than by market logic (Thompson, 1971; Scott, 1979). Moral economic theory analyzes or emphasizes legitimacy, reciprocity, and moral limits on accumulation and authority (Thompson, 19971). When these indigenous norms are violated, social resistance emerges, as in the continued struggle of the Oromo nation and other oppressed Southern nations, nationalities, and peoples. Moral economic theory applied to indigenous governance explains how indigenous democratic and egalitarian systems, such as the Gada system, embed accountability, redistribution, and restraint within economic and political life.

This dissertation engages African historical thought not as an alternative to political economy, but as a corrective to its prevailing institutional assumptions. While dominant institutional theories explain development outcomes through the configuration of formal rules, property rights, and elite incentives (North, 1990; Acemoglu & Robinson, 2012), they remain largely silent on the historical displacement of indigenous governance systems that once performed these same functions. The literature review therefore situates Oromo governance within the tradition of historical institutionalism, treating the Gadaa system as an

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endogenous institutional order rather than a cultural residue. In this sense, Gadaa is analysed as a pre-colonial constitutional framework that structured authority, constrained power, regulated access to resources, and enforced accountability through rotation of office and collective sanctioning—functions central to institutional political economy.

By extending North’s (1990) conception of institutions as “humanly devised constraints” to indigenous constitutional systems, the study challenges the tendency to treat African governance failures as institutional absences rather than as outcomes of institutional rupture. Similarly, while Acemoglu and Robinson’s (2012) inclusive–extractive dichotomy is analytically useful, it presumes that inclusivity emerges primarily from modern state bargains, overlooking earlier republican systems that were dismantled through conquest and internal colonisation. Sen’s (1999) emphasis on agency and capability provides an important normative lens, yet it remains under-theorised with respect to collective rule-making and political authority. Mbembe’s (2001) critique of postcolonial power exposes domination and subjectivity but stops short of reconstructing viable institutional alternatives. This dissertation bridges these gaps by demonstrating that indigenous governance systems such as Gadaa constituted historically grounded, institutionally coherent political economies whose suppression reshaped state formation and development trajectories in Ethiopia. In doing so, it integrates African indigenous governance into mainstream institutional theory while preserving its historical specificity and analytical autonomy.

The Necessity of a New Narrative for the Oromo and Ethiopia

Competing Nationalisms and the Implications

Modern Ethiopia was built during the last decades of the 19th century (Adejumobi, 2007; Boahen, 1987; Bulatovich, 1897, 1993; Bulcha, 2005; Etefa, 2012; Hassen, 1990, 2002; Jalata, 1998, 2005, 2014; Melbaa, 1988; Vaughan, 2003; Baissa, 2004; Gidada, 2016;

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Gnamo, 2002; Legesse, 2006; Ta'a, 2004). It was built through a protracted military conquest that expanded the kingdom of Abyssinia by about threefold and established a new non-Western colonial order in East Africa. The kingdom claimed that the conquest was a reunification of the territories over which it had lost authority centuries ago. However, the conquered nations, nationalities, and peoples (NNPs) maintain that they had never been part of the kingdom's authority, and the conquest was, in fact, colonisation. These have divided Ethiopian historiography into two main theses: reunification and colonial. This dissertation ascribes to the latter thesis. The kingdom conquered independent NNPs and tried to extend Abyssinian-centred nationalism over them. The conquest incorporated around seventy of the recognised NNPs of the Ethiopian Federation. Since then, they have struggled to preserve their identity and compete with nationalism. One has been Oromo nationalism, an overly broad form of Ethiopian nationalism.

Oromo nationalism and Abyssinian-centred Ethiopian nationalism are competing nationalisms in East Africa. Oromo nationalism was founded on Oromo history, language, Oromummaa (Oromo national identity), the Gadaa System (republican ethos), Oromo philosophical thinking, the ancient monotheistic belief (Waaqeffannaa) in one universal God (Waaqa), the claim that the Oromo are the ancient Kush (the true ancient Ethiopia), and the struggle of the nation to do away with Abyssinian settler colonization (since the late 19th century). Oromo nationalism draws its roots from ancient Kush, Upper Egypt. It is an ancient, multi-lingual, multinational, and multicultural form of Ethiopian nationalism. Abyssinian-centred Ethiopian nationalism, on the other hand, is based on Abyssinian history, Geez-based languages, Habasha identity, Abyssinian monarchy, and the legend of the descent of its monarchs from King Solomon of Israel, Coptic Christianity, the religiously motivated claim that modern Ethiopia is the ancient Ethiopia of the Holy Bible, and the hoopla of the

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unification of former territories. It is an archaic Abyssinian nationalism that promotes an Abyssinian-centred, mono-lingual, mono-national, and mono-cultural perspective in a truly multi-lingual, multinational, and multicultural state. It is Abyssinian Ethiopian nationalism. Yusuf (2009) argues, “Just like its Ethiopian counterpart, Oromo nation/nationalism is a modern, glocal [“simultaneous interplay of ‘global’ and ‘local’ forces”] creation” (p. 301). As such, “both nationalisms are in no fundamental way different from each other in terms of their logic; both have remained to be products of social engineering that specifically began to take place in the modern era and the context of globalisation” (Yusuf, 2009, p. 302). Both nationalisms draw from the emergence of a new order in East Africa in the late 19th century. For the former, “The [Abyssinian] occupation was a formative factor in the creation of Oromo nationalism out of the traditional Oromo culture” (Erlich, 1994, p. 672). In other words, Oromo nationalism is “rooted in a common language and shared modes of thought and feeling, and which has been nurtured in shared colonial-style oppression” (Baxter, 1978, p. 295). The latter also started to take root from the end of the 19th century, after the Abyssinian conquest of the Oromo and other NNPs to its south, southeast, and southwest. Since then, it has been characterised by pugnacious nationalism, where the rest of the NNPs of modern Ethiopia have continued to be absorbed forcefully and tactfully into this Amhara-centred nationalism. It was this nationalism that has been competing with Oromo nationalism antagonistically, particularly since the late 1960s.

Since the institutionalisation of Abyssinian settler colonialism in Oromia, Oromo nationalism has been on the rise. The late 19th century marked a significant turning point for the Oromo nation. It was when the kingdom of Abyssinia, the Oromo, had been overwhelmed for over four centuries, primarily by the sheer power of firearms. That was the trigger for the rebuilding of stronger Oromo nationalism. However, Oromo nationalism came to take a well-

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thought-out shape more than half a century later, starting in the 1960s, following the global movement for national self-determination of nations. The 1960s were the formal beginning of the struggle of Ethiopia's oppressed and marginalised nations, nationalities, and peoples. It was also a period when the oppressed and marginalised nations and nationalities asserted the multinationalism of the empire.

Successive governments have attempted, but failed, to suppress Oromo nationalism. Baxter (1978) argues that Oromo nationalism "can only be repressed by an extremely ruthless, strong and efficient state" (p. 295). However, no state or regime could repress it, however ruthless and robust they may have been. Neither the political and legal suppression of Oromo nationalism by the Imperial regime of Atse Haile Selassie I, nor the brutal military suppression of the Derg regime from 1974 to 1991, nor the systemic suppression by the EPRDF regime to date, could produce the desired result. Successive unfriendly regimes have tried and failed. The growing multinationalism ultimately led to the abolition of the monarchy. After 1974, the socialist regime brutally quelled the emerging multi-nationalism. This led to a devastating civil war between the state and the armed nationalist groups. The latter's victory over the former in 1991 ushered in a new dawn of multinational Ethiopia. To this effect, the new Constitution formed the Ethiopian Federation in 1995. The EPRDF regime, which has stifled the federation since its formation, has oppressed Oromo nationalism systemically by equating its development with the disintegration of the modern Ethiopian state. Despite these attempts, Oromo nationalism has continued to thrive.

Abyssinian-centred Ethiopian nationalism has failed because Ethiopia is a multinational state, contrary to what Ethiopian nationalists have tried to purport. In failed nationalism, the Oromo had a marginal place as subordinates. It is also clear that Oromo-centred Ethiopian nationalism, where others would be subordinates, would fail. This is one of

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the reasons why this dissertation does not promote Oromo nationalism to eclipse Ethiopian nationalism but, instead, a growing Ethiopian multi-nationalism, where the Oromo would be promoted peacefully and democratically to the socio-political centre, taking into consideration the current national political self-awakening of the NNPs and the challenges to maintaining the Ethiopian federation. Doing so could promote old-fashioned nationalism. However, nationalism has never been a settled issue in Ethiopia: It is growing and thriving.

Following the failed Abyssinian-centred Ethiopian nationalism, Oromo nationalism, which focused on the unity of the Kushite nations of East Africa, offers an alternative point of convergence for the nations, nationalities, and peoples of Ethiopia and East Africa. Modern Ethiopia is a federation of profoundly Kushite nations and nationalities. The religiously motivated claim of oriental or Semitic descent in sections of the northern part of the country is a mere cultural and linguistic Semitization of the indigenous Kushites in antiquity. Every nation, nationality, and people, including the southern minority Omotic and Nilotic peoples, could quickly and consciously coalesce into the ancient Kushite identity. Beyond modern Ethiopia, it anticipates collaboration and cooperation among the contiguous Kushite nations of East Africa. It also foresees the formation of a commonwealth of these nations that would rebuild the glorious and pervasive Ancient Ethiopia through voluntary cooperation and economic and socio-political integration. In a long gaze into the future, a united and stronger East Africa rests in forming the confederated commonwealth of the Kushite nations. Oromo nationalism also predicts that the unity of the Kushite nation will remain the socio-political agenda of the nations of East Africa in this century.

The Constitution recognises all the nations in the federation. There are close to eight nations, nationalities, and peoples in the Ethiopian Federation. Nine recognised nations have set up their National Regional States separately or jointly. The Harari, Amhara, Tigre, Afar,

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Somali, and Oromo are among those nations. The Constitution has also recognised the unconditional rights of nations, nationalities, and peoples to self-determination, including the right to secession. Not only that, but the Constitution also anticipates and provides for the formation of new nations, ethnicities, and peoples in the Ethiopian Federation. These provisions make the Constitution and the model of nationalism in Ethiopia unique. The constitutional recognition began the official inauguration of the resurgence of Oromo nationalism in Ethiopia.

Epistemic Violence of “Ethiopian Historiography” and “Ethiopian Studies”

This dissertation departs slightly from the traditional approach to “Ethiopian History.” Hence, it ascribes to the colonial thesis rather than the unification thesis on the formation of modern Ethiopia in the last decades of the 19th century. The departure is on approach rather than in content or on evidence. It departs from the tradition that places only Abyssinians and their kings, cultures, and religion (the Church) at its centre. Instead, it adopts the Oromo and their Gadaa System, their aadaa (culture), and Waaqeffannaa, not as the sole ‘centre’ but as one of the multinational centres of modern Ethiopia. It emphasises the historical reality that the kingdom of Abyssinia (Abyssinia Proper) colonised the numerous smaller kingdoms, republican states, and autonomous peoples who presently constitute the States of Oromia, SNNP, Gambella, Benishangul-Gumuz, Afar, Somali, and Harari with the support of European imperialist expansionists to build the Empire of Abyssinia-cum-modern Ethiopia in the late 19th century.

Furthermore, it departs from the contention in “Ethiopian History” that relegates the history of the Oromo, both those who had been part of the kingdom of Abyssinia and those who had had their republican Gadaa governments and later their traditional African monarchies (Mootii) before their forceful incorporation into the Empire of Abyssinia. Instead,

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it views the history of the Oromo, particularly the histories of the latter two groups, not only as independent but also as one that can stand on its own, parallel to Abyssinian history. Such departures have been standard in Oromo Studies, as published in the *Journal of Oromo Studies* (JOS), since the early 1990s, and in the Studies of settler-colonised southern nations of Ethiopia. Oromo Studies have emerged as an alternative to Abyssinian-monopolised “Ethiopian” Studies.

As “Ethiopian History” has failed and “Ethiopian” Studies, as an institution of the Abyssinian instrument of knowledge monopolisation, is struggling[[iii](#)], the emergent Oromo Studies and others have made a significant stride, particularly after the formation of the Ethiopian Federation that has restored some autonomy to the conquered peoples of the multinational state. This, however, could not be achieved without challenges from the establishment. The Abyssinian, long-standing intellectual guards of the failed “Ethiopian History” and the struggling “Ethiopian” Studies have continued to fight back, sometimes with the strength of verbal violence. They had also solicited support from Western Ethiopians, mainly Orientalist Europeans, who had founded the Studies in Europe before it relocated to Addis Ababa after the establishment of Haile Selassie I University, the precursor to the present-day Addis Ababa University, which hosts the Institute of Ethiopian Studies. In the meantime, the voices of Ethiopian History and “Ethiopian” studies have been growing. They are, however, yet to make a significant change: “While many scholars continue to support the Ethiopian version of history, others have realised the necessity of a plurality of centres in knowledge production and dissemination” (Jalata, 1996, p. 101). The same could be true in the case of “Ethiopian” studies. The struggle appears to have given Oromo Studies currency among some scholars, and their intellectual assurance for its potential to become a significant reformist to both “Ethiopian History” and “Ethiopian” Studies is only burgeoning.

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The emergent field of Oromo Studies has documented that “Ethiopian” Studies often overlook significant aspects of the Oromo people’s history, focusing almost exclusively on the history of Abyssinians (Amhara and Tigray) and their historic kings (Jalata, 1996, p. 95). Similarly, the state-sponsored “Ethiopian History” not only dismisses the plain recorded history of the Oromo but also distorts and undermines any historical facts or events related to the Oromo and other nations that were annexed to the kingdom of Abyssinia. It has fundamentally been the history of Abyssinian kings compiled by Abyssinian “Knowledge elites” (to use Professor Asafa Jalata’s expression), but it has become the “official” history of multinational, modern Ethiopia. Jalata (1996) summarises: “The Ethiopian knowledge elites, with the support of the Ethiopian state, produced ‘official’ history that completely denied a historical space for the Oromo and other colonised peoples” (p. 96).

Continued Marginalisation of the Oromo

During the building of the Empire of Abyssinia in the late 19th century and the first two decades of the 20th century, some prominent assimilated Oromo figures served in the administration of Atse Menelik. These assimilated Oromo heroes were incorporated into the administration to act on behalf of the Abyssinian elites, mainly due to the reputations they had earned through their bravery and the instrumental role they had played in the conquest of the Oromo. In other words, their role in the administration was limited, and their appointments to higher and higher positions were instrumental in allowing the Abyssinians to use them as a window dressing for the settler colonisation they instituted in the “colony countries” immediately after the conquest. Otherwise, the Oromo nation only became a second-class citizen with lost political autonomy and confiscated land and other resources. This did not happen before the war of colonial conquest, which would decimate half of the Oromo population.

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The few assimilated and agent Oromo personalities had continued to serve in the administration of Atse Haile Selassie I, aggrandising Abyssinian rule. The marginalisation of the Oromo nation from the cultural, political, and economic spheres of the empire continued. In 1930, with the ratification of the country's first written Constitution, the Empire of Abyssinia became known officially as the Empire of Ethiopia. However, this "Ethiopia" was reserved exclusively for the Abyssinians. They were the "Ethiopians"; the rest of modern Ethiopia's nations, nationalities, and peoples were not. The usurping of the name "Ethiopia" by Semitic Abyssinians of southern Arabian origin was a typical illustration of the love of a latecomer for the good old name. However, they loved it so much that they would not allow the ancient Ethiopians to be identified equally with the name. For the Oromo, the largest of the ancient Ethiopians, this was less important than the misery they had fallen into, which only grew. The administration of Atse Haile Selassie I banned the public use of the Oromo language. I denied equal opportunity to education, employment, and the manifestation of identity to the Oromo children. Increased settler-colonists (nafxanyaa/ [nɛft'ɲa:]) arrived in the Oromo country, uprooting a large number of Oromo and making them serfs. However, more Oromo were able to enrol themselves in the service of the administration at the lowest levels. Only a few could excel among the Abyssinians and prove they were fully assimilated into Abyssinian culture, earning higher government positions. Even so, they operated not as Oromo but as incorporated Abyssinians or as self-denying and selfless "Ethiopian" servants (galtuu) of the person of the Atse. The Government of Atse Haile Selassie I was confident that none of its officials had an Oromo agenda or represented the Oromo nation. Still, it inserted a few persons of Oromo origin in prominent positions in the government to alleviate Oromo resistance in their name. The Oromo nation remained far from the political centre of the Empire of Ethiopia.

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Under Mengistu Haile Mariam's Regime, more Oromo were integrated into the administration but remained intrinsically subordinate. The abolition of the monarchy in 1974 had given the Oromo a sense of optimism. Initially, the military government appeared to be listening to the voices of the oppressed. Some prominent Oromo leaders had established the Maccaa-Tuulamaa Self-help Association, the precursor of OLF, and it had mobilised a significant number of Oromo elites and masses. The Oromo members of ESM were also highly active in the movement that led to the abolition of the monarchy and the establishment of the newly formed government, at least in its early stages. A few years later, however, the Amhara bureaucracy and political elites dominated the military government. The Abyssinian-designed bureaucracy, which was built progressively during Menelik's and Haile Selassie's reigns, could not allow newcomers, such as the Oromo, to take prominent positions, nor could it allow the few Oromo military officers who held public offices to manoeuvre within the bureaucracy. The so-called "scientific socialism" ideology of the military government also continued to promote the 'one-nation, one culture, one national language, one Ethiopia' mantra of its predecessors that placed Abyssinian culture, language, and political view of the country at the centre. Nonetheless, regarding the representation of the Oromo in the government, the military government of Mengistu Hailemariam was better than its predecessors. However, the Oromo who took office were namesake Oromo and marginal players in the country's critical political circles, and they were structurally subordinate to the Abyssinian elites, even though the Oromo constituted about half of the population.

Simply put, these few namesakes, Oromo who served in the imperial and socialist governments of modern Ethiopia, were denatured from their Oromo identity and stood against the interests of the Oromo nation. They were mere agents who were delusional about both the history and identity of their people. They were ideologically fixated on the nation-

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building scheme of the Abyssinians and acted in good faith to achieve their objectives. However, that might have affected the people they came from. For most of them, the appreciation and appointment they received from the egotistical Atse Haile Selassie I (later from the belligerent Mengistu Hailemariam) or the praise they received from their duping Amhara or Tigre colleagues were more important than the interests of their people. They were mortified to be identified as Oromo and tried to hide their ethno-national identities. Except for the few who later realised they were selling out their people, they acted in the agency of the politically dominant oppressive nation, allowing the continued marginalisation of the Oromo nation from the political centre.

This unpropitious trend would continue even after the fall of the socialist regime in 1991. Under the TPLF/EPRDF regime, the Oromo nation has been represented by OPDO. It is a proxy party formed by TPLF in 1989 by organising captured Oromo soldiers of the Mengistu regime to counter the OLF. It has neither presented a genuine representation nor reflected the true agenda of the Oromo nation. It was formed to pave the way for the TPLF in its venture to take and monopolise the political power in Ethiopia. It was dreadfully successful in doing so. After the TPLF/EPRDF took state power in Ethiopia in May 1991, the OPDO could enlist self-interested members with undeveloped or misguided Oromo agendas.

The purge of the OLF from the Transitional Government of Ethiopia (TGE) in the summer of 1992 gave the OPDO sole representation of the Oromo nation in the government and the opportunity to succeed in its long-standing mission, which the TPLF had hindered. As a result, despite being dictated by the TPLF, the OPDO has effectively administered Oromia state since 1992. Despite the provision in the Constitution and the fact that it has been a critical sustainer of the TPLF/EPRDF regime, the OPDO has demonstrated little autonomy in administering the Oromo people and the resources of Oromia. It has been

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noticeably clear that the TPLF has been in total control of Oromia through its proxy. OPDO has been the third tier in the subordination echelon to the TPLF. The ANDM has been the second and proxy party of the TPLF, controlling the Amhara nation.

The OPDO has been the underdog of the TPLF-dominated EPRDF regime for over a quarter of a century. Some OPDO members, including the founders, have become laughingstocks in the public eye: they hold big titles but have little or no power to effect change as part of the federal government or as the government of Oromia State, which the TPLF disapproves of. Only recently have the younger generations of the Oromo, whose circumstances of livelihood forced them to join OPDO, started to stage an internal revolution against the TPLF-dominated EPRDF. This internal quiet revolution has threatened the OPDO with implosion. It has begun to pressure the TPLF-dominated EPRDF, which is also likely to implode if the OPDO does so, and it can no longer ignore the vital interests of Oromia.

Otherwise, the Oromo nation has not been able to have its fair share in both the shared rule and self-rule that the federal arrangement has constituted, nor has the position of the Oromo as a second-class citizen and as a political periphery in modern Ethiopia changed fundamentally. Due to a lack of strong representation in the federal government and the tailor-made, subservient nature of the OPDO, Oromia, despite being the “centre” of modern Ethiopia in all intents and purposes, has remained in the political periphery.

Challenging Stances in Oromo Politics

Misguided Attribution of “Ethiopia”

Oromo scholars who are highly affiliated with the politics of secession misattribute Ethiopia only to the Abyssinians. They inadvertently portray the Oromo as not being Ethiopians. This is mainly because they aspire to build an Oromo identity separate from Abyssinian Ethiopia-ness and as an antithesis to Habasha’s identity. It is instead a form of

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revolt against the political dominance of Abyssinians who considered themselves “Ethiopians” and the “owners” of modern Ethiopia. The revolution is driven by an aspiration to break free as an independent nation-state. Political revolts, however, must not obscure the Oromo of their identity, nor do the marginalisation and domination by Abyssinians in the last five quarters of a century forced the Oromo to abandon their identity and the aspiration to restore their true ancient Kushite Ethiopian identity. It is a mistake to recede one’s rightful ancient identity and designation simply because of the wish to build a separate nationalism and distinct identity excluding Abyssinians.

The reservation of the name Ethiopia for Abyssinians by these scholars is not without understanding that the Oromo are the largest nation of the true ancient Ethiopians and that they are more Ethiopians than Abyssinians. Indeed, the Oromo are not Habasha but Ethiopians. They are ancient Kush, the true Ethiopians. The Habasha (Abyssinians) are not the true ancient Kushite Ethiopians. They, however, have become Ethiopians: they are Abyssinian Ethiopians. Kushite Ethiopian nationalism and Abyssinian Ethiopian nationalism are not antithetical nationalisms but they are also not converging nationalisms. Modern Ethiopia comprises ancient indigenous Kushite Ethiopians (Oromo, Afar, Sidama, Kimant, Somali, Agaw, Beja, etc.) and Abyssinian Ethiopians (Tigre, Amhara, Argoba, etc.). Since its formation in the late 19th century, modern Ethiopia, where the Oromo are the largest nation with the largest territory, has become a motherland for all the NNPs who inhabit it. The attribution of the name “Ethiopia” to Abyssinia and Ethiopian nationalism only to Abyssinian Ethiopian nationalism by these scholars, while the Oromo and other Kushite nations in Ethiopia are the true ancient Ethiopia, and these could be an enormous animating force to rebuild genuine and ancient Kushite Ethiopian nationalism, is truly misguided.

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Promotion of Secession

It is also well known that a significant section of the Oromo people believe that secession from modern Ethiopia is the best course of action for the Oromo. The pioneer in this political idea is the OLF. The core of OLF's quest for political separation of Oromia from modern Ethiopia is linked to the colonial thesis that the kingdom of Abyssinia colonised Oromia in the last decades of the 19th century; this colonisation has continued to the present time in the form of settler colonisation and marginalisation. The more the Abyssinian political and religious elites, including the predisposed historians, have continued to undermine the Oromo nation. The Abyssinian-centered central governments have continued to marginalise the Oromo in the country's political, social, cultural, and economic spectrum despite being the majority, the more the OLF has become hardened at its struggle for independence of Oromia. In addition to those who prescribe the OLF political ideals, some Oromo elites believe that the historical relationship between the Oromo and the Abyssinians has proved that the two are incompatible. They argue that separation could be the best option for these two competing but incompatible nations. The Oromo, who subscribe to the political idea of OLF and the incompatibility hypothesis, could go for secession.

One of the main drives for secession has been the marginalisation of the history, culture, and language of the Oromo in modern Ethiopia, placing the Oromo in second-class citizenship. Abyssinian propaganda for total dominance and the ill-informed social and cultural policies that successive governments had implemented for over a century resulted in making the Oromo feel estranged and disenfranchised in their own country where they have always been the majority and their country has been the mainstay of the Ethiopian state. Also, the economic and political marginalisation of the Oromo in modern Ethiopia has made them resolve for independence where they would rebuild their identity, govern themselves with

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their democratic system (Gadaa System), and build the country of the Oromo people with the resources-rich Oromia at its centre.

However, resolving these grievances is more conceivable than political divorce because of it. Some of the grievances have been resolved since the formation of the Ethiopian Federation in 1995. The Oromo have the constitutional right to administer themselves (self-rule), to take part democratically in the administration of the federation (shared rule), and to rebuild their identity. They also have the right and the obligation to reverse the impacts of past governments' ill-informed policies and programs: the Constitution has granted, in its Preamble, "rectifying historically unjust relationships." Modern Ethiopia exists only if the Constitution is in place. The constitution presupposes that the Ethiopian state is indivisible unless the NNPs of Ethiopia decide so. The Constitution is also the guarantor of the national self-determination of NNPs, including the Oromo, if they wish. Nonetheless, it is evident that the present federation does more for the common good of all NNPs of modern Ethiopia than secession would do for any of them. Practically, the secession of Oromia would mean the end of modern Ethiopia. Neither the Oromo nor other NNPs of modern Ethiopia could be certain of a better prospect after the disintegration of modern Ethiopia, nor could the social and economic interconnectedness built for over a century allow peaceful and orderly political divorce. It is logical to conceive that the Oromo should aspire to attain their rightful socio-political and economic positions within modern Ethiopia rather than contemplating secession, which has become untenable.

Some factors make the secession of Oromia untenable. First, the unattainability of the secession of Oromia has its roots far back in history. As discussed above, northern Oromo communities who had infiltrated deep into the kingdom of Abyssinia had already been integrated with large numbers into the Abyssinian kingdom before the formation of modern

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Ethiopia. They constituted most of the population of the provinces of Wollo, Gojjam, Shewa, southern Gondar, and a district in southern Tigray. Considering the Oromo who had been incorporated into the kingdom of Aksum and the Oromo who had joined the kingdom of Abyssinia, it is highly likely that they constitute the majority in Abyssinia Proper. Also, they had already been integrated, at least partly, with other contiguous nations that have now constituted modern Ethiopia in all directions. Before their conquest in the late 19th century, they had inhabited a more extensive territory than the present Oromia. The integration and assimilation of the Oromo to Abyssinian identity have continued both in Abyssinia Proper and in the rest of the country since the formation of modern Ethiopia. Even though the Oromo constitute the largest nation in current Ethiopia, the imagined independent Oromia should not exclude these millions of assimilated Oromo residing outside Oromia. Besides, the Oromo have assimilated interested minority nationalities throughout history and intermixed with other NNPs of modern Ethiopia for centuries. The historical inter-relationship between the Oromo and other NNPs of Ethiopia alone makes the Oromo (Oromia) secession untenable.

Second, the geographical location of Oromia in modern Ethiopia and the interdependence of the NNPs make secession next to impossible. Having a look at the map of Oromia in Ethiopia suffices this point. The secession of Oromia means dismemberment of the whole of modern Ethiopia. It is evident that, even if such is the interest of the Oromo, it may differ from that of all other NNPs of modern Ethiopia, who have signed the constitutional pact and formed one nation.

Third, modern Ethiopia's economic integration and infrastructure network do not allow secession. Even though the Oromo have been disadvantaged for so long in this regard, Oromia has always been the economic and infrastructural hub of modern Ethiopia. Since the

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last two decades, the economic integration and infrastructural interdependence between and among the states of the federation have been growing steadily. The federal government has been investing a large amount of money, which it borrows in the name of all Ethiopians, on mega development projects dotted across the country. The economic and infrastructural links among the states have now reached the level that one is necessarily complementary to the other, and each is too dependent on the other. Global socio-political and economic trends also fully support the continuation of such interdependence if the people are to benefit from it.

Fourth, the very social position of the Oromo in the Horn of Africa region stands against secession. As illustrated in detail above under From Kush to Oromia: A General Introduction, the Oromo are the largest Kushite nation not only in modern Ethiopia but also in the whole region of the Horn of Africa. In modern Ethiopia, a federation of over eighty NNPs, the Oromo alone constitute about forty per cent of the population. By the very virtue of being the largest nation, the Oromo have the sociological legitimacy to take the central leadership position in modern Ethiopia democratically, not the compulsion to secede from it. This is not only because the Oromo are the embodiment of ancient Kush and ancient Ethiopia but also because they are the majority in modern Ethiopia. It is also because they are better positioned to unite and lead democratically the Kushite and non-Kushite nations and nationalities of modern Ethiopia and beyond. To this, their demonstrated democratic and republican government system, the Gadaa System, now a UNESCO-inscribed heritage of humanity, stands as a testament.

Averting Divisive and Dangerous Narrative

In addition to the limitations of Oromo Studies mentioned briefly above, emerging narratives about the Oromo of modern Ethiopia offer little practical or theoretical help. Donald Levine (2007) has attempted to categorise them perilously into three: traditionalist,

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colonialist, and Ethiopianist. Some argue that this compartmentalisation has the merit of contributing to the understanding of the Oromo history and self-perceptions, or “the comparison of collective narratives forms a theoretically fascinating subject for historical sociology” or “plays a necessary part in orienting Ethiopian actors, like any others, to a changing world” (Levine, 2007, pp. 44, 45).

However, the narratives are neither mutually exclusive nor do any of them capture the full view of the Oromo about themselves in Ethiopia. The traditionalist narrative emphasises the traditional Oromo values, including the Gadaa and Qaalluu institutions. However, it de-emphasises the historical reality of Abyssinians’ settler colonisation of the Oromo. The Ethiopianist narrative affirms that the Oromo have always been Ethiopians. However, it fails to make clear distinctions: first, between Ancient Ethiopia (Kush Ethiopia) and Abyssinian Ethiopia; second, between the Oromo who had integrated with the kingdom of Abyssinia since the 16th century and the Oromo who had remained independent under their republican Gadaa governments until Atse Menelik II subjugated them in the last decades of the 19th century. It also fails to acknowledge the brutality with which Atse Menelik II incorporated the Oromo into the Empire of Abyssinia-cum-modern Ethiopia. The colonialist narrative emphasises the historical turn of events in the late 19th century, where the republican Gadaa governments and the traditional Oromo monarchies (Mootii) fell under the political, economic, social, cultural, and linguistic dominance of Abyssinians (Amhara and Tigre). It de-emphasises the historical fact that sections of the Oromo had not only been part of the domain of the kingdom of Abyssinia and its rulers and monarchs. In addition, it overlooks the shared values that the Oromo have developed with the Abyssinians over centuries through their interactions, whether in war or peace. Moreover, all three narratives focus exclusively on the Oromo of modern Ethiopia, excluding passively those who reside in Kenya and

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elsewhere in the Horn of Africa region. As a result, one finds that they are neither complete by themselves nor mutually exclusive, and the compromise would be too much to promote any of them.

In addition, although it may be intended for genuine academic purposes, attempting to establish three narratives based on the unjustified differences among them, considering a more extended historical period, would only result in dividing the Oromo, as some Oromo may subscribe to one or the other narrative. Since its emergence about a decade ago, the Oromo scholars have already shown interest in choosing between the narratives, at least temporarily. Ultimately, this would likely become a significant dividing element for the Oromo nation. Oromo is one nation; ordinary sensibleness dictates that one nation should have one national narrative, not three. Unifying the three narratives that currently divide the Oromo nation, or developing a new unifying national narrative, before the cursory compartmentalisation takes hold, may save the Oromo nation from the scorn of allowing yet another potentially long-lasting source of division that would only weaken the Oromo nation.

Three Perilous Narratives

It is also well known that some Oromo scholars and politicians promote continued integration of the Oromo under the Abyssinian-centered “Ethiopian” umbrella. This group of scholars and politicians subscribe to the “Ethiopia-nist” narrative. They cite some historical contributions of the Oromo in the kingdom of Abyssinia (Abyssinia Proper) and the process of the formation of modern Ethiopia. Few of them, such as Fikre Tolossa Jigsa, even go further and assert without convincing evidence that the Oromo and the Amhara descended from the same ancestry. The frontier minority northern Oromo communities had been an integral part of the kingdom of Abyssinia before the conquest of the rest of the Oromo of modern Ethiopia. It is also true that the conquest of the rest of the Oromo would not have

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been possible without the active and dedicated collaboration of political elites and warlords of these minority Oromo communities. In both cases, however, these minority Oromo communities did not act on behalf of the Oromo nation, nor did they represent the whole Oromo nation. They functioned as assimilated Abyssinians and, in the interest of the kingdom of Abyssinia, as proxies. Of course, the Oromo constituted an incredibly massive portion of the Abyssinian population and even managed to rule the kingdom by installing puppet Atses on the so-called Solomonic throne during the Yejju Dynasty, aka Era of Princes.

Nevertheless, the claim that the Amhara and the Oromo descended from the same mythical ancestry as Abyssinian Ethiopians is farcical. This dissertation has illustrated the Oromo are the true ancient Ethiopians: the core of Abyssinian Amhara has only become Ethiopians arriving from southern Arabia around the turn of the Common Era. The dissertation has also illustrated that, except for the northern minority Oromo communities, which integrated with Abyssinian Proper and Maccaa Oromo communities of Gibie region and Qeellam Wellega, which instituted Oromo monarchies (Mootiis) starting from the first half of the 19th century, the vast mainstream Oromo had remained independent and administered itself with its noble Gadaa System until the conquest by the kingdom of Abyssinia in the last decades of the 19th century. Therefore, it is baseless to claim that the Oromo have been part and parcel of the kingdom of Abyssinia, and hence, they have been just as ‘Ethiopians’ as the Abyssinians.

Recent Oromo Studies subscribe to the colonial thesis on the formation of modern Ethiopia and tend to promote faultily the secession of Oromia based on it. In line with the colonial thesis, this dissertation has illustrated how the failure of the Oromo struggle against Abyssinian subjugation resulted in the institutionalisation of Abyssinian settler colonialism. The kingdom of Abyssinia, which morphed itself into modern Ethiopia, systematically colonized the Oromo first by subduing them by force and the threat of force and subsequently

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by settling Amhara and Tigre *nafxanyaa* (armed settler-colonists) among them for about a century. The settler colonisation is evident across Oromia, where the descendants of *nafxanyaa* are scattered across the rural Oromo land and stand out in the former garrison towns. They stand out because of either state-engineered economic domination that favoured them or the inheritance of a significant property plundered and seized from the Oromo by their colonist grandfathers. However, the colonial thesis remains valid only for the historical period in which the Oromo were under settler colonisation, from the last decades of the 19th century until the fall of the imperial regime in 1974. This period was very limited in the long history of the Oromo nation in the Horn of Africa. Overemphasising this short period of settler colonisation of the Oromo and playing excessively as a victimised nation only undermines the long history of the Oromo nation and undercuts the more significant role the Oromo nation should play both in modern Ethiopia and in the Horn of Africa region. The Oromo are not under any active settler colony anymore, but they are under continued systemic marginalisation from the political centre, which must be redressed with holistic, unifying, and visionary socio-political narrative and democratic processes. Constitutionally speaking, they have been in a voluntarily suspended liberation since the ratification of the Constitution in 1995 that guarantees the self-determination of NNPs, including secession. Hence, the colonial thesis ceases to make any political sense but preserves a history. No active political program of the Oromo nation in modern Ethiopia should be based on the colonial thesis or a narrative thereof. Indeed, such a narrative should be abandoned from the politics of the Oromo for the greater good of the peaceful and democratic promotion of the Oromo to the political centre of modern Ethiopia and its leadership in the Horn of Africa region.

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A growing group of scholars promotes the idea that the Oromo nation had a traditional form of government before the emergence of some Oromo monarchies (Mootii) and the formation of modern Ethiopia to which it should stick. This conventional form of government is the republican Gadaa government. Gadaa's government existed alongside the traditional monarchy of the Abyssinian peoples and principalities and sultanates of the Muslim peoples of northeast Africa. The scholars also promote traditional philosophy and the way of life of the Oromo as a uniquely Oromo. They believe everything that defines the ethnographic character of the Oromo (for example, the Gadaa System and its institutions, the Qaalluu, and the Waaqeffannaa religion) have been uniquely theirs. They hold that the social institutions of the Oromo are based on reasonableness and the power of logical thinking. They also acknowledge that Oromo are always cognizant that their ancestors had achieved an advanced thought process that helped them to develop a unique and unconventional socio-political system, the Gadaa System, and pioneered monotheistic belief in one universal Waaqa, Waaqeffannaa. The Oromo are known for happily sharing their values, including ethnographic characters and worldviews, with every nation without any imposition. However, scholars believe that adopting the values of others in recent centuries, including the ethnographic character of other neighbourly peoples, has brought Oromo wretchedness. As a result, they contend, the Oromo today find it increasingly difficult to accept the cultures and values of others than share theirs with them. In other words, they contend, the Oromo tend to be inward-looking and specific than outward-looking and universal. The scholars suggest that the Oromo would do well by upholding their unique traditions, including their traditional form of Government. This group of scholars, therefore, promotes the "traditionalist" narrative.

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This narrative, however, is embedded in the former two narratives: it cannot stand by itself. It is also complementary to the new narrative that the present dissertation submits. Also, paradoxically, the traditional form of government of the Oromo was much more advanced in some respects than modern American republicanism and modern federalism. Furthermore, it is evident that ‘particularism,’ ‘traditionalism,’ and ‘exclusivism’ are declining as globalisation and international integration are pressing forward. In the context of the Oromo in modern Ethiopia and the Horn of Africa, Oromo political traditionalism must give way to the accommodation of views and traditions of other nations. In other words, except when necessary, the Oromo should abandon traditionalism and particularism (and exclusivism) to accommodate and reasonably share the views of other nations in preparation for taking national and regional leadership in Ethiopia and the Horn of Africa, respectively.

Summary and Conclusion

Abyssinian historiography, or Ethiopian history, has never been fair to the Oromo. Since the 16th-century victory of the Oromo over the kingdom of Abyssinia, the records of the kingdom have always portrayed the Oromo as “strangers,” “newcomers,” “invaders,” and “pagans,” and blamed them for their misfortunes or failures. Most of their spiritual and secular records from the 16th to the mid-19th century reflect these hostile portrayals. During the late 19th and early 20th centuries, following their military success against the Oromo, Abyssinians made a concerted effort to undermine the Oromo nation in retribution for their defeats over several centuries. Some Abyssinian monks and learned elites who ventured to write the history of the Oromo gave little emphasis on presenting historical facts. They were concerned with asserting Abyssinian State propaganda of “unification” of ancient territories, an excuse for the colonisation of over a dozen independent kingdoms and states at the end of the 19th century.

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Additionally, they were engaged in a unilateral psychological warfare campaign by the Amhara-dominated kingdom against the Oromo. These have been incorporated into the “official” history of the Kingdom of Abyssinia, now modern Ethiopia. Until the 21st century, almost all the medieval and modern “history” of the Oromo has been written by its historical enemy, who fought with them for nearly four hundred years without success until the end of the 19th century, when external influences tipped the status quo. It needs no reasonable effort to illustrate how biased the history of a nation could be when it is written only by its historical “enemy” for many centuries. Alternatively, when the writings of this “enemy” and its oral traditions are used by distant travellers, explorers, geographers, and diplomats, who had only visited the nation very briefly over centuries, as significant input or as the only source in their attempt to write the history of this “enemy.” The non-Abyssinian writers of some accounts of the Oromo’s history within the context of the Abyssinian Empire were largely unfamiliar with the Oromo. They invariably orchestrated the Abyssinian version of the hate-filled “history” of the “enemy” of Abyssinians, the Oromo. As a result, the history of the Oromo to date has remained largely confined to a parochial view of its enemies.

The 20th-century Abyssinian and Western writers of “Ethiopian History” continued to embellish and “Aryanize” earlier records. They followed their predecessors in vilifying the Oromo nation in Abyssinian historiography. After the formation of the Empire of Abyssinia at the end of the 19th century, the only notable new addition of styling to the Abyssinian pseudo-history was its “Aryanization.” This was a “contribution” by Europeans. Following the praiseworthy military and diplomatic successes of Atse Menelik II, “Ethiopian history” was “Aryanized” to further distinguish it from that of the rest of the African continent” in the supposition that such successes “could only be attributed to a people superior to the rest of the Africans even if they are not as good as the Europeans” (Adejumobi, 2007, p. 31). This

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supposition not only continued to galvanise the settler colonisation of the Amhara-Tigre alliance that was instituted in the regions conquered by Atse Menelik II, but also its tone found its way into the Abyssinian mentality and the “Ethiopian History.” Together with the fable of the new “Chosen People,” attributed to Abyssinians in the legend of Kebra Nagast since the 14th century (Haberland, 1992, pp. 705-706), the “Aryanization” was perhaps the main reason why some Abyssinians, including Atse Menelik II and Atse Haile Selassie I (Spencer, 2006, p. 306), had considered themselves Caucasians. Until recently, some scholars in Abyssinia were convinced that Abyssinians excelled in intelligence over other Africans, including the Oromo. Such conviction, however, has remained coded not only in the self-identification of Abyssinians as “Habasha“ to distinguish themselves from the rest of the peoples of sub-Saharan Africa (Even though the term historically meant otherwise in its Arabic origin) but also in the failed “Ethiopian History” that presents Abyssinians as historically superior to the rest of the nations, nationalities, and peoples of modern Ethiopia.

Especially regarding the Oromo, “Ethiopian History” goes much further. It portrays the Oromo as “newcomers,” “strangers,” and “invaders” in their own ancestral land. This is a portrayal that would not be different from, for example, the ludicrousness of white settler Europeans portraying the Native Americans or Australian aboriginals as alien when they would write their history after a millennium in what would appear to be an attempt to transpose the history of migration of their own. One of the core injustices of “Ethiopian history” had been this resolute and ethnocentric attempt of Abyssinian political and religious elites to invert the migration history of the Agazi and Habashat Abyssinians by absurdly projecting it to the contending indigenous Oromo.

The primary objective of claiming that the Oromo were 16th-century newcomers to central Ethiopia and relentlessly propagating this claim has been part of the failed attempt by

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Abyssinian elites to inversely glorify Abyssinians (Tigrethe Amhara–Tigre alliance) by attempting to invert the history of migration of their own people by projecting it onto the Oromo. This attempt has been evident in the ambiguous identity that the Abyssinians have had, even as recently as the first half of the last century. By viewing themselves as non-African by origin, by emphasising their Sabaeen, Jewish, and Christian heritage over their African culture and identity, Abyssinians viewed the true African peoples of modern Ethiopia as “alien and inferior” (Legesse, 2006, p. xiii). Unfortunately, the embellished and “Aryanized” pseudo-history has been accepted at face value as “Ethiopian History” at least by some Abyssinian-Ethiopianist historians and their Western translation copyists and “Aryanizers” until the 1960s. This attempt to invert the history of the Oromo’s origin had continued in the failed “Ethiopian History” until very recently. It has had a lasting damage on the history of the Oromo. It has only been since the end of the Abyssinian monarchy in the 1970s that the long attempt finally came to fail conclusively. By the 1990s, it had become clear that Abyssinian concocted “Ethiopian History” had failed. However, the unpretentious history of the Oromo and other nations of Ethiopia, even those that had not yet been written, had survived against the odds.

The failure of Abyssinian fashioning “Ethiopian History” could be attributed to three reasons. First, the end of the systemic suppression of Ethiopian nations and nationalities by successive governments dominated by the Tigrie–Amhara alliance; second, the exposition of historical facts that have been deliberately neglected or brushed under the rug by Abyssinian political, historical, and religious elites; and third, the emergence of historical scholarship from the part of the non-Abyssinians.

However, a comprehensive history of the Ethiopian nations, nationalities, and peoples that would fully and justly replace the failed “Ethiopian History” is yet to be written. The

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failure of Abyssinian-produced “Ethiopian History” has encouraged some nations to write their own history. However, these newly written histories have been primarily self-centred, and some have shown little regard for other nations or peoples. Furthermore, the country’s predominantly ethnic and language-based political orientation has historically sparked competition among Ethiopia’s nations, nationalities, and peoples. This appears to have generated a sense of overcorrecting history as a form of retaliation by formerly disadvantaged groups against the historical records produced and written into the failed “Ethiopian History” by the former socio-politically dominant Abyssinians.

On the other hand, the formerly advantaged groups in the failed “Ethiopian History” have continued to hold to it even more aggressively so that their political and historical elites have continued to produce more absurd claims, all intended to the advantage of their ethnicity. There is no consensus on any part of the “History of Ethiopia” among the Ethiopian nations, nationalities, and peoples on how it has been produced and taught at schools. For the Tigrie and Amhara Abyssinians, on the one hand, it could not have been written and taught any better. For non-Abyssinians, on the other hand, it could not have been written and taught any worse. As a result, Ethiopian history, so to speak, appears to be in total disarray. As a multinational nation, Ethiopia has no comprehensive written history, nor does the Oromo.

The Oromo (and other non-Abyssinian peoples) have been systematically marginalised in Abyssinian historiography and Ethiopian history. Even though they have been the majority – accounting for almost one-third of the geography and population of modern Ethiopia – and the Oromo largely shape Ethiopia, the Oromo have been relegated to second-class citizens with apparently little or no history of their own in Abyssinian historiography. As historiography, compiled mainly from hate-filled writings of religious and political elites of the kingdom of Abyssinia who considered the Oromo as the political and religious enemy

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and wrote about them accordingly, Abyssinian history is known for being more of a legend than genuine history. It has always been far removed from professional fairness, historical evidence, and the truth itself. Transforming such “history” to a multinational history of modern Ethiopia by Abyssinian and a few cooperating Western scholars was one of the historical injustices ever committed. This injustice stands to be corrected, and it is high time that the Oromo find their rightful place in the history of modern Ethiopia and set Oromo historiography on course.

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Chapter 3. Sociological Realignment: The Oromo as Ancient Ethiopians

The Oromo as the First Nation of Ancient Ethiopia

The northeast Africa, specifically the Horn of Africa region, is known to be the cradle land of humanity and the origin of civilization. The region had been known as Kush before the Greek Αιθιοπια and its latter English transliteration, Ethiopia (ancient Ethiopia) replaced it. Kush, according to the Bible, is the geography encompassed by the river Ghion (Nile) (Genesis, 2:13 [KJV]). This refers to the region east of the Nile. The modern human has inhabited it for tens of thousands of years. In the historical center of Kush, the modern Republic of Sudan, archeologists have found Paleolithic tools dating 70,000 years. Kushite peoples have inhabited it since antiquity. The Kushite civilization, which enriched Egypt, crossed to Europe, and was further developed by the Greeks and Romans. It began some 15,000 years ago along the river Nile in modern Sudan. Scholars believe this region is where human society formed a political entity and a nation and began unraveling human creativity and civilization. This human creativity and civilization are commonly known as the Kushite civilization.

The Oromo--the largest Kushite nation of the present time--have maintained a firm belief that they were the first nation (Keane, 1920). Their oral chronicles claim that they were the first nation on earth; hence, they were the first to introduce nationalism, political entity, and organized worship. The fact that Kushites (Hamitic race) “were the first to give the world ideas of government” (Sir H. H. Johnson cited in Houston, 1926 [2004], p. 17) reinforces the claim. Furthermore, “Stephanus of Byzantium, voicing the universal testimony of antiquity, writes, ‘Ethiopia was the first established country on earth, and the Ethiopians were the first to set up the worship of the gods and to establish laws’” (Houston, 1926 [2004], pp. 17-18).

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Through progressive cultural and socio-political advancements, the Oromo of Upper Ethiopia (Cush–Ethiopia) gradually became one of the distinct Cushitic nations. They have, however, kept the ancient culture (aadaa) and at least the closest variant of the ancient language (afaan) of Kush. In the true sense of nationalism, the Oromo are indeed pioneering in promoting and implementing the very political ideal that public administration (state and government) must represent and serve the people (the nation) that have personal liberties and shared culture, history, and everyday psychological make-up. The Oromo have always believed that they are born free; only laws made by themselves have governed them; they have always had a country that they call Biyya or Biyya Abbaa (Father Land); all the Oromo sub-moieties, junior moieties, gosa (clans), lineages, etc. descended from common ancestry. Regardless of where they live, they have always maintained that the Oromo are one nation, and they have only one pan-Oromo system, the Gadaa System.

On this antediluvian sense of nationhood, the Oromo were able to form the Gadaa System and republican form of government, Gadaa Government. According to oral chronicles, they could form as early as the beginning of the first millennium BCE (Lata, 1998; Bokku, 2011). The Gadaa System is a holistic political, social, cultural, economic, and ritual system. It is a democratic and republican system. Gadaa Constitution (Heera Gadaa) is the foundation of the Gadaa government. Gadaa government is a government with no king, no masters, and no hereditary influence but led by the men elected by the people for limited single-term office according to the laws made by the people. It is a form of government that would fit perfectly with Abraham Lincoln’s revered expression: “Government of the people, by the people, and for the people.”

The Gadaa System has prevailed to date. The pioneering Oromo nationalism may have invented the Gadaa System and formed the Gadaa Government at least tens of centuries

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before the emergence of the political ideology of nationalism in the West. However, historical records about them from before the 16th century are very scarce. The first detailed account of the Gadaa System comes from Abyssinian records. Even though relatively recent, embellished, and self-centered records of Abyssinian chroniclers have recorded that the Oromo had a full-fledged pan-Oromo republican form of government. This republican government mobilized the Oromo nation and defeated the powerful Christian kingdom of Abyssinia in the 16th century. Since then, the Gadaa System has been through challenging times, but it has endured. In some parts of the Oromia State of modern Ethiopia, the Gadaa government, though with minimal political legitimacy, is functioning to date as both a parallel and complementing system to the state and local governments of the federal system.

The homeland of the Kushites, ancient Ethiopians, was known in antiquity as Kush. In pre-historical times, the ancient Egyptians knew all the known peoples of the continent of Africa beyond Egypt, such as Kush. Kush existed as a contending power in ancient Egypt for at least two millennia before the Common Era. From the tiny and flat world, centered with the Mediterranean Sea, the Greeks understood Kush in pre-history as the unknown end of that world beyond Egypt. This was known to the first historian, Herodotus (490-425 BCE), and represented on the reconstructed ancient map, “The World according to Herodotus,” which barely depicts the northeastern part of Africa. The diminished representation was due to minimal knowledge of the expanse of the vast continent of Africa. This part of the continent has been the homeland of the ancient Kushites. They are readily identifiable today by their Cushitic languages.

During the first half of the last millennium BCE, the land of Kush (Αιθιοπια) was a wonderland to the Greeks. They knew little but admired everything about it. They even believed that it was inhabited not only by human beings of ideal body features but also by

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gods. From around 800 BCE accounts of Homer in the *Iliad* and *Odyssey*, humanity learns not only those Greek gods (Jupiter, Zeus, and Poseidon) had solid affections for Ethiopians (Kushites), but both gods and the heaven dwellers visited them frequently. Humanity also learns from Homer that children of an Ethiopian (Kush) and Eos, Menon, and Emathion ruled Arabia and Troy, respectively, and the former died fighting the Greeks. “The inhabitants of Troy ... who fought so valiantly in the Trojan War, were Cushite Ethiopians” (Houston, 1926 [2004], p. 30).

Modern linguistic studies have shown that the Cushitic language represents the ancient indigenous peoples of east and northeast Africa. It means three ancient peoples: Puntine in the Horn of Africa, Nubian in the Upper Nile Valley, and Egyptians in the Lower Nile Valley (Delebo, 2007, p. 14). Before the use of the name Αἰθιοπία (Aithiopia) by the Greeks, these three ancient peoples were known as Kush (or Kushites). They have inhabited the northeast and east Africa since antiquity. In other words, they have inhabited the region between the Nile, the Red Sea, the Equator, and the Mediterranean Sea since the end of the Stone Age. They were “encroached upon in prehistoric times by Semites and others in Egypt and Abyssinia, and in historic times chiefly by Semites (Arabs) in Egypt, Upper Nubia, Senaar, and Somaliland” (Keane, 1920, p. 89). Among these ancient peoples represented by the Cushitic language, the Oromo are the largest and the most widespread in the region.

Geographically, Cushitic language-speaking peoples (the three ancient peoples) of Africa have inhabited the vast territory that, according to the Bible, belonged to the Hamitic domain of Africa. In antiquity, however, the language of the ancient Kushites, “Hamitic tongue,” was spoken in a much wider region, including the Middle East, part of Asia, and part of Europe (H. G. Wells and Sir H. H. Johnson cited in Houston, 1926 [2004], p. 17). This shows the scope of the ancient Cushite Empire that gradually shrunk to the Upper Nile in

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historic times. The old “Hamitic tongue” might have split into many localized dialects that might have become the many Cushitic languages currently spoken in northeast and east Africa. Afaan Oromoo, the Oromo language, is the most widely spoken Cushitic language.

The practical geographic application of the name “Kush” had shifted over the millennia before it was demoted to the historical kingdom of Kush in modern Sudan (North). The ancient Kushites had a glorious empire (the first to have been established) that encompassed parts of Africa, Asia, and Europe (Houston, 1926 [2004]). During Dynastic Egypt, however, Kush was simply the name of the region and kingdom south of Egypt with unknown limits into the little-explored heartland of the continent. Ancient “Ethiopia” of the Greek antiquity was “Kush” of the Bible.

Herodotus (490-425 BCE), however, made it clear that his Ethiopia, aptly Kush, was a country where Ethiopians (Kushites) lived, “where the south declines towards the setting sun,” and both the country and the people were loved by Greek gods. It was the last inhabited rich country in the southwest (from Egypt), with its capital at Meroe. Its inhabitants, though culturally like ancient Egyptians, were tall, handsome, long-lived, and unmatched anywhere. At the later stage, the Empire of Kush was limited to the historical Kingdom of Kush. It was unmistakably the region that is encompassed by the Blue Nile and Lake Tana in the south, the Nile in the west, the Red Sea in the east, and Elephantine in the north.

The Kingdom of Kush existed in the region that includes North and South Sudan and some parts of northwestern Ethiopia and western Eritrea. This was the “Ethiopia” of Drusilla D. Houston, described as “The whole of the space between the Nile and Abyssinia, and northward to Lower Egypt once constituted Ethiopia” (Houston, 1926 [2004], p. 40) except that it excluded northwestern Ethiopia by excluding Abyssinia. The kingdom of Kush

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existed during Egypt's Old and Middle Kingdoms (2686–1650 BCE). Some early historians have referred to this kingdom as the representation of the rest of Sub-Saharan Africa. This was when only little was known about the rest of Africa beyond Egypt.

Kush gradually became the central northeast and East Africa region in the first half of the first millennium BCE. Homer (440 BCE), Herodotus (490–425 BCE), Siculus (60 BCE), and Strabo (63 BCE–24 CE) have indicated the territory of Ethiopia as the vast country south of Egypt in the Nile Basin regions and beyond the sea (including southern Arabia) inhabited by handsome, brave, and civilized peoples of dark skin. The kingdom was also known as Ancient Ethiopia.

Kush was also a racial representation during the late Hellenistic and Roman times. During this period, the continent of Africa, especially Sub-Saharan Africa, became the racial geography of all the dark-skinned peoples. In Hebrew, Kushi means both Samaritan and a black person or black African (Leeman, 2005, pp. 96, 130, 136). Also, note in the Bible (Jeremiah, 13:23 [KJV]): “Can the Ethiopian [Kush] change his skin, or the leopard his spots?” Accordingly, regardless of where they lived, all people with dark skin were known as Ethiopians. In line with this racial geography, some geographers employed the name “Ethiopia,” an English transliteration of the Greek Αἰθιοπία, on their maps to designate regions inhabited by people of dark skin until as recently as in the late 19th century. Some have employed the name not only to refer to the non-Arab Sub-Saharan African peoples in general but also to the Atlantic Ocean as well, calling it the “Ethiopian Ocean.”

The “dark-skinned” peoples of modern Sub-Saharan Africa were further categorized into geographic groups based on presumed relative cultural advancement, the depth of the dark pigmentation of their skin, and their general facial features. The Sub-Saharan Africa region inhabited by people believed to have Hamitic origin became known as “Ethiopia,” the

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geographic “Ethiopia.” Some early detailed maps of Africa represented this geographic “Ethiopia” itself as “Upper Ethiopia“ and “Lower Ethiopia” (see Figure 2) (Frankel, 2008). The former may aptly be called “Cush–Ethiopia.”

This geographic Upper Ethiopia and Lower Ethiopia constituted most of the continent of Africa. Upper Ethiopia (Cush–Ethiopia) included Nubian Ethiopia, Abyssinian Ethiopia, and the greater Upper Ethiopia. Nubian Ethiopia is the present Sudan. Abyssinian Ethiopia is the current State of Eritrea and Tigray, Amhara, and Afar national regional states of modern Ethiopia combined. The greater upper Ethiopia is a vast region. It includes most of southern modern Ethiopia (Oromia, Southern Nations, Nationalities, and Peoples’ (SNNP), Gambella, Somali, and Benishangul–Gumuz national regional states of Ethiopian Federation), South Sudan, western Somalia, Kenya, Uganda, Burundi, Rwanda, northern Malawi, northwestern Mozambique, west Tanzania, Zambia, Central African Republic, the Democratic Republic of the Congo, and northern Zimbabwe. Lower Ethiopia included western Sudan, most of part of Chad, Niger, Mali, Senegal, and Burkina Faso, southern Mauritania, northern Guinea, northern Ivory Coast, northern Ghana, northern Togo, northern Benin, northern Nigeria, and northern Cameroon. It included the western part of the region, otherwise known as the Sahel in modern times.

The Kushites of the Horn of Africa region belonged to Upper Ethiopia (Kush Ethiopia). They most likely had a vast multinational empire located between the Equator and Lower Egypt in northeast Africa. They had built the ancient Empire of Kush. Ancient Kush was the greatest, perhaps the first, civilization that began on the banks of the river Nile some 15,000 years ago. This ancient Kush is sometimes referred to as ancient Ethiopia because, according to Stephanus of Byzantium, Ethiopia [Kush] was the first country established on earth (Houston, 1926 [2004]). This prehistoric ancient Kush could be referred to as the ancient

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Empire of Kush. At its height, the Empire of Kush could have exerted economic and cultural influences over the vast territory between the Nile Basin, the continent's northeast coast, and a significant part of the Middle East and the eastern Mediterranean world. Punt might be part of the Empire of Kush at its height. Historical evidence indicates that a Kushite polity known to the ancient Egyptians as Punt existed farther southeast of the political center of the historical kingdom of Kush. It existed starting from the third millennium BCE. It might have included the Horn of Africa region north of the equator and south of Upper Egypt. It had a strong trading relationship with Egypt from about 2800 to 1000 BCE, as attested by pictorial depictions of the present peoples of the Horn of Africa region (Delebo, 2007). The peoples of ancient Punt include facial features and cultural elements (including the style of dressing) of the pictorial depictions from ancient Egypt illustrates those who still inhabit the Horn of Africa today. These include the Oromo, Somali, Afar, and other Cushitic and Omotic language-speaking peoples of the Horn of Africa region. The Oromo are one of the indigenous nations that have inhabited the Horn of Africa region of Upper Ethiopia since their ethnogenesis in Upper Egypt and the beginning of their southward movement along the eastern flank of the Nile and its tributaries in highland modern Ethiopia. Presently, the Oromo constitute forty percent of the population of modern Ethiopia (Ofcansky and Berry, 2004; Adejumobi, 2007; Baxter, 1996; Hussein, 2005). They are estimated to be about fifty million in the Horn of Africa region.

It was during 3500–1000 BCE that demographic increase, which led to state formation in other parts of the world, resulted in the formation of what could be called the “proto-Gadaa System” among Eastern Kushites (Ehert, 2000, cited in Hinew, 2012, p. 99). This proto-Gadaa System was a cycle of an age-set system that repeated itself in an initiation ceremony every eight years. It was developed for achieving social cohesion. Through time, it

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might have served the Oromo as the springboard to developing the full-fledged socio-political system known as the Gadaa System. According to some studies and the scholars of Oromo oral chronicles (*argaa-dhageettii*), the Oromo people invented the Gadaa System of government around the end of this period (Lata, 1998, p. 131; Bokku, 2011, p. 162).

This suggests that when the State was formed in the Middle and Lower Nile regions, the Gadaa System (*Sirna Gadaa*) was included in the Upper Nile Basin. According to Christopher Ehret, the Kushites expanded in the Northeast and East Africa region during 3500-1000 BCE, and the separate Oromo identity development (ethnogenesis) from among the *KonsOromo* communities took place in the early first millennium BCE (Ehret, 2002, cited in Ta'a, 2004, p. 1). This later period could be the time the Oromo nationhood was born. An etymological analysis of the name Oromo from Ormaa also suggests that the formation of the Oromo nationhood could result from the gradual development of the would-be Oromo nation's political distinction and subsequent separation seeking liberty and freedom. Since its formation, according to oral traditions, the Oromo nation has governed itself almost entirely by the Gadaa System.

There is little doubt that the Oromo oral traditions, which place the genesis and nationhood of the Oromo far back in antiquity, are accurate oral records of the history of the Oromo. The *argaa-dhageettii* ("seen-and-heard") scholars are well-respected and authoritative historians of the Oromo nation. They are highly skilled and purpose-trained former *Abbaa Gadaas* who have been tested for honesty, memory, and accuracy. It is necessary that they have a higher level of mental competence for comprehension of the Oromo philosophy, knowledge of nature, knowledge of the Gadaa System, and the Oromo laws. They must be well versed with *Seera Uumaa* (natural laws) and *Seera Tumaa* (man-made laws). The latter includes *Heera* (Gadaa Constitution) and *Seera* (Gadaa laws that have

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been made at central and regional assemblies of the multitude (Caffees) and are current).

Also, they must be gifted with higher wisdom. They were sages of the Oromo. This makes the Oromo oral chronicles authentic chronicles, i.e., authentic history, short of only the “scientific method” as it is understood now.

The Oromo as the True Ethiopians

There has been an Abyssinian clamor that they are the true Ethiopians, which they are not in proper perceptiveness. The true Ethiopia is the ancient Kush of antiquity that is referred to as Ethiopia since the translation of the Old Testament to Greek. The ‘Ethiopia’ of the Bible is the broader appellation of Cushitic peoples of Africa. In modern Ethiopia, it defines the Cushitic language speaking nations, nationalities, and peoples (NNPs). This does not mean that Abyssinians are not modern Ethiopians in as much as every NNP of Ethiopia is. Even though their Semite progenitors arrived from southern Arabia, the Abyssinian people have inhabited the northern part of modern Ethiopia and part of the State of Eritrea for about two thousand years. During this prolonged period, they have culturally and linguistically Semitized many Kushite communities and nations and have assimilated many more. This has led to the degeneration of the core Semite element making the present generation devoid of Semite identity. Only since their arrival, they have been part of ancient Ethiopia. Nonetheless, Abyssinians are not ancient Ethiopians. The ancient Ethiopians were Cushite Africans.

Historically, the true Ethiopians have been all the Cushitic peoples of northeast Africa. These peoples live in modern Sudan, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Somali, Djibouti, Kenya, South Sudan, Uganda, Burundi, Rwanda, and Tanzania. The “Kush” or “Ethiopians” of the scriptures are also these peoples:

Ethiopian whose manner and customs have been fully described by Herodotus, Diodorus, Strabo, Pliny and others were not Abyssinians at all, but native of the

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Upper Nubia and the inhabitants of the hot, moist land which extends from Southern Abyssinia to Equator... (Budge, 1928, quoted in Melbaa, 1988, p. 35)

Some Abyssinian political and religious elites and a few historians, who claim that Abyssinians are the ancient Ethiopians, or the Abyssinians are more genuine Ethiopians than any other nation in modern Ethiopia, or Abyssinians and/or the peoples of modern Ethiopia deserve to be identified as Ethiopians than the Cushite peoples of Eritrea, Djibouti, Somalia, Kenya, Sudan, South Sudan, Uganda, Rwanda, Burundi, or Tanzania, are illusory only to themselves. It is noticeably clear that the ancient Ethiopians were/are the indigenous Kushite peoples of northeast Africa. Abyssinians, who claim Semite identity and descent from across the Red Sea, have only become modern Ethiopians.

The Semite Abyssinians had not yet arrived on Africa from southern Arabia when these Cushite Africans were known as “Kush” or “Ethiopia.” As it is well known in history, the core of the Abyssinians (Agazi and Habashat) arrived on the continent largely during the last centuries before the dawn of the Common Era from the southern Arabian Peninsula. Even after their arrival and the formation of the kingdom of Aksum, and until the very recent history of the kingdom of Abyssinia, the historic kingdom of Kush, Sudan, as part of the greater ancient Ethiopia, was the historic representation of “Ethiopia” than Abyssinia.

The Abyssinians are more Semite Sabaean than Cushite Ethiopians of east and central Africa regions. Even though he confuses the Kushite Oromo with Berber, Block (1899) points out that the Semites infiltrated east Africa and make clear that, they are not the true Ethiopians in as much as the Oromo are:

The Semitic element . . . spread, particularly over the Tigré country. Its language is called the Giz [Geez]. . . . The so-called Ethiopian [Kushite] race is also spread

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over the Tigré; but it predominates almost exclusively in Amhara [one of the Abyssinian provinces] and the rest of the country. It presents striking points of resemblance to [Oromo] tribes in the southwest of Abyssinia, a remnant of the Berber nation which possessed northern Africa in ancient times, and whose origin has been so much mooted. (p. 44)

Reclus (1892) also notes:

The Himyarites (Abyssinians) are intruders from Arabia; the Hamaites [Kushites] are the true autochthones, hence best entitled to the title of “Ethiopian,” which by the ancients was applied, although somewhat vaguely, to all the native populations stretching south from the frontier of Egypt proper. (p. 467).

The indigenous peoples of ancient Ethiopia are the Kushites. The main stock of these Kushites, both in terms of population and the geography of their habitation, are the Oromo. None from modern Ethiopia’s nations may be true Kushites and true Ethiopians as the Oromo. The Oromo are the keepers of the ancient Kushite culture and traditions. The avowal by some Oromo nationalists that they are not Ethiopians and the tendency by some Oromo scholars, for example by Jalata (2005), to dissociate the Oromo from Ethiopia must be considered as political activism rather than historical discourse. Even if such effort is clearly to extricate the Oromo from Abyssinians, who have used the devolved and limited scope of the name as if it had belonged only to them, it is worthwhile to bear in mind that most modern confessed Semite Abyssinians are Semitized Kushites. The indigenous Kushites had been Semitized culturally and linguistically since the formation of the Kingdom of Aksum and the Oromo in particular had been assimilated aggressively to the Christian Abyssinian

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culture, language, and political system since the formation of Kingdom of Abyssinia in the late 13th century.

It is important to note that the Kingdom of Abyssinia only recently appropriated the name “Ethiopia” from the true Ethiopians for religious and political purposes. Otherwise, they have no direct connection to ancient Ethiopia (Harden, 1926; Reclus, 1892; Melbaa, 1988). Harden (1926) further explains:

The name Abyssinia comes to us from Arabic writers who speak of the land of Habash . . . The name given to the country by the Christian inhabitants was Ethiopia. It has no direct connexion [sic] with the Ethiopia of classical writers, and with the Ethiopia of the Bible it is also unconnected, except that its adoption was no doubt due to a desire on the part of the Church of Abyssinia to trace back its own history to biblical times. (p. 1)

“Ethiopia” had been a name that applied to the wider region in the northeast, east, and central Africa regions, including Abyssinia. In this sense, it rather narrowly referred to the northeast African region, east of River Nile, north of the Equator, and south of Aswan. The Cushite peoples have inhabited it since antiquity. Since its formation in the late 13th century in the central highlands of modern Ethiopia, the kingdom of Abyssinia had been part of the greater Ethiopia in the geographic region that was designated as Upper Ethiopia.

On the global stage, “Ethiopia” became an exclusive official name of the Empire of Abyssinia only after the formation of the United Nations (UN). In its membership to the League of Nation, the precursor of the UN, modern Ethiopia was officially known as Abyssinia. Atse Menelik II had built the Empire in the late 19th century by quadrupling the formal territory of the kingdom of Abyssinia by instituting Amhara-Tigre settler colonization

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in the conquered regions in the south, southwest, and southeast of modern Ethiopia. Before that, despite the claim by Coptic Abyssinian Church elites since the 14th century that it referred to Abyssinia, “Ethiopia” was a name of a vast region in East Africa as recently as the 18th and the 19th century and “Ethiopians” were all the peoples who inhabited this region. This “Ethiopia” has now become several independent countries in the region.

Abyssinians (Amhara, Tigre, etc.), in general, have been rightly known by the name Abyssinia. Despite the wishful self-styling of some of their kings as “king of kings of Ethiopia” since the establishment of the kingdom of Abyssinia in the late 13th century, neither Abyssinia nor the Abyssinian peoples (Habasha) have ever been known formally among the nations of the world as Ethiopia or as Ethiopians before the 1930s. They have been known but variably as “Abassia,” “Abassinos,” “Abesha,” “Abesines,” “Abessina,” “Abyssinians,” “Habasha,” “Habesh,” “Habeshi,” and “Abyssina.” The adoption of the name was motivated by the wishes of some Church elites who were obsessed with snatching the ancient regional name for their Christian enclave because of the religious and historical importance of the name. They had accepted Abyssinia (Habasha) as their appellation throughout history, and they still draw a sense of pride by identifying as ‘Habasha’, though some of their contemporary elites have suggested recently that Abyssinia and Habasha were the names given to their country and them respectively by others. Even today, Abyssinians (both in Eritrea and northern Ethiopia) not only proudly call themselves “ሐበሻ” in the sense of their almost racist colorism but also try to project the name to the rest of the peoples of modern Ethiopia (excluding people with Negroid, Nilotic, Omotic, and Somali backgrounds) with slightly lighter dark pigmentation in their skin. Approving phrases like “የሐበሻ ልጅ” (literally, “Son of Habasha”) and the use of “Habasha” as an instrumental racial designation that appears to stand somewhere between the Sub-Saharan Africans and the north African and

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Middle Eastern Arab seems to romanticize Abyssinians. They see the appellation as their unified identity and as a marker of their “distinction” from other peoples of modern Ethiopia.

Nonetheless, after the successive conquest of the independent nations, nationalities, and peoples to its south, southwest, east, and southeast, and had carved modern Ethiopia from wider Horn of Africa region that was genuine “Ethiopia,” the now greatly expanded kingdom of Abyssinia, which was known as “Empire of Abyssinia“ started to give more weight to being known as “Ethiopia” than “Abyssinia.” “Ethiopiawinet” (Ethiopian-ness), albeit extremely slowly, started to eclipse “Habashawinet“ (Habasha-ness). The newly appropriated Ethiopian-ness and the Abyssinians who appropriated it to themselves, now Ethiopians, became first-class citizens while the genuine Kushite Ethiopians, most importantly the Oromo, were reduced to second citizenship as “others.” Yet, they could not let go of their genuine name, Habasha (Abyssinia), but try to morph the two different names together as if they were interchangeable or the same.

The narrowing of “Ethiopia” to Christian Abyssinia by the religious elites, the creation and forceful promotion of the legend of Kebra Nagast since the Medieval period, and the pensive instrumentation of Christianity by the Abyssinian monarchy must have played a greater role in motivating the Abyssinian Church and Court to claim the broad name of a wider region and many nations to themselves. Ancient Ethiopia had neither the unity of dominion nor the common character with the recent Abyssinia. Geographically, Abyssinia was a part, a small part, of greater Ethiopia. The appropriation of the name “Ethiopia” by the Abyssinians to themselves and only to modern Ethiopia is a recent religiously and politically motivated and spurious construction of Abyssinian elites. The source of motivation for the Abyssinians to appropriate the name Ethiopia from its rightful owners, the Kushite peoples of Africa, was neither history nor genetic, but religion and politics.

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However, the use of “Abyssinia” or “Habasha” respectively as the name of a country or as a national identity has always created apprehensive confusion. Those who found it useful for their causes have exploited the confusion. Abyssinian historians who try to place modern Ethiopia in the Biblical period have tried to equate “Abyssinia” with “Ethiopia.” They have continued to do so by trying to present as if “Abyssinia” and “Ethiopia” have represented the same geography and the same people throughout history even though it has never been the case. Abyssinian Church elites have always claimed misleadingly that the “Kush”/ “Ethiopia” of the Bible is synonymous with Abyssinia and with modern Ethiopia. Most of the legends (including the legend of Kebra Nagast) that the Church has produced—the most of which has now become part of failed Ethiopian history—have been based on this misleading claim.

Also, the confusion around the self-styling of religiously motivated Abyssinian kings as “king of Ethiopia” or “king of kings” has been exploited similarly. Unless some great misapprehension is at work “Ethiopia” was a vast region instead of a single country. Also, there was no historic “Empire of Ethiopia” ruled centrally by an Abyssinian. This self-styling designation of some Abyssinian kings since the late 13th century was no different than, for example, one European king calling himself “king of Europe,” or one middle eastern king calling himself “king of Middle East.” Besides, both Aksumite and Abyssinian “king of kings” were, in effect, kings of a loose federation of chiefdoms in the northern regions of modern Ethiopia until the Kingdom of Abyssinia became federation of Kingdom of Tigre and Amhara. Afterward, the Tigre and Amhara kings competed for influence and the title of “king of kings.” In the end, it was the king of Kingdom of Shewa (a breakaway from Amhara), Atse Menelik II, who took the title of “king of kings”, and his successor, Atse Haile Selassie I was the last monarch to use the title.

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However the false equivalence and false representation would continue, the Semite Abyssinians cannot be Kushites, and neither the “Kush” nor the “Ethiopia” of the scripture can be Abyssinia. More importantly, it is impossible to deny the Oromo (and other Cushitic peoples of east Africa) being the true Ethiopians. Abyssinians have nothing to do with ancient Kush or ancient Ethiopia (Harden, 1926, p. 1; Block, 1899, p. 44; Reclus, 1892, p. 467).

The Oromo and the Ancient World (Egypt, Greece, Persia)

The Oromo and Ancient Egypt

The Oromo were very intricately connected to the ancient Egyptians, or they were part of the ancient Egyptian society. The predynastic Egyptians, ancient Egyptians, were “leucodermic” or “dark” people, as all the Kushites are, and belonged to the same eastern Cushitic groups as do the Oromo, Somali, Bejja, and Afar (Vercoutter, 1978, p. 19). As the people of the same stock and language group who have inhabited the same region since antiquity, the ancient Egyptians and the Oromo have had strong influences on one another in many ways if they were not the same people. Such influences of the Oromo on ancient Egyptians or vice versa, or their shared identity and common past, could be understood today from the connections that had existed between the two. The following are illustrations for this connection.

First, the Oromo and the ancient Egyptians were connected by cosmology through their emphasis on primordial water (Hornung, 1990 and Megerssa 1983 cited in Verharen, 2013b, p. 84). The Oromo cosmology, where “everything is interconnected through myriad of webs and threads” (Dewo, 2013, p. 163), is closer to that of ancient Egypt so much so that it is plausible to speculate the beliefs of the two might have influenced each other mutually (Verharen, 2013b, p. 84), or, they had the same belief as held by Oromo oral chroniclers.

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Second, the modern Oromo and the ancient Egyptian philosophies are closely related. Charles C. Verharen argues that, in addition to its geographical and conceptual proximity, “the ontological and ethical analogues between the two cultures are so strong as not to be coincidental” (Verharen, 2013, p. 186). It is highly likely that the two shared the same philosophy.

Third, only the Oromo widely practices core ancient Egyptian cultural elements today. These include Irreecha and Ateetee. In fact, in a way that suggests a direct link between the two cultures (Verharen, 2013, p. 185), some relatively recent studies hypothesize that “modern Oromo cultures are an expression of wider Cushitic cultures that extended from Africa to India in antiquity, with connections to ancient Egypt” (Gemetchu, 1993, cited in Verharen, 2013b, p. 97). This hypothesis is in congruence with that of Cheikh Anta Diop who has emphasized that ancient Egypt might have strong cultural influence farther south in Africa (Verharen, 2013, p. 186).

Fourth, ancient Egyptians and modern Oromo people look-alike in features. Most images of the Egyptian Pharaohs that have been preserved in statues and the few uncovered mummies depict typical figures of the Oromo. The observable similarity between features of the ancient Pharaohs and typical living Oromo men of the present time is striking; everyone can see it. The similarities could also be observed in ancient Egyptian paintings. The seven-thousand years old Egyptian paintings depict the present features of the Oromo people and other indigenous peoples of the Horn of Africa (Delebo, 2007). It is, thus, not without good reason that some suggest the Oromo are the best representation of the pre-dynastic (Proto-Egyptian) race. Du Bois (1915), for example, argues that the BaHima (WaHuma) Oromo who “invaded” the African Great Lakes region and built the Empire of Kitwara (Kittara) to the west of Lake Victoria region around the 16th century, were “startlingly Egyptian in type,” and

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perhaps represent “the best racial picture of what ancient Egyptian and Upper Nile regions were in pre-dynastic times and later” (p. 52).

Fifth, both the Oromo and ancient Egyptians were Cushitic Africans. Both belonged to the eastern Cushite group. In their traditions, both claim that they were the first nation on earth. Several studies have confirmed that the pre-dynastic ancient Egyptians were indeed black. This black Africa was “the principal scene both of man’s emergence as the royal species of the planet and of the emergence of a political society,” and “all evidence available concurs with the statement Ancient Egyptians were Negroes” (Chang’ach, 2015, p. 8). The well-known and ardent proponent of the African origin of Western civilization, Cheikh Anta Diop, argues: “The original and pure Black Negroid race that first inhabited Egypt eventually merged with a Mediterranean race to create the Egyptians that we know today” (Bauval & Brophy, 2011, Diop and the case of his struggles).

Sixth, the ancient Egyptian language is filled with keywords and concepts that are still in use among the Oromo with the same or similar form and sound. In this regard, Ayele Bekerie reportedly “unveils discoveries of ‘ancient Egyptian documents and artifacts’ in which ‘significant Oromo conceptual terms’ are found” (Birbirso, 2013a, p. 29). Indeed, most of the Latin transliterations of ancient Egyptian Hieroglyphics, texts are not only readable just as modern Oromo language written in Qubee (see Table 6), but also intelligible as is to a lingual expert or contextually informed Oromo. One study on the linguistic relations between ancient Egyptian and some modern black African languages, Afaan Oromoo included, has concluded that “a single linguistic type, the same formal and grammatical structure” prevails between the two (Obenga, 1978, p. 71). It worth mentioning that some scholars claim, Cushitic languages are older than some Semitic languages. One of them is Jean Doresse, the well-known French historian and a scholar of Egyptology and Greek papyrology who

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established the first archaeological service in Ethiopia in the 1950s. In an interview in Ethiopia in 2002, he is reported to have made clear: first, the languages of the closely related eastern Cushitic peoples (i.e., the Oromo, the Somali, and the Afar) are among the oldest languages, older than Sabaean; second, the origin of some of their words are older than that of the hieroglyphics of Dynastic Egypt (Another Study Points to Africa as the Origin of Languages, 2001). Though empirical linguistic studies must be conducted to come to a secured conclusion on the interconnections of Afaan Oromoo and ancient Egyptian language as very ancient languages, these clues strongly suggest the existence of significant linguistic interconnection between the two since antiquity.

Seventh, the connection between ancient Egypt, its historical rulers, and the Oromo may also be comprehended from certain historical records. Historically, the Oromo are known to have inhabited northeast Africa region in the period of pre-dynastic Egypt as part of the ancient Eastern Cushitic groups of peoples that includes ancient Egyptians, Danakils (Afar), and Bejja (Vercoutter, 1978, p. 19). Ayana (2015) argues that the ancestors of the Oromo, whom he referred to as Proto-Oromo, “played a significant role in the ancient world.” During the transition from the Second Intermediate Period (1786–1570 BCE) to the New Kingdom in Lower Egypt, the Kingdom of Kush was in the making, as a breakaway independent kingdom from Egypt in Upper Egypt (Southern Egypt) now known as Sudan (North Sudan). A separate Kushite kingdom in Upper Egypt has a history dating as far back to the Egyptian New Kingdom (1570–1069 BCE). Oromo oral traditions also claim that Wawat, located between the second and the third cataract on the Nile, was the politico-religious center of the Oromo around 900 BCE. In the Egyptian historiography, the present Oromo land, Oromia, is referred to as the “Cinnamon Country,” an aspect of which has been documented and described by geographers Eratosthenes, Ptolemy and Strabo and by

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Hipparchus and Pliny between third century BCE and first century CE (Ayana, 2015, Notes on cinnamon country and the “Peace of Jamjam”). As to the connection between the historical rulers of Egypt and the Oromo, first the Egyptian Pharaohs, then the Persians and the Greeks, who ruled Egypt, “relied on ancestors of the Oromo for information on the sources of the Nile River” (Ayana, 2015).

Eighth, the oral Oromo mythology of origin suggests that the ancestors of the ancient Egyptians were also ancestors of the Oromo. According to mythology, the progenitors of the prehistoric nation of Kush were Horoo and Hawwa. Presently, the Oromo are the main stock of the Kushite nations of east and northeast Africa. The Oromo also maintain Ora (Osiris) was their first leader. Ora was the son of the sun god, from whom the Oromo believe their present name has originated. Even though not in the same importance, the place of Osiris, Isis, and Horus (Horoo) in ancient Egyptian mythology is remarkably similar. An in-depth study may reveal a deeper connection or unity of origin.

Ninth, and lastly, the present Oromo might be the ancient Egyptians. The above relations and connections between modern Oromo and ancient Egyptians have inspired speculation that the Oromo were the ruling Dynasty in Egypt. The typical Oromo facial features on the statues and sphinxes of ancient Egypt further strengthens the speculation. In connection to this, Sir William Matthew Flinders Petrie (1853–1942), the celebrated English scholar of Egyptology, suggests, in his 1896 book *A History of Egypt: Part I*, pp. 126-129, that the Oromo were founders of some of the ancient Egyptian dynasties. He claims that, though the Oromo do not appear in Egyptian records, they have left their style of sculpture in the black sphinxes, probably from during the 7th–10th Dynasties, before the Hyksos (The Reunion Black Family, 2012). Few scholars have also theorized that among the ancient dynasties of Egypt were Oromo dynasties. There are supporting pieces of evidence, but no

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one has proved the theory yet. Nevertheless, the assertion that the Oromo were once rulers of ancient Egypt has become commonplace. Its advocate claim, “Historians have abundantly documented that some of the old Egyptian dynasties were, in fact, Oromo dynasties” (Arga-Dhagetti over Inexorable, 2008). If so, the Oromo were among the multinational ancient Egyptians. Old Egyptian civilization is Kushitic and Oromo political, spritual, philosphocal, and consmological traditions have preserved that old Kushite civilization. More research is however needed to prove the Oromo identity of the the anciant Egyptians of the Upper Egypt.

The Oromo and Ancient Greek

The connection between Greek and the Oromo, based on the indications from the relationship between languages of the respective peoples, appears to be strong despite the relatively recent connection. Eurasian peoples arrived in large numbers in northeast Africa about 3,000 years ago (Gibbons, 2015). They may have influenced the northern Cushitic region of Nubia, Napata, and Meroe before the arrival of the southern Arabian peoples. After the arrival of Eurasian peoples, but before the emergence of the south Arabian language in the region, the indigenous Kushites (the Oromo and others) and the Eurasian peoples might have developed a hybrid culture and language along with the trading roots in the northeast Africa region. Nonetheless, available studies have not yet confirmed it.

After the later arrival of the Greeks, however, there are clear indications of the strong influence of the Hellenistic culture in the region. The Oromo, one of the indigenous peoples of the region, could not be immune to this influence. The influence and the connection between the Greek culture and the Oromo may be illustrated by the common characteristics of the Oromo and Greek grammar. The connection and the influence are evident in the origins of grammars of the two languages: “The Oromo and the classical Greek concepts of grammar correspond both in form and meaning” (Birbirso, 2013a, p. 29). Moreover, Birbirso and

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Gerba (2016), in their in-depth comparative historical linguistic and literary analysis of “Homer’s Epic Society Versus Oromo Epic Traditions,” suggests that “similarities of unimaginable magnitude/significance in the entire semiotic triangle, i.e. (1) form/sign/phonology/syntax, (2) meaning/semantic/philosophy, and (3) social-natural referents/structure/objects” between “Homeric society as in *The Iliad* and the Oromo Qaallu-Gada tradition,” can only be explained by “cultural-historical origin from Oromo-Cush,” suggesting the existence of “Stolen Legacy” or black African dominance of the ancient world (p. 135). Thus, it is no surprise that the two languages have developed an element of a common grammatical foundation. Furthermore, the Oromo and the Greeks have a common way of counting periods (Calendar): the Oromo count periods by eight years (and four years) by their Gadaa System and the Greeks by four years by their Olympiads (Cerulli, 1922).

In addition, in their study that “contends that Oromo and Hittite might be historically, typologically and genetically related,” Birbirso and Gerba (2015) state, “Many scholars also associate Oromo to ancient Anatolian and the Biblical peoples such as Hittite and Israelites” (p. 252). Birbirso and Gerba (2015), based on the finding of their comparative linguistic research on Oromo and Hittite, conclude genetic, in other words, “common proto-language from which both descended,” is “the only plausible explanation” (p. 275). They report:

the comparison of Oromo, Hittite and PIE [Proto-Indo-European] lexico-semantic features confirm that the Oromo vocabulary, by and large, cognates with both Hittite and PIE languages. In addition, not only have we observed corresponding “clitic chains” between Hittite and Oromo, but also... Hittite-Oromo languages resemblance, in both form and meaning, along the grammatical properties of nominative and accusative cases, ergativity, sentence connectives, possessive construction, lexical-semantics and degree of adjectives. (p. 275)

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These studies and other factors (the existence of a common way of measuring period) suggest that not only ancient Greece and ancient Kush (Oromo) were related cultures, but also the Ancient Mediterranean world might have been influenced very significantly by the Kushite civilization of antiquity (Birbirso and Gerba, 2015, 2016; Houston, 1926 [2004]; Bauval & Brophy, 2011).

In addition, as recorded in history, present northern Ethiopia was under the influence of the Greeks at least from the 3rd century BCE to the 4th century CE. (This period includes few centuries before the arrival of south Arabian peoples who established the kingdom of Aksum around 100 CE.) Some of the Aksumite kings confessed proudly on their stone inscriptions that they were sons of Greeks. The 4th-century trilingual inscription of King Ezana, for example, indicates that he is from the Hellenistic (Greek) tribe (Delebo, 2007, p. 232). The Greek language served as *lingua franca* in the region, and some elements of Greek culture were introduced to the region. Though not directly related, the Gadaa System of the Oromo (Oromo Republican Democracy) and the Athenian Democracy, Lata (1998) suggests, may have been contemporary.

The Oromo of Horn of Africa, in particular, have achieved much socio-political, religio-cultural, and time reckoning advancement, as did the Greeks. The most notable advancement of the Oromo has been the creation of the Gadaa System (Sirna Gadaa). Gadaa System (Gada/gada System) is the democratic and republican government system of the Oromo. Through Gadaa System, the Oromo have made egalitarian democracy and republican systems of governance their enduring culture. Though Gadaa System came to be known in recorded history during the medieval time, when exactly the Oromo invented the Gadaa System is not yet known for certain. The Oromo oral chronicles (*argaa-dhageettii*) and some studies based on cycles of the Gadaa System and Gadaa chronology, however, suggest that

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Gadaa System was contemporary to Athenian democracy (Lata, 1998, p. 131; Bokku, 2011, p. 162). It is known that Athenian democracy flourished during 500-300BCE before it was extinguished by the rise of the Roman Empire under Alexander the Great in the 320s BCE.

There are many parallels between the Athenian democracy and the Gadaa democracy. The full comparison is beyond the scope of this work: just to mention some: both had an assembly of the people (men only) as the legislative body, an elected governing council, council of judges, and related supportive assemblies and councils, including the council of war leaders. Also, the practice of public information agent (keettoo) in the Gadaa System is similar not only by function but also by etiquettes with “old Greek euxenoi, they are also required to represent the citizens with all strangers, to introduce them into the villages and offer them the bowl of milk, a symbol of hospitality (Reclus, 1890, p. 402). Besides, the Oromo have always been a nation of assemblies. Historically, these assemblies made all the important decisions both at the national, regional, local levels of governments. The names, the compositions, and the working structures and working procedures of the Greeks and the Oromo assemblies and Councils, however, may differ slightly. Both were democracies of men who were sovereign or citizens and above a certain age.

Three facts suggest that the Oromo democracy (Gadaa System) is similar to Greece democracy: First, the fact that the Gadaa System, in general, excludes women from political discourse and public office. Second, the fact that it ensures political participation is limited to the sovereign heads of households, except during the general assembly’s meeting that would allow the practice of popular democracy. Third, the fact that it excludes alien heads of households at least until they shall have become political equals according to the law, customs, and necessary religio-cultural rituals.

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The Oromo and the Persians

The Oromo are also believed to have had contact with the ancient Persian Empire when the former inhabited the coastal regions of the Gulf of Aden and the Indian Ocean (Burton, 1872, cited in Etefa, 2012, p. 2). Burton (1872) also appears to be convinced that the black and white-furred sheep of the Somali and the Oromo originated from Persia. The coastal region of northeast Somalia has been suggested as the cradle land of both the Oromo and the Somali (Lewis, 1966, cited in Hiney, 2012, p. 98). Moreover, the Oromo had inhabited the territories of present northern Somalia before the Somalis (Lewis, 1959). It is, therefore, highly likely that the Oromo have had trading contact with yet another ancient world, Ancient Persia

Migration and Challenging Neighbourhood

The Disintegration of Kush

Before the establishment of the first Egyptian dynasty (3100–2890 BCE) in the Lower Nile region, advanced Cushitic societies had thrived in the Upper Nile region for centuries. These advanced societies, experts believe, were patriarchal societies and had formed a loosely controlled prehistoric dominion, the ancient empire of Kush. Scholars believe the Oromo people were part of this prehistoric ancient empire of Kush.

The ancient empire of Kush encompassed part of Africa, the Arabian Peninsula, the Middle East, part of western Asia (Budge, 1926; Houston, 1926[2004]). This vast empire, however, gradually declined, and its people started to move apart; and through time, they formed separate ethnic identities. In sub-Saharan Africa, the Cushitic speaking nations started to move further south as the Sahara Desert continued to expand. From among its peoples, the Nubians remained in the core region of the empire while the Oromo, as it appears, moved to the southern flank of the empire. The Nubians were able to keep the name of the ancient

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empire as Kush. Historians have been referring to this Kush as the Empire of Kush or Kingdom of Kush. It was the Kush of the Bible. Kush, as referred to in the Bible, might have encompassed Sudan, South Sudan, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Somalia, Kenya, Uganda, and southern Egypt. The Oromo were part of this Kush before they developed a fully distinct national identity and attained sovereignty.

Historical Kush was one of the powerful kingdoms of its time. Its power was based on trade. Egypt was its trading partner. It competed with ancient Egypt during the Old and Middle kingdoms (2686–1650 BCE). From the Kushitic Period (1500-315 BCE) to Meroitic Period (260 BCE-370 CE) in northeast Africa, however, Megalommatitis (2007, pp. 9-10) explains, the Kushites underwent significant social and political dynamics. From 1500-950 BCE, Ancient Egypt loosely annexed them. During this period, the Kushites engaged in a continued revolution against Egyptian rule. From 950-800 BCE they became independent and set up their capital far south at Napata (Karima). From 800-670, they expanded and took control of Lower Egypt and ruled over both Upper Egypt (Kush) and Lower Egypt. From 671-351 BCE, they were expelled gradually from Lower Egypt because of successive invasions by Assarhaddon in 671 BCE, Assurbanipa in 669 and 666 BCE, Psamtik/Psammetichus II in 591 BCE, and Shah Kambudjiyah/Cambyses in 525 which forced them to move the capital once again further south to Meroe.

These annexations, invasions, and the revolts that followed might have encouraged some of its peoples, including the Oromo, to begin the gradual southward movement to the heart of Horn of Africa following River Nile, and further develop separate ethnic identities and political systems. The southward movement would only be accelerated by the formation of the kingdom of Aksum. As they moved south and moved apart, the central political force would decline to allow those who formed national identity to device an effective government

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system that would fit the new reality. In this regard, the Assyrian conquest of Kush might have triggered not only the national self-rule of the Oromo but also the subsequent invention of their governance system, the Gadaa System. Even though Oromo oral literature places the invention of the Gadaa System to around 1000 BCE (Lata, 1998, p. 131; Bokku, 2011, p. 162), archaeological evidence suggests that it may have been invented sometime around 400 BCE (Legesse, 1973, 2006).

Arrival and Expansion of South Arabian Peoples

After the continued decline of Kush, the nations of the kingdom of Kush, as did the nations of the ancient Empire of Kush, started to move apart, and moved further. It had survived the Assyrian conquest and the emergence of Middle Eastern peoples (southern Arabians) on the middle and lower (western) shore of the Red Sea around the turn of the Common Era. When they could not cope anymore, they continued to migrate south. It is highly likely that two natural and one man-made factors might have guided the choice of the general direction. The former are the variations of seasonal rain (climate change) that could have forced them to move along the Nile and to the east African highland regions and the southward expansion of the Sahara Desert. The latter could be the regular raid of the Upper Nile region by the growing occupying powers of the Persian and Ptolemaic Egypt, in search of economic resources.

After the turn of the Common Era, the dying Kush (kingdom of Meroe) faced a new challenge from alien peoples in the 4th century CE. It had survived for millennia after the Assyrian conquest with its capital at Napata and Meroe in modern north-central Sudan. The south Arabian people who had crossed the Red Sea and had settled in the coastal region set up trading centers. These, mostly Yemenite, people gradually grew in population size and military strength and set up small chiefdoms in the region. These chiefdoms, owing to their

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cultural and trade connection to the then advanced civilizations, were able to Semitize some of the Cushitic peoples in the region. In doing so, they ultimately created a hybrid culture and identity that came to be known as Habasha. The Agazi Habasha (Ge'ez Speaking Habasha) established the Aksumite kingdom around the turn of the second century CE. This kingdom gradually grew to a major trading kingdom and established trading and political relations with the Roman Empire. The growth of the wealth of the Aksumite kingdom helped it in expanding its territory further south and northwest. Aksum raided the now exceedingly contracted kingdom of Kush and sacked its capital, Meroe, in the mid-4th century CE. The kingdom of Kush fell not to recover.

The victorious kingdom of Aksum continued to expand its territory through the instrument of a military raid. Because of this expansion, the northern Oromo who were believed to have settled present northern Ethiopia started to move further south in the direction that they had already set for themselves in search of better pasture and climate for their cattle because they had become predominantly pastoralist nation. The military expansion propelled Aksum from city-state to an empire that controlled many small Cushitic peoples, kingdoms, and chiefdoms in the present State of Eritrea and northern Ethiopia.

In the northwest, Aksum continued to expand rapidly. It conquered Kushite Meroe. The continued attack by the Nuba people from the west of the Nile had already weakened Meroe (Adams, 1995). More importantly, the growing power of Lower Egypt (above the Tropic of Cancer) on Upper Egypt (Nubia) had forced the Meroitic kingdom to decline since the early first century CE. These offered a fantastic opportunity to the growing and expanding young Aksumite kingdom to easily attack and subdue Meroe. This conquest of Meroe by the Aksumite king resulted in the migration of its peoples further south along the Nile River for a practical reason.

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Throughout most of their known history after their ethnogenesis from Ancient Kush which most likely took place during the last centuries of the second millennium BCE, the Oromo of Upper Ethiopia have lived independently and consistently within the Horn of Africa region together with other indigenous Cushitic, Nilotic, Bantu, and Omotic nations. They have also lived, at a later stage (since the first century CE), with the Semitic migrants from Arabia and other culturally Semitized Kushites of the region. They traversed this region in those ancient times when there were no national boundaries as such to constrain people from moving from one place to another. Since the emergence of the Aksumite kingdom in the second century CE, however, it appears that they were forced gradually to move south.

The emergence and the continued expansion of South Arabian Semites peoples in the Horn of Africa, west of the Red Sea, was in all probability the reasons for the south movement of the Kushite northern Oromo. There is no historical ambiguity that some Semitic Arabian peoples (Saba, Habasa, Hemyarit) migrated to the Horn of Africa from Southern Arabia across the Red Sea starting from around the middle of last millennium BCE. They intruded into the Kush country of Northeast Africa (Reclus, 1892, p. 467). They gradually expanded in the coastal region of the present State of Eritrea. After centuries of migration and expansion, they became dominant and powerful in the region. They continued to intermingle with the indigenous Kushites and subsequently Semitized some of the indigenous peoples and languages. The result of the genetic mix was a mixed people that would later come to be named as Habasha, meaning mixed people. Habasha people, primarily Amhara and Tigrie, “evolved through the children of Arab immigrants and Africans in the Horn of Africa” (Jalata, 2005, p. 4). The Habasha formed a fresh territory that would become the kingdom of Aksum around the end of the 1st century CE. By the 4th century CE, they had set up the present city of Aksum (Leeman, 2005, p. 56). These resulted in the division of the Cushitic nations into

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Northern Kushites and Southern Kushites and their further expansion southwest into the heartland northeast Africa to the northwestern highlands of modern Ethiopia resulted in the further division of the Cushitic family of nations into Northern, Eastern, and Southern Kushites.

Though initially Aksum and Saba constituted one empire, later Aksum became independent around the turn of the 2nd century CE. By then, new hybrid civilization, commonly known as Aksumite civilization, which, after some archaeological studies on some historical sites in central Tigray, the Institute of Ethiopian Archaeology has proposed that it was “an outcome of contact and links between South Arabian immigrants and indigenous northern Ethiopians” (Aalund, 1985 and Brandt, 1997 cited in Nigus, 2012, p. 86), had emerged. It “evolved through the cross-fertilization of cultures brought together by migration, commerce, and religion (Jalata, 2005, p. 47). With the support of this relatively advanced civilization and their growing power and influence in the region due to the control of trade on southern Red Sea ports, the Aksumites embarked in further expansion along the trade routes northwest and south of Aksum after subduing smaller states and controlling the trade of the region.

Aksum soon embarked on further expansion to the heart of Africa south of Aksum. In this expansion, the Aksumites gradually started to “push” the native Kushite stock of nations, including the Oromo, further south (Jalata, 2005, p. 30). The Aksumite warriors settled the territories that were evacuated by the fleeing peoples. The southern settler-colonists of Aksum came to be known, later in Amharic, as ጭዋ [tʃʷwa:]. The successors of the Aksumite kingdom, the Cushite Agew [a:gɛwɥ] (also spelled as Agaw), and their successors, the “Solomonic” Abyssinian kingdom, continued the same policy of expanding south by establishing settler-colonists for many centuries that would follow. After it was formed in the

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late 13th century, the Abyssinian kingdom, in particular, made the expansion and establishment of military colonies in the south its main economic and politico-religious program until all became too much for the Oromo to tolerate in the 16th century.

The migration of Arabian peoples across the Red Sea and the Gulf of Aden continued: so did the displacement of the Oromo. Already in the second century CE, the Oromo who inhabited the modern northern Ethiopia region had started to move southwards because of the formation of the kingdom of Aksum. Also, more Arabian elements continued to arrive at the shores of East Africa in the 11th century. As a result, the Somali clan system was formed from among the Islamized and somewhat Arabized Oromo started to pressure the eastern Oromo to retreat southwest from central modern Somalia along the coast and in the hinterland to south-central modern Ethiopia. The contact of the Oromo with the Bantu people of southeastern Africa may have been consequent to their movement or expansion from northeast to south-central Upper Ethiopia. By the 16th century, the Oromo inhabited most of the Upper Ethiopia region together with other Cushitic peoples of the region.

Starting from the early 4th century, the kingdom of Aksum became a Christian kingdom and grew even more powerful to mayhem the Cushitic peoples of the region and the Semitic peoples in Southern Arabia from across the Red Sea. Aksum joined the religion of the most powerful empire of the time, the Roman Empire, by adopting Christianity abandoning its polytheistic religion. Aksum had kept a cordial relationship with Rome and had continued to trade with the Roman Empire. Its emerging relationship with Byzantium was however appeared to be stronger. Byzantium and Aksum saw themselves as allies in the swiftly expanding religion, Christianity. Within this alliance, in the early 6th century, the Christian Justin I of Byzantium is reported to have requested Kaleb of Aksum to protect Christians in southern Arabia from persecution by a Jewish king. Aksum invaded southern

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Arabia, modern Yemen, and controlled a section of the southern Arabian region for several decades until the end of the century. On the African continent, Aksum was geographically limited to most of the State of Eritrea and northern Ethiopia but its trade influence might have reached further south as far as the port of Zeila and Berbera in the present republics of Djibouti and Somalia, respectively. By then, Djibouti was inhabited by the Oromo; latter by the Adal, and finally by the Somali (Burton, 1856 [2012]). By the beginning of the 8th century, Aksum had declined but not before displacing most of the indigenous Cushitic peoples further south or linguistically Semitizing some of them. Towards the end of the 10th century, an alleged Falasha (Ethiopian Jew) queen by the name Judith (also known as Yodit, Gudit, Esato) sacked and destroyed the capital of the kingdom of Aksum, Aksum city. This led to the utter fall of the kingdom.

The coming to power of the brotherly Cushitic people, the Agew, in the former territory of the fallen Aksumite kingdom at the end of the 10th century was neither an alarm nor a welcome to the northern Oromo. The Oromo nation, then known by several of its ancient clan names (Suba, Madabay, Asebo, Rayya, etc.), lived peacefully in the northwestern and central plateau of modern Ethiopian highland and the Rift Valley region. Though they had already been pushed further south, they did not decide to return north during the decline and fall of the Aksumite kingdom (7th –9th century) nor did the Christian Abyssinians try to return during the period of the subsequent non-Christian dynasty that is believed to have been established by Judith, a warrior queen who allegedly persecuted Christian Aksumites and forced them to flee south to the present North Shewa Zone of Amhara State. This was because they were welcome in the southern fertile country of the Oromo.

The Oromo, who had, by then, accepted immigrant Christian communities into the present central Oromia and southern and southeastern Amhara states, chose to remain at

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peace with the kingdom and avoided conflict owing to the fundamental Oromo principle of *qixxee, wal-dandeettii, and nagaan*. They also received the people who were newly crossing the Red Sea and the Gulf of Eden from southern Arabia and appeared to their east. These peoples were mostly followers of Islam. Both the Christian and the Muslim communities thrived in central Oromia during the reign of the Zagwean Dynasty in the region that would become Abyssinia Proper. The Oromo remained passive, receptive, and accommodative to both the Christian and Islamic powers until the Zagwean Dynasty (10th–13th century), following its predecessor Aksumite kingdom, started to expand into their territory.

Three centuries later, both Muslim and Christian communities that the Oromo hosted not only had greatly expanded (within the Oromo territories) but also had grown immensely powerful. By the end of the 13th century, at the expense of the Oromo, the Muslims had established several small Islamic principalities while the Christian communities opposing the Zagwean rule had organized themselves into several large army contingents. The Christian communities who had settled in the mountainous regions of Shewa battled with the Zagweans. With the aid of persuasion of conspiring church elites, such as Telke Haimanot and Yesus Moa and military power, they overthrew the Zagweans and established the kingdom of Abyssinia. This new kingdom encompassed not only the territory that was under the Zagwean but also most of the present northern half of Shewa. With the new legend of origin of the kingdom and its kings and the absolute unity between the state and the Church, the kingdom of Abyssinia soon became one of the most powerful kingdoms on the continent.

It took the new powerful Abyssinian kingdom no time to start expanding into the Oromo territories and the territories that were under the control of the Islamic principalities in present central Ethiopia. The Islamic principalities tried to defend themselves by keeping the Christian kingdom to the highland region and western edges of the escarpments of the Rift

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Valley. The Oromo on the other hand, could not put strong resistance to the expansion because of the loosening of their unity and the breakup of their Gadaa System in the early years of the establishment of the Abyssinian kingdom. The Muslims and Christians had infiltrated the central Oromo in the present central Oromia. Moreover, because of their principles that encourage peaceful coexistence with the nations of the world and universal humanism, the Oromo never focused on military confrontation but peaceful conflict resolution and reconciliations. As a result, they were too tolerant while the Abyssinian kingdom and the Islamic sultanates were aggressively expanding into their territories and gradually pushing them further south in the next two centuries.

Challenging Neighbourhood

The co-existence of the Oromo with both indigenous and amalgamated nations in the northeast and equatorial Africa had not always been peaceful. Some historical evidence indicates that they had had violent encounters. Abyssinian historical records show that the Oromo had several protracted conflicts with Abyssinian peoples for centuries. Even though it might have been smaller in the scale of its military maneuvers, it also had protracted conflict with the Somali peoples. As discussed above, it is also known that the Oromo, in their southward expansion, had conquered some Bantu and other peoples in the African Great Lakes region. The Oromo who had invaded the region from the north established the Empire of Kitwara in the 16th century (Keane, 1896, 1920; Du Bois, 1915, p. 52). Likewise, the kingdoms of Baganda (Uganda) and Tutsi (Rwanda) were established by the descendants of the Oromo who had continued to rule in the region until the emergence of the Colonial Era in east Africa (Keane, 1896, 1920; Du Bois, 1915; Reclus, 1892; 1993; E. A. Literature Bureau, 1969). However, whether the Oromo had protracted military conflict with the peoples they

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met in the central East Africa region is not clear. Historical records on the nature of the conquest are hardly available.

On the nature of their conflict in the north and east with the Christian Abyssinian kingdom and the Muslim Sultanates respectively, however, there are some historical records of fierce protracted conflicts between the Oromo and the two. Starting from its formation around 100 CE, the kingdom of Aksum had continued to expand into the territory of the former leading to some frictions. By the time Aksum started to decline, Islam had arrived on the continent and had started to expand along the east coast. Muslim merchants who infiltrated into the hinterland from the trading port of Zeila in the 8th and 9th centuries gradually introduced Islam to urban settlements and trading posts from where Islam took root among the Oromo who later became Muslims and partly adapted Arab identity and culture. This was followed by the period for the formation and expansion of some small Islamic sultanates deep in-land along the lower Awash River. From the 11th to 16th centuries, the Oromo passively resisted the expansion of the Arabized Somali from the coastal Horn of Africa into the hinterland.

When the Abyssinian kingdom introduced the policy of occupation of the Oromo land through the force of organized army and expansion of Christianity (after the 13th century), the Oromo confronted the warrior and expansionist kings of the former in disorganized minor resistances. From the late 15th century to the early 17th century, however, the Oromo were forced to engage in massive and protracted offensive-defensive struggles. To ensure their survival as a nation in their ancestral region and to preserve their identity (culture, religion, and Gadaa government) the Oromo decided to defend themselves from the continued socio-political and economic pressures.

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The Oromo organized themselves effectively under their Gadaa government, set the goal of reclaiming lost ancestral territories, devised an effective warfare strategy, and launched Gadaa-cycle based military campaigns against the Christian Kingdom of Abyssinia and the Islamic Sultanate/principalities in the early 16th century. The Oromo were successful in reclaiming most of the lost ancestral territories from both the Christian and Islamic encroachments in less than a century. The northern Oromo, as political splinter groups from the rest of the Oromo, latter established a political alliance with the kingdom of Abyssinia and became its masters from mid-18th to the mid-19th century. The rest of the Oromo remained independent and maintained their Gadaa government.

The relationship of the rest of the Oromo with other people' appears to be largely peaceful: there had been no recorded protracted military campaigns, though sporadic conflicts over resources were inevitable. The fact that several of these peoples have voluntarily adopted/adapted the Gadaa System of the Oromo indicates that the relationship has been largely peaceful. The eastern and the southern Oromo maintained the strategic defenses against the Islamic Emirate of Harar [ha:ra:r] (the remnant of the Sultanate of Adal [a:da:l] (also spelled as Adel)) and the southern Somali clans up to the end of the 19th century.

The conflict between the Oromo and the Abyssinians was so protracted that it lasted for centuries. The Abyssinian kingdom was founded in the 13th century in the north-central mountainous highland region of the Horn of Africa. It soon claimed to be a successor to the legendary "Solomonic kingdom." It was founded deep-rooted in the legend of origin and the political, ideological, and theological doctrines offered by the Coptic Church in Egypt around the time of the formation of the kingdom of Abyssinia in the late 13th century (Delebo, 2007). The legend and the doctrines were later incorporated in the book of the legend of

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Abyssinia, a “historical romance” known as *Kebra Nagast* (“Ethiopia”, 2011), which gave the legend its lasting triumph and apotheosis.

The newly emerged and wantonly expanding kingdom of Abyssinia started to pose a lasting challenge to the Oromo nation through raids and occupying settlements (petty military colonies). The welcoming and accommodating culture of the Oromo soon proved to be futile to the Oromo. In a few centuries that followed, they lost large territory to the kingdom, and some Oromo communities were incorporated into both the Christian kingdom and Muslim Principalities. This became the overarching cause for the beginning of the highly organized and protracted struggle of the Oromo. After earlier trifling defensive attempts by some Oromo communities proved to be ineffective, in the mid-15th century, the Oromo reformed their Gadaa System for liberation struggle (*Duula Walabummaa*) to reclaim their ancestral territories that had been lost not only to the expanding Christian kingdom but also to its predecessors over many centuries. Using their elaborate democratic governance system, the Oromo conducted Gadaa based Offensive–defensive campaigns for about one century from 1522 to 1626 and reclaimed most of the ancestral territories that had been taken from them.

3.5 The Oromo as the First True Republic: Reconceptualizing Republican Democracy

3.5.1. Oromo Republicanism

The renowned French geographer and writer Jacques Élisée Reclus (1892), who claims Western thoughts were seeded in Africa in the River Nile valley, does not only emphasize the Upper Nile (Kush) as the origin of the Egyptian civilization but also makes an interesting comparison to illustrate that Western civilization is indeed an ancient Cushitic civilization. He writes:

The inhabitants of Asia Minor and Hellas, who were destined to become the teachers of the nations succeeding them, were still cavemen and denizens of the

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forest, armed only with clubs and sharpened flints, at a time when astronomical observations, arithmetic, geometry, architecture, all the arts and nearly all the industries of the present day, as well as the games which now delight our childhood, or afford relaxation from the serious work of life, were already known to their Egyptian contemporaries. The origin of our sciences, and many moral precepts still taught by the “wisdom of nations,” are found recorded on the papyri and on the bas-reliefs of the monuments of Upper Egypt; whilst many a dogma on which existing religions are based, may be traced in its original form to the documents discovered in the tombs of Thebes and Abydos. (Reclus, 1892, pp. 307–308)

Moreover, it has been suggested that the Kushites had reached “the true zenith of democracy” at some point in their glorious prehistoric times (Houston, 1926 [2004], p. 15). It appears that the descendants of the ancient Cushites have now lost their true democracy except the Oromo. This ancient “Ethiopia” or Ancient Empire of Kush, or Kush–Ethiopia, was the first country: the first country to make laws; and the first country not only to institute organized worship but also to lend to the Greeks and the Romans their kings and queens as gods and goddesses (Houston, 1926 [2004], pp. 15–18). The greatness of Ancient Kush and ancient Egyptians appears to have been preserved to date only by the Oromo—the largest and the core of the Cushitic peoples who claim to be the first nation on earth. (For more on the relations between the Oromo and Ancient Egyptians, see *The Oromo and Ancient Egyptians* above)

Even though ancient Kush included many nations, including ancient Nubians, ancient Egyptians, ancient Bejja, the ancient Oromo (Suba / Madebay / Madibe / Madille / Matite), it is only by the Oromo that the “zenith of democracy” of the ancient Kush has been preserved

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to date. The fundamental principles of the republican form of governments, “equality, temperance [sic], industry, intelligence, and justice,” of the ancient “zenith of democracy” are learned by their successors from the Ancient Cushites (Houston, 1926 [2004], p. 18). The reason why Gadaa-like generation-set systems are a common heritage to the Cushitic language speakers of Lowland East and even East Cushitic languages (Schlee, 2008, p. 7) is, perhaps, because they have inherited it from their ancient common Cushite civilization.

The Oromo are however distinct. While other Kushites have lost this socio-political civilization, the Oromo have maintained it to date. They have been able to do so regardless of the successive influence from the Pharaonic, Kerman, Napatan, Da'mat, Sabaeen, Meroitic, Aksumite, Zagwean, and Abyssinian kingdoms that have imparted elements of their respective social, political, and cultural settings on the peoples of northeast Africa region. They are not only the single largest Cushitic nation but also the only custodian of part of the ancient Cushitic civilization in the form of a democratic and republican system of government, presently known as the Gadaa System, which upholds the ancient fundamental principles. These fundamental principles make the backbone of the Gadaa System and the Oromo society today. The Oromo Democracy (better known as Gadaa System) is likely the living avatar of the form of government of Ancient Kushites that has been described as “the true zenith of democracy.”

During their protracted offensive-defensive military campaigns against the kingdom of Abyssinia in the 16th century, the northern Oromo demonstrated that there existed an effective and efficient republican, democratic, and yet egalitarian form of government that could easily defeat the traditional medieval monarchy that had gathered hundreds of thousands of soldiers and an army of commanders. The effective social and political organization of the Gadaa System of the Oromo succeeded in defeating the kingdom of

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Abyssinia. In other words, the Oromo were able to introduce and demonstrate that their superb republican political ideals, socio-political and military organizations that they had invented, refined, and tested for many centuries were superior to such corresponding ideals and organizations of traditional medieval monarchy.

Unfortunately, the indigenous republican form of government of the Oromo and its corresponding socio-political advancements would remain unrecognized fully until the West would marginally rediscover its variant centuries later only after the American and French revolution of the late 18th century. The fact that the Oromo had no kings, but elected leaders in a republican form of democracy, which was not yet well known in the Western societies, the European and Arab explorers and scholars could not comprehend it in the framework of the contemporary political thoughts of the Medieval time. Hence, they could not give enough attention to Oromo polity (Gadaa System). The regular total and complete transfer of power from one Gadaa to another every eight years through an election system which “proceeded by an energetic election campaign, featuring oratorical skills, traditional wisdom, as well as recitations of military prowess” (Zewde, 1994, p. 6), and recounting of the Gadaa principles (constitution) and the laws were new. The history of the world had been the history of kings and kingdoms until the emergence of Western democracy in the late 18th century: There is no wonder that the flourished indigenous African Democracy of the earlier centuries was ignored.

The difficulty of the Western travelers and explorers was not only in understanding the Oromo democracy but also in acknowledging that it existed. The latter would be much difficult for them because acknowledging an indigenous African Democracy that had already been in practice for centuries before the West had started to revolt against the rule of the absolute monarchy would have sounded absurd. The attitudes with which the travelers, the

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proselytizers, the explorers, and the colonizers came to Africa are also understandable. The later in particular categorically believed they came with “light” of civilization to “dark” Africa. They had neither the expectations, not the willingness to learn such an advanced democracy from Africa.

Even today, there are some Abyssinian and Western Abyssinian- Ethiopianist scholars who have continued to downplay Gadaa democracy. No Abyssinian scholar has ever studied or written about Gadaa System. They, however, have embellished anything about Abyssinia, including the myths and legends, in as much as giving them a meaning and a new life. Only a few Western Abyssinian-Ethiopia-nists but none of the Orientalist Ethiopia-nists have researched or written about Gadaa System. They do so even though the Oromo Democracy is an ideal form of the republican system of government (Plowden, 1868, p. 307). The fact that UNESCO has registered it as “an indigenous democratic socio-political system of the Oromo” in the list of intangible heritage of humanity appears to make little sense to them. They have continued to undermine obstinately this great socio-political achievement of humanity not because of what it is but because of their contemptuous attitude and insolence to the Oromo nation. In other words, they do so for two reasons: first, it came from the “unlikeliest” nation to whom they could not attach their affiliation or association; second, it stands as the antithesis to the Abyssinian history, legends, heritage, and values that they have long projected as an authentic representation of the whole of Ethiopia.

The Imperceptible Republic

By the 16th century, the time they allegedly came in to contact with the Abyssinians for the first time, the Oromo had made democratic practices their core culture: Gadaa System had already been a full-fledged egalitarian socio-political and republican government system of the Oromo (). If the Oromo had made Gadaa System their full-fledged form of

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government by the beginning of the 16th century, there can be no doubt that they had it as such for many centuries before. The Oromo might have practiced their republican democracy at a grass root level for many centuries (perhaps for few millennia) before the 16th century. It might have taken them many generations to institute the republican and democratic Gadaa System as their overarching socio-political culture at the time when the rest of the world was still at the Age of Empires.

Even after the 16th century, little has been written about the Oromo polity as having a democratic system of government because it has been imperceptible. The political system of the Oromo has been uniquely unobtrusive and extremely pervasive. There have been no revolts and beating of war drums, but regular peaceful and orderly elections and only peaceful power transfers. This nature of the Oromo Gadaa System and the fact the monarchy was considered as a universal model of polity until the 18th century, made the Oromo deep-rooted republican polity imperceptible. Because it was imperceptible it could not catch the attention of explorers, missionaries, traders, or historians.

Even after the Gadaa System, the Oromo polity started to become known since the mid-19th century in segmented form, some Western scholars, such as Legesse (1973; 2006), Bassi (1996; 2005), Cerulli (1922), who have studied some section of the Oromo and their institutions since the late 20th century, have failed to acknowledge the full extent of the Gadaa System of the Oromo even at present. A typical example of such scholars is P. T. W. Baxter (1978), who, despite conducting many useful studies on the Oromo, appears to be fully dedicated to undermining Gadaa System and other Oromo institutions whenever an opportunity comes around. Several of Abyssinian and non-Abyssinian Ethiopianist scholars, for example, Getachew Haile (2002) share the determination of Baxter. Such intentionally biased determination may have more to do with condescension than scholarship.

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Had the Oromo had kings and kingdoms, however, historians would have written the history of their kings and their kingdoms. The Oromo had a contrasting republican form of government and popular democracy that involved every Oromo at a grass root level with a bottom-up approach of elected leadership (Legesse, 1973; 2000; 2006). In contrast, power emanated only from the top and taken for granted as God-given to the kings in an absolute monarchy. The kings scarcely delegate power to his appointees who governed regions or districts. Power of the Abbaa Gadaas, that are acquired through a contested election and established social and legal contracts (Legesse, 2006), were not commanding attention. Highly distributed, consensus-based, time-bound power of Abbaa Gadaas were instituted within balanced opposition, balanced representation, vertical power-sharing, separation of powers of the state into legislative, executive, and the judiciary. This was either unheard of or got little or no attention of adventurous intellectuals of the old days who neither knew nor expected another form of government than traditional monarchy in the continent that they presumed not enlightened. Hence, the Gadaa System and Gadaa Government remained imperceptible. As a result, little has been written about the form of government of the Oromo, not only before the 16th century but also afterward.

Gadaa System remained imperceptible until very recently. This was not because it was less effective or the people who belonged to it were not aware of it or did not enjoy it as an egalitarian and republican system of governance. It was because the outsiders had neither the readiness for the conception of this new political ideal nor the expectation of the existence of such a system of government in this “uncivilized” part of the world. In other words, it was imperceptible because it was rejected by contempt, or it was not commendable to outsiders who knew and expected a government only in the form of kingdom, advanced or traditional, not a republican system so sophisticated and challenging comprehension. Indeed, the Gadaa

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System is complex. It has remained a serious challenge to outsiders to understand easily, prompting them to wonder faultily that the Oromo could not be its inventors.

A very good illustration for this could be the case of a German ethnologist, Haberland (1992), who had already been indoctrinated by the Semitist and Ethiopianist Enno Littmann before his adventure into the southern part of the Empire of Ethiopia. Though he lived with the southern Oromo and studied the Gadaa System, he held a very arrogant attitude towards the achievements of the Oromo. He not only contemptuously dismissed the mental faculty of the Oromo to create a very advanced and highly democratic system like Gadaa System and the Oromo Calendar, but he also could not hide his “chauvinistic jealousy” when he suggested that Gadaa System probably came from another society that he could not specify (Bokku, 2011, p. 166). Besides, he denied the Oromo origin of the Oromo calendar without a mention of any evidence (Bokku, 2011, p. 166). His denial, in his own words, is on the ground that “the complicated nature of Gadaa-system makes it appear a foreign element, like the calendar, whose foreign origin is unquestionable” (Haberland, 1963, cited in Bokku, 2011, p. 166).

For Haberland and the likes of him, something complicated and surprisingly advanced could not have simply been invented or developed by the people, who appeared to be less sophisticated and “less civilized” than the Westerners. Something of Oromo, which is beyond comprehension to them, they believed dishonestly, was beyond the intelligence of the Oromo. Such arrogance and Western chauvinism were perhaps one of the main reasons why the noble Gadaa System and the astronomically based Oromo Calendar could not cross the horizon of the Oromo country and reach Europe to enlighten further the European Enlightenment Era.

One other factor that might explain partly the “invisibility” of the Oromo republicanism, for such a long, even after the end of the Colonial Era in Africa, is what

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Asmarom Legesse (2006) calls “monarchist illusion,” an illusion in British social anthropology that erroneously equates law and order (and statehood) only with the existence of an authoritarian head, a monarch. From the point of view of his social anthropology research on the Oromo democratic institutions and government since the early 1970s and his observation on lack of proper recognition of African political institutions in the annals of British political anthropology, Legesse (2006) argues:

there is a monarchist *illusion* [Emphasis in the original] that equates law and order with kings, chiefs, emirs, and sultans implying that the democratic African societies are stateless and lawless. It is an illusion because the achievement of “law and order” is likely to occur in democratic as in a monarchic environment. ... Oromo society with its complex laws, long legislative tradition, and effective method of checking the abuse of power, maintained orderly government and successions to political office for four centuries while many “civilized” nations were going through centuries of insurrections and civil wars. (p. 27)

This “illusion” might have been at work among German and Italian Anthropologists. These European social and political anthropologists, who studied the African communities of East Africa, might have missed the democratic Gadaa governments of the Oromo because of this “illusion.”

Legesse (2006) suggests one of the reasons why Europeans long ignored African democracy and constitutional government, like that of the Gadaa Democracy and Gadaa Government of the Oromo, has been because it was contrary to their “civilizing mission” in Africa, and heretical to their aspiration to become pioneer democracies. At the time most of Europe had aspired to transition from monarchy to democracy (an epitome of the advanced

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political ideal of the time), Legesse (2006, pp. 29-30) contends: First, admitting that some African countries have had practiced some form of democracy since the 16th century would have made their “civilizing mission” far-fetched. Second, admitting that some African polities had had an advanced constitutional feature than theirs could have been considered heretical. Thus, to be the “pioneers” themselves, they ignored or downplayed the true pioneers. The Oromo, the pioneer inventors of Gadaa democracy and truly republican form of government, have sometimes been categorized as “stateless societies” because they had no monarchy but democratically elected leaders, a political reality that had probably been suppressed by the West.

In summary, the republican polity of the Oromo (Gadaa System) has historically been imperceptible because of many reasons. First, it has been peaceful and orderly by its nature. It beats no war drum and creates no chaos to catch attention. Second, it has become a unified socio-political culture. It has been holistic and unexpectedly deep-rooted to create overt oppositions and confrontations. Third, it has no imposing permanent center or towering institutional amenities. Fourth, it has no written records. Fifth, and most importantly, it has been a republican system. It was a system that neither individual historians nor the rest of the world anticipated its practice in Africa or prepared to accept it for what it was, and it has been. It was a republican democratic system invented by the indigenous Oromo people. They had invented it many centuries before the much similar political ideal emerged during the formation of the USA. Sixth, until very recently scholars who studied Oromo had been obsessed with the authoritarian form of governments headed by kings, chiefs, emirs, and sultans than Oromo democratic governments led by elected leaders. Seventh, Gadaa Democracy may have been intentionally ignored because the West was not willing to

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acknowledge that Africans had championed such advanced political ideas. These reasons might have variably contributed to making Gadaa System imperceptible.

Gadaa Republic: Oromo State

The idea of a supreme man or family or divine appointment to a political office or absolute monarchy, or any of such power that deprived the people of their freedom, liberty, and sovereignty, had been alien to the Oromo polity. This was reflected partly in the first century CE account of the anonymous author of *The Periplus of The Erythraean Sea* where he emphasized that the people of Horn of Africa had neither the central government nor kingly authority. The latter description was very true, but the former part reflected a lack of knowledge of the author about other forms of government or the fact that could not observe grand edifices akin to the Egyptian courts. Implying a lack of strong central governments as a lack of government is a mistake, which uninformed foreigners have continued to make when commenting on African societies (Mwanzi, 1985, p. 150). Indeed, the Oromo nation had no kings: but, at the time, oral chronicles suggest, that they had a loose central republican Gadaa government. According to Oromo oral chronicles known as “argaa–dhageettii,” the Oromo had Gadaa System starting from as early as 1343 BCE (Bokku, 2011, p. 162) or 1000 BCE (Lata, 1998, p. 131). Historically, the Oromo had a republican mode of polity known as the Gadaa System since, at least, as early as 851 CE (Ayana, 2016).

The Oromo have always had a democratic polity and a republican government until some of them had started to integrate with the kingdom of Abyssinia after the beginning of the 17th century. The Gadaa System is a republican and an egalitarian form of government based only on the free will of the Oromo people where elected Abbaa Gadaas are vested with state power for eight years single term of office and serve in the local, regional, and national Gadaa institutions taking up political, administrative, economic, military, ritual, and

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reconciliation responsibilities. The polity of the Oromo is well known to be a democracy.

About the polity of Boorana Oromo, who have best preserved the Gadaa System, one scholar exclaims: “Borana polity, of which gada is only one component, may certainly be considered a democracy, if “democracy” is strictly taken in its classic meaning of “government of the people, by the people, for the people” “ (Bassi, 1996, quoted in Lencho, 2013, p. 97). The Oromo have never been organized under one king, as a kingdom or as an empire, in their recorded history. Gadaa System has been the republican form of government of the Oromo.

The Gadaa System has been more than that to the Oromo. It has been an all-inclusive system. Many anthropologists and historians who have studied Oromo, at least partly, have witnessed this. One among them, Haberland (1992), despite his condescending attitude about its origin, described the all-inclusiveness of the Gadaa System as follows:

The gada [Gadaa] was a central institution that ruled the life of the Oromo with an exclusivity unknown among any other people. Nothing was not subject to its rules: birth, baptism [Hammachiisa/Child naming], marriage, circumcision, emancipation from paternal authority, permission to beget and bring up children, conscription for war and for hunting, obligation to kill and to sacrifice, civil death by exclusion from the system, burial, the style of adornments, hairstyles, clothing, furniture and ceremonial trappings, the installation of house and kraal and more. It represented the sum total of the laws by which life was governed. (pp. 717-718)

By the 16th century, the Gadaa System was so advanced that it had included democratic principles that later emerged in the west in the late 18th century. It, however, found itself odd with the monarchist socio-political ideals of its neighbors. The Christian neighbor had a different socio-political system. The people were ruled by a man with

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absolute power, often advocated that the man was chosen by the divine and the power was given from the divine; succession to power was hereditary; the distinction between masters and servants was starkly clear; all the subjects also had their respective places in the strictly hierarchical social structure. These socio-political ideals and structures were alien to the Oromo and their Gadaa democracy.

These contrary ideas were introduced to the Oromo gradually. Most of the Oromo strongly resisted them from 16th to 18th centuries. The introduction of such ideals first divided the northern Oromo communities as frontier Oromo minority groups tolerated or joined the Abyssinian monarchy fitting to the existed structure. They abandoned the political aspect of the Gadaa System in favor of the Abyssinian monarchy. These Oromo (mainly Yajjuu and Walloo Oromo) were a minority but they soon controlled the Kingdom of Abyssinia and ruled it (directly and indirectly) for over a century. Later, in the early 19th century, sections of the frontier Oromo communities in the north and southwest also built few petty states that were much like the Abyssinian monarchy than the republican Gadaa System. The alien socio-political system and other factors gradually weakened the Gadaa System and divided the Oromo. Finally, the ruler-ship of the absolute monarchy was imposed on the Oromo nation in total after the people who had long been ruled by absolute monarchs contrary to the Oromo republican ideals subjugated the Oromo of modern Ethiopia in the late 19th century.

Despite the introduction of such contrary ideas, most of the Oromo have always remained republican and upheld the Gadaa democracy. Though the Oromo remained under the domination of the Abyssinian monarchy for about a century (from the 1880s to 1970s), the colonial rule of the Abyssinians had little effect on their fundamental ideals. During that century, it was only the political aspect of the Gadaa System that was forced out of regular

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practice in regions where the colonial institutions took the place of the Gadaa government. The socio-cultural and ritual aspects of the Gadaa System, however, remained intact and continued to be practiced. In remote regions and among the Boorana, Gujii, and Karrayyuu Oromo, where the effect of settler colonization were minimal, Gadaa remained in full practice. Despite the imperial banning of the political aspect of the Gadaa System for many decades since the late 19th century in modern Ethiopia, most of the Oromo communities continued to practice Gadaa as a cultural and ritual system.

Summary and Conclusion

The Oromo are one of the indigenous peoples of the prehistoric Ancient Empire of Kush, as well as the ancient Ethiopia known to the Greeks, and the Kush of the Greeks and Romans. They consider themselves the first nation on earth. Historically, they have inhabited both the Upper Ethiopia and Lower Ethiopia regions. Their main homeland, however, has been the East African region, spanning from northern Ethiopia to northern Tanzania. Even though they have inhabited this vast region, their cradle land in the 16th century was believed to be south-central Ethiopia. They are the largest Cushitic people in the region, from whom other Cushitic peoples (for example, the Somali, the Afar, and the Maasai) might have branched out in relatively recent history. They had strong socio-cultural and economic interactions with the ancient Egyptians and the Greeks.

The Oromo have a republican form of socio-political system, known as the Gadaa System, which they have practised, according to Oromo oral literature, perhaps since 1000 BCE. The Gadaa System is a republican form of democracy that predates American democracy, dating back several centuries in recorded history, and represents an advanced form of republicanism. It existed before America was discovered, before the first European communities arrived on that continent. The Gadaa System is currently registered with

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UNESCO as part of its “intangible heritage of humanity.” As a full-fledged socio-political and purely republican democratic system of the Oromo nation, the Gadaa System has been in practice, without interruption, in some regions of Oromia since Gadaa Jibbenaa (1490–1498) in the late 15th century or since Gadaa Malbaa (1522–1530) in the early 16th century, when it formally entered historical records. The recorded chronologies of Abbaa Gadaas (equivalent to elected presidents) of some Oromo junior sub-moieties have reached the 71st and 72nd generations. Each Abbaa Gadaa was elected. He served for only eight years, after which he handed the power over to the succeeding elected Abbaa Gadaa peacefully as per the Gadaa constitution.

The Oromo were the inhabitants of northern Ethiopia before the arrival of the South Arabian and Abyssinian peoples on the continent around the turn of the Common Era. They are the faithful “Kush” and “Ethiopia” of the scripture and prehistory. They have remained the single largest Cushitic nation to date. A new identity and language, known as Amhara and Amharic, respectively, were developed from the amalgamation of nations and languages in present-day north-central Ethiopia, lending strength to the powerful expansionist Christian kingdom that emerged in the 13th century. Both the integration and the neighbourhood of the Oromo with the newcomers to the region and with the amalgamated identity were not always easy. Its struggle with both the Christian kingdom and the Islamic sultanates in the present-day central and eastern Ethiopia during the 16th century was notable. Due to the continued expansion of the Christian Abyssinian kingdom and the Muslim sultanates, the Oromo were forced to reclaim part of their lost territories in their Gadaa-based offensive-defensive military campaign during the 16th century. Through the campaign, they not only neutralised the Christian and the Muslim powers but also expanded further north and southwest in the present Ethiopian territory.

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Although the Oromo nation has come a long way from Ancient Kush to Oromia in northeast Africa, its renaissance has not yet been fully grasped. The Oromo are indigenous peoples of the northeast African region. They were part of the ancient Cushite empire, the true ancestors of the modern Ethiopians. Their ethnogenesis from Cush resulted in the formation of the Oromo national identity. This new national identity resulted in the formation of the first nation, the Oromo nation. The Oromo nation has inhabited the Upper and Lower Ethiopia, as well as central east Africa. The Oromo nation had remarkably close connections with the ancient Egyptians, and the two groups shared similarities. The Oromo also had some connections with ancient Greece. The cradle land of the Oromo has always been the Horn of Africa region, where they share close cultural and linguistic ties with other Kushite peoples, such as the Beja, Afar, and Somali peoples. The latter has developed into a separate national identity from the Oromo in relatively recent times, and the two nations started to drift apart, mainly since the introduction of Islam into the Horn of Africa. Though the Oromo are believed to have lived peacefully and in harmony with the other Cushitic peoples in northeast Africa for time immemorial, the arrival of southern Arabian peoples to the region starting from the Middle of the last millennium BCE and their subsequent expansion started to disrupt the economic, social, political, religious, and cultural equilibrium in the region. This ultimately resulted in the Gadaa-based protracted campaign of the Oromo in the 16th century, during which they reclaimed most of their lost territories from the Kingdom of Abyssinia and the Sultanate of Adal in the north and east. The Oromo may have conducted similar Gadaa-based military campaigns in the south and southwest against the Bantu and Nilotic peoples, expanding at least as far as northern Tanzania, southeastern Kenya, and the eastern Democratic Republic of Congo. However, little has been recorded about their military advances in the south and southwest, except that they had formed ruling aristocracies as

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“northern invaders” in the region as early as the 16th century. These aristocracies and their Oromo descendants were vibrant in this vast African savanna region just before the dawn of European colonisation in the late 19th century.

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Chapter 4. Historiographic Rectification: The Oromo Resistance Struggles and Influence in the Kingdom of Abyssinia, 1550s-1880s

The Oromo affectionately call their country Biyya Abbaa (Father Land). They love their Father Land so dearly. They see him as synonymous with a provider for their livelihood. They believe they own him, and he holds them: they think they are inseparable. They impersonate Father Land and praise him in every ritual and blessing. They sing about “him” and praise him every day. Their Father Land is synonymous with their existence, identity, and overall development of the Oromo nation (finna).

The Oromo, however, had been under continuous assimilation and displacement from the northern part of their Father Land, mainly starting from the dawn of the Common Era. Until the beginning of the 16th century, they had been pushed continuously southwards or fully or partially assimilated by the northern successive Christian Aksumite and Zagwean kingdoms and the eastern Islamic Sultanates. This started from the time of the emergence and expansion of the Christian Aksumite kingdom in the present combined territories of the Tigray State of the Ethiopian Federation and the State of Eritrea. The northernmost ancient Madabay Oromo of the region had been assimilated by the Aksumite kingdom as early as the second CE. The kingdom had reached the present South Wollo Zone of the Amhara State in its south expansion. As the kingdom of Aksum declined in the 7th century, Islam emerged in the region. By the time the kingdom of Aksum almost disappeared in the 9th century, the expansion of the Islamic principalities had started to gain momentum in the south-central Ethiopian highland and the central Ethiopian section of the Great East African Rift Valley. Islam expanded rapidly in the region of the 10th and 11th centuries. The emergence of yet another powerful Christian Zagwean Dynasty in the former territory of the kingdom of Aksum did not affect the expansion of Islam or its principalities. The Zagwean kings

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continued to expand their territory south, including into the Oromo land, until the so-called Solomonic Dynasty would replace it at the end of the 13th century. By the 14th century, seven Islamic Sultanates (Ifat, Dawwaro, Arbabini, Hadiya, Sharka, Bali, and Darra) had been established (Delebo, 2007, p. 214). During this time, the mainly mostly sedentary Oromo who were engaged in mixed farming and lived in the frontiers of the expansions of both the Christian and Islamic powers had become tributary parts of either the Islamic principalities or the Christian kingdom while most of the Oromo who were predominantly pastoralists had moved further south to present south-central Ethiopia. Atse Amde Tsion (r. 1314–1344) later annexed Oromo communities that had fallen under the influence of the Islamic principalities during the first significant expansion of the Abyssinian kingdom into the region (Hassen, 1990, pp. xii, 5). A century later, the Yaayyaa, the Galaan, and other northern Oromo communities were cut off from the rest of the Oromo geographically, politically, and culturally. The political and cultural disconnection resulted in the relocation of some of the ancient Oromo politico-cultural centers, including Odaa Nabee (dated to 204 CE (Hinew, 2012, p. 86)), at the foot of Yerer Mountain near Addis Ababa (Finfinnee), to Madda Walaabuu in the south. By the beginning of the 16th century, the Galaan and the Yaayyaa Oromo, living in the present North, Southwest, and East Shewa Zones of Oromia State, respectively, had already adopted Abyssinian affiliation. The Galaan even had established marital relationships with the families of Abyssinian kings in the early 16th century during the reign of Atse Gelawdewos (r. 1540–1559), as reported by the Portuguese soldier Bermudez (Gidada, 2016). Their chief (most probably Abbaa Gadaa) had married the aunt of Atse Gelawdewos. The Yaayyaa Oromo had, at least in part, adopted Christianity because of the extensive proselytization by the most popular Abyssinian monk (later saint), Tekle

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Haimanot, who lived from 1215–1313 CE and had adopted more of a sedentary mixed farming life akin to the Abyssinians than mainly pastoralist life.

Because of their immediate neighborhood, gradual overtaking of their land, and their socio-cultural assimilation to both the Christian and the Islamic powers, the northern Oromo had already established strong connections with the kingdom of Abyssinia and the Islamic Principalities before the eruption of the Muslim-Christian war in early 16th century. Before the invasion of Ahmad Gragn in 1529, some Oromo communities had participated in the power struggle in the kingdom during the reign of Atse Be'ede Mariam (r. 1468–1478) and the successive years (Gidada, 2016, p. 57). Tekletsadek Mekuria, the author of most of the traditional Ethiopian history books (in the Amharic language), argues that the Oromo already had political influence in the courts of the Abyssinian kingdom during the Jihad of Ahmad Gragn (Mekuria, 1945 Eth. C. 1957 cited in Gidada, 2016, p. 55). He concludes that Tullu, whom Atse Libne Dengle is reported to have exclaimed after the first defeat of the kingdom by the army of Ahmad Gragn in 1527, saying, “Even if all were frightened, how come Tullu was frightened?” was a high-ranking Oromo, Ras Agafari (headmaster of ceremonies), in the army of the kingdom. The Islamized Oromo living in the Islamic principalities likely had similar affiliations and internal power struggles.

It is worth mentioning, though with caution, because of certain doubts on the validity of his primary source that Jiksa (2016) argues that not only the founder of the Abyssinian kingdom, Yekuno Amlak, had married an Oromo and the descendants of that union had ruled Abyssinian/Ethiopia for seven hundred years, but also, based on the works of Meriras Aman Belay, the Oromo chiefs of Shewa had maintained religiously motivated neutrality during the early invasion of Ahmad Gragn helping the latter to have an advantage over the Christian kingdom. This action would lead to a series of events. First, the prosecution of Abba Guchi

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Ulmaya (probably an Abbaa Duulaa) by the Atse Libne Dengle (r. 1508–1540) with the catastrophic effect of all the Salale (northern Shewa) Oromo leaders (Abbaa Gadaas), namely Abbaa Merzo, Abbaa Bulaa, Abbaa Qoricho (probably Abbaa Bokkuus), and Abbaa Guuta, to eventually take side with Ahmad Gragn. Second, war erupted between the army of the Oromo and the army of Libne Dengle after the defeat of Atse Libne Dengle (r. 1508–1540) by Ahmad Gragn at Baduqe (Bishooftuu), and all the Oromo leaders were killed; Third, in the end, the followers of the Oromo leaders were dead and the entire Oromo nation was defamed by the Abyssinians as traitors, pagan, and cruel, among others (Jiksa, 2015, p. 81). Based on the same source, Jiksa maintains that the Oromo were indeed the መደባይ (Madabay) of the 10th century BCE who inhabited the northern part of modern Ethiopia, including Tigray and the Amhara States. He says they have been consistently present in the Horn of Africa region, with some movements throughout history. Also, they have had more State control and political power than the Amhara in the history of Abyssinian Ethiopia. His assertions, however, await validation of the sources. The source is an ancient book allegedly discovered in Jebel Nuba, in Sudan, by certain Mariras Aman Belay. Belay is the author of the many books that Professor Jiksa has acknowledged and has used extensively as the source in his book, የአሮሞ እና የአማራ እውነተኛው የዘር ምንጭ (The True Origin of the Oromo and Amhara).

Those Oromo who were pressed to present south-central Ethiopia, commonly referred to as Boorana today, had remained unbroken either by the Christian or the Islamic powers and preserved the Oromo culture, traditions, religion, and most importantly, the Gadaa System. By the beginning of the 16th century, the Oromo had established multiple regional centers for their politico-religious centers that would later become known as “cradle lands” for these southern Oromo moieties. Mohammed Hassen indicates the “cradle land“ of historical Booranaa (Maccaa and Tuulamaa) at Haroo Walaabuu, southern Booranaa at Tulluu

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Walal, northern Booranaa (Marawwaa, Karrayyuu, Waraanticha) at Bareedduu Kurkurtuu, central Baarentuu (Akkicchuu, Ituu, Hubannaa) at Mormor, southern Baarentuu (Gujii, Warra Dayaa) at Haroo Garjaa, and Ormaa at Tulluu Namdurii (Hassen, 1990, p. 19). This recently established southern “cradle lands” served as the epicenter of the offensive defense of the Oromo in the early 16th century.

Both the northern and the southern Oromo did not doubt that the migration of Semites people from the Southern Arabian Peninsula to the continent from about 500 BCE to about 100 CE and the subsequent establishment of the kingdom of Aksum from a mix of Yemeni Arabs and some Semitized Cushitic peoples around 100 CE in the eastern territory of the ancient Kingdom of Kush along the middle Red Sea coast was the beginning of the large scale displacement of the Oromo in the region. Though they tried to accommodate and integrate the alien peoples, by the beginning of the 16th century, the Oromo were highly frustrated because of the aggressive land-grabbing expansion and all the imposing religions and absolutist forms of government these people brought. In addition to the loss of their land, the alien religions and political system posed a significant threat to the Oromo religion, democratic form of government, and the Oromo identity.

As a result, the Oromo must have felt that they had to defend their well-formed and deeply established national identity. The national feeling that had been unceasingly agitated by continued pressure from the expanding Abyssinian Christian kingdom, Islamic (Muslim) Sultanates, and the Somali and Omotic peoples was probably the main factor that resolutely united the Oromo in the 16th century to defend their Father Land and reclaim the territories that had been their ancestors’ a few centuries before. Besides, the defense of the Oromo Father Land has always been part of the Gadaa System. Organized defense of the Father Land has been the constitutional responsibility of the Gadaa government. So long as Gadaa was in

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practice, the Oromo had always defended themselves. Still, only when their principles of qixxee and wal–dandeettii did not work, they became victims of aggression. Even though the Oromo had avoided for the more significant part of their ancient history organized military confrontations due to their principles of qixxee, wal–dandeettii, safuu, and nagaa (peace), from among others, they were pushed to the limit where they could not avoid war because of existential threats. By the end of the 16th century, the Oromo proved that these principles had failed, and they were highly pressured by the expansion of the Abyssinian Christian kingdom and the Adal Islamic Sultanate, as well as the Somali and Omotic peoples into their heartland.

At the beginning of the 16th century, the aspiration of the Oromo to reclaim their lost territories was at its height. The Oromo had continued to aspiration to reclaim the vast land of their ancestors. They had always believed that part of their more enormous country had been taken away gradually from them, starting from the early years of the migration of alien peoples, mainly from southern Arabia, into the Horn of Africa region. They believed that the Father Land once enclosed most of the East Africa region stretching from south of Tanzania to north of Sudan and from coastal Somalia to central South Sudan. There was a strong sense of indebtedness and craving among the Oromo to restore the Father Land to the glory and the scale they believed it had achieved before the arrival of southern Arabian peoples onto the continent of Africa.

The Oromo started their protracted offensive–defense struggle against the hard-pressing peoples, notably the Abyssinians, out of the necessity of national self-defense and the urge to reclaim the lost territory of the Father Land. They had been pushed south for centuries; the Abyssinians gradually overtook their land through military occupation and settlement. By then, the highly militarized Abyssinian kingdom and the newly emerging religiously fanatic Islamic kingdom of Adal had posed an existential threat to the Oromo. The

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Oromo had already started their humble offensive-defensive campaign against the expansionist Muslim kingdom of Adal and Somali clans in Bali in the 1520s. At this time, the Oromo had “a form of constitutional government known as gadaa” (Gadaa government) (Jalata, 2012, p. 130); they had long reformed their Gadaa; their military was effectively organized based on age sets. Soon, the religiously motivated war between the Islamic Sultanate of Adal and the Christian Abyssinian kingdom began in 1529. The former quietly gained the upper hand over the latter in a few years and overrun vast territories. During those few years, north-central Oromo, the Galaan, waged a war against the Abyssinian kingdom that had long distressed them. They fought a great battle in the Gurage land, south of Shewa near the river Gála (“Gallas,” 1911). The Abyssinian kingdom very quickly fell under the control of Islamic power. This Muslim-Christian war between the two major powers allowed the Oromo to scale up their offensive–defensive campaign against both powers.

Finally, the Oromo deepened *duula galaa* commendably. By then, they must have decided to start reclaiming their ancestral land. They must have realized that it could only be possible through the instrument of violence, a protracted offensive-defensive war. *Duula galaa* was the only viable option to return to “the land which earlier had been taken away from them by the Christian authorities, at least in the south of what is today Shewa” (Hassen, 1990, p. xiii) and beyond. Thus, they began their century-long, Gadaa-based, offensive-defensive war that would enable them to take back most of the territories they had lost and to free themselves from the threats to their religion, identity, and democratic form of government.

The Oromo had no undemocratic political system throughout their recorded history. They have an indigenous socio-political system that is founded on “Oromo institutions of *aadaa* (custom and tradition), *seera* (laws), *safuu* (all-inclusive harmony) and *heera* (justice)”

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and led by principles that are found in the modern polity; among them is the principle of equality (Geshe, 2013, pp. 64–65). This socio-political system is known as the Gadaa System or Gadaa Democracy. It is a distinctive set of democratic and republican institutions uniquely Oromo. The ideals of Gadaa represent being an Oromo (Oromummaa) (Lewis 1966 cited in Mole, 2014, p. 25). The only socio-political system the Oromo had known before their settler colonization by the Abyssinian kingdom was the Gadaa System.

Gadaa System is an ancient institution in East Africa that emerged for governance and social cohesion (Hinew, 2012, p. 99). It is “highly endowed with legal and moral values” (Hinew, 2012, p. 105). It, according to American anthropologist Bonnie Holcomb, “organized the Oromo people in an all-encompassing democratic republic even before the few European pilgrims arrived from England on the shores of North America and only later built a democracy” (Holcomb, 1991, quoted in Jalata, 2004a, p. 12). The Oromo reformed their Gadaa before Christopher Columbus (1451–1506) discovered America. The eight-year and uninterrupted chronologies of the Abbaa Gadaas start from the 15th century among southern Oromo communities in modern Ethiopia. The chronology, which is more than double the span of the chronology of American presidents, has been recorded since about six hundred years ago. For example, the Boorana and the Gujii Oromo of southern Ethiopia have recently elected their 71st and 74th Abbaa Gadaas, Kuraa Jaarsoo, and Jilo Mandhoo, respectively. Gadaa System “operated at the national pan-Oromo level in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries and the local republics from the eighteenth century” (Baissa, 2004, p. 118). By “distributing authority and responsibility across the whole life course” of the Oromo (as per the instituted age-set, Gadaa stages, and generation-sets), Gadaa System ensures “intergenerational equity” and “separation of powers on sequential scale” (Legesse, 2006, p. 128). The Gadaa System gives respect to the supremacy of the rule of law and opposes

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“despotic and authoritarian” rule by providing for removal of “unfit or corrupt leaders even before their term expired” (Baissa, 2004, p. 117). The Oromo “believe that when laws rule all men, the possibility of the prevalence of peace is high, but when men rule, peace loses ground” (Dawo, 2013, p. 170). “The egalitarian ethos, communal solidarity, democratic governance structure, separation of powers, and civility in political deliberation are elements of the Gadaa System” that have allowed the Oromo nation to sustain itself and to maintain the collective peace of the people (Levine, 2007, cited in Dawo, 2013, p. 177). Gadaa System has always stood as a statement of egalitarian and democratic ideology, the embodiment of the supremacy of the law over men, and the manifestation of republican values. As such, the Gadaa System was a pronounced antithesis of the Abyssinian monarchy.

Since the 16th century, the Gadaa System stood in sharp contrast to the absolute monarchy of Abyssinia (Baissa, 2004, p. 106). When the monarchy was highly centralized under the person of the Atse, the Gadaa government was, in fact, a federal system with three levels of central, regional, and local governments under the constitution and laws of Gadaa (Baissa, 2004, p. 106). The central government allowed self-administration at the local level itself, being content with pan-Oromo (national) policymaking, military strategy formulation, coordination of war campaigns, maintenance of internal peace of the Oromo, and conducting relations with non-Oromo neighbours. The highest level of government conducted customary execution of the high-level military, judicial, legislative, and ritual responsibilities. In practice, the Oromo had a loose federal arrangement, while the Abyssinians had an absolute monarchy.

Furthermore, the chapter elaborates the historical relationship between the Oromo and the Kingdom of Abyssinia, two apparent paradoxes are prevalent: on the one hand, many contend that the Oromo have had no or little place in the Abyssinian monarchy, while on the

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other hand, some Abyssinian Ethiopia-nists contend that the Oromo nation was part of the kingdom of Abyssinia. This dissertation shall illustrate that both contentions are incorrect. The first is because the Oromo had been warlords and monarchs in the kingdom. The latter is so because only the assimilated and politically integrated minority groups of northern Oromo had been part of the kingdom. The vast Oromo country, which was almost the present Oromia, was incorporated into the kingdom of Abyssinia-cum-modern Ethiopia, as shall be discussed in the next Chapter, only in the last decades of the 19th century. Until then, Oromia freely governed itself partly by Mootiis but mainly by its Gadaa government. This chapter shall discuss and illustrate the early influences of the Oromo on the Abyssinian kingdom from the reign of Atse Susenyos to Atse Iyasu II (1604-1755) and the political dominance and the Oromo rule of the kingdom during the Yajjuu Dynasty (1769–1855). Ultimately, it summarizes the relegated history of the Oromo in the Abyssinian kingdom.

Origins of Oromo Military Campaigns

A sufficiently detailed record of periodic wars between the kingdom of Abyssinia and the Oromo during the 16th century exists. These wars are referred to as Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaigns in this dissertation. Starting from the early 16th century, Abba Bahrey recorded detailed accounts of the wars between the Oromo and the kingdom of Abyssinia. This record shows that the Oromo waged war against the Abyssinians every eight years following an eight-year rhythm of the Gadaa cycle. Bahrey recorded such wars during 1522–1593 in fair detail. The rhythmic wars that followed the Gadaa power transfer years were known as the Buttaa wars, and the Oromo fought twelve of them between 1522 and 1618 (Jalata, 2005, p. 20). It occurred every eight years following the power transfer from the retiring Luba to the new Luba. Buttaa wars were waged for “revenge or for defensive and offensive purposes” (Jalata, 2005, p. 20; 2012, p. 132). Those wars were based on the Gadaa

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cycle. Their purpose was both defensive and offensive. They were conducted in the form of a national campaign. Thus, referring to them as Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaigns is proper.

The whole Oromo nation was already organized into age-based groups with a clear responsibility of preventing any external force, Christian or Muslim, from entering their sovereign territory under Abbaa Gadaa Gadawo Galgalo in the 1470s (Bokku, 2011, p. 410). During Gadaa Malbaa, the Oromo started to occupy Bali (not Bale), taking the defense further steps ahead. During this Gadaa, the Oromo organized themselves under the non-partisan institution of Abbaa Duulaa (the equivalent of Minister of Defense in the modern government system) not only to defend themselves where they were but also to reoccupy the land that had been taken away from them (Bokku, 2011, p. 411).

It is important to note that Bali was not the present Bale. Bali was located in the middle and Lower Awash basins (Gidada, 2016, p. 91). According to the map made by Ludolf, it was found “on the two banks of the Awash River” (D’Abbadie, 2007, p. 121). However, some Abyssinian historians place it, perhaps by an association of the sound of the name, somewhere near present Bale, one of the Zones of Oromia State, south of the then Abyssinian kingdom. Haile (2002), asserts that modern Bale is the historical Bali. Concerning the Abyssinian historian’s assertion, James Bruce further claims, though erroneously, that seven tribes of the Oromo first settled in the coastal region of the Indian Ocean, moving east from “the center of the continent”(Bruce, 1791, p. 402). From there “after multiplying exceedingly,” they “marched forward due south into Bali and Dawaro” which they “conquered and settled” in 1537 (Bruce, 1791, p. 402). He is suggesting that not only Bali and Dawwaro were located to the south of the kingdom of Abyssinia, but also the Oromo moved south—not north—into them. According to Bruce (1791, p. 504), Bali was

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located northeast of Ennaria and west of Adal (Haile, 2002). However, other historical evidence indicates that Bali was situated east of the kingdom. These include: In 1839, Combeset Tamisier recorded that Bali was located between Mille and Awash Rivers; Maps of Jacops Gastaldi (1561), Abraham Ortelius (1570), Hughes de Linschter (1599), Gerard Mercator (1607), Gui Ilaume et jean Blau (1635), and Melchise de Thevenot (1660s) locate Bali in the northeast of lower Awash; and maps from before 1524 finds Bali to the west of the Lower Awash and the east of Tigray, Angot, and Amhara (Gidada, 2016, p. 91). These historical records and maps show that Bali was, in fact, not exactly the present Bale, and it was located to the east—not to the south—of the then Abyssinian kingdom. This contradicts the Abyssinian assertion that Bali was the present Bale or was in its vicinity. Their effort, however, has been apparent: harmonizing the myth of the “arrival” of the Oromo from the south in the 16th century.

Historically, the Oromo decided whether wars must be declared on their pan-Oromo jaarraa /gumii assemblies (assemblies that happened every eight years). Only this assembly has the constitutional right to declare war. They had to wait for the jaarraa cycle to make a new declaration of war. The war leaders, Abbaa Duulaa, were subordinated to the national assembly. Abbaa Duulaas were required to hold in their hands the Bokkuu (scepter) of the Abbaa Bokkuu at all times until the end of the war as proof of authorization by the local or national Caffee to carry out the war campaign or the war itself. They had neither the authority to declare a new offensive war nor a political affiliation with Gadaas (parties). However, they may declare an emergency defensive war in case of unexpected invasion and carry out localized offensive attacks in consultation with the local Gadaa Council after economic cattle raids by their neighbors as necessary. Elsewise, Abbaa Gadaas declared war after eight years only when it was required. Every eight years, after the Buttaa ceremony, the elected Luba

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(Abbaa Gadaa) organized the Oromo, according to the established age-sets and Gadaa grades, for battles in the wars that the national assembly had declared, i.e., jaarraa assembly.

Nevertheless, it is not possible to pinpoint when exactly the Buttaa wars in general and the Buttaa defense struggles of the Oromo against the encroaching Abyssinian kingdom or the Islamic sultanates started, nor there exists available historical record on whether the Buttaa wars were introduced immediately after the reformation of Gadaa System in the 15th century or earlier. Because the Oromo have been mainly people of oral tradition, and some older oral historical accounts have been continually eroded, it is also challenging to determine the exact year of the beginning of the Buttaa wars from Oromo oral traditions. Most Oromo scholars, however, agree that Buttaa wars for offensive purposes started immediately after the reformation of Gadaa in the mid-15th century. Before that, Buttaa wars were probably limited to chasing out people who were banished by their clans for one reason or the other but had taken homage in the Oromo country as an auxiliary to some Oromo hosts, a tradition which has continued until very recently.

If, as most Oromo scholars agree, the Buttaa wars started immediately after the reformation of the Gadaa System in 1445, the Gadaa-based offensive defense of the Oromo probably began during the Gadaa of the fathers of Gadaa Jibbenaa (1450-1458). Bahrey's record shows that Gadaa Muudanaa is the Gadaa of the sons of Gadaa Jibbenaa (1490-1498), who must be forty years younger according to the principle of the Gadaa genealogical generation (Luba). This supports the accounts held by the traditional oral chronicle of the Oromo. However, there are no records in Abyssinian history that the Gadaa-based war of the Oromo started in the 15th century.

On the other hand, the Gadaa-based offensive-defense of the Oromo started around the same time the Muslim-Christian war began. The earliest mention of the war of the Oromo

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with Abyssinians is in the account of Abba Bahrey, the first learned Abyssinian monk who recorded the history of Gadaa-based military campaigns of the Oromo. Bahrey stated that the first group of Oromo came from the “west” of the Galan River to the frontier of Bali during the region of Atse Libne Dengle (r. 1505–1540) (Tafla, 1987; Hassen, 2016). Most Abyssinian and Western Abyssinian Ethiopianist historians place the beginning of the war between the Oromo and the Abyssinians to the early years after the defeat of Ahmad Gragn in 1543. Richard Pankhurst, one of the highly respected Abyssinian Ethiopianist historians who lived and researched in Ethiopia for nearly half of a century, however, noted that the Oromo started their highly organized defense against the Abyssinian kingdom “immediately before or just at the time of the first incursions of Imam Ahmad Ibn Ibrahim” which began in 1529 (Pankhurst, 1997, p. 281). Besides, some studies show that in 1522, the Oromo “had already begun to participate in the extensive and intensive struggle in the Horn of Africa” before the breakout of the religious war between the Muslims and the Christians in 1529 (Jalata, 2012, p. 132). Mohammed Hassen, one of the prominent Oromo historians, asserts that the Booranaa Oromo, who launched their offensive defense against the Abyssinian kingdom in two stages, launched their first offensive defense in 1522 from west of Genale (Galana) river to the east to Bali (Hassen, 1990, p. 18).

However, the location of the Bali and Galana Rivers is disputed. Dr. Negaso Gidada (2016, pp. 64, 95) asserts that the locality known as Bali-Genz was located to the north of the locality known as Guragie Medir, and he claims that the first victory of the offensive–defense of the Oromo occurred in Guragie Medir near the river “Gala.” The very word “Galla” is associated with the river Gála in Guragie, where the Oromo had a decisive victory over the Abyssinian army (“Gallas,” 1911; Burton, 1856[2012], Chap. IV). The assertion is most likely based on the account by Ludolf in 1537 about a revolt of the oppressed subjects against

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the Abyssinian governor by the name of Thomas in Bali, which, due to the war with Adal, the Abyssinians could not control. According to Gidada (2016), these oppressed people were Oromo; their leadership was from the Walloo Oromo. He, thus, contends that, unlike the famous account of the Abyssinian monks, the first intensive anti-domination war of the Oromo must have started in the location north of Awash River in Shewa. He also suggests that the Oromo might have crossed the river “Gala” (not Galana or Ganale); they traveled to the east to Bali (north of Awash River), not to Bale (north of Wabi Shebele). He mentions the existence of Minor Wabi and Major Wabi rivers in the present Guragie country to strengthen his point.

Even though the exact historical time when the Buttaa wars started is unknown, and the location of historical Bali is disputed, the accounts mentioned above ascertain that the Oromo offensive wars had begun before the Christian–Muslim war of 1529. Accordingly, the first Gadaa-based offensive-defensive war of the Oromo was declared during Gadaa Malbaa (1522–1530) by the Gadaa government of the Oromo. According to the principles of the Gadaa government that gives the power to declare war only to the national assembly, the war must have been reported after the Gadaa National Assembly (Caffee) had deliberated and saw no other option than going to war.

The Oromo must have been confident in their competence to challenge or defeat the Abyssinian monarchy that had grown so powerful when they decided to launch their offensive-defensive campaign. The confidence must have been based on their military readiness and effective socio-political organization. At the beginning of the 16th century, they had developed several exceedingly sophisticated military and socio-political competencies as a result of the accumulation of knowledge and experience from many centuries and the recent reformation of the Gadaa System. Adequate mobilization of the public through the Gadaa

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System and government, age-set-based organization of warriors, and clear strategic goals were the central elements of the Offensive–Defensive campaigns of the Oromo.

In their offensive defense for reclaiming their ancestral territories, the Oromo highly relied on their effective organization of age–segmented social structure and generation-based socio-political system in the framework of the national structure of their republican democratic system, the Gadaa System. During each Gadaa cycle of eight years, they organized offensive-defensive campaigns where both the apprentice warriors (Kuusaa) and the warriors (Raaba) took part in a universal drill for the Gadaa-based offensive defense. As a result, there were no shortages of infantry and cavalry fighters. All the Kuusaa and the Raaba were battle-ready. Individual Oromo clans were said to be able to raise an army of 20,000–30,000 equestrians (“Gallas,” 1911).

The Oromo began their duula galaa with evolving but clear goals and strategies. The goals and the strategies of the protracted military campaign continued to evolve and were articulated throughout the offensive defense of the Oromo. The goals of the campaigns were to reclaim lost part of the ancestral Father Land, to maintain their liberty, security, and peace, to restore their kaawoo (entirely dignified, peaceful, and purposeful life and living of the Oromo), and to achieve the height of finna (democratic and egalitarian socio-economic development). The strategies were bolstering the intrepidity of the Oromo warriors, an innovation of the gaaduu military strategy, designing and effectively executing the galaa (provision) system, and formation of alliances and confederacies, and the effective use of Gadaa System were among the critical factors for the success of the campaign. These goals and strategies, which shall be discussed later, were the key to the success of the offensive-defensive campaigns of the Oromo in the 16th century.

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Being cognizant of (1) the fact that the Oromo had developed effective military and socio-political competencies, (2) that they had been passively and intermittently defending the expansion of the Aksumite and Abyssinian kingdom starting from the time the latter ever started to expand from its city-state centered at Aksum and (3) that the 16th-century pan-Oromo offensive-defensive campaigns of reclaiming their Father Land based on the eight years cycle of the Gadaa System of Oromo government started during Gadaa Malbaa (1522-1530), the cyclic (Gadaa-based) protracted campaigns of the Oromo against the Christian Abyssinian kingdom and their successes shall be discussed in the following section.

The discussion shall be based primarily on the historical records in the works of Abba Bahrey and Atsme Giorgis, 16th-century, and 20th-century Abyssinian self-styled historians, respectively. The works of the former, translated into Amharic by Getachew Haile (2002), and that of the latter, as extensively edited and translated into English by Bairu Tafla (1987), have been consulted extensively. Later analyses by historians and anthropologists have also been consulted. Works by Dirribi D. Bokku, Dereje Hineu, George W. B. Huntingford, Richard Pankhurst, and many others have been referred. Besides, Oromo oral traditions, as studied by scholars, have been incorporated. Based on these sources and the analysis thereof by the researcher, the offensive-defensive wars of the Oromo in the 16th and early 17th centuries shall be presented in considerable detail than has been attempted before.

Duula Galaa: Liberation and Resettlement

The early 16th century began the formidable liberation struggle of the Oromo in modern south-central Ethiopia. Some northern Oromo communities had resisted the expansion of the Christian and Muslim powers before the turn of the 16th century, while others had joined either side. However, their defenses were poorly organized and had a negligible effect. Even though most of the Abyssinian records indicate that the Gadaa-based

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offensive-defensive military campaigns of the Oromo started after the invasion of Ahmed Gragn, it might have begun during the Gadaa of the fathers of Gadaa Jibbenaa (1450-1458). This is because, first, Abba Bahrey has recorded that this Gadaa existed; second, the Gadaa System was reformed during this Gadaa; and third, it is highly probable that the rhythmic Gadaa-based defense of the Oromo that Bahrey recorded has had a long history, going back at least to the reformation, where the latter Gadaas continued the tradition. Nonetheless, it indeed started before the breakout of the religious war between Adal and Abyssinia (Jalata, 2012, p. 132; Hassen, 1990, p. 18) or “immediately before or just at the time of the first incursions of Imam Ahmed ibn Ibrahim” (Pankhurst, 1997, p. 281).

The south-central Oromo, who elicited the Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaign of the Oromo, had clear goals of reclaiming their ancestral Father Land, defending and maintaining their nagaa (holistic peace), and birmaduu (liberty/sovereignty), restoring their bilisummaa (freedom) and kaawoo (“Oromo Dream”), and to achieve the height of finnaa (development). Each of the goals had elaborate specific strategies and tactics. Starting their Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaign from present central Ethiopia in the 1520s, a century later, in the 1620s, the Oromo reclaimed more significant parts of the current territories of Ethiopia. They had attacked everywhere in Abyssinia Proper except Tigre. That included all the present Amhara State. Also, they had reclaimed some regions from the kingdom of Adal, save the walled city of Harar and most of the kingdom of Awsa, which has become chiefly Afar State. With their success over the kingdoms of Adal and Awsa, they also reclaimed territories from the Somali people. They had reclaimed territories from the Hadiya and Sidama peoples in central Ethiopia. Moreover, they had begun expanding into the region that has now become western Oromia. They achieved this monumental success during the successive Gadaas of the fathers (Malbaa, Muudanaa, Kiilolee, Biifolee, and Michillee) and

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the Gadaas of the sons (Harmuufaa, Roobalee, Birmajii, Mul'ataa, and Duuloo) during 1522-1562 and 1562-1602, respectively.

The transition from the Gadaas of the “fathers” to the Gadaas of “sons” in the 1560s witnessed:

- (a) Restoration of ancient Gadaa centers in central Ethiopia
- (b) Reunion of the northeastern and south-central Oromo
- (c) The beginning of the integration of other peoples with Oromo
- (d) The beginning of the formation of Oromo Confederacies.

Around the transition time between the Gadaas of the fathers and the Gadaas of the sons, the Oromo were able to re-establish their ancient Gadaa centers (religion-political centers) in the reclaimed territories in the present central Oromia (Central Ethiopia). The most notable of these restored odaa, Gadaa centers, was Odaa Nabee near Addis Ababa/Finfinnee, the capital city of Oromia State and the federal government of Ethiopia. In addition, the south-central Booranaa and the northeast Baarentuu Oromo were reunited in central Oromia during this time. Jointly, they formed a formidable force against the kingdom of Abyssinia and soon overrun the retreating kingdom. In addition to this reunion, the Oromo also began the ethnographical transformation of exceedingly minority peoples in central Ethiopia to Oromo through the institution of moggaasaa. The defeated or submitted peoples, gabbaroo, shared the Oromo identity gradually and began becoming part of the Oromo polity. This time was also the beginning of decentralizing one Gadaa government into regional and local (Clan) Gadaa governments. The rapid geographical expansion of the Oromo encouraged decentralization, but the formation of Oromo confederacies made the decentralization possible. Oromo confederacies were decentralized Gadaa government of the Oromo where

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the central government ceded most of its powers to the regional governments but maintained some control over them through the mechanism of the Gadaa Constitution.

After ten Gadaa cycles, however, some of the northern Oromo groups had joined the kingdom of Abyssinia under the leadership of Atse Susenyos (r. 1607–1632), who was an adopted Oromo and perceived by some Oromo communities as their Gadaa leader. This might have divided and weakened the Oromo and resulted in the loss of momentum of the Gadaa-based campaigns of the Oromo. Throughout the 17th century, unfriendly Oromo communities continued their resistance against the kingdom of Abyssinia. They would score sporadic victories against Abyssinian Atses. These Oromo communities would help maintain the territories that the Oromo of the 16th century had reclaimed from the kingdom of Abyssinia. On the other hand, starting from the beginning of the 17th century, some Oromo communities, mainly the northern Yajjuu, Walloo, Raayyaa, and Asaboo, and some groups of the central and south-western Tuulamaa and Maccaa Oromo started to ally themselves and integrate with the Abyssinian kingdom. Through their political and cultural integration, as discussed later, these northern Oromo communities would ultimately become the masters of the Abyssinian kingdom. They would rule it both directly and indirectly for almost a century. This, however, would cost the rest of the Oromo dearly: first, more and more Oromo would continue to assimilate to Abyssinian identity; second, the unity of the Oromo would continue to be elusive until in the late 19th century, when the Abyssinians would use this opportunity to subjugate the Oromo.

The Oromo of the successive Gadaa Malbaa, Muudanaa, Kiilolee, Biifolee, Michillee Harmuufaa, Roobalee, Birmajii, Mul'ataa, and Duuloo achieved monumental successes in the 16th century. Those two generations rebuilt the greater Biyya Oromoo, which is more significant than the present Oromia. They defeated mighty Christian and Muslim armies in

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battle after battle for over eight decades and gradually but surely restored both the dignity of the Oromo and their ancestral territories. With their traditional but democratic and egalitarian organization and their traditional but voluntary and self-motivated warriors, they defeated massive, highly organized medieval armies of the kingdom of Abyssinia. They obliterated the Sultanate of Adal (the kingdom of Adal and Awsa). The history of their enemy has preserved their determination, heroism, and impressive successes.

The present generations of Oromo, who are sloppily beholding the poaching of Oromia from almost all sides, are highly indebted to their ancestors. Their forefathers fought the expanding adversary powers heroically, defeated the enemy multiple times for several decades, reclaimed the vast territory from the opponent, and passed it on to the next generation with restored Kaawoo. Kaawoo represents “freedom, peace, prosperity, success, and happiness” (Jalata, 2005, p. 32) or simply, “prosperity and peace” (Jalata & Schaffer, 2013, p. 294)) of the Oromo nation. If the present generation should learn an important lesson from the 16th-century generation, it must be by asking one question: ‘Why was the Oromo of the 16th century so successful?’ The next chapter will try to answer this question.

Successes of the Offensive–Defensive Campaigns

Restoration of Gadaa Centres and Reunion of the Oromo

The Gadaa centers are known as Odaa. Odaa is a consecrated living monument for Gadaa legislation. The Odaa are selected open-air convention venues for the meetings of the national, regional, and local Gadaa assemblies. Traditionally, the Oromo pay “divine honor” to odaa and coffee (Bruce, 1790c, p. 68). Their affection with Odaa is so much so that, in the late 18th century, James Bruce (1790c), though he called it Wanzey, further explains:

Under this tree, their king [Abbaa Gadaa] is chosen; under this tree, he holds his first council [Gadaa Assembly], in which he [the assembly] marks his enemies

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[declares war or peace], and the time and manner in which his own soldiers [Oromo warriors] are to make their irruption into their country. His scepter is a bludgeon made of this tree, which, like a mace, is carried before him wherever he goes; it is produced in the general meetings of the nation and is called Buco [Bokkuu]. (p. 68)

A graceful giant tree with ample shades in flat grassland, in a meadow, on a flat top of a hill, or by a hillside designates Gadaa centers for identification. Such trees are usually giant Sycamore trees (odaa) visible from a great distance to locate. Odaa is evergreen. It grows exceedingly long and drawn-out branches that provide considerable shade. It has deep roots and is very stable. Because of its perennial nature, it maintains its dense, glossy leaves at all seasons.

Odaa is regarded highly among the Oromo for its symbolism. As an evergreen, giant, stable, majestic, and ever-expanding tree, it has symbolic meanings to the Oromo. For their hope to maintain their peace, unity (social, political, spiritual, and psychological), culture, and Gadaa as one entity that perpetuates intact into the future through the changes of seasons, the Oromo see odaa as a symbol. As odaa maintains itself through seasons while growing and expanding, the Oromo aspire to preserve their identity, unity, peace, and Gadaa System while developing and expanding.

Because of this symbolism of the odaa, the Oromo historically had their socio-political centers located by a prominent odaa and used its shades as an assembly place whenever necessary. Such odaa have been protected by Gadaa laws. The Oromo, in general, do not cut down any odaa tree; they revere any giant tree, for that matter. In the absence of odaa, such giant trees may well serve as the markers of the socio-political or religio-ritual centers of the Oromo.

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The Oromo had practiced Gadaa at different centers for centuries before re-establishing the old centers after the mid-16th century. These ancient Gadaa centers (politico-religious centers) include Walaabuu, Nabee, Xuqqur/Jibaat, Kaatat/Qaatat, Galana, and Xuxxe Bisil (see Table 4 for details). The Oromo had been forced to move their politico-religious centers many times within the borders of modern Ethiopia. They had moved from Kaatat/Qaatat to Dawwaro (Dawwaaroo), from Xuqqur Midir to Dawwaaroo, before it was finally returned from Dawaro to Odaa Nabee (and since then remained there for many years) in the 14th century due to the repeated military campaign of Abyssinian Atses, Amde Tsion and Seife-Ared (Gidada 2015, p. 63). Some Oromo oral traditions mention Wawat in ancient Upper Egypt, modern north Sudan, as the first politico-religious center of the Oromo nation around 900 BCE. The politico-religious center of the Oromo in 1230 CE was at Odaa Nabee, at Yerer, east of Addis Ababa (Finfinnee), according to mainstream Oromo oral traditions (Gidada 2015, p. 40).

The Oromo of Gadaa Michillee not only started to re-settle the part of their Father Land that they had freed from the Christian Abyssinian kingdom and the Islamic Sultanate of Adal and older principalities but also re-established the Oromo socio-political center at Odaa Nabee as part of the restoration of the ancient Oromo such centers. Odaa Nabee is located in east Shewa north of Chuqqaalaa (now known as Ziquala as Amharaized name) mountain at the foot of Yerer Mountain, only a few miles east of Addis Ababa (Finfinnee). The history of Odaa Nabee is dated “as far back as 204 AD” (Hinew, 2012, p. 86). The Gadaa System was functioning in the 3rd century CE at Odaa Nabee (Alemayehu et al., 2004, cited in Sirna, 2012, p. 50). Other centers like Qaatat, Dawwaaroo, Odaa Roobaa, and other centers located in central Shewa were also ancient politico-religious centers of the Oromo (Hinew, 2012, p. 86). This was before the Abyssinians and other peoples arrived at the territory. After

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reclaiming most of the present central Oromia, the Oromo restored one of their ancient socio-political centers —Odaa Nabee—during Gadaa Michillee (1554–1562).

Odaa Nabee holds another significant event in the history of the Oromo: the reunion of northeastern Baarentuu Oromo with the southwestern Booranaa Oromo. Abba Bahrey's account informs that the Booranaa, not the Baarentuu, began their expedition from the south, and some Booranaa stayed behind. Those who stayed behind were more likely the Boorana of the present southern Oromia (southern Booranaa). Regarding the Baarentuu Oromo, Bahrey has not recorded their origin and whether all or only a part of them went on the expedition, nor is it possible to find any other record. The most likely explanation would be that the Baarentuu were already in the immediate south of the Christian Abyssinian heartland and east of the main center of the Muslim kingdom of Adal in the territories that were occupied by both powers in the present north, east, and central Oromia. After they were freed from occupation by the offensive-defensive force that began in southern Oromo, it would be an entitlement for them to be reunited and to join forces to liberate more Oromo and the Oromo ancestral territories. Hence, the reconnection (addition) of Gadaas of the Baarentuu as a parallel institution to that of the Booranaa under the same Gadaa names chronicled by Abba Bahrey. This was probably what “mended” the so-called cinnaa Gadaa, dismemberment of the Gadaa from the late first millennium to the early second millennium (Alemayehu et. al., 2004, cited in Sirna, 2012).

After its restoration, Odaa Nabee served as the place of the political and socio-cultural reunion of the two Oromo moieties. The Oromo, who had remained behind centuries ago and had integrated into the new communities of the small Islamic sultanates that emerged and expanded in the region over the last several centuries, had become Muslims. Besides, the Islamic teachers from Harar had converted the Walloo Oromo en mass to Islam in the 1530s

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after Ahmad Gragn had defeated the Christian Abyssinian kingdom (Gidada, 2016, p. 54).

Under Ahmad Gragn's rule (1529–1543), the conversion had not been an exception for the Oromo. In fact, from among the inhabitants of the Christian kingdom, “nine men in ten” were converted to Islam (Jones & Monroe, 1935, p. 83). These included the northern Oromo because most of the Oromo (“Ilm-Ormas”) who inhabited southern Abyssinia—the present Shewa Zones and possibly South Wollo and East Gojjam Zones—at the time were converted to Abyssinian Christianity before the invasion of Ahmad Gragn (Reclus, 1892, p. 197).

Farther north, in the Abyssinian kingdom, the Ashangee, Raayyaa, and Asaboo Oromo, the three generations of Hubannaa who had already accepted Christianity and had integrated with the Tigrie and Afar, must have accepted Islam during the rule of Ahmad Gragn, at least “nine men in ten” of them. These Oromo communities had lived in the region long before accepting Christianity (Aleka Taye, 1948 Eth. C., cited in Gidada, 2016, p. 54), and they must have adopted the Amharic language. These newly Islamized Oromo were reunited with the Waaqeffataa Oromo at Odaa Nabee without renouncing their Muslim faith. Similarly, those Oromo who probably had maintained their Christian faith during the reign of Ahmad Gragn might have also been united without renouncing their Christian faith. Two noticeable Islamized Oromo clans who were reunited with the Booranaa at Odaa Nabee were the Jiddaan Ali group and the Ennango clans (Gidada, 2016, p. 31). Similar reunions between the southern and northern Oromo in central Ethiopia might have occurred at Odaa Nabee or other re-established ancient Oromo politico-religious centers (Table 3) in the reclaimed northern territories. Similar reunions must have happened between the Booranaa, the northern Raayyaa, and Asaboo Baarettumma Oromo farther north at Odaa Makoodii in Wollo and Odaa Ashangee in southern Tigray.

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Table 3: The Oromo Politico-religious Centers before the 16th Century

Name of the politico-religious center (In Afaan Oromoo)	Location of the center	Source		
		Oral traditions	Old Abyssinian records	Recent Studies (Hinew, Sirna, Alemayehu et al.)
Walaabuu	Unknown/ not mentioned	1110		
Odaa Nabee	Southeast Shewa, at the foot of Yerer Mountain	1230	1344–1370	204
Xuqqur /Jibaat	West Shewa	1360		
Xuxxee Bisil/ Gibee	West Shewa	1480		
Haroo Makkoo /Tulluo Joorgoo or Western Ulmaya	West Wallagga	1610		
Xuqqur / Booranaa	Unknown for certainty		1314	
Kaatata [Qaatat/Qatat/Katata]	Near Debre Berhan, Central Shewa		1314–1344	Before the 13th century
Galaana	Northeast Shewa in Dewaro		1314–1344	
Odaa Bultum	West Harargie			13th century
Odaa Roobaa	Bale Zone			14th century
Madda Walaabuu	Southern Bale, Madda Walaabuu			1378–1500s

Note. Adapted from Gidada (2016, pp. 40; 42), additional information from Hinew (2012), Alemayehu et al. (2004), and Sirna (2012).

Such reunion of the Islamized or Christianized Baarentuu Oromo with the Waaqeffataa Booranaa Oromo explains the sudden re-absorption of the Oromo who had fallen under the influence of the cultures and religions of the Islamic principalities and the Christian kingdom throughout the remainder of Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaigns.

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This, in turn, might have helped the Oromo to reassert their identity easily and quickly and reclaim an incredibly significant part of their long-lost territories by reversing the long course of history in just a few decades. The Oromo, who had begun their offensive-defensive campaign from Madda Walaabuu in the south alone, could not have traversed most of the expanses of the territory that had been taken from them over many centuries in few decades, nor could they independently have moved to almost all territories of the then Abyssinian kingdom from across the Awash River and resettle there. It appears that the fact of this phenomenon was instead that the northern Oromo who had already been living in these territories under the occupation of the kingdom of Abyssinia or Muslim principalities immediately joined the Gadaa-based offensive-defensive struggle when the opportunity to do so came around because of the initiative taken by their determined southern relatives.

This was perhaps why, according to some Abyssinian and their copyist Western disheartened writers, suddenly, the Oromo became an inundating “human flood,” even a “national disaster” to the Abyssinians (Hultin, 1996, quoted in Gusarova, 2009, p. 1324). Otherwise, contrary to the speculation by less informed anthropologists, there is no evidence of the Oromo population explosion in those three decades. According to the eyewitness account of Abba Bahrey, the Abyssinians were more numerous than the Oromo in the 16th century (Haile, 2002). Also, it is a well-known fact that the Gadaa System has an inbuilt population control mechanism: it allows marriage only after the age of thirty-two or after reaching the Raaba stage, and having a child is allowed only after the age of forty or after reaching the Luba stage (Legesse, 1973; 2006; Bassi, 2005). Among Booranaa Oromo of southern Ethiopia and northern Kenya, for example, the age of forty is fatherhood age, after which an Oromo man may beget a child, and its initiation rite is known as Dannisa (Daannisa) (Legesse, 2006, Fig.3.2a and Fig.3.2b, p. 122-123). If children were born to an

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Oromo man before he had reached the age of the Luba stage, and before he had celebrated his initiation to the stage with circumcision in the 16th century, Bahrey has recorded, the children were abandoned (Haile, 2002). Traditionally, any child born to Kuusa (usually 24-32 years of age) and any daughter born to Raaba (usually 32-40 years of age) were abandoned (Bassi, 2005, pp. 60, 63, 67). Also, the Oromo men typically do not beget children after they have reached the age of 48 or have passed the Gadaa (Luba) stage. Such restrictions would not have allowed any significant population to increase, let alone allowing the so-called population explosion. If the Oromo became an inundating “flood” to Abyssinians in the mid-16th century, it could have been because of the sudden reunion of the Oromo against them. The dishonorable claim that the Oromo engulfed newcomers to present central Ethiopia due to the sudden population increase must be revisited.

This reunion of the northern (north-eastern) Baarentuu and the southern (south-western) Booranaa Oromo in present central Ethiopia and the subsequent rapid absorption of the north of Oromo into the offensive-defensive campaign that the south-central Oromo had initiated have been presented uncharacteristically in the Abyssinian historiography.

Abyssinian historiography has no place for the Oromo, who had been estranged by the expansion and dominance of the Muslims and the Christians in their ancestral territories. The Abyssinian monks and chronicler dabtaras, somewhat uncharacteristically, presented the reunion of the Oromo and their momentous rapid advances from the combined forces into the heartland of the Abyssinian kingdom as an “invasion” of the Oromo arriving from the south. Western explorers and travelers who came to Abyssinia after the 16th century echoed the same notion. They served as the mouthpieces for the Abyssinian elites who held the purposely flawed view. Gradually, the misguided and deliberately obscured view that accepts

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the indigenous Oromo as newcomers would become part of the ‘historical fact’ in the circles of Abyssinian-Ethiopianist historians.

Regarding strategic goals, the Oromo did not limit themselves to reclaiming territories and being reunited. The restoration of ancient Oromo socio-political centers likely was one of the goals of the Oromo offensive-defensive struggle. The existence of such a goal is manifested in the subsequent restoration of more Gadaa centers. After the restoration of the politico-religious center at the ancient Odaa Nabee, more major Gadaa centers were later established or restored at Odaa Bisil (West Shewa), Odaa Bultum (West Harargie), Odaa Makoodii (northern Wollo and southern Tigray), Odaa Bulluq (Horroo Guduruu), and Odaa Roobaa (Baale). From these efforts, it is reasonable to suggest that the goals of the *duula galaa* also included the restoration of the Gadaa System and its centers in the regions where it had been weakened or abandoned.

This restoration of the ancient centers is, however, considered by some mistakenly as the succession to Odaa/Madda Walaabuu (Baissa, 2004, p. 106). This is perhaps because Bahrey and others who wrote the history of the Oromo and its Gadaa System wrongly considered Madda Walaabuu to be the initial politico-religious center of the Oromo. About ten Odaas existed before Madda Walaabuu; only some of them were restored. The restoration of ancient Oromo Odaas was not a succession to Odaa Walaabuu, which is dated much later. Still, a restoration—about three centuries passed between Walaabuu and Madda Walaabuu.

Presently, there are five widely recognized and active Gadaa Centers (Odaas) in Oromia. Odaa Bultum in West Harargie Zone of Eastern Oromia, Odaa Bisil in West Shewa Zone and Odaa Bulluq in Horroo Guduruu Zone of Western Oromia, Odaa Roobaa in Bale Zone of Southern Oromia, and Odaa Nabee in East Shewa Zone of Central Oromia. They have been serving as the regional Gadaa Centers. They are essential and highly functional

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local and regional socio-political centers of the Gadaa System. Recently, a symbolic small assembly hall with an architectural element shaped like the Odaa tree was constructed at Odaa Bultum.

Table 4: Some Decentralized Gadaa Governments before the late 19th century

Name of Odaa/Caffee	Location	Sub-moiety/Gosa Republic
Gooro Sirbaa	Tikur Incinnii	Liiban and Ammayya
Bokkuu Citaa	Southwest of Ambo	Kuttaayee
Mi'aa Irreessa	?	Calliyaa
Bulluq	North of Odaa Bisil	Horroo
Qobboo	North of Odaa Bisil	
Hullee	Jimma Kaka	Hullee
Barakaat	Naqamtee	Leeqaa Naqamtee
Colii	West of Gimbii town	?
?	Near Dembidollo	Sayyoo
Tulluu Walal	Around Mount. Walal	Leeqaa
Mi'aa Gnaa Goro	Najjoo	Western Sibuu
Ballo	?	Bacho
Birbirsa Tiya	?	Soddo
Foqa Awas	?	Jidda
Galaan	South of Addis Ababa	Galaan
Kara Qurqura	?	Ittu
Bullullo	Harar	Oromo around Harar

Note. Compiled from Baissa (2004, pp. 108-114)

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However, Odaa Makoodii, the sixth Odaa in northern Oromia, has been inactive. It seems it has been abandoned due to the extensive assimilation of the Oromo to Tigraian and Amhara culture in the region. The Oromo in the area had been victims of aggressive Abyssinian assimilation projects for centuries. The fact that these Oromo have been cut off from Oromia and divided between Amhara and Tigray States based on their linguistic and cultural assimilation since the formation of the federation, the revival of Odaa Makoodii has become almost impossible.

Confederacies and Decentralization of Gadaa Government

The remarkable achievements of Gadaa Michillee and its predecessors posed a significant threat to the Oromo. As they quickly overstretched themselves over a vast territory, they became weak. To maintain the liberated territory and continually defend it, communities of the south-central Oromo had to move to the retaken territories. The Oromo who had been living there under the Christian and Islamic occupation had already been assimilated and sparsely distributed. They likely needed socio-political and military reinforcement from the south-central Oromo. This, in general, would cause the dispersion of the Oromo over a large territory and would gradually weaken their offensive-defensive strength and socio-political and religious-cultural cohesion, ultimately affecting the effectiveness of their Gadaa System.

In response to this rapid expansion of the Oromo, the hayyuu of the Oromo devised a sturdy solution. The solution was to confederate the Oromo into two Booranaa and Baarentuu and decentralize the Gadaa government into two Hambisaa and Harmuufaa, respectively. The

This type of decentralization of the pan-Oromo Gadaa government into two dual and complementary parts (moieties) was not a one-time-only experiment. Historically, as they expanded in territory and grew in population size, the Oromo would continue to decentralize

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their Gadaa government by forming dual moiety structures. Through time, they would create scores of sub-moieties and confederacies. Each newly formed sub-moiety or confederacy established its own subordinate Gadaa government, Gadaa center (Odaa), and Caffee (Gadaa assembly and Council) based on the universal pan-Oromo Gadaa constitution, which has remained the core uniting factor of the Oromo. The northern Oromo formed several junior confederacies under the two-broad umbrella (i.e., Booranaa and Baarentuu) confederacies. Such confederacies also existed farther south in present-day southern Kenya. Here, the southern Oromo formed the “Bararetta” and the “Kokawe” confederacies on the south and northern banks of the Tana River, respectively (Reclus, 1890, p. 369). Similar Oromo confederacies might have been formed in the Great Lakes Regions before the Bantu peoples would dominate the region. Various such confederacies must have existed in ancient times in the present regions of northwest Ethiopia, southeast Sudan, and southwest Somalia. However, all Oromo confederacies adhered to the central pan-Oromo Gadaa constitution and remained under the loose central Gadaa government that allowed the confederacies maximum liberty of self-administration as a fully decentralized republican government.

Despite the extensive social and political decentralization, the dual moiety structures of the decentralized Gadaa government of the Oromo served as an effective socio-political organization of the Oromo nation. It helped the northern Oromo to maintain unity and the integrity of the Gadaa System. By upholding the Gadaa constitution (Heera Gadaa), natural laws (Seera Uumaa), and safuu, and by maintaining the central pan-Oromo Gadaa government, the north-eastern (mostly Baarentuu) and the south-central (mostly Booranaa) Oromo of the 16th century they remained united at the primary pan-Oromo level during the Gadaa of the sons while maintaining almost an independent self-rule in their respective extended territories.

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Moggaasaa and the Transformation from Captivity to Full Integration

It is understandable that as they continued to expand, the Oromo overwhelmed many small non-Oromo minority communities that they encountered on their way. These communities could not have equal rights as the Oromo as they were not a member of the Gadaa System. They had to pass through a lengthy social integration process to attain full membership in the Gadaa parties. During the transition period, they had to remain subject to the Gadaa government, which did not fully represent them. Thus, politically speaking, they were subjects (gabbaree).

It is highly likely that Abba Bahrey's Amharic common name, "Geber" or "Gebbar," was derived from the Afaan Oromoo term "gabbaree," which means 'those who surrendered or defeated or subjects.' In the territories the Abyssinians formerly occupied, the farmers were known by the trade name አራሽ (farmer). This name is more honoring and still in use. The Oromo made more of them gabbaree (meaning captive, those who submitted, or subject). The new name for farmers, Gabare/ገበሬ, may have been adopted by the Abyssinians from gabbaree.

Despite the popularization and official use of the name as an occupational trade name for farmers in its Amharic form (ገበሬ) by successive governments, the negative connotation of the name has remained. Despite widespread and official use, the Amharic common name still carries a negative connotation in the Amharic language. In addition to the trade of living off tilling land, it implies less civility, culture, and even lack of independence. In the Oromo language, the historical meaning is clear: It means, among others, 'subject.' The Oromo have continued to avoid using the name to apply to them because of its original meaning.

The gabbaree of the 16th century were probably the gabbaree of Maccaa of today, and they probably lived in similar arrangements. Among the Maccaa Oromo of today, gabbaree is

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someone, a man, who earns a living by working full time for others voluntarily. The work may be looking after a herd of cattle, working on a farm, working in the home, or doing certain combinations of these. Gabbaree earns meager payments in cash or kind. Gabbaree usually lives as a dependent in the household where he serves. The family of gabbaree may also live with him. The head of the household in the Gadaa System represented the Gabbaree because they were considered part of the family. Today, Gabbaree (Gabbaro) are free men but economically dependent.

According to Abba Bahrey, the Oromo introduced the name “Geber” or “Gebbar”—a socio-political distinction—during Gadaa Biifolee. It was a common name given to war captives. The Oromo, however, might have used the distinction in different contexts and connotations starting many centuries before Gadaa Biifolee (1546–1554).

Most of the gabbaree before Gadaa Biifolee were the artisans (blacksmiths, weavers, tanners, potters, carpenters, etc.) who lived among the predominantly pastoral Oromo. The artisans had limited political and economic rights: They did not have full liberty, as they were not members of the Gadaa parties. They were considered to be a lower caste than the sovereign Oromo. However, they were not enslaved but clients (Cerulli, 1922). They were persons among the Oromo community who employed themselves in the trades that the Oromo did not condescend to accept them as their trade. They lived off their artisan services to the mostly pastoralist Oromo, petty trade, and paltry agriculture. During Gadaa Biifolee, their number increased as the Oromo took more captives from the battles. As the Oromo moved into farming territories and settled there, the new captives were likely petty farmers by then and afterward.

There is also the question of the accuracy of the name Gabbaro. From the works of Hassen (1990), it is clear that this name was modified slightly by Abyssinian Abba Bahrey or

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by those who have translated his original work from Ge'ez to English or Amharic. The Oromo called captives gabbaro (Hassen, 1990, p. 63). Gabbaro in Afaan Oromoo is the same as gabbaree. The former is a plural form of the latter. In the context of Abba Bahrey's 16th-century account, Gebar meant enslaved (Haile, 2002). If the Oromo had meant slave or enslaved by Gabra/ Gebar or gabbaro, they could have used the proper Oromo expression.

Oromo oral tradition attests that the designation of the non-Oromo or the war captives as gabbaro was customary among the Maccaa Oromo, particularly after the beginning of the mid-16th century, and it does not necessarily mean that slavery existed among Oromo. It simply means those who have submitted. However, in his explanation of the name "gabbaroo," Gidada (2016) mistakenly used the more recent context of slavery among the Leeqaa Oromo. By the late 19th century, the Oromo Mootiis would develop the habit of slaving the Dinka and the Gambili peoples who took refuge in their territories after their attacks by the Arab Egyptian contemporaries in the neighboring region of Sobat (Reclus, 1892, p. 117). During the same period, the eastern Oromo would only allow slave traders free passage; they kept no slaves themselves (Reclus, 1890, p. 403).

The western Oromo would liberate and integrate some of the Dinka and Gambil peoples and would keep some others as enslaved people. "From among those known by the name "Gabbaro," most of them were offspring born to Oromo heads of households and liberated male slaves from female slaves." Gidada, 2016, p. 199). In addition, in his translation of Martial de Salviac's work, Ayalew Kenno reflects the assertion by the former in 1901 that the Oromo neither killed their captives nor enslaved them but freed even the slave captives and integrated them into their families (D'Abbadie, 2007, p. 145). In general, until the late 19th century, when Abyssinians introduced slavery in the Oromo country, the Oromo had no participation in slavery or the slave trade (Melbaa, 1988, p. 65).

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By the early 17th century, the number of gabbaree (or Gabbaro) had increased tremendously among the Maccaa Oromo, so much so that they not only demanded equal political rights as the Maccaa Oromo but were granted probably the demand. Historian Mohammed Hassen explains: The “gabbaro” demanded “the political right to form their own assembly,” Caffee, parallel to the Maccaa assembly in Western Oromia in the early 17th century (Hassen, 1990, p. 65). The Maccaa Oromo probably granted the demand when some of the gabbaro rebelled and threatened to join the Abyssinian Christian kingdom in Gojjam during the early years of the reign of Atse Susenyos (r. 1607–1632). The subsequent formation of the two Caffees in Maccaa land suggests that the demand was granted and the gabbaro had formed a dual moiety, as they were “already part of the complex Gadaa System“ (Hassen, 1990, p. 69). Legesse (2006) suggests that “Gabbro” is the name of the junior moiety (p. 176), complementary to the dual Maccaa–Gabbaroo moiety.

Following the contexts given by Abba Bahrey and adding the relatively recent context of slavery in the 19th century, some Abyssinian writers have continued to misrepresent “Gabra” or “Gebar” as “slave,” implying that the Oromo, as a society, enslaved their captives. This representation is misguided, and the implication is unfounded. The very term “Gabbaro,” as explained above, does not mean a slave or a servant in the Oromo language. In Bahrey’s portrayal, it means subjects: it does not necessarily mean slaves. It simply indicates the compliance of the gabbaree/gabbaro to the supremacy of the Oromo. Implying the Oromo as a historically slave-owning society is also far-fetched.

Under the Gadaa System, in principle, no one could be born into slavery or could be enslaved. The very participation of a man in the Gadaa System is a testimony of the sovereignty of the man and his family. The Oromo have historically practiced the Gadaa System, save a few exceptions in some parts since the 19th century. According to the Gadaa

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System, all born to an Oromo are born sovereign. Once an Oromo has become enslaved, he loses his sovereignty forever. By the mid-19th century, Speke (1863/2013, *History of the Wahuma*) notes that the Wahuma women “were put to death by their husbands, because, by becoming slaves, they had broken the laws of their race.” . The Wahuma are characteristically Oromo (Du Bois, 1915). Similarly, Reclus (1892, pp. 117, 197, 224) explains, by the late 19th century, able Oromo men in the East Africa region would choose their death to be captured as slaves . The sovereign Oromo loathe slavery so much so that they prefer death.

Furthermore, according to the Gadaa System, a household is a sovereign entity. It is the basic unit of authority where the head of the family represents every Oromo household in the Gadaa System (Gidada, 2016, p. 193). Yet, every member of an Oromo household is free in principle. The head of the family is a sovereign “political representative of his family” (Gidada, 2016, p. 193). He wears a head turban (ruufoo) made of the three colors of the Oromo (black, red, and white), holds a decorated whip (alangaa) in his hand (most of the times), and wears kallachaa on his forehead occasionally (Gidada, 2016, p. 193). The symbolism of ruufoo (turban), alangaa (whip), and kallachaa (a phallus-shaped ornament), in this context, are sovereignty, lawmaking, and Gadaa leadership, respectively. So long as born an Oromo, no one could be reproduced in any form of bondage. Every Oromo and every Oromo household is sovereign. This sovereignty is manifested with standard visual symbols of the Gadaa System.

In the Gadaa System, not only those born Oromo are sovereign. Non-Oromo were also made sovereign by law. Any person born to an Oromo from a non-Oromo is born free by virtue of his father’s sovereignty. Also, fully integrated aliens are liberated and made sovereign by law.

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However, the social and legal process of full integration of alien communities took time. It involved cultural and ethnological integration through the institution of moggaasaa. This does not mean that the Oromo considered other peoples who lived among them as enslaved people until they were integrated fully into the Oromo social and political structures. From the principle of qixxee of the Gadaa System, it can be inferred that the Oromo considered them “equals” in humanity. Their fundamental principle of qixxee (equality of human beings) reflects this equality in being human. It would not allow the Oromo to make anyone an enslaved person, but subjects (Gabbaro), even if captured at a battle, before Gadaa Biifolee, as testified by Bahrey. Besides, the Oromo promoted the non-Oromo among them to political equality through the institutional processes of Oromsuu (naturalization), moggaasaa (ethnographic integration), and guddifacha (adoption).

There is no recorded practice of slavery or slave trade in the history of the Oromo when and where the Gadaa System was practiced fully. After a few Abbaa Duulaas evolved to become monarchs and formed Mootii form of government starting from the early 19th century and the total banning of the Gadaa System after the mid of 19th century, however, the fundamental principle of qixxee began to wear away fast. Afterward, not only did some Oromo communities practice slavery and take part in the slave trade, but they also became victims of the practices. Slavery is believed to have been first introduced into the Oromo country by the Muslim traders and Abyssinian settlers. Slave raids and trades remained uncommon among the Oromo until the 16th century. Though some Oromo communities started to have political subjects starting from the second half of the 16th century and some of these Oromo communities began to adopt the Abyssinian culture and way of life that encouraged slavery starting from the mid of 17th century, both slavery and slave trade never took root among the Oromo until the 19th century. The northern and the western minority

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Oromo, who had adopted monarchy as their system of government, started practicing slavery. Even then, the Oromo made slaves from among Nilotic Dinka and Gambil peoples in the Leeqaa region, as an able Oromo would starve himself to death than become a slave (Reclus, 1892, pp. 117, 197, 224). In the rest of the Oromo country, where the Gadaa System continued to function in its full strength and full implementations of its laws, slavery and slave trade by the Oromo remained nonexistent. Since the beginning of the 19th century, however, some of the chiefs and kings (Mootii) in the Oromo kingdoms and some prominent Oromo traders, in collaboration with their Arab and Abyssinian partners, took part in both the making and the trading of slaves from among non-Oromo people among themselves and in their neighborhoods.

This is, however, not to deny the fact that there were groups of people who lived among the Oromo but had limited political, social, and economic rights, at least temporarily in the history of the Oromo. As mentioned above, the artisans living among the Oromo for centuries had limited political and social rights. The gabbaree/gabbaroo, the war captives who had lived among the Oromo, had limited political freedoms. However, when it comes to the Gabbaroo in particular, it is necessary to note that the limited political rights had to do with pending membership to the Gadaa System rather than the wish of the Oromo to keep their captives as subjects. As the Oromo advanced and made more war captives, they instituted one of the most advanced institutions for the social and ethnological integration of aliens, known as moggaasaa.

Moggaasaa is an innovative Oromo institution for total social and ethnological integration. Through time, the gabbaroo achieved the same liberty and socio-political and economic equality as the Oromo. Tens of thousands of gabbaroo are believed to have been

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fully and completely integrated, socially and ethnologically, with the Oromo nation by their free choice. They became equally Oromo as those born to Oromo.

Factors Explaining Oromo Victories during 16th and 17th centuries

By the end of the 16th century, the Oromo had reclaimed most of Abyssinia Proper but Tigre in the north and most of the Sultanate of Adal but the walled city of Harar in the east after neutralising both the Christian and the Muslim powers in the region that has now become central modern Ethiopia. They achieved this monumental success in just a little more than half of a century by successively defeating the most organised and the most advanced forces of the kingdom of Abyssinia and the Sultanate of Adal.

This has left every interested person wondering how the Oromo, who had neither king nor master nor a standing army, could achieve such height of success. Abba Bahrey has attempted to make an advisory sociological analysis for his king. He primarily proposed that the Oromo were successful because, unlike the Abyssinians, where only a tenth of able men fight, all able men of the Oromo were warriors. However, the real reason for the successes of the Gadaa-based offensive-defensive military campaigns of the Oromo in the 16th century cannot be found in Abba Bahrey's analysis. Nonetheless, his analysis, though contradictory in part to his records, is essential in illustrating aspects of the fundamental reasons.

Based on the information in the record of Bahrey, other related Abyssinian records, the structure of the Oromo society, the organisation, institution, and continued practices of the Gadaa System, and Oromo oral literature, the real reasons may readily be identified.

Accordingly, the real reasons include:

- (1) Gadaa System (Oromo democracy)
- (2) Age-set institutions and cibra regiments
- (3) Guerrilla warfare (gaaduu)

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- (4) The goal to reclaim lost territories (galma)
- (5) The determination to regain their kaawoo (Oromo Dream)
- (6) Innovative military provision (galaa)
- (7) Ethnographic social integration policy (moggaasaa)
- (8) Dual and parallel social organization (moiety)
- (9) Extrapolated clan structure (gosa)
- (10) Decentralization and alliance building (confederation)
- (11) Oromo monotheistic religion (Waaqeffannaa)

Each of these complemented one another in making the Oromo victorious against their enemies militarily, socially, and politically. Thus, the dissertation concludes that the real reason for the military and socio-political successes of the Oromo in the 16th century are to be found not in Abba Bahrey's analysis nor some recent suggestions but in the combined effects of several Oromo institutions, traditions, social and military innovations, and more importantly the determination of the Oromo people.

However, interested individuals have tried to diminish the successes of the Oromo against the Abyssinian kingdom. More recent suggested reasons other than these or analyses excluding these that some Abyssinians have proposed in the form of disconsolate literary retribution have been only attempting to undermine the success of the Oromo. It is impossible to undercut or disregard the achievements of the Oromo ancestors of the 16th century, who had not only triumphed over their enemies but also restored most of the Oromo Father Land and the kaawoo of the nation.

Abyssinian Responses to Oromo Campaigns and Victories

The Oromo regained their ancestral territory through their Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaigns during the 16th century. They rescued it from the Christian Abyssinian

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kingdom and the Islamic sultanates (principalities). The Abyssinian kingdom and people had been expanding south into their territory since the time of the Aksumite kingdom. The Oromo started to reclaim territories from the Abyssinian kingdom after successive victories in decisive battles beginning in the 1520s. The consecutive victories of the Oromo lasted until the mid-17th century when the northern Oromo communities began to take center stage in the kingdom and became its masters a century later.

This walabummaa (liberation) reaction of the Oromo, mainly against the expansionist policy of the Abyssinian kingdom, and the legitimate cause of sustained struggle for more than one and a half-century to reclaim their ancestral territory has been rather uncharacteristically referred to as the “Oromo migration” by few historians and the “Oromo expansion” or the “Oromo movement” by some others. As such, it served as the propaganda machine of the Abyssinian kingdom to massacre the Oromo in their northern territories when they gained superior military power in the late 19th and early 20th centuries.

Furthermore, the Abyssinian kingdom tried to erase from its history the fact that it had occupied the land of the Oromo in its gradual expansion to the south over centuries to the land that the Oromo just regained from them, by portraying the Oromo as having just “invaded” the kingdom afresh in the 16th and 17th centuries.

In response to the humiliation of successive defeats, the Abyssinian self-praising chroniclers and some of the learned Coptic Church fairy-tale historians aggressively and hatefully purported the Oromo as invaders and savage while writing about themselves as the “source” of civilisation, righteous, defender of “Solomonic” Dynasty, and defenders of Christian faith. The purpose was clear: It was an effort to abort their migration history from across the Red Sea into the territories of the Oromo and other Cushitic peoples that constituted the ancient Kush. The Abyssinian learned church elites effectively used their

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advantage of being literate and advanced in the art of writing due to the introduction of scripture-based faith for this purpose. The Abyssinian Coptic Church and court elites, in the end, produced one of their legendary stories that portrayed the Oromo as newcomers to the region and their military successes as a punishment sent from God to the kingdom, not as the result of the brainpower and the valor of the Oromo and their socio-political and military advancements.

Such instrumental portrayal of the Oromo and others gave the Abyssinian kingdom the apparent single victory on the most crucial page of their historiographical records as a settlement to the many battles of the wars it had lost to the Oromo. A few Western historians and Ethiopia-nist writers would invariably copy such “victory” for centuries, including this 21st century. They have continued to exploit heavily the long-existing bias that written sources, however dubious, are considered more scholarly than oral traditions (Hassen, 1990, p. 3). Likewise, Abyssinian Church elites and historians still accept, without a second thought, that the recorded hagiography of Abyssinian kings in their respective chronicles are written in a flowery and flattering custom of the Abyssinian Church as historical fact. Worse, being misled themselves, they have continued to deceive others. There are those who do so with apparent but deceitful purposes.

In the immediate aftermath of the victories of the Oromo, the Abyssinian elites devised another form of propaganda that would have an instrumental implication on the psych of the Oromo who had become an integral part of the contingent communities and those who had infiltrated deep into the heartland of the remainder of the kingdom. This was the propaganda of literacy in Amharic and the use of Geez as a literary language. Though only Coptic Church elites and later the students of the Jesuit Catholic fathers were literate, the Abyssinians presented themselves as a literate society, heavily emphasizing that the

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Oromo were a non-literate oral society. All illiterate masses pretended to be an advanced society by fiat of being Christian because the people in the service of the church and the service of the court were literate. The presence of the European Catholics who abhorred the Waaqeffannaa religion of the Oromo gave a supporting hand to the literacy and “literary civilization” propaganda of the Abyssinian Church and court elites. This was even though the Oromo, after taking Abyssinian state power, “became more learned in Amarenga [Amharic language] than the Amara” and “the pure Amara constitute [sic] not even one-fifth” the Abyssinian population (Tafla, 1987, p. 441). This propaganda would have instrumental implications for the Oromo who had settled among the Abyssinians.

To achieve these instrumental implications, through its institutionalization in the Abyssinian culture, Abyssinian elites associated the level of civilization and the genius of the faculty of the Oromo who live among them with the level of their comprehension of Amharic and Ge’ez languages and Abyssinia culture. How well they follow the Amhara accent of Amharic language (the Christian Semitic language), how well they understood literary language—Geez, how well versed they are in the Christian faith, and how well they practised in the Christian culture (abandoning their own culture), were the measures of “civilization” and assimilation of these Oromo communities, in other words, total homogenization.

These criteria had been Abyssinian “standards” for portraying the Oromo and other peoples who lived among them for years. If they fell out of the self-centered “standard” in any measure, they were automatically considered culturally less sophisticated. The Oromo, no doubt, could not do well on these “standards,” even to the present day, because they never entirely abandoned their culture, language, and traditions like a total sell-off to adopt the Abyssinian language, culture and religion, nor did other nations, nationalities, and peoples with few exceptions. As a result, some Oromo communities who were highly affected by

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such influence over a long time became innocent victims of the psychological warfare that prepared them for assimilation and adopting some elements of Abyssinian identity.

The Amhara Abyssinians gradually designed an effective and sustained assimilation mechanism for some Oromo groups and individuals. The advantage of their political domination was transformed quickly into economic and cultural domination because of the adoption of a multi-level and multi-layer strategy of hegemony. The state and the church together functioned as one in achieving the hegemony of the Amhara. Once the political, cultural, and economic hegemony was achieved in Abyssinia proper, the Amhara identity suppressed the identities of the other peoples of the kingdom. It became the national identity of the kingdom of Abyssinia. Amhara identity “provided the framework for upward mobility,” because of which other Ethiopians “tended to assimilate themselves into Amhara culture without a need to trace their identity through Amhara genealogies” because “the Amhara identity model was culture-based and did not require blood credentials” (Deng, 2008, pp. 68–69). The assimilation into Amhara identity has been made easy since the Amhara became the dominant political force in the 13th century in the north-central highland of the present Ethiopian Federation.

The ramifications of the assimilation of some Oromo to Amhara ethnocentric culture and identity have been affecting the self-realization of some of the uninformed Oromo who have been living among the Abyssinian societies and immediate boundaries, particularly during and after their colonization. The culturally based, purposely broad, and instrumentally absorptive assimilation policy of the Abyssinian rulers robbed off successful and prominent sons and daughters of the Oromo their identity since the late 19th-century incorporation of the Oromo into the empire of Abyssinia created by Atse Menelik II. All the Oromo who made themselves name and fame through enduring physical and mental talents and witty

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determinations to a position of prominence soon were considered as Amharans and thus an Abyssinian/Ethiopian, not anymore as the Oromo. The Oromo intellectuals, heroes, artists, governors, war leaders, kings, and all successful notable personalities acquired an Abyssinian ethnocultural identity because of their successes. The best of the Oromo, by the simple fact of being so, acquired Amhara identity and Abyssinian/Ethiopian nationality because of the imposition of Amharan ethnocentric culture.

Some Oromo personalities became committed to their acquired Amharan identity and Abyssinian/Ethiopian citizenship. They turned out to be zealous proponents of the Amhara ethnocentric culture and policy. They also became the protagonist of the institutionalization of the assimilation project that victimized them. Few Oromo have been less informed about their history and ancestral identity (mainly because of their self-alienation from their true kin) and could not cast their eyes and their mind through the veil of “Tabbot Christianity” — the long-standing Abyssinian cultural, linguistic, and ideological instrument of domination — that has taken them hostage, have remained in the dark. They are promoting the legend, pseudo-history, culture, religion, language, ideology, and identity of the Abyssinians against their true Oromummaa even to date. Less instructed among them are exceptionally vocally in the Church and the State apparatus. Others promote it crookedly and cynically in public and through enemy networks. Very few of them do so in literary works, authoring new myths in myth books and writing self-insulting and self-important articles on electronic media.

Nevertheless, most of the Oromo who had lost their Oromummaa and adopted Abyssinian identity have joined the momentum ignited by the Qubee Generation for the political, cultural, social, economic, and ritual renaissances of the Oromo. The restoration of true Oromo history, Gadaa Democracy, and Oromummaa are on the way (Jalata, 2014). Recently, many independent first-hand account records of European and Arab geographers,

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explorers, merchants, and archaeological and anthropological findings have become accessible to emerging Oromo historians and politically disinterested anthropologists and historians. This has shed a contrasting light on the history of the Horn of Africa in general and that of the Oromo in particular. As a result, the true history of the Oromo has started to be reconstructed. Only some works of shading true light to the darkness remain to wipe away the acquisitive black stains that have been left on the history of the Oromo by Abyssinian court chroniclers and dabtaras. These self-centred Abyssinians are exposed to their well-known natural tendency of self-praise and embellishment, which dictates their every effort. Their successive Abyssinian-Ethiopianist propagators have also remained in the tradition and have continued to echo their purloiner of their predecessors' embellishment and self-centred distortion. Nonetheless, in the end, the true history of the Oromo (and that of other peoples who have suffered the same treatment) is emerging from the ashes of Abyssinian chauvinism.

In summary, the Abyssinian kingdom portrayed the offensive defense of the Oromo in the 16th century that helped them to regain most of their ancestral territories (Father Land) from many centuries-long gradual occupations by Abyssinians as "invasion." In reaction, the kingdom made ill attempts. To reverse the history of migration of the Abyssinian people from across the Red Sea in the continent, it portrayed the indigenous Oromo as 16th-century newcomers. To present itself as an advanced culture, it engaged in aggressive propaganda to portray itself as religious, culturally advanced, and literately civilized. It tried to impose itself as such on the Oromo communities who had settled among its people. Despite the historical fact that the Oromo personalities and their progenies have been the most significant contributors to Abyssinian literary works since the 16th century, its elites were relentlessly engaged in undermining the Oromo for not having their own writing in their language and for not having written scripture for their religion. In doing so, the Abyssinians were able to win

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some of the Oromo communities who had settled among them or in contingent territories to their culture, language, and identity through assimilation that still has reminiscence on some Oromo people who have remained physically or psychologically astray from their Oromo kinship and Oromummaa identity. The “Qubee Generation” has now aborted the ill attempts of Abyssinian elites. This generation has now kick-started the momentum of the all-inclusive renaissance of the Oromo under the name Qeerroo.

The Oromo Influence in the Kingdom of Abyssinia, 1600-1850s

Abyssinian Nobility and their Admiration for Oromo Laws and Freedoms

At the turn of the 17th century, when some Oromo groups started to abandon their Gadaa System by rallying behind Prince Susenyos as their Luba and king, the Abyssinian ruling elites, Mekuwanent, were contemplating copying the Gadaa System for themselves. They wanted the Oromo republican Gadaa System, where democratically elected Gadaa government rules for a fixed term of eight years and the people have a regular assembly to elect their leaders, criticize them, and depose them if they failed to work for them according to the laws the people have made for themselves.

The Mekuwanent knew that the Oromo ruled themselves by law. They obeyed elected leaders, Abbaa Gadaa, who took power every eight years (Pankhurst, 1997, p. 280). They freely and democratically elect their leader for a single eight-year term of office. This was universal among the Oromo nation. One of the learned Abyssinian monks, Abba Bahrey, had observed the in 1593: “They have neither king nor master like other peoples, but they obey the Luba during eight years; at the end of eight years another Luba is made, and the first give up office” (Bahrey cited in Baissa, 2004, p. 104). The Jesuit father Jerome Lobo would record the same in the 1620s in Kenya. From his experience with them in his attempt to reach Abyssinian from the south accompanied by a small army, Lobo recorded that the Oromo who

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inhabited coastal and hinterland Malindi in southern modern Kenya chose “a king [Abbaa Gadaa],” whom they called “Lubo [Luba]” every eighth year (Lobo, 1887 [2007], Part I, Chap. II). The local Gadaa government that Lobo met had all the intelligence not only on the number of the nations who inhabited the region between Malindi and Abyssinia Proper but also on the nature of these nations, who are presently known to be over forty-five in the SNNP State of Ethiopia alone. Such was the sophistication of the Gadaa government, yet its Abbaa Gadaa and his Council sat in “straw huts.” Though he had to abandon his attempt based on the intelligence provided to him by the Gadaa government, Lobo would later succeed in reaching Abyssinia from the east; he would spend nine years (1624–1633) in the country.

The powers of the Gadaa government were separated into legislative, executive, and judiciary. The legislative body was the national assembly (Caffee, Yaa’ii, Gumii, Manbadha, etc.). All Abbaa Gadaas and interested individuals and groups constituted it. In other words, it was constituted by all the male Oromo in the ruling Gadaa (Party) who have reached the Gadaa Stage (Luba Stage) and any interested Oromo. However, only the Abbaa Gadaas had voting power exercised by veto because all the laws were made by consensus. The Caffee regularly met “in the middle of the Gadaa period once every eight years to review the laws, to make new laws, to evaluate the men in power and to resolve major conflicts” (Lemmu, 1971, quoted in Hineu, 2012, p. 87). All Abbaa Gadaas were legislators at the national, regional, or local assemblies. Abbaa Gadaas were elected at the local and regional level assemblies and were delegated to attend the national assembly on behalf of their local and regional assemblies. Non-executive Abbaa Gadaa (Abbaa Bokkuu), selected (or elected) by the Luba class (Abbaa Gadaas), served as Chairpersons of the national, regional and local Caffees and

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as the ceremonial head of the respective governments. The Abbaa Bokkuu also proclaims the laws made by the legislative convention.

Elected Abbaa Gadaas held national, regional, and local executive powers. The multitude elected them from among the Luba Class (Abbaa Gadaas), including the Abbaa Gadaas and the Qaalluus. (The Qaalluu have a hereditary spiritual office; hence, they are barred by the Gadaa constitution from taking any secular office.) The elected Abbaa Gadaas administered the institutions and offices of the Gadaa government during their single eight-year term of office. These executive Abbaa Gadaas govern as Council. Also, they appoint competently and vetted experts (hayyuu) to the institutions and auxiliary offices of the Gadaa government as executive organs. These executive organs include, among others, the offices of Economy (Abbaa Horii/Sa'aa), Prosecutor (Abbaa alangaa), War (Abbaa Duulaa), Spokesperson (Abbaa Dubbii), and Speaker of Assembly (Abbaa Caffee) among the Tuulamaa Oromo of central Ethiopia. They also appoint hayyuus as councillors, always in odd numbers, to each office and as higher-order councils to the Gadaa government.

Abbaa Gadaas, who had merits in the Oromo laws, led the judiciary. Council of retired Abbaa Gadaas who have become legal experts served as justice. They also served as memorizers of the laws and preservers of the Gadaa constitution (Heera Gadaa). They guided the General Assembly in making new laws and repealing old laws. The retired local Abbaa Gadaas (Jaarsa Biyyaa) and the jaarsa—senior citizens who are above 80 years old—administered justice daily in their respective localities. Juries made up of at least three people delivered adjudications. Severe legal disputes, however, were brought to upper Gadaa Assemblies, including to the National General Assembly, when the issue had universal implications, i.e., it was constitutional. The public investigated crimes openly and transparently through the afarsaataa [əfərsa:ta:] and lukaa-lukkee [luka:-lukke:] system.

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Public and grassroots community-based criminal investigation systems are still used in parts of Oromia. They have been part of the criminal investigation institution of the Oromo. In case of serious offenses, including loss of life, a council of selected retired Abbaa Gadaas and Qaalluus delivered justice and administered reconciliation measures through the Gumaa System, an institution of the Gadaa System for restorative justice.

Because of this clear separation of powers, the Gadaa government of the Oromo functioned more efficiently and effectively than the Abyssinian monarchy during the 16th century. Contrary to that of Abyssinians, the Oromo's freedom and sovereignty were well respected and preserved. Every household of the Oromo was sovereign. The Oromo were free people who governed themselves based on only the laws they made. They differed very much from Abyssinians who lived under the tyranny of absolute Atses.

By the second half of the 16th century, being a free people with no king or master, the Oromo had demonstrated not only that they had instituted an effective republican government but also that their social organisations, their military capabilities, and their peace and security had surpassed that of the Abyssinians. The Abyssinian military and political elites must have learned this reality of the time the hard way only after their kingdom had experienced successive defeats at the hands of the Oromo and the Oromo had annihilated almost all of its army regiments and threatened to destroy the kingdom. These elites (Mekuwanent) did not doubt that the Oromo had better social cohesion, better government, and better laws from where they derived their successes. The key to these was, they understood, the Gadaa System and Gadaa laws. This was the source of the aspiration for the Mekuwanent to emulate the Gadaa System (Oromo Democracy), which was based only on the rule of law. The Mekuwanent, in the words of Atsme Giorgis, "wanted freedom and the [Oromo] laws" (Tafla, 1987, p. 273).

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The beginning of the Political Dominance of the Oromo in the Kingdom of Abyssinia

The northern Oromo group gradually became the masters of the so-called Solomonic kingdom during the Gondarine Dynasty. In addition, “The Oromo of Maccaa played an active role in the Gondarine (ca. 1636 to 1855) politics throughout the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries” (Etefa, 2012, p. 22). During the first half of the Gondarine Period (roughly from 1632–1750), there was no region in the then Abyssinia (except in coastal Eritrea) where the Oromo were not present. By 1700, the ruling dynasties of Warra Sheekaa and Warra Hemanuu had been founded (Gebre Selassie 1975 cited in Melbaa, 1988, p. 29). By the 1750s, the Oromo had established their political dominance in the kingdom as rulers of some provinces, as part of the royal army and as a territorial dynasty. The Walloo dynasty of Warra Hemanuu was formed in the second half of the 18th century (Hassen, 1990, p. 80). By the beginning of the second half of the Gondarine Period (roughly from 1750–1850), the Oromo had been widely distributed in the Abyssinia Proper, had intermingled with the Abyssinians, and had adapted some of Abyssinian culture and identity. The northerly Oromo soon became integral to the Abyssinian monarchy and its political and military masters. This prompted one of the distinguished American historians who studied the history of Abyssinian (as the history of Ethiopia), Harold G. Marcus (1994), to call it “subversion to the Solomonic monarchy” (p. 43).

Marcus (1994) argues that the subversion resulted from Susenyos’s decision to incorporate the Oromo leaders into Abyssinia’s nobility and use their forces against his feudal enemies. However, Atse Susenyos had no other choice. The Oromo had progressively flooded the kingdom. He was dependent on the Oromo for his survival. His bid to get firearms from Catholic Europe, particularly from Portuguese and Spain, even at the cost of becoming

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Catholic and changing the state religion from Alexandrian Coptic Christianity to Roman Catholicism, did not work well. The support he had obtained was not enough either to defend the kingdom from the advancing Oromo or to force the old church's laity and clergy to change their over-a-millennium-old doctrine almost overnight. The Oromo were overrunning the kingdom. There seemed to be no option left for the Abyssinian monarch. Still, the systematic incorporation of the Oromo in the nobility to avoid a total give up of the state power and succumbing to the looming Oromo hegemony. Defending the kingdom in any other way was untenable. The "subversion" was the option he had to maintain the kingdom as an Abyssinian kingdom. The Oromo allowed that option by becoming an integral part of the monarchy rather than abolishing it.

The result of the "subversion" would, however, be the political dominance of some northerly Oromo groups in the power structure of the Abyssinian kingdom. While the vast majority of the Oromo remained under its Gadaa government in the territories that they had reclaimed from both the Islamic principalities and Sultanate of Adal and the Christian Abyssinian kingdom during the Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaigns (mainly from the 1520s to 1610s), some of the northern Oromo willy-nilly became incorporated in the Christian kingdom and associated themselves with the remainder of the kingdom in their immediate neighbourhoods. These northern Oromo gradually became the region's decisive military and political forces. Based on their past victories and future hopes for integration, peace, and prosperity, they chose to become part of the diminished kingdom of Abyssinia rather than destroy it. From being part of it, they gradually became masters of it.

Observing the realisation of the challenges that the northern Oromo posed to the kingdom of Abyssinia, the decision of Atse Susenyos to incorporate the Oromo into the Abyssinian nobility, and the success of the Oromo in being masters of the kingdom, Harold

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Marcus noted. The Oromo represented both past problems and future hopes of the kingdom, and the monarchy “tied its fate to the social and political integration of the Oromo” that eventually transformed them into “the puppets of the Oromo political leaders whom they legitimised” (Marcus, 1994, p. 43). The Oromo entered the political power struggle of the Gondarine Dynasty during the reign of Atse Bakkafa (r. 1721–1730). Subsequently, during the Era of Princes (1769-1855), they ruled the kingdom by making enthroning puppet kings.

The Ascendancy of the Oromo to Power

The Oromo joined the Gondar Palace during the reign of Atse Bakkafa (1721–1730), also known as Atsme Giorgis (Huntingford, 1955, p. 21). Bakkafa, like Susenyos and Iyasu I before him, had taken refuge among the Oromo and had lived with them (Pankhurst, 1997, p. 442; Huntingford 1955, p. 21; Levine, 2007, p. 57). He had a good relationship with his host, the Yajjuu Oromo. He had established many friendly ties with them (Huntingford, 1955, p. 21). He built his surroundings with his Oromo friends when he ascended the Abyssinian throne. Levine (2007) further explains:

Although the Oromo and Amhara interacted in many ways for generations, the process gathered momentum with the escape of future Emperor Bakaffa from the prison fortress at Wohni, from whence he went to live among the Yejju Oromo of Gojjam. Bakaffa grew up in the Oromo culture and became fluent in Oromiffa. As emperor (1721- 30), he filled the court with his Oromo friends and soldiers and sent Oromo fighters to rule over rebellious Amhara in Begemdir and Gojjam. (p. 57)

During Atse Bakkafa’s reign, the Oromo secured a strong foothold in the Abyssinian court and started to play an ever-increasing part in the domestic politics of the kingdom

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(Huntingford, 1955, p. 21). According to Huntingford (1955, p. 21), Atse Bakkafa was dominated by his Oromo followers, Oromo army regiments, Oromo guards, and an Oromo master of households. In addition to his Oromo “Master of Household” known as Kucho (Huntingford, 1955, p. 21), Bakkafa had an important Oromo advisor, Waragna (waraana), who played a “major role” in the affairs of the kingdom (Pankhurst, 1997, p. 442; Budge, 1928; Tafla, 1987). Moreover, Bakkafa had married Mentewab, an “Oromo from Kwara (Chilga)” (Marcus, 1994, p. 47). The marriage was essential to keep the Oromo, on whom the survival of his kingdom depended, in good friendship. The Jaawwii, one of the Oromo army regiments, who settled around Azzezo, were also involved in internal politics (Tafla, 1987, p. 919).

After the death of Atse Bakkafa, the dominance of the Oromo continued. The increasing involvement of the Oromo in the kingdom’s internal affairs and the Atse court would continue through the regency of Etege Mentewab. His wife, Etege Mentewab, was made, extraordinarily, co-ruler as Queen Regent with her young son and successor, Atse Iyasu II. During her regency, the Queen Regent would exercise unprecedented power in the court and throughout the kingdom. She first filled the palace with her assimilated Oromo relatives from Quara. Then, she appointed her brother Wolde Leul as Ras of the kingdom. Next, she installed her Quaran relations in high command in the palace and the army. To consolidate the support of Oromo in political intrigue, she married her son, Atse Iyasu II (r. 1730–1755), to a daughter of a paramount chief of Walloo Oromo, Amito (Levine, 2007, p. 57). Accordingly, Atse Bakaffa’s successor, his young son, Atse Iyasu II, was married to an Oromo princess. Besides, Etege Mentewab gave her daughter, Walata Israel, in marriage to an Oromo from Gojjam, Yesedeq (Tafla, 1987, p. 427). The talented Etege Mentewab, an assimilated Oromo, would soon find herself dominating the monarchy and the politics of the

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Abyssinian kingdom for over forty years: as Etege (1722–1730), as Queen Regent and crowned co-ruler of Atse Iyasu II (1730–1755), and as Queen grandmother of Atse Iyoas I (1755–1769). Also, the new Etege Wubit (also known as Welete Bersabe) had come to the Gondar palace with many Oromo followers. Soon, not only did Afaan Oromoo start to be spoken in the Abyssinian court, but the number and the power of the Oromo in Gondar palace and its surroundings started to grow exponentially.

The Oromo joined the royal bloodline of the Gondarine dynasty in the mid-18th century. Wubit, the Oromo wife of Atse Iyasu II, gave birth to the prince who would become Atse Iyoas I. Atse Iyoas I (r. 1755–1769) succeeded Atse Iyasu II. A publicly acknowledged half-Oromo monarch was now on the Abyssinian “Solomonic” throne. Atse Iyoas I, as Atse Iyasu II before him, clearly favoured the Oromo and spoke Afaan Oromoo in court. He surrounded himself with Oromo officials and filled the Gondar palace with Oromo. Increased Oromo arrived in the royal capital, Gondar city. This became the beginning of the Oromo hegemony in the Abyssinian kingdom. It would continue for almost a century. The northern Oromo would rule the kingdom, installing puppet Atses on the throne for nearly a century. This period of the Oromo rule of the kingdom would be known traditionally as *Zamane Masafent* (1776–1855). Gondar became the first permanent residence of the Abyssinian sovereign in the first half of the 17th century.

Following the ascendancy of the Oromo to the Abyssinian throne and the critical turn of events in the kingdom court, the Oromo language became an exclusive language of the Gondar palace, and Gondar City became an Oromo town. During the 25 years of the reign of Atse Iyasu II and the 14 years of the reign of Atse Iyoas I, the Abyssinian capital was effectively an Oromo town, and the Oromo language (Afaan Oromoo) was the only language spoken in the palace. The Atse Iyoas I and his Oromo officials and kin made Afaan Oromoo

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(Oromo language) the preferred court language. Afaan Oromoo became “the only language spoken in the palace” (Budge, 1928, p. 461). The Oromo, perhaps due to their number, also threatened the ethnic balance of the city of Gondar, which “with all intents and purposes” had become an Oromo town (Budge, 1928, p. 461). As much as Finfinnee city (Addis Ababa) is in the heart of Oromia, it has mainly become an Amharan city, speaking mostly Amharic, and the parliament speaks only Amharic. Gondar city in the heart of the Abyssinian kingdom in the 18th century was essentially an Oromo city, its palace speaking only Afaan Oromoo. This was achieved because of the coming to power of Atses of Oromo descent and because of more and more Oromo taking leadership positions in the army and the civil administration of the minimised kingdom. The Amhara and the Oromo cultures and languages started to flourish competitively in the city. The city continued to be filled by the Oromo. This was because of many factors. First, Oromo relatives of the Atse filled the palace enclosure. Second, hundreds of Oromo bodyguards and attendants to the Atses were in the city. Third, the elite Oromo warriors in the royal army were settled around the city. Fourth, the families and relatives of these Oromo moved to the city to serve the kingdom.

Budge (1928) explains how Gondar had become an Oromo town:

When the minority of Joas [Iyoas] ended, [The Oromo] sent a body of about 1200 horsemen to Gondar as a gift to the king, and with this came a number of [Oromo] nobles, who were formed into a small army of infantry about 600 strong, under the capacity of [Oromo] chief Wosheka. The king summoned two of his uncles to Gondar, Brulhe and Lubo, and they came accompanied by 1000 horsemen. Thus, there was in Gondar [Oromo] army of about 3000 men, to say nothing of their kinsfolk and friends who had followed them there. *The only language spoken in*

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the palace was [Afaan Oromoo], and to all intents and purposes, the capital had become [Oromo] town [Emphasis added]. (p. 461)

Beyond the reign of her son, Atse Iyasu II, when Mentewab was co-crowned, the old Etege continued to exercise the power of the state during the reign of her grandson, Atse Iyoas I, despite the challenge from his mother. The mother of Atse Iyoas I, Etege Wubit, fiercely opposed Mentewab's excessive power and influence from the very beginning. When Atse Iyasu II, who used to favour the Yajjuu Oromo, the relatives of his wife, died in 1755, and her son (half Oromo) took the throne, the influence of Etege Mentewab started to decline. The exceedingly talented Etege, however, tried to maintain her influence. Wubit, on the other hand, firmly asserted that she, the mother, not the grandmother of the Atse in power, must preside at his court and have as much influence as Mentewab had on her son, Atse Iyasu II. Nevertheless, the impact of Etege Mentewab continued largely because of her experience in state affairs as a co-ruler and because of her tested wisdom in handling people in power.

In addition, the kingdom had fallen out of the power of the Abyssinian Atses stationed at Gondar. Budge (1928) asserts this fact: “[The Oromo] were not slow to see the opportunity which presented itself to them, and they intrigued and formed a government of their own with the king as their head” (p. 461). These included the Oromo chiefs of Yajjuu, Walloo, and Gojjam. These local provincial governors, known as Masafent, grew so powerful and started overriding the imperial decrees and orders. They became self-declared autonomous governors.

Meanwhile, the confrontation and power struggle in the Gondar palace between the two Eteges continued to grow until the two were in a full-blown conflict, and a civil war would erupt. As the hostility between the two grew, both summoned their relatives and their forces from Yajjuu and Quara [k'ɔwa:ra:] to Gondar for support and a show of force. The

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internal power struggle between the two most influential women of the palace and their respective powerful chiefs from two sides of the capital made the prospect of civil war inevitable. In 1766, a civil war broke out “between assimilated (Quaran) and non-assimilated Oromo (Yajjuu)” (Marcus, 1994, p. 47). This began the so-called Era of the Princes (Zamane Masafent), a.k .a. Yejjuu Dynasty.

The distressed old Etege invited the governor of Tigre province to neutralise the power struggle between the Quarans and the Yajjuu. With the decline of the power of the Atse due to resentment and the civil war on one hand and fierce political friction between the Quara and the Yajjuu Oromo factions on the other hand, Etege Mentewab of Quara invited the powerful governor of Tigre, Dajazmach Michael Schul to Gondar for the rescue. He would soon be appointed Ras. He had remained neutral to the Quaran and Yajjuu scuffle. He wanted neither to take state power in his new authority as Ras of the kingdom.

Ras Michael, in general, would do nothing helpful for the Yajjuu Oromo who dominated the palace and the kingdom. He had always hated the Oromo, as the celebrated British Egyptologist and Orientalist Sir Ernest Alfred Thompson Wallis Budge recorded. According to Budge (1928), Ras Michael was “a shrewd and very capable intriguer” and “a master-hand at bribery,” and “he hated the [Oromo] and had always done so” (pp. 457– 458, 467). James Bruce, the Scottish explorer who had befriended Ras Michael during his time in Abyssinia for the claimed reason of discovering the source of the Nile, had witnessed that bribery and corruption were the favourites of Ras Michael: no one liked him (Bruce, 1790b, pp. 128, 252). As a hated person, he was of love but feared for his cruelty and intrigues; he too might have loved no one, even among his fellow compatriots. His hatred towards the Oromo was reflected in how he treated some of his Oromo captives. He ordered taking out of the eyes of twelve Oromo chiefs (whom he had taken prisoners in Gondar) and forty-four

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Oromo soldiers after the battle of Fagitta (Bruce, 1790b, pp. 219, 55) and about twenty that he had captured from Fasil, an Oromo chief and warrior, at the bank of Tekezie River (Seyoum, 2015, p. 194). In addition, he had ordered the skinning of an Oromo captive called Cawwaaqaa Live (Syoum, 2015, p. 194).

With the wicked interplay of animosity and friendship, cruelty and justice, and provocation and mediation, Ras Michael managed not only to divide and destroy first the power of the Quaran and then that of the Yajjuu but also to remain the master of the kingdom until the Yajjuu Oromo revived and took control of the kingdom. Ras Michael exploited the opportunity of the civil war between the Quaran and the Yajjuu for himself (Marcus, 1994). With the support of a Christian faction on the nature of Christ known as Uinctionists that opposed Atse Iyoas I because he supported the Unionists, Ras Michael defeated and assassinated his master, Atse Iyoas I, in January 1769. After the assassination of the Atse, Ras Michael made himself a “kingmaker” until he was finally defeated by Dajazmach Wand Bewesan, chief of Lasta, at the battle of Sarba Kusa (Sarbaa Kuusaa) in 1771. He had fought several battles with Fasil and Woodage Asahel, two of the most prominent Oromo who gave him several battles in Damot, Gojjam, and Agaw Meder (Bruce, 1790b) before his defeat. At the Battle of Sarbaa Kuusaa, where James Bruce was present, the Oromo “constantly received new reinforcements” that forced Ras Michael to flee back to Gondar, where he was encircled and reduced to the state of a prisoner (Russell, 1985, p. 175). This defeat of Ras Michael marked the re-ascendancy of the Oromo to the Abyssinian political power in the capital.

Though they had all the power to do so, the Oromo chiefs refrained from enthroning themselves on the Abyssinian throne. Instead, they started to dictate their wills to the puppet monarchs whom they enthroned and dethroned as they wished. The “Solomonic” dynasty

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became an apparent Oromo Dynasty. Starting from the coronation of Iyoas I as “king of kings” of Abyssinia in 1755 through the ascendancy of Ras Gugsu the Great up to the crowning of Atse Tewodros II in 1855, except the intervention by Ras Michael Sehul, the Oromo wielded the political power of Abyssinian kingdom for one hundred years (Tafla, 1987, p. 47).

The Oromo Rule of the Kingdom of Abyssinia

The supremacy of the “unassimilated” Oromo in the Abyssinian kingdom had begun when, in 1753, the widowed queen from Walloo Oromo, Etege Wubit, continued. Wubit started to rule in the name of her young son, Iyoas (Joas) I (Jones & Monroe, 1935, p. 122). An Oromo chief, Atse Bakaffa’s faithful minister, Waragna (whom James Bruce calls “Old Fasil” or “Kasmati Waragna” (Bruce, 1790b, p. 534)), was already governor of Damot. He, indeed, was more than just a governor of a province: He led an expedition to Sennar (Sudan) together with Atse Iyasu II (Pankhurst, 1997, p. 370). His son, Fasil, succeeded Waragna. Fasil was one of the provincial governors of the Abyssinian kingdom during the reign of Atse Iyoas I. However, the queen regent nominated her brother, Eshete, as Ras of Gondar in place of the deceased Ras Welde Nul. Hubna Fasil (the captain of Jaawwii Oromo) killed Eshete at Fagitta and proclaimed Fasil king of Damot and the Agew (Budge, 1928, p. 463). The king later sanctioned Fasil’s appointment as Ras of Damot.

The two brothers of Wubit, uncles of Atse Iyoas II, Lubo and Brulhe, were appointed governors of Amhara and Begemeder, respectively, but only to the effect of causing widespread resentment among the predominantly Amhara population, resulting in the quick removal of the former (Jones & Monroe, 1935, p. 122). Ras Michael Sehul deposed Lubo (Budge, 1928, p. 465). The reason for the removal was to appease the uproar of the old Abyssinian nobility for fear of total handing over of their country to the Oromo, “their

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hereditary and amicable enemies” (Budge, 1928, p. 463). Dajazmach Lubo governed Amhara and commanded the Ilmaan Dhinsaa and the Maccaa (Tafla, 1987, p. 938). Ilmaan Dhinsaa and the Maccaa were the Oromo army regiments. Brulhe attacked the serving governor of Begemeder, Maryam Barea, for resisting his appointment and was killed in that action (Jones & Monroe, 1935, p. 122).

The power of the Walloo Oromo reached its pick when the aged Etege Mentewab gave up to the dominance of the Yajjuu Oromo in the imperial palace after the civil war between the faction of Etege Mentewab (assimilated Quaran Oromo) and the faction of Etege Wubit (unassimilated Yajjuu Oromo). The Yajjuu Oromo faction had emerged victorious and powerful. It would continue to dictate both the making and the duty of the imperial kings to ascend the Abyssinian throne in Gondar after the civil strife. The Yajjuu Oromo remained influential in the Gondar Palace both as the royal family and as setters of the puppet–Atses on the throne of the kingdom starting from the reign of Atse Iyasu II with the interruption of the intrigues of Ras Michael. After the 1770s, they controlled the palace from within by being Atses of half-Oromo descent and by making kings (puppet–kings) from Debre Tabor (the stronghold and capital of Ali of Yajjuu Oromo) from without). In addition to Yejju province (Angot), the Oromo controlled the most powerful province of the kingdom, Begemeder, about 10 800 square miles, except for a few villages during the 1760s and 1770s (Bruce, 1790b, p. 254). Ali and his descendants dominated the Abyssinian kingdom from the 1780s to the 1850s (Crummey, 2005, p. 503).

Though the anti-Oromo front revived in the 1810s, Ras Gugsa Marsa, son of Guangul (the chief (“king”) of Yajjuu Oromo of Baarentuu (Bruce, 1790b, pp. 265, 279)) broke it in 1817. He succeeded by the supremacy of armed forces on the one hand and by arranging a matrimonial alliance with Dajazmach Haile Mariam Gebre, the ruler of Simen province, on

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the other hand. Gugsä had deposed Atse Yonas (r. 1797–1798) in January 1798 (Budge, 1928, p. 479) and controlled the political power of the Abyssinian kingdom, placing several puppet Atses on the “Solomonic” throne in Gondar. His military power played a significant role in his ascendancy to the pinnacle of power. He had organised elite Oromo cavalry and infantry. After consolidating most of the power, Gugsä sought stability and resorted to the Abyssinian tradition of “buying peace” through marriage. Gugsä gave his daughter, Hirut, in marriage to the son of Haile Mariam, Dajazmach Betul (Tafla, 1987, p. 945). Their son, Merso, would govern some districts in Yajjuu, Simen, and southern Tigray during the rule of his uncle, Dajazmach Wube, and their daughter, Taytu (Taitu) would become Etege in 1889 because she had married King Menelik since 1883. His other daughters, Tiringo and Walata Takle, were married to Wag Seyum Kenfu and Dajazmach Maru of Dembia, respectively. Gugsä also married his sister, Walata Iyesus, to one of the puppets Atse that he installed, Egwale Tsiyon (r. 1801–1818), who had five children with her (Budge, 1928, p. 480).

In arranging such marriage, in addition to his military might composed of over 90,000 men (Budge, 1928, p. 480), Ras Gugsä, until his death in May 1825 and his kin successors until 1853, remained “the masters of the Gonderine monarchy” (Marcus, 1994, p. 53). They deposed and enthroned shadow Atses as they wished. This historical fact is well captured by the words of Budge, who wrote, “The kings [Atses] who reigned from 1800 to 1855 were kings in name only; they had neither influence nor power ... Though king succeeded king the monarchy had ceased to exist” (Budge, 1928, pp. 483–484). During this time, the Abyssinian monarchy was effectively an Oromo dictated monarchy or simply an Oromo regency of kings.

During the period of no real Abyssinian central political power, the Oromo chiefs held the real power of the kingdom, making the Atse their puppet (Jalata, 2005, p. 53). In 1777,

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the Warra Sheekaa Dynasty, another Oromo power base, was founded (Tafla, 1987, p. 922). The same year, Kenfu Addam, an Oromo chief of Maccaa near Lake Tana, who had killed Ras Fasil and had been promoted to Dajazmach by Atse Tekle Haimanot II, installed Atse Solomon on the Abyssinian throne in Gondar only to rebel against him two years later and take him at the battle of Sabisa Ber (Tafla, 1987, p. 934). Soon enough, however, in 1779, Kenfu himself became a captive of Dajazmach Beqetu. Atse Tekle Giorgis I was installed on the Abyssinian throne in 1779. He had good support from the Tigre and the Gojjam chiefs (Tafla, 1987, p. 435). Relying on such support, he attempted an expedition against Shewa, but the offensive attack by the Walloo Baarentuu and Marawwaa Oromo turned back. Ras Ali the Great also defeated Atse Tekle Giorgis (r. 1779–1784) and Dajazmach Welde Gebr’el of Tigre in 1784 (Tafla, 1987, p. 437).

This victory of Ras Ali marked the beginning of the absolute control of the Abyssinian kingdom by the Oromo. Atsme Giorgis, writing the history of the Oromo in the early 20th century, asserts, “From then [1784] on until present-day Ethiopia [Abyssinia] became the kingdom of [The Oromo]” (Tafla, 1987, p. 435). Atsme Giorgis was referring to (a) the Oromo rule of the Abyssinian kingdom from Ras Ali the Great until Ras Ali II for seventy years (1784–1855), (b) the continued resistance of the northern Oromo to the rule of Atse Tewodros II and Atse Yohannes IV, and (c) the continued influence of the Oromo warlords in the early years of Atse Menelik II. The consolidation of power by Atse Menelik II in the 1880s effectively ended the dominance of the Oromo in the Abyssinian kingdom except in Wallo, where Ras Michael Ali, an Oromo, remained very influential.

Immediately after defeating Atse Tekle Giorgis I in 1784 and constraining him to retire to the monastery of Waldebba, Ali the Great of the Yajjuu Oromo Dynasty he assumed the power without crowning himself (Tafla, 1987, p. 878). He installed a shadow Atse named

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Hezqeyas on the throne in Gondar. When Ali died in 1788, Tekle Giorgis I was reinstalled. However, he was deposed a year later in 1789. Ali Gaz, the brother of Ali the Great, ruled Abyssinia for five years. After him, two brothers from Lasta, Ras Asrat (paternal cousin of Walda Gabr'el according to Tafla) and Ras Welde Gebr'el, continued to rule for seven years. During these years, the deposition and reinstallation of Tekle Giorgis I, the shadow Atse, continued. He was reinstalled four more times: 1794–1795, 1795–1796, 1797–1799, and in 1800 until he died in 1817. He was the puppet played with the most by the power behind the “shadow kings,” who enthroned and deposed him six times (Mekuria, 1982 Eth. C., p. 19).

According to Atsme Giorgis, after seven years of joint rule of Abyssinia, Ras Asrat and Ras Welde Gebr'el entered the conflict. Fighting broke out. Ras Welde Gebr'el was exiled to Warra Hemanuu when Amde was the governor of Maqdala. Maqdala formed an advanced outpost in the country of Walloo Oromo (Reclus, 1892, p. 169). The latter ordered Gugsa and Alula to aid Ras Welde Gebr'el. Ras Wlada Gebr'el conferred the title of Dajzmach to Gugsa and appointed him governor of Fogera, east of Lake Tana. Ras Welde Gebr'el forcefully marched from Warra Hemanuu and camped at Wagara. Ras Asrat, supported by Ras Mared of Gojjam and Ras Gabre of Simen, fought with Ras Welde Gebr'el in Wagara. Only Ras Gebre escaped, fleeing for his life; the victory went to the camp of Ras Welde Gabr'el. However, his son declined to take power. This allowed young Gugsa and Alula to take state power.

Atsme Giorgis further recounts the question and answer between Gugsa and Alula and the decree that followed when Alula told Gugsa to take the throne of Abyssinia (Tafla, 1987). Gugsa asked: “Who shall we say gave it to us?” Alula replied, “Let us say that Rabbi gave it to us.” Rabbi is the name that the Oromo use interchangeably with Waaqa – the universal Divinity they believe and worship as the creator of everything. Alula issued a decree: “The

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dead are we, the livings are we; any man who does not pay allegiance to Gugsa shall suffer castration, and any woman shall have her breasts cut off” (Tafla, 1987, p. 439). Gugsa, the chief of the Yajjuu Oromo of Warra Hemanu, became Ras of the kingdom of Abyssinia around 1802. He ruled Begemeder, Simen, Gojjam, Lasta, Yajjuu, and Walloo from Dabra–Tabor, his capital, without crowning himself Atse though he could, for over a quarter of a century (27 years) (Tafla, 1987, p. 925).

Ras Gugsa’s kin successors ruled the kingdom for a further quarter of a century through the chain of successions. In 1825, Ras Yemam, one of the sons of Gugsa the Great, succeeded his father. Ras Mareye succeeded his brother, Ras Yemam, in 1828. The Tigre (Tigrie people of Tigre country) resisted the rule of the Oromo, equating it to the “loss of one’s religion”, and voluntarily submitted themselves to the appointee of Agame, Saba Gadis, whom Ras Mareye defeated and took captive at the battle of May Eslamay. In 1831, following the assassination of Ras Mareye by the son of Saba Gadis, an imposter as an Oromo as if about to present a trophy, another son of Gugsa the Great, Dori, succeeded his brother, Ras Mareye. However, Ras Dori died in a few months. Ras Ali II, the son of Ras Alula Gugsa of Yajjuu and Wayzero (later Etege after she married Atse Yohannes III) Manan Liben Amede of Walloo, succeeded his uncle Ras Dori in 1831. He was the one who installed yet another “shadow king,” Yohannes III (r. 1840–1841, 1845, 1850–1851) in 1840. Yohannes III dies in 1868.

Ras Ali II ruled Abyssinia for twenty-two years by enthroning shadow Atses. He gave his mother, Menen, to Atse Yohannes III, a shadow Atse, as a wife. His mother became the Etege of the Abyssinian kingdom. Ali also gave his daughter, Tawabech Ali (1831–1858), to Dajazmach Kasa of Qwara, the future Atse Thewodros II, after much disagreement with her mother (Budge, 1928, pp. 487–488) and ordered him to govern under his mother, Etege

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Menen Liben Amade. Etege Menen, the daughter of Liben Amade Kolase of Walloo, in addition to playing an active role in the rule of her son, Ras Ali II, commanded an army of her own, which she led against Dajazmach Kasa (Tafla, 1987, p. 943).

According to Budge (1928), the beautiful young Tewabech was given to Kasa despite her mother's characterisation of him being "a low-born savage from the pagan country of the Kawara [Qwara]" in exchange for Etege Menen whom the latter had made prisoner after occupying Gondar. After his marriage to Tawabech, Kasa became Dajazmach of Dembia in 1847, heir and successor of Ras Ali II. Dajazmach Kasa, however, rebelled together with his wife. After the death of his wife in 1851, Kasa defeated the army of Ras Ali II (his father-in-law) in 1853. Ras Ali II fled to Darra, then to Shewa, and then to Yajjuu, where he died in 1866 (Tafla, 1987, p. 878).

In the meantime, Amade Kolase, the son of Abba Jebo Liban, became the ruler of Warra Hemanuu and Yajjuu from 1815 to 1839 (Tafla, 1987, p. 879). He was succeeded by Yemam Liben (Abbaa Jiruu) at age fifteen or younger, and he died fighting against Atse Tewodros II in 1855 (Tafla, 1987, p. 938). He was the father of Ali Abbaa Bulaa of the Warra Hemanuu, who was succeeded by his son, Mohammad Ali, who would later become Ras Michael in 1878 after adhering to Christianity (Tafla, 1987, p. 940). Ras Michel became Christian, abandoning Islam under the threat of force from the Christian Atse Yohannes IV. Ras Michael (Mohammad Ali) married the daughter of Atse Menelik II, Princess Shewareged. Shewareged was born to Menelik II and Princess Desta of the Walloo Oromo. Shewareged gave birth to Kifle Yaqub, Lij Iyasu. Lij Iyasu was designated heir to the "Solomonic" throne by Atse Menelik II. Ras Michael was later crowned king of Wollo and Tigre by his son, Lij Iyasu, in 1913 after the death of Atse Menelik II.

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In such a way, the Oromo of Walloo kept enthroning puppet Atses on the Abyssinian throne at Gondar and ruled the kingdom from behind the curtain. They installed puppet Atses several times. To mention some, in February 1784, Ras Ali the Great enthroned the first “shadow king”, Iyasu III (r. 1784–1788) (grandson of Iyasu I) by the throne name Ba’al Seged (Tafla, 1987, p. 931). In 1818, Ras Gugsa the Great installed a “shadow king”, Iyoas II (r. 1818–1821), on the Abyssinian throne. In June 1830, the Yajjuu ruling family enthroned yet another “shadow king,” Iyasu IV (r. 1830–1832) (Tafla, 1987, p. 931). They chose to install puppet Atses instead of crowning themselves Atses out of the reverence they had for the legend of the Solomonic bloodline of the Abyssinian monarchs, as has been asserted by the Church. Nonetheless, by installing shadow kings (Puppet Atses) on the Abyssinian throne in Gondar, the northern Oromo, mostly Yajjuu, effectively ruled the kingdom of Abyssinia except for some parts of Tigray and northern Shewa. To its most significant extent, the then kingdom of Abyssinia included the provinces of Tigre, Gojjam, Wollo, Amara, Lasta, and Begemeder. These provinces constitute presently the Amhara and Tigray States of the Ethiopian Federation.

In effect, Zamane Masafent was the period of the Yajjuu Oromo Dynasty in the Abyssinian kingdom (Seyoum, 2016, p. 207). Throughout Zamane Masafent (1769–1855), historian Harold G. Marcus notes, “the real actors were the mayors of the palace, often Oromo, who took their place in the Abyssinian power structure ... represented in the person of the Atse” (Marcus, 1994, p. 48). Similarly, historian Tekletsadek Mekuria asserts that the real central power of the Abyssinian kingdom was in the hands of the Yajjuu Oromo of the Warra Sheik (Warra Sheekaa) dynasty during Zamane Masafent (Mekuria, 1982 *Eth. C.*, p. 19). The powerful northern Oromo aristocracy “ruled Gondar for nearly eighty years” (Mole,

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2014, p. 27). The power of the Oromo in Gondar lasted until Atse Tewodros II finally drove the descendants of Iyoas out of Gondar after 1855 (Budge, 1928, p. 463).

Nonetheless, the northern Oromo, though defeated and driven out of Gondar, did not submit until the death of Atse Tewodros in 1868 (Tafla, 1987, p. 457) and until after the 1880s consolidation of power by Atse Menelik II. Even after that, the Walloo Oromo ruled Walloo and Tigray through their king Michael (Mohammad Ali), the father of Lij Iyasu, until Atse Haile Selassie I ascended the imperial power in the intrigue against the uncrowned Lij Iyasu (Atse Menelik II's heir to the throne) and the latter was deposed. The Walloo Oromo remained in rebellion against the rule of Atse Haile Selassie I after the death of Mohammad Ali (Ras, later King Michael) in 1918, most notably in 1929, 1943, 1948, and 1970.

A remark made by Atsme Giorgis in the early 20th century, though it manifests the Abyssinian attitude of the time, recapitulates the impact of the rule of the Oromo over the Abyssinian kingdom, which by then encompassed the combination of most of the present Amhara and Tigray states and the State of Eritrea. He states:

When [Oromo] held power over Ethiopia [Abyssinia], all the people became like the [Oromo]. The [Oromo], however, became more learned in Amarenga [Amharic] than the Amara; they intermingled in marriage, in possession of land and the army. Nowadays, the pure Amara constitute not even one-fifth [of the population]. [The Oromo] decimated and drove out the Amhara and took over Ethiopia, with the exception of Tigre. (Tafla, 1987, p. 441)

The exception of Atsme Giorgis is not a region free of the Oromo. He was echoing an earlier statement of Bahrey where he stated that the Oromo overrun all the provinces of his kingdom except Tigre (Tafla, 1987, p. 165). This 'Tigre' must not have included the southern

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Tigray of the present time, where the Rayyaa and Azzabo Oromo have inhabited, at least since the mid-16th century or before the emergence of the Kingdom of Aksum.

Summary and Conclusion

Most of the restored Oromo Father Land has survived in the form of Oromia to date. However, the kaawoo of the Oromo has been lost since the conquest of the Oromo of modern Ethiopia by the kingdom of Abyssinia in the late 19th century and the consequent institutionalization of settler colonization in the Oromo country. The Oromo of the present generation is indebted to the Oromo of the 16th century. They must also emulate them to restore the glory of the Oromo nation and their Fatherland. Greater Oromia (Ormania), where the Oromo nation would enjoy true Oromo democracy under the Gadaa government and the kaawoo of the Oromo fulfilled, should always be the vision of the sub-boonaa Oromo.

By the 1560s, the Oromo had retaken a third of the Abyssinian kingdom (Bechhaus-Grest, 2005, p. 1182). The kingdom included more than the present Amhara and Tigray States at the time. Two decades later, in the 1580s, they attacked all the Abyssinian provinces except Tigre (Tafla, 1987, p. 165). By the beginning of the 17th century, the Oromo had controlled about two-thirds of Ethiopia. At the time, most of the Oromo communities remained in the regions that would become Oromia State. These Oromo communities would remain in a mutually defensive status quo with the kingdom but continued to govern themselves according to their republican Gadaa System during the two following centuries.

Some Oromo groups from among northern Booranaa (Maccaa and Tuulamaa) and northern Baarentuu (Walloo, Yajjuu, Raayyaa, Asaboo, Ashangee, Waajjiraat), however, decided to join the kingdom under the leadership of Atse Susenyos (r. 1607–1632). Susenyos was an adopted Oromo who first appeared to have the intention to unite the Oromo and the Abyssinians but succeeded only in dividing the Oromo by winning some Oromo

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communities to his camp. Consequently, these Oromo communities who decided to follow him became politically integrated with the Christian kingdom. The rest of the Oromo estranged them because of their alliance with the enemy. Nevertheless, because of being Oromo, they always had the backing and support of the rest of the Oromo from the south when threatened.

Even though the state power would remain in the hands of the so-called descendants of King Solomon of Israel, the success of the Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaigns of the 16th century would give the Oromo, who would willy-nilly join the Abyssinian kingdom an insurmountable political power in the kingdom throughout the 17th century. Nonetheless, even though they had already started to significantly influence the power structure of the kingdom starting during the reign of Atse Bakkafa (r. 1721–1730), an Oromo bloodline would ascend to the Abyssinian throne only during the reign of Atse Iyoas (r. 1755–1769). This was when the hegemony of the Oromo, which would last until 1855, began in Gondar palace and throughout the kingdom. Following the increase of Oromo's political power in the royal capital, Oromo moved into Gondar, the kingdom's capital. Soon, Gondar became an Oromo town "by all intent and purpose" (Budge, 1928, p. 461), and the kingdom fell under the influence of the northern Oromo. After a brief civil war in which Atse Iyoas was killed, the dynasty of the Yajjuu Oromo effectively ruled the kingdom for about a century. This includes the era traditionally known as *Zamane Masafent* (1776–1855). The Oromo governed the kingdom by installing puppet Atses on the so-called Solomonic throne. The Yajjuu Oromo enthroned many "Solomonic" Atses on the Abyssinian throne during *Zamane Masafent*. However, they effectively ruled the kingdom of Abyssinia as did the Abyssinian Atses before them, but with more provincial autonomy.

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This period of the rule of Abyssinia Proper by the northern Oromo, who had become part of the kingdom, has been lamented by the Abyssinian political and religious elites as the period of division and weakness of the kingdom. Beyond the apparent reality, they did so not to recognise either the historical influences of the Oromo or the period of the Yajjuu Oromo dynasty, aka Zamane Masafent, in the kingdom's history. Almost every Abyssinian record since then reflects this effort: they portray the northern Oromo as strangers even though they had not only been an integral part of the kingdom for several hundreds of years but also had ruled it for many decades.

Nonetheless, the dissertation shows that the historical influence of the minority northern Oromo on the Abyssinian kingdom from the 16th to 19th centuries was prevalent. Owing to inadequate literary tradition, earlier influences of the Oromo on the Abyssinian kingdom have not been recorded. Since the 16th century, however, the impacts of the Gadaa-based military campaigns of the Oromo on the kingdom have been recorded vividly. The records show that the Oromo had controlled two-thirds of modern Ethiopia by the beginning of the 17th century. Some Abyssinian records show that, though the Oromo were divided, the minority Oromo who were estranged from the rest of the Oromo because of their alliance and integration with the Abyssinian kingdom were successful in ultimately controlling the political power of the kingdom. The Yajjuu Oromo successfully ruled the kingdom by installing puppet Atses during Zamane Masafent. In addition, the Oromo in Gojjam remained the regional masters during the Gondarine period (1632-1855). Except during the brief time when Ras Michael Sehul was the kingmaker in Gondar, the Oromo were masters of the Christian Abyssinian kingdom for a century, from 1755 to 1855. This was the century of the Oromo in Abyssinian political history. During this time, the northern minority Oromo communities shaped and reshaped the kingdom's political, social, linguistic, and cultural

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landscapes. They, too, were being continually assimilated to the Abyssinian identity as their estrangement by the rest of the Oromo of the present Oromia State, who remained mainly under the Gadaa government and in a continued socio-political and military stand-off with the kingdom, continued.

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Chapter 5. Conquest of the Oromo and the Making of Modern Ethiopia in the late 19th century

The second half of the 19th century began the Colonial Era in Africa. Powerful and aggressive European countries were able to establish colonies in Africa. At the same time, another form of colonialism was in the making in the Horn of Africa, more specifically in the region that has now become modern Ethiopia. It was a black nation, the kingdom of Abyssinia, subduing other black nations and nationalities. It was doing so with the implied support of European colonial power and the sheer number of firearms they supplied the kingdom competitively. The subjugating power was ambitious in building a Christian empire in the region by expanding the old Christian kingdom. The subjugation would follow with settlers from the dominating nation, hence institutionalizing settler colonization. Among the nations that would be settler colonized was the Oromo nation, the greater of the entire nations in terms of population, landmass, and natural wealth.

This chapter shall detail the failure of the Oromo struggle against colonial subjugation and the consequent emergence of modern Ethiopia. Among others, it shall discuss (a) the weakening of the Gadaa System and the formation of Oromo monarchies (Mootiis), (b) the multi-directional attacks on the republican Oromo, (c) the main reasons for the failure of the Oromo struggle, and (d) how modern Ethiopia was formed only because the Oromo nation was conquered.

In addition, I shall illustrate that the assimilation of frontier minority Oromo communities to Abyssinian identity in Abyssinia Proper has been a continued sociological process for centuries. Through their expansion during the Gadaa-based offensive-defensive campaigns, the Oromo assimilated other peoples to their culture and adapted other peoples' cultures (Haberland, 1992). Some further advanced Oromo clans and sub-clans were exposed

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to Christian cultural and monarchical political influences, because of which the Oromo communities in Abyssinia Proper gradually lost their national identity (Oromummaa) and culture in the subsequent centuries (Haberland, 1992, pp. 704, 716, 717). These Oromo communities, who lost their identity and culture in Abyssinia Proper, became willfully assimilated Abyssinians.

However, by the end of the 19th century, distinctly Oromo communities were present in multiple districts in the present Amhara and Tigray states as a pocket of vibrant Oromo polities or self-governing minority communities. In Gojjam and Gondar, ancestors of some communities that now credulously confess Abyssinian identity were Oromo. The people with non-Oromo ancestry in Gojjam have been artisans (potters, weavers, tanners, blacksmiths, etc.) minority communities that have been considered as low cast until very recently (Seyoum, 2015; Jiksa, 2015). In the early 17th century, the Oromo had the second largest Caffee in Gojjam (Tafla, 1987; Gidada, 2016, p. 70). This may mean that Gojjam was only next to the present Oromia in terms of the Oromo population. It is worth mentioning that the Oromo that Atse Susenyos (r. 1604-1632) settled in Gojjam and Begemeder (Gondar) alone were “so numerous that Susenyos had to confiscate church land to satisfy his Oromo allies” (Etefa, 2012, p. 21). Atse Sertse Dengel had also settled Oromo communities in Gojjam and Dembia (Etefa, 2012, p. 17). Several successive Atses also did so. Some of these Oromo and those who had moved into the kingdom over several centuries made the region around Lake Tana their home. They became ancestors of the present generation that inhabits the region. Most of the people of Wollo Zones of Amhara State are Oromo in every aspect of their identity. Similarly, the Raayyaa Oromo in the southern Zone of Tigray State are distinctly Oromo, even though some have recently given up on the Oromo language in favour of the state-sponsored Tigrigna language. By the end of the 19th century, the people with Oromo

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ancestries were estimated to be no less than half of the region's population that would become the present Amhara State. Atsme Giorgis was asserting this reality when he stated, "Nowadays [early 20th century], the pure Amara constitute not even one-fifth [of the population]" (Tafla, 1987, p. 441).

However, after the conquest of the Oromo of the present Oromia State by Atse Menelik II in the last four decades of the 19th century, essential social dynamics emerged in Abyssinia Proper in particular. It was the "forced assimilation [of the non-Abyssinians] into new social groups, as witnessed in the 'Amharization' of Oromo migrants to the native Amhara [Abyssinia]" (Adejumobi, 2007, p. 32). Indeed, it was not new as it had begun in the mid-19th century, and such was the social policy of Atse Tewodros II and Atse Yohannes IV. The difference could be only on the scale. Under Tewodros II and Yohannes IV, there was continued resistance to such forced social engineering programs and the scale of the "Amharization" of the Oromo in Begemeder, Dembia, Lasta, Damot, Gojjam, and Shewa (and the Tigraization of the Raayyaa and Assaboo Oromo) was minimal. The new dynamics of the post-conquest of the Oromo were, however, forced mass assimilation of the Oromo who had inhabited Abyssinia Proper to Amharan identity. This new social dynamic brought the Abyssinian population down to less than "fifth" "pure Amara" and transformed it into a fictional homogenous Amhara. The same new social dynamics also apply to the Oromo in Tigray. Everywhere in Abyssinia Proper, when the Oromo communities were off-guard in preserving their Oromummaa, they were forced systemically to replace it with Amharan or Tigre identity. This was a state-sanctioned total assimilation program. The Oromo of the present Oromia, on the other hand, were not forced into mass "Amharization" but continued cultural assimilation.

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The post-conquest massive assimilation of the Oromo could be classified into (a) Total assimilation and (b) Cultural assimilation. The former refers to the full adoption of the Abyssinian language, culture, way of life, etc., resulting in the self-identification of the Oromo with the newly acquired identity because of political and social pressures. Through time and because of the pressures from the politically dominant group, total assimilation has resulted in the self-suppression of own language, religion, traditions, and culture. This has led to the self-denial of some Oromo individuals and families of their Oromo identity. In the end, such Oromo communities who had been cut off from the mainstream Oromo society developed a phoney Abyssinian identity to cope with the massive force of involuntary cultural assimilation programs and planned social homogenisation, mainly in Abyssinia Proper. The latter refers to the adaptation of some cultural, linguistic, and religious elements of the Abyssinian or other societies by some Oromo communities both in Abyssinia Proper and elsewhere in Modern Ethiopia for some time for various non-coercive reasons. These Oromo communities, however, continued to identify themselves as Oromo. They uphold some of the Oromo cultural, religious, political, and socio-economic values and traditions within the dominant Abyssinian identity in urban centres across the Oromia State.

Monarchical Adaptations and the Gadaa Tradition

The formation of the northern Oromo dynasties and south-central and western Oromo Mootiis had multiple motivations and goals that emanated from within rather than without. This section highlights some of the possible motivations, reasons, and intended goals for the formation of the dynasties and the Mootiis.

First, the primary goals could be to cope with the pressure of the expansionist powerful Abyssinian princes, some of the Oromo, during “The Era of the Princes.” Some of the Oromo princes who had already been integrated into the Abyssinian monarch intended to

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bring the rest of the Oromo under the kingdom of Abyssinia, mainly after they had secured the kingdom's dominance in Gondar. However, the Oromo in the south held out their liberty and the Gadaa government and disapproved of the political mix. The Oromo kingmakers in the Abyssinian kingdom and the Abyssinian princes had repeatedly attempted to bring the southwestern Oromo under the domain of their feudal rule but failed.

Second, the leaders of these Oromo groups may also have intended to resist the expansion by centralising power and organising the Oromo society into influential smaller polities without losing the Gadaa constitutional unity of the Oromo. By the early 19th century, the regional Gadaas and Gadaa assemblies had become more popular and effective than the pan-Oromo central Gadaa and the Gadaa general assembly. This was owing to the over-stretching of the Oromo people over a vast territory. Though the national Gadaa Assembly (Kaawoo Gadaa) had maintained the responsibility of the central Gadaa government, the local assemblies had grown more potent for local governance. In addition, the assemblies of regional Oromo confederacies increasingly appeared to represent the general Gadaa assembly. These might have given the impression that the smaller the size (geography and population) of the Gadaa government, the more influential the administration would become, and the same social structure would be competitive with the Abyssinians. This was perhaps how the northern Oromo adapted the Abyssinian style feudal system and dynasty starting from the 17th century.

Third, the Abbaa Duulaas deliberately exploited the “weakening” of the central Gadaa government (Gidada, 2016). By the early 19th century, the Abbaa Duulaas among southwestern Oromo had grown so powerful. They had started to deviate from the Gadaa constitutional principle of subordination that required them to be entirely answerable to the deliberative Gadaa Assemblies. They gradually formed subsequent monarchies to which they

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appointed themselves as kings. In western Oromia, the self-serving interest of the Abbaa Duulaas, in deviation from the Gadaa constitution and admonition of the Qaalluu institutions, to become local monarchs had its part in the formation of western Oromo monarchies (Gidada, 2016, p. 220).

Fourth, these Oromo groups may intend to control the local trades and cross-country trades by instituting central trade and tax administrations in urban settlements and at caravan lodging centres through which the main trade routes passed, sharing the experiences from the kingdom of Abyssinia. The western and south-central Oromo communities where monarchies evolved in the early 19th century were the primary source of goods for exports to the Red Sea ports and the coastal Indian Ocean. They also served as platforms through which the caravan trade routes to the northeast, central, and east Africa crisscrossed.

Fifth, the economic exploits of the offensive-defensive war offered varying opportunities to some Oromo groups and their Abbaa Duulaas, especially in western Oromia. The Oromo developed social clusters and classes based on the gradual wealth accumulation in resource-rich recaptured areas. With the accumulation of wealth, wealthy individuals and their allies started to aggressively challenge the egalitarian foundation of the Gadaa System, leading to the formation of a feudal structure. In this structure, the Oromo became masters and owners of the land, and the subjected people became workers of the land (gabbaree). The gabbaree would become fully sovereign like the Oromo passing through the social integration processes. In the process, the Abbaa Duulaas, who, due to other reasons mentioned above, had become so powerful and accumulated more economic exploits, started to assume first the status of a local chief, then the status of a king (Mootii). The war exploits visibly enhanced the powers of the Abbaa Duulaas (Zewde, 1994, p. 7). In such a way, the growing

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authoritarianism of the Abbaa Duulaas gave way to the formation of Abbaa Duulaa kings (Mootii), particularly in Gibie Regions of southwestern Oromia.

Sixth, in western Oromia, among the Maccaa Oromo, the Abbaa Duulaas ultimately won the struggle with the Qaalluu, who maintained the Gadaa constitutions and the safuu (Gidada, 2016, p. 220). Both were engaged in aggressive private wealth accumulation. In the transforming socio-economic landscape and increasing clashes over resources in the western Oromo in the late 18th and early 19th centuries, the Abbaa Duulaas started to prove their power as warlords to maintain some level of peace and security. This further encouraged them to aspire to become kings. After becoming more politically and economically powerful, the Abbaa Duulaas preferred to establish a semi-feudal system with some rudimentary Gadaa principles and values, where they became its chief of state to maintain their powers. The semi-feudal rulers, former Abbaa Duulaas, stylised themselves in Mootii from the Oromo dual organisation and moiety but acted and ruled like kings. Instead of abandoning Gadaa System, they protected it in its weakest form; instead of opposing Gadaa ideology, they protected it (Gidada, 2016, p. 220). However, they became monarchs because they ceased to subordinate themselves to Gadaa Councils and Gadaa Assemblies.

In general, the reasons for the formation of Oromo monarchies were internal rather than external. It had no underlying connection with the Abyssinian monarchy or any form of monarchy, nor was it a widely practised change in the Oromo society. The driving force for the formation of northern Oromo monarchies must do more with assimilation than abandoning the Gadaa System. In the western and south-central Oromo regions, the form of the Mootiis was purely an internal evolutionary change. It was expedited by the need to cope with the rapid socio-economic changes. The changes were introduced because of the growing formation of social classes and wealth accumulation, which were facilitated by the region's

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trade and natural wealth. These rapid changes overshadowed the effectiveness of the Gadaa government. They encouraged the Abbaa Duulaas to take steps towards making themselves kings, turning their backs to the Gadaa Assemblies and Councils. Even then, it is far from the conclusion that the Gadaa System was abandoned in its totality in these regions where the Oromo monarchies had emerged. It indeed remained undercurrent to the monarchies with ineffective masking. In most of the Oromo countries, the Gadaa System remained the Government of the Oromo during the brief existence of these northern Oromo dynasties and south-central and western Oromo Mootiis.

Some northern Oromo groups, particularly the Yajjuu and the Walloo Oromo, made a strategic decision when they joined the Abyssinian kingdom as its co-ruler in the mid-18th century. Though it did not happen until the early 19th century, this abandoned the Gadaa System as the predominant mode of pan-Oromo government. Gradually, the Yajjuu Oromo became an integral part of the Abyssinian kingdom and the royal family based in Gondar. In Wollo, Queen Warqitu, Ras Gugsa Maru, and Ras Ali had established a strong foundation for the Abyssinian-style Oromo monarchy by the mid-19th century. Some prominent Oromo families of the Maccaa Oromo in Gojjam also individually joined the Abyssinian royal family and the ranks and files of the monarchy. The same was true for the Booranaa Oromo, who had settled farther north in the Dembia, Quara, and Begemedder regions. These northern Oromo communities soon integrated with the Abyssinian kingdom. They started to attain prominent positions in the kingdom, including becoming its rulers. They also made their language the language of the palace and its capital city during the second half of the 18th century and the early 19th century.

The amalgamation of the northern Oromo into the kingdom of Abyssinia in the 18th century, by virtually loosening themselves off the pan-Oromo Gadaa Government and by

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forming Abyssinian-style dynasties in addition to becoming both masters and servants of the kingdom, may have indirectly expedited the formation of some of the south-central and western Oromo monarchies. The Oromo knew that their Gadaa System was incompatible with the monarchy; indeed, it was contradictory. Hence, the choice of some of the northern Oromo communities sent a solid message to the rest of the Oromo nation. The message was a signal for the beginning of the weakening of the unity of the Oromo, or worse, the beginning of the disintegration of the Gadaa Government. This initial frustrating action-driven message from some of the northern Oromo communities might have encouraged first the south-central Maccaa Oromo of Gibie region and then the western Maccaa Oromo of Wallagga to take decisions of their own in their localities as to how to restructure their section of the polity based on the pressing need that emerged gradually.

The gradual shifting of the northern Oromo from the Gadaa System to the Atse system also sent a mixed signal— one good, the other evil— to the rest of the Oromo nation. Forming smaller and stronger Oromo dynasties like the Warra Sheekaa and Warra Hemanuu may have been considered a good strategy for the vastly expanded Oromo nation to organise itself locally more effectively. On the other hand, it might have been viewed as the initiation of another round of division among the Oromo and the abandonment of some of the democratic and republican principles of the Gadaa System. The Oromo were likely divided according to these two considerations. Those minority Oromo subgroups who considered it was a better choice formed monarchies. These were, however, very few. Those who thought it was not good preserved the Gadaa System and the Oromo Gadaa government.

By the beginning of the 19th century, some of the Oromo confederacies started evolving into Oromo kingdoms ruled by influential war leaders (Abbaa Duulaas) who made themselves kings in the south-central Oromo nation. The five Gibie Oromo states (Limmuu

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in 1800, Gumaa in 1810, Gommaa in 1820, Geeraa in 1820 and Jimmaa in 1830) were the first to institute an Oromo hereditary monarchy (Mootii) in the primogeniture line after their respective founders—Abbaa Gommol, Onchoo Jiilchaa, Abbaa Mannoo, Tulluu Gunjii, and Abbaa Jifar (Hassen, 1990, p. 113). The Guduruu Oromo also came under one influential leader, Gama Muras, who defeated his rivals in the 1850s (Tafla, 1987, p. 917). In the second half of the 19th century, emulating the five Gibie States, the Wallagga Oromo of Leeqaa and Qeellam had transformed themselves into monarchies through internal evolution, abandoning the political aspects of the republican Gadaa System.

Nonetheless, except in the kingdom of Jimma, the Gadaa System remained an alternative form of government for the people during the short lives of these monarchies. For instance, just sometime before the Abyssinian conquest, the formation of the Oromo Gadaa confederacy was still in practice in the regions where Oromo monarchies were established. When some internal conflicts arose between the Oromo of Gibie states and the Oromo of the Leqa states, each formed a confederacy to fight one another. The former formed the confederation of four merchants, Afran Naggaadotaa (Gommaa, Gumaa, Jimma, Limmuu) and the latter also included a federation of four Oromos, Afran Oromootaa (Leeqaa Billoo, Leeqaa Horda, Leeqaa Naqamtee, Noolee Kaabbaa) (Melbaa, 1988, p. 32). The significant change that the Oromo monarchs introduced into the existing Gadaa System was the installation of themselves as hereditary rulers of the people and their control of the standing army and the trade economy of their respective kingdoms.

From among the Oromo kingdoms in the Gibie region, only the kingdom of Jimma was highly centralised and could survive for a century. It was a strong centralised state. The centralization of the authority in the kingdom was achieved after the death of King Abbaa Jifaar I in 1855. During this highly centralised rule, conversion to Islam was rampant in the

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kingdom and throughout the Gibie region. Islam was the undeclared state religion of the kingdom. The conversion of most of the Oromo and other peoples in the kingdom to Islam contributed to the further weakening of the Gadaa System and the strengthening of the monarchy. Jimma remained a strongly centralised kingdom until the Abyssinian conquest. The kingdom submitted peacefully to the kingdom of Abyssinia under arranged autonomy and self-rule. Accordingly, King Abbaa Jifaar II was a nominal ruler under Atse Haile Selassie I's son-in-law, Ras Desta Damtew (Marcus, 1994, p. 135). This nominal self-rule of the kingdom continued until July 1932.

During the formation of the northern Oromo dynasties and the south-central and western Oromo Mootiis, the Oromo in central Oromo lands were in an alternating peace-war relationship with the Shewa dynasty since its emergence as a kingdom during the "Era of the Princes." Negasi Kristos (1696–1703) founded the Shewan dynasty at the end of the 17th century. However, gradual political assimilation between the two had already been ongoing for centuries. Despite the assimilations, the Shewan Tuulamaa Oromo continued to practice the Gadaa System. The social integration and the two-way assimilation between the Tuulamaa Oromo and the minority Amhara had little effect on the Gadaa government. The two maintained their political borders: the Amhara inhabited the small enclosures of Menz, Gidim, and Minjar in the hill lands, and the Oromo occupied the rest of mainly flat land that included most of the Shewa Zones of Oromia and North Shewa Zone of Amhara States. There were no Oromo monarchies in central Oromo land. However, there were noticeable religious conversions to Christianity of the Oromo in this region due to the extensive expansion of churches and aggressive proselytisation by Abyssinian monks, particularly around the monastery of Debre Libanos. These peace-war relationships and religious

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conversions weakened the full implementation of the Gadaa System in the areas where their effects were profound.

The eastern and south-eastern Oromo of Karrayyuu, Ituu, Hubannaa, Siiqqo, and Mandoo had remained fully content with the Gadaa System. They adopted the political systems of neither the Abyssinian monarchy nor the Islamic Emirate. However, some of these Oromo, who inhabited the highlands, had started accepting Islam similarly and for a similar reason as the Shewan Oromo, who accepted Christianity. The Emirate of Harar, an enclosure in the Oromo country, pressured the surrounding Oromo to accept Islam by coercive and persuasive means. Few Oromo communities succumbed to the pressure and accepted Islam superficially. Nevertheless, these Oromo communities maintained their Gadaa government and politico-religious center when the northern, south-central, and western Oromo communities formed Oromo monarchies (Mootiis). The Karrayyuu Oromo, in particular, are equally credited for unflinchingly keeping the Gadaa traditions in as much as the Boorana and the Gujji Oromo of the south and south-central Oromo during those centuries.

The southern and south-central Oromo of Gujji, Karrayyuu, Boorana, and Ormaa, far from the direct or indirect influence of the northern or western Oromo who had, at least partly departed from Gadaa, attempted to neither make changes nor saw any need to reform their Gadaa democracy. They stayed connected to their far south counterpart, as witnessed by *Élisée Reclus* in the late 19th century. The decentralised local government of the junior sub-moiety (clans) of the Oromo in present-day southern Kenya maintained their pan-Oromo Gadaa government and their national and political connections with the Oromo of present-day southern Ethiopia (and northern Kenya). They did so through the subordination of their elected local or regional leaders to an elected higher regional or pan-Oromo leader and through the dispatch of envoys (*jila*) (*Reclus*, 1890, p. 369), an act that the northern Oromo

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must have reciprocated. The Oromo of southern Ethiopia (Gujii, Karrayyuu, Boorana, and Ormaa) maintained the Gadaa democracy in as much as its originality as in the early 16th century during the past four hundred years. In so doing, they have earned the honoured reputation of being the repository of the ancient Oromo Gadaa practices. Without interruption and delay of power transfer every eight years, these southern and south-central Oromo have been practising the Gadaa democracy and the peaceful transfer of power every eight years since the reformation of the Gadaa System in the middle of the 15th century.

Regardless of some significant developments, most of the Oromo nation maintained the Oromo culture (aadaa), language, tradition, and, most importantly, the noble Gadaa System. The changes include (1) the adoption of feudal-style monarchy as a form of local government and some Abyssinian cultural elements connected to it as a form of a political experiment from the 17th to 19th century by the northern Oromo of Yajjuu, Walloo and Gojjam, (2) the adoption of Mootii system by south-western and western Oromo of Gibie region and Wallagga to cope with the internal socio-economic transformation, (3) the gradual weakening of the Gadaa Assemblies and Councils as well as the Qaalluu institutions in late 19th century.

Historical records and recent studies have illustrated that the Oromo maintained their Gadaa System in the vast territory. According to Reclus (1892), some of the northern Oromo who inhabited the immediate region southwest of the kingdom of Abyssinia, i.e., south of the present southern borders of Amhara State, were organised “into republican federations” in the last decades of the 19th century (p. 197). The “elected heyu or chiefs [Abbaa Gadaas]” were “invested with power merely for a term of years” (p. 197). In addition, the Oromo who inhabited the Guduruu plains and Jimma and Lagamara valleys were republicans (p. 212). In the southeast, beyond the Awash River, the Oromo had “republican confederations” (p. 211).

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Even when they were divided into the influences of the Egyptians from Harar and the Abyssinians from Shewa, the eastern Oromo were not only governed by their republican Gadaa Government but also had an effective foreign relations system conducted with “special functionaries” who represented the people (Reclus 1890, pp. 401-402). Similarly, the republican government of the Oromo among the Guduruu has been recorded by Antoine D’Abbadie (1810–1897) and Walter C. Plowden (1820–1860) as the ideal form of a republic that can exist (Baissa, 2004, p. 109). The Republican Gadaa System of the Boorana Oromo of southern Ethiopia and northern Kenya, which is identical to that of the Gujii and Karrayyuu Oromo and has been presented in the studies conducted by Legesse (1973, 2006), Bassi (2005), and many others as indigenous republican democracy that preceded the Western democracy, existed for many centuries without interruption. Despite the formation of the Oromo dynasties and Mootiis, the Gadaa System has never been abandoned. In those Oromo monarchies that constituted an exceedingly small section of the Oromo territory and population, Gadaa remained the mainstream culture of the Oromo. There was no time in the history of the Oromo nation when the Gadaa System was abandoned totally, even by a section of the society that had shortly fallen under the control of the Mootii governments.

Even after the subjugation of the Oromo and other NNPs of the Ethiopian Federation by the kingdom of Abyssinia with the sheer power of firearms and European colonial strategy, Gadaa remained the socio-cultural institution of the Oromo. Neither the Amhara-centred unitary totalitarianism of Atse Haile Selassie I nor the socialist standardisation policies of the Derg regime could abolish the Gadaa System. Among the Booranaa Oromo of southern Ethiopia, the Gadaa government and modern colonial state government have existed simultaneously and independently since the last decades of the 19th century (Bassi, 2005, p. 13). In Kenya, even though the British colonial rule and the government of the Republic of

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Kenya curtailed its political sphere, the Gadaa System remained an integral and complementary part of the Oromo identity. Gadaa System has remained the legitimate form of government and the socio-cultural and politico-legal institution for most of the Oromo since its invention.

Multi-Directional Attacks on the Oromo (1850s–1890s)

Northern Oromo and Atse Tewodros II

During the last decades of Zamane Masafent (1769–1855), the kingdom of Abyssinia was roughly one-fifth of the landmass of the present Ethiopian Federation. It included the provinces of Begemeder, Dembia, Gojjam, Lasta, Tigre, Simen, and Shewa. However, the kingdom had little influence on Shewa: It was almost autonomous. The central government of the Yajjuu Oromo had lost absolute control over some provincial governors. The long-isolated Shewa had almost been autonomous, refusing to submit to Ras Ali II. The provinces of Tigrie and Simen had grown so powerful, and their governor had started to threaten the central government with insubordination. Part of Gojjam had also rebelled. Ras Ali II maintained his Begemeder, Dembia, and Gojjam strongholds while controlling Tigre and Simen through alliances. His subordinate ally, Dajazmach Wubie, was governing Tigre and Simen.

However, Ras Ali II's attempt to bring Shewa under his rule became increasingly frustrating. Shewa, a small enclave of mainly Amhara settlers made of several very small chiefdoms, was cut off from the direct political influence of the Gondarine Dynasty. The Daccii, Wolloo, Torban Oboo, and Bacchoo Oromo, who were not controlled by the Abyssinian kingdom, surrounded this enclave. These Oromo helped, though not intentionally and directly, the Shewan Amhara to “gain independence from their overlords at Gondar” (Pankhurst, 1989, p. 381). It had remained independent for over a century. In the early 19th

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century, it had fully consolidated its autonomy. Shewa retreated from central Abyssinian politics starting from the reign of Nigus Sahle Selassie (r. 1813–1847), the first king of Shewa. Sahle Selassie, who was related to the local Oromo by marriage, spoke the Oromo language and could recruit his elite soldiers from among the Oromo. Relying on his Oromo warriors and having established his capital at Angolala—the Oromo country that he had taken recently (Pankhurst, 1989, p. 382)—in 1830, he refused to submit to Ras Ali II, the then most powerful ruler of the kingdom of Abyssinia.

After it declared itself a kingdom, Shewa vied to be fully autonomous from Gondar in the 1840s. To secure its autonomy in the eyes of the external European superpowers that were looking for an instrumental ally in their adventure to occupy the inland territory in the Horn of Africa region, Nigus Sahle Selassie signed a bilateral agreement with Great Britain and France in 1841 and 1843 respectively (Pankhurst, 1989, p. 382). By signing the contract, Shewa moved one step towards self-sufficiency in diplomatic and trade relations with Europe and many steps away from the control of the Gondarine Dynasty of the Yajjuu Oromo. This was a remarkable success for the Nigus but a testament to the failure of Ras Ali II in his desire to consolidate Shewa. Shewa, however, remained loyal in paying tribute to Gondar.

Soon, Shewa went loose from Gondar, resulting in a total cut-off. The cut-off was practical due to the buffer zone created between Wollo and Shewa by the Republican and independent Tuulamaa Oromo. Initially part of greater Shewa, Sahele Selassie's Shewa (i.e. Menz, Tagulet, and Wagda) had remained relatively unaffected by the continued war between the Oromo and the kingdom of Abyssinia in the early seventeenth century. This was because, according to Atsme Giorgis, Susenyos, who befriended the Oromo of the surroundings and lived with them, had “separated them by a boundary”, and it was inaccessible (Tafla, 1987, p. 245). However, quoting Krapf, 1860, Huntingford (1955, pp. 21–22) attributes the relative

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independence of Shewa from the Oromo rule in the first half of the 19th century to natural river dikes and the strategic location of Angolola. Chacha, Adabai, and Jamma rivers from the south enclosed Shewa. These river dikes obstructed the Oromo at their potential entry from crossing into Shewa and the strategic location of Angolola, the capital of Shewa.

This politically insulated province was sitting at the center of the crossroad of trade between the Abyssinian kingdom, the Abyssinia Proper under the rule of Ras Ali II, and the Gulf of Eden. It had a robust trading economy because of its strategic location. It controlled the trade routes between the sea and the inland. Secure trading from inland, particularly from south and southwest, to the seaboard passed through, enriching it with taxes. It also established robust economic ties between the ports of Tajurah and Zeila and the city of Harar (Pankhurst, 1989, p. 381). “Through these routes, a succession of rulers of Shoa [Shewa] obtained small but growing quantities of firearms with which they conquered the neighbouring Oromo who lacked such weapons” (Pankhurst, 1989, p. 381). Starting from the mid-19th century, the economically emboldened Shewa was waiting for an opportunity that would propel it to become ultimately the strongest kingdom around which an empire of Abyssinia (modern Ethiopia) would be built at the end of the 19th century.

In the meantime, the non-Abyssinian people who inhabited the south, east, and west of Abyssinia had also emerged more potent and more competitive to the Abyssinian Gondarine (Oromo) and Shewan (Amhara) dynasties. These non-Abyssinians included the kingdoms of Kaffa, Wolaita, Hadiya, Yem (Yangaro), Dawwaro, and Danakil; the five Gibie Oromo States of Jimmaa, Gommaa, Gumaa, Gearaa, Limmuu; and the Konso, Burjii, Gedeo, Konta, Kullo; the Emirate of Harar; the Ogaden that occupy vast territory to the far southeast; and most importantly, the extended Oromo republic to the south and southeast. These kingdoms, republics, and autonomous states of peoples, who would become part of the

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Empire of Abyssinia half a century later and would consequently constitute most of the Ethiopian Federation, had no political connection to the kingdom of Abyssinia by the end of Zamane Masafent nor they had ever been under complete control of the kingdom of Abyssinia except that very few of them had remotely paid friendship and alliance tribute in the past once or twice to some powerful Abyssinian warrior kings.

The last decades of the Zamane Masafent were critical times in Abyssinian history. On the one hand, the “Solomonic” Dynasty that had been “restored” in the late 13th century was about to disappear slowly. Since 1755, kings with mixed and no mixed of the so-called Solomonic lines had occupied the Abyssinian throne in the Gondar palace. Since the Civil War in 1756, the Oromo dictated their terms to the puppet kings. The Yajjuu Oromo accepted the kingdom as theirs and tried their best to rule it justly. In doing so, some of them had earned the trust of the Abyssinians and had been chosen to rule. Ras Ali II was one of such rulers. The Yajjuu Oromo knew they had little connection to the Abyssinian legends and did not care for the so-called royal bloodline or the Christian faith. For them, the Abyssinian throne was the gift of Rabbi (Waaqa). On the other hand, the “Solomonic” kingdom, founded so dearly in the 13th century by the legend of the origin of the Abyssinian kingdom, was priceless to the Abyssinians to fall both in earthly and heavenly terms. The proponents and the beneficiaries of the legend of the kingdom’s origin, particularly the Abyssinian regional kings (princes) and their barons (governors), always tried their best to save it. For them, according to their myths and legends, the kingdom was the source of many things: their pride, survival, dominance, birthright, source of legitimacy to rule, the promise from God, hope for the new Zion, the symbol of the second chosen people, the symbol for custody of the Ark of the Covenant, or simply their life both bodily and spiritually. However, none of them was powerful enough or could subordinate their regional interest to the kingdom to save it until a

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committed and dedicated man by the name of Kasa Hailu emerged as a mighty rebel in Quara. Because of the pervasive anarchy in the kingdom, there was no substantial and compelling central government. A few decades before the rise of Hailu, the Abyssinian kingdom was divided into four kingdoms (Tigre, Amhara, Shewa, and Gojjam) and 19 provinces (Budge, 1928, p. 123). These provinces were governed by rival chiefs who had little in common with the kingdom other than for themselves. Nor could Ras Ali II offer a unifying vision to unify the rivals.

Kasa Hailu joined the anarchy after formally being appointed governor of his sturdy base, Quadra. After giving Hailu his daughter (Tewabech), Ras Ali II made him governor of Quara and answerable to his mother, Etege Menen, in Gondar. Hailu, however, rebelled, but not before his wife pushed him over indignation by her mother. Blanc (1868 [2005]) explains the story:

Instead of returning to the seat of his government, he was obliged, on account of a severe wound received during the fight, to halt on the frontier of Dembea. From his camp, he informed his mother-in-law [Etege Menen] of his condition and requested that she send him a cow—the fee required by the Abyssinian doctor. Waizero [Etege] Menen, who had always hated Kassa, now took advantage of his fallen condition to humble his pride still more; she sent him, instead of the cow, a small piece of meat with an insulting message. Near the couch of the wounded chieftain sat the brave companion who had shared his fortunes, the wife whom he loved. On hearing the sneering message of the Queen [Etege Menen], her fiery [Oromo] blood flamed with indignation. She rose and told Kassa that she loved the brave but abhorred the coward; and she could not remain any longer by his side if, after such an insult, he did not revenge it in blood. Her passionate words fell upon

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willing ears; vengeance filled the heart of Kassa, and as soon as he had sufficiently recovered he returned to Kouara [Quara] and openly proclaimed his independence.

(Chap. I)

Etege Menen, an Oromo Queen, was the first to lead a campaign against Kasa in Quara. She led a large Oromo army against him when he rebelled. In the battle, she was wounded, defeated, and taken prisoner. This was the first stage of failure of the reign of Ras Ali II and the beginning of the rise of Kasa Hailu. Perhaps, all began with the gallant encouragement he had received from his wife.

Hailu triumphed in the successive victories that followed. He defeated a large Oromo army led by Dajazmach Goshu Zewde at the battle of Gur'amba in Dambia, which led to the rebellion of Dajazmach Beru Goshu, the son of Dajazmach Goshu Zewde, against Ali II. Ras Ali II sent an army led by four Dajazmaches to fight Kasa. Dajazmach Wube of Simen also joined Ali II's camp. Regardless of the build-up of alliance against him, Kasa was victorious. He defeated all and burned down Debre Tabor, the then capital of the Oromo, forcing Ali II to flee to his Yajjuu Oromo base. Kasa also defeated Dajazmach Birru Goshu, an emerging contender to Ras Ali II. A year later, he led an expedition to Simen, where he defeated Dajazmach Wube at Bwahit in Simen.

Hailu defeated Ras Ali II and his allies in Gojjam and Tigre, heavily relying on his closely attached bandits who had marched with him from the remote Quara to the cities because they had built trust in him for his leadership from their time as brigands. Hailu had no one to stop him from subduing the disenfranchised provincial governors one after the other, nor could anyone question his claim of descent from the "Solomonic bloodline" and hence his wish to "restore" the so-called Solomonic Dynasty. His determination, personal heroism, and effective bandit leadership earned him so much victory he had never expected.

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Kasa Hailu claimed descent from the royal line of the “restored” “Solomonic” dynasty, and hence, he vowed to “restore” the “Solomonic” dynasty once again. He claimed a paternal relationship with Atse Fasil through the daughter of the latter, Seblewengel. His great-great-grandfather was married to Seblewengel. Even if the claim was valid, it was distant: Not close enough to entitle him to the heir of the Abyssinian throne. Maternally, he is related to Ras Wedajo Lencho, the father of Wendbeweson. Atitegeb, his mother, was the daughter of Wondbewesen. There was not a royal line on this side of his lineage.

Matrimonially, he was related to Etege Menen, the wife of the puppet Atse Yohannes III and the mother of Ras Ali. The de facto Atse Ras Ali installed the puppet Atse Yohannes on the throne. He had married the daughter of the Etege, Tewabech, an Oromo princess. Though the claim was distant, if not absent, its importance was instrumental to his rise and the source of legitimacy of his future rule.

Kasa Hailu had the vision to unite Abyssinia. His vision was, however, based on the false prophesy conspired by Abyssinian monks out of their hate for the Muslims, the Oromo, and the relatively darker-skinned people inhabiting the lowland country southwest of Abyssinia Proper, including the present Benishangul–Gumuz and Gambella states. The false prophecy run:

A new king should arise, called Theodore, and he would destroy all the Muslims and the Shankilla [Negroids], and the Empire of Abyssinian was to extend as far as Jerusalem. Peace, plenty, and happiness would mark his reign and last for 1000 years afterwards. Enoch and Elijah would rise again and destroy Gog and Magog, though there would be no war. (Budge, 1928, p. 475)

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Finally, the Egyptian Coptic Bishop Abuna Salama III hastily crowned Kasa Hailu, the former brigand ridiculed by the Gondarine gentry for his low birth, Atse Tewodros II, in 1855. “He took the title... claiming, according to... Fikkere Iyesus (Explication of Jesus), that he was a righteous, just, and popular king who would come to the throne after a period of divine punishment had been heaped upon the Abyssinians for their evil deeds” (Adejumobi, 2007, p. 25). The coronation was conducted days after defeating Dajazmach Wube, the powerful governor of Simen and Tigre, to quickly calm the kingdom for himself and bar away potential uprisings for a power struggle. It occurred in a small remote church named Derasge Maryam near the southern edge of the Janamora plateau in the Simen Mountains. Kassa Hailu had just reinstated the bishop, and the two had agreed in such a way that if the Abuna crowned Kassa Atse of Abyssinia, Kassa would expel “all Roman Catholic Missionaries” and the Abuna would convince the Abyssinian clergy that “Kassa had been the Chosen of God” (Jones & Monroe, 1935, p. 129).

As it has been a tradition in the Abyssinia Coptic Church to create a legend and a miracle for political events, it was done. An elaborate legend and vision would be created subsequently by the Church to legitimise the coronation of Kasa. He initially styled himself “Elect of God”, and after some time, he claimed descent from King Solomon of Israel, akin to his predecessor Abyssinian monarchs. The claim, supported by the Abuna’s help according to their pact, earned him acceptance among the core Abyssinian aristocratic elites and the foreign missions. This helped him tremendously against his battered legitimacy due to his low birth.

Atse Tewodros II took what he called “ruling Abyssinian as a unified kingdom” seriously. Indeed, the then Abyssinia was divided, weakened, and disunited. However, his “unification” was far from the “reunification” that his successors would claim five decades

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later. For example, it was very and utterly different from the red herring “reunification” claim of Atse Menelik II. Menelik’s “reunification” after he became Atse of Abyssinia would be the colonisation of non-Abyssinian neighbourly peoples, a colonisation project no different in style and effect from the European colonisation of the rest of Africa except that it would be settler colonisation and the colonisers would be black African Abyssinians. At best, according to Legesse (2006), it would be a “revisionist history that bears only a faint resemblance to the truth” (p. 8). Tewodros’s “unification” was to unite Amhara, Gojjam, Shewa, and Tigre. More precisely, it was to join the then Abyssinian provinces of Enderta, Antalo, Siraye, Baher–negash, and Tigre, Simen, Waldiba, Begemeder, Walaka, Dambia, Damot, Agewmider, Kuara, Enerya, Ras-al-Fil, Chilga, Sakahala, Guto, Lasta and the kingdoms of Shewa and Gojjam (Budge, 1928, p. 123). Ultimately, he aimed to mould and rule the unitary kingdom as an absolute king. He was the first Abyssinian monarch to have the idea of establishing a unitary state (Zewde, 1994, p. 8).

Nevertheless, the fierce resistance from the northern Oromo (and the clergy) could not let him achieve his vision. Despite defeats at some decisive battles, the Yajjuu and the Walloo Oromo resistance remained strife, and their local power remained intact. The autonomous political units of the Yajjuu and Walloo Oromo gave him the biggest challenge. The Walloo Oromo, who were strong autonomous political units, could not accept the sovereignty of such a person as Tewodros, who declared war on them. In addition to rallying the Walloo Oromo to his assistance, the defeated and exiled Ras Ali II also formed an unsuccessful alliance of collaboration with Nigus Hayle Melekot of Shewa and queen Warqitu [wɛrk’i:tu:] of Wollo to fight Kasa. Tewodros relentlessly campaigned against them, declaring them ancestral enemies. His attack was brutal. He massacred hundreds and thousands of Oromo. He uprooted the Yajjuu power centre from their capital at Debre Tabor and camped there himself.

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Regardless of all the atrocities, the Walloo Oromo sustained their struggle against him. They never fully surrendered to him. They fought with him until his death.

Though achieving the alleged vision of “unification” and “ruling Abyssinia as a single unit” was his primary goal, neither could be a reality a decade after he had become Atse because of internal resistance, external clashes, and personal failures. Internally, he faced fierce resistance from the powerful northern Oromo, the Christian clergy, the Muslims, and his regional chiefs. The Christian clergy opposed his policies on the Abyssinian Church and their part in it. Though subdued and submitted, the regional chieftains of the kingdom from Gojjam and Tigre remained strong and continued to contest his power. The Tigrie rebellion of 1860 was particularly devastating. From within himself, his worldview of the Abyssinian kingdom as a Christian kingdom and his paranoia about the encroaching Islam from the northwest may have motivated him to set his unpopular goal: “to expel all Moslems who would not adopt the Christian faith” (Jones & Monroe, 1935, p. 131). This goal put him at odds with the Muslims of Abyssinia and the neighbouring peoples. The reason why he chose the name Tewodros (Theodore) was that he believed he was the one who would one day wipe out Islam, conquer Jerusalem and occupy the throne of Solomon as it was in the legend of a just and righteous king in this adopted name (Jones & Monroe, 1935, p. 139). Furthermore, his growing impatience and megalomania sent a sense of fear and insecurity among his army and court. His naïve ego would also bring him with the silly confrontation with Great Britain when he had imprisoned its envoys for the failure of the latter to respond to his request to join hands and help him to destroy the common enemy of Christians, i.e., the Muslims and the Oromo.

Meanwhile, in the remote Shewa too, Tewodros was being resisted. Though he had assigned Mared Azmach Hayle as his appointed governor of Shewa after taking Menelik

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captive, Ato Seyfu, the brother of Hayle Melekot and the son of Sahle Selassie rebelled, and the Oromo of Tuulamaa and Maccaa had joined Kinfu in his campaigns against Tewodros. Moreover, some Tuulamaa and Maccaa Oromo in Shewa had started to attack the Amhara sent by Tewodros and had settled among them recently. The attack happened after the massacre of the Oromo in the hands of the army of Tewodros became rife, and the brutal march of Tewodros on the Oromo in Gojjam and Wollo became known to them. The rest of the Oromo gradually felt the hostility and brutality of the Atse towards the Oromo. Besides, the young Menelik, whom Atse Tewodros II gave the title of Dajazmach, had just escaped from him in 1865 and started to strengthen his Shewan kingdom with the support of the Oromo aristocracy.

Atse Tewodros had only a big vision, ego, and dream throughout his reign but little success. He could not put any of these into meaningful reality because of his failures and the resistance he faced. As he continued to realise his failure, his anger grew against the northern Oromo, whose pioneering resisted him and stood to him after he had declared them the enemy. The fact that he was related to the Oromo could not help him have fellow feelings towards the Oromo. He directly associated his failure with them and continued to avenge his anger on the weakest and most vulnerable of them through his turbulent reign.

Based on the historical animosity between the Abyssinians and the northern Oromo that led to open hatred of Tewodros towards the Oromo and the historical successive victory of the Oromo over the Abyssinian kingdom in earlier centuries, Tewodros must have realised the power of the Oromo in Shewa, in Wollo and Yajjuu that was ready to fight against him. One of Tewodros's goals was, therefore, "to destroy or convert [the Oromo]" (Jones & Monroe, 1935, p. 131), the northern Oromo, as fast as possible, akin to his restless and excessively ambitious goal of "ruling the Christian world from Jerusalem." He divided the

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northern Oromo into two: the “Gallas” and the “Mohammedans.” The latter were those Oromo (and non-Oromo) who had claimed descent from Prophet Mohammed and had established the Oromo dynasty known as Mohammedoch. He believed there was no option for Waaqeffataa northern Oromo, who had become part of the kingdom of Abyssinia and its rulers and subjugation. Whereas for the Muslims whom he believed were immigrants, he offered a stark choice: convert to Christianity or leave. Plowden wrote, “To Mohammedans, he has declared that he would first conquer the [Oromo] ... and, after that, Mussulmans [Muslims] now residing in Abyssinia will have the option of being baptised or of leaving the country” (Plowden, 2011, p. 458). To both categories, however, with some exceptions, Tewodros declared war and forced conversion on the northern

Tewodros went head-to-head with Great Britain, the most powerful kingdom of the time, to fuel the internal opposition and instability. His attempt to sell his idea of “an anti-Muslim entente” to Queen Victoria and his request for support to destroy his Oromo enemies and internal rebellions failed to produce any desired response. His puerile approach to diplomatic means did not work. The self-absorbed Atse imprisoned British missionaries and diplomats to get the attention of Queen Victoria and the response he had hoped for. He was oblivious to what he was entering.

His clash with Great Britain resulted from the power-hungry personality of the Atse and his delusion about the greatness of himself and his kingdom. “His megalomania caused him to rank himself with the great kings of Europe and ultimately drove him into a conflict with Great Britain, which destroyed him” (Budge, 1928, p. 501). His close British friend Walter C. Plowden, in his official report of June 25, 1855, described Tewodros’s peculiar jealousy and ignorance. Plowden attested: “The most difficult trait in his character is this jealousy and the pride that, fed by ignorance, renders it impossible for him yet to believe that

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so great a monarch as himself exists in the world” (Plowden, 2011, p. 458). This was quite a telling story for a barefoot “king of kings” who lived in tents and ruled tyrannically the disenfranchised and divided petty provinces from a temporary court of tents under continuous revolts and insurrections to his rule from the clergy, the masses, the soldiery, and the northern Oromo.

The actions of the Atse gradually infuriated Great Britain. It sent an expedition of 32,000 men for nine million pounds (Marcus, 1994, pp. 71–72). The expedition consisted of thousands of Indian mercenaries, the British army, about two thousand Chinese road builders, several thousands of carrying animals, and forty-five Indian Elephants (Jonas, 2013, p. 26). General Robert Cornelius Napier (1810–1890) led the British expedition that landed and re-embarked at Zulla on the Red Sea. Dajazmach Kasa of Tigray, who would later become Atse Yohannes IV of Abyssinia, logistically assisted the expedition for inland travel from Zulla (Mitsewa) to the border of Wollo. From Wollo, queen Warqitu allied herself with the British expedition and led it to the heart of the Warra Hemanuu Oromo, who inhabited the territory around Maqdala.

The expedition defeated the demoralised army of Tewodros at Maqdala on April 10, 1868. By all accounts, it was an easy victory for the British expedition. The expedition was “without parallel in the history of England and modern times, not only for the justice of the cause and mathematical precision of the operations, but also its complete success, almost without bloodshed, and the disinterested conduct of the victors” (Reclus, 1892, p. 181). For the kingdom of Abyssinia, however, the defeat abashed the kingdom, the army, and the person of the Atse.

First, it was a sell-out of the sovereign by his regional chief. The then governor of Tigre, Kasa Mercha, later Atse Yohannes IV, committed a treasonous act against his sovereign

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and his kingdom by helping the enemy of his kingdom who had arrived to engage in Battle with the Atse. Upon its return journey, the expedition rewarded Dajazmach Kasa for his help against his sovereign and his kingdom. He received thousands of firearms. Kasa Mercha would use these firearms against his people to achieve political power in the kingdom. In the decisive battle against the self-crowned Atse Tekle Giorgis (r. 1868–1871) after the sudden death of Atse Tewodros, Dajazmach Kasa Mercha would defeat the large army of the former with the smaller army but equipped with better weapons and become an Atse of the kingdom in 1872.

Second, the humiliating military defeat of the kingdom encouraged the Egyptians and the Italians to attempt to take territory from it. The army of the Atse could not inflict any significant loss of life on the British army. It wounded or killed about twenty expedition members, while hundreds of its members were killed (Jones, 2013, p. 28). For an Atse who had boasted of his military might and envisioned to rule from Africa to Israel, it was a colossal embarrassment. The outcome could have been different if he had engaged the British on their way to Maqdala in the testing rugged terrains. This was impossible for Atse Tewodros because he had his governor of Tigre (most of present Tigray State and the State of Eritrea) against him, and he was checked by the Oromo armies of Warqitu and Mestawot [Mɛsta:wɔt] who had surrounded his army atop Maqdala. Being a prisoner atop Maqdala massif in the kingdom, he claimed he was its sovereign; he had to wait for his foreign enemy in his best fortress and his army could only wound or kill less than two dozen of the enemy but itself killed in hundreds before the mission of the military expedition was completed. This humiliating defeat encouraged its interested enemies to grab territory from it after the disinterested British expedition had left.

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Third, it was a personal embarrassment for the Atse. The attempt of Atse Tewodros to buy the empathy and sympathy of General Robert Cornelius Napier with a thousand cows and five hundred sheep (Jones, 2013, p. 28) was uncharacteristic of how he was known as the Atse of the kingdom. He had presented his persona as heroic and never to be defeated. He had blown loud his own trumpet of himself of not lowly to the queen of Great Britain. It is hard to imagine that this persona would try to buy for himself mercy by sending his enemy cows and sheep. Also, his last contemplations, seen in his previous letter, portray the Atse not as heroic but as a terrible, fearsome person who was wailing for mercy.

After completing its mission, the British expedition left the country. It did not want to occupy the country. Doing so was not its mission, nor did it have the warrant to kill the Atse. Its only mission was freeing the British hostages. It achieved that very successfully. It had no other interest more than that. Jones and Monroe's quote of Lord Edward Gleichen's writing about Napier's exploit suggests why the expedition had no different plan. Gleichen wrote: "Having spent an immense sum of money with an extremely inadequate return for it for the country which we had conquered, northern Abyssinia, was commercially valueless and not worth annexing, we were content to let the matter drop" (Jones & Monroe, 1935, p. 141). The expedition handed the Maqdala fortress to Queen Mestawot (Mekuria, 1982 Eth. C., p. 23). It left Maqdala after one week and started the arduous journey to Mitsewa. On its way, General Napier left behind artillery, muskets, rifles, and munitions worth approximately 500,000 pounds to Dajazmach Kasa of Tigray (later Atse Yohannes IV) as a reward for his help against his fellow citizens and his Atse (Marcus, 1994).

Reign of Atse Tekle Giorgis II and Division of Northern Oromo

Atse Tewodros had three sons: Mengesha, Alemayehu, and Hailu. After the death of their father, the eldest, Mengesha, moved to the country of his mother, Amara Saynt;

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Alemahyeu was taken to England by the British expedition; Hailu, the youngest, remained in Tigray with his Oromo mother (H. Rassam cited in Makuria, 1982 Eth. C., p. 20). After the death of Atse Tewodros, none of his sons had any reasonable chance to succeed him. Nor did the public want any of them, as they hated their father, who had massacred so many innocent people and destabilised the existing norms of the Abyssinian society. Thus, his death was followed by a power vacuum.

This power vacuum attracted three leading contenders: (1) Dajazmach Menelik of Shewa, who had already declared himself Nigus (king) of Shewa three years ago, (2) Dajazmach Kasa Mercha of Tigre, who had guided and pleased with the British expedition for they caused the death of his sovereign, and (3) Dajazmach Gobezie of Wag (Agew) who had already gathered the energy and the enthusiasm to overthrow Atse Tewodros before the arrival of the British expedition. Among the three leading contenders, Wag Shum Gobezie was the most powerful. Though the Yajjuu and the Walloo Oromo were aspirants to the return of their rule of the kingdom, they were divided and caught up in local rivalries: they could not amount to a serious contender.

Based on the explanations given by Tekletsadek Mekuria (1982 Eth. C., p. 23), Wag Shum Gobeze was in a better position to take power shortly after the death of Atse Tewodros II. He immediately controlled the old capital, Gondar. He had expanded his lordship in Lasta, Tiray, and Tigre before Atse Tewodros's death (Mekuria, 1982 Eth. C., p. 42). The Oromo queen, Mestawot, perhaps to gather alliances because of her rivalry with Queen Warqitu, had submitted to Gobeze before she had taken Maqdala from the British. In Gojjam, Gobezie deposed Dajazmach Desta Gualu and promoted Adal Tesema to the position of Ras after he married his sister, Lakech. Ras Wolde Mariam of Begemeder also submitted it to him. In

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Simen and Wegera, he crushed the armed resistance of Tiso Gobezie and appointed his cousin, Tafari, Wag Shum.

However, he faced a problem legitimising his power through a formal coronation. There was no Archbishop to crown him, nor could he bring one from Egypt because the Turks had occupied the ports, and by land, Kasa Mercha, the governor of Tigre, would not let the archbishop pass through his country to crown his opponent. The urgency for the coronation was, however, evident. Gobeze had hoped that coronation would help him get the submission of Menelik of Shewa and Kasa Mercha of Tigre. He looked for an alternative, though less legitimate and less majestic. In the same year or a year after the death of Atse Tewodros, the local bishop crowned Wag Shum Gobeze as Atse Tekle Giorgis II. Throughout his reign, he hoped for the submission of Nigus Menelik and Dajazmach Kasa Mercha, which would never happen.

From 1868–1871 Tekle Giorgis II was Atse of the kingdom. He oversaw a weak and divided kingdom where half of it never submitted to him. Indeed, his opponents grew in military and economic power more than he did. Kasa Mercha and Menelik were amassing firearms and trying to establish diplomatic relations with foreign powers independent of him, each for its advantage. Kasa Mercha, whom Atse Tekle Giorgis II had helped to protect himself against Atse Tewodros II and had married his sister in the friendship they had built in their alliance, has gradually grown strong and started to threaten the Atse. Nigus Menelik, on the other hand, has shown a gesture of submission by sending some tributes through the Shewan Oromo warlord, Goobanaa (Mekuria, 1982 Eth. C., p. 24). Atse Tekle Giorgis's multiple attempts to earn diplomatic relations for his kingdom and personal favour for himself over his opponents from European powers were not successful. In the end, the military campaign of the Atse to subdue Kasa Mercha in 1871 resulted in the capture of the

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Atse and the end of his reign. The victor, Dajazmach Kasa Mercha, declared himself the Atse of the kingdom.

During these brief years of the reign of Atse Tekle Giorgis II, the northern Oromo were divided. The Walloo, Yajjuu, and the Oromo were divided between the two queens. Yet, their resistance to the Abyssinian claimants of the throne remained strong. They lost to Kasa, Gobezie, or Menelik in the territories, but the Raayyaa, Yajjuu, and Walloo Oromo maintained low-scale resistance. In Gojjam, the assimilation of the Oromo had made the governors think of themselves as Abyssinians. They have already started to expand their territory into the Maccaa Oromo territory to their immediate south as part of the expansion of the Abyssinian kingdom. The leaders of the frontier Tuulamaa Oromo of Shewa started to trust Nigus Menelik and adopted the Abyssinian feudal lifestyle, breaching further division among the Oromo.

Reign of Atse Yohannes IV and Abyssinian Attacks on the Oromo

During the early reign of Atse Yohannes IV, the kingdom remained divided. Kasa Mercha emerged after defeating and capturing Atse Tekle Giorgis II in 1872. However, his rival, Menelik of Shewa, refused to submit to him. As a result, Abyssinia of Atse Yohannes IV (Begemeder, Gojjam, Tigre) and the kingdom of Shewa of Nigus Menelik (Shewa and part of Wollo) existed parallel to each other for seven years (1871–1878) until the latter submitted under the threat of force in March 1878 (Mekuria, 1982 Eth. C., p. 172). In Yajjuu, the revolt of Dajazmach Ali Birru of Yajjuu Oromo failed when the army of Wag Shum Tefari, who had submitted to Atse Yohannes IV, killed him (Mekuria, 1982 Eth. C., p. 80). The combined efforts of Atse Yohannes IV and Nigus Menelik finally crushed the continued resistance of the Yajjuu, Wallo, and Raayyaa Oromo. Queen Mestawot of Wollo allied with Menelik of Shewa. Thus, by 1878, the Walloo and Yajjuu Oromo were under the control of

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the two contending Abyssinian monarchs until the submission of Menelik to Yohannes IV in 1878, making Beshilo River their line of separation, the two not only forced and persuaded local chiefs to join their respective clubs but also engaged in a diplomatic contest with European powers, both claiming the title of king of kings (Mekuria, 1982 Eth. C., pp. 71, 172).

The Atse's policy of forced conversion of Muslims to Tewahdo Christianity met with fierce resistance after the Boru Meda theological conference that declared Tewahedo [tɛwa:hedo:] as the only doctrine of the Abyssinian Coptic Church. The policy of forced conversion of all Muslims to Christianity followed this. Refusal by the Muslims resulted in the genocide of the northern Muslims, mostly Oromo. About forty thousand Muslim Oromo were killed because of their resistance to the forced conversion project. Determined Muslim opponents of the religious policy of the Atse decided to flee to neighbouring Sudan. There, they organised a resistance to overthrow Atse Yohannes IV by joining hands with their Muslim brothers, the Mahdist, a mission in which they would ultimately succeed.

However, the declaration of Tewahdo as the only theology of the Abyssinian Church and Christianity as the only state religion would have consequences beyond his reign. The forced conversion of hundreds of thousands of Muslims to Christianity would not only dissipate the resistance of the northern Oromo but also would result in the conversion of some of the prominent leaders of the Raayyaa, Yajjuu, and Walloo Oromo to Christianity and their total submission to either Atse Yohannes IV or Nigus Menelik. Three prominent Oromo leaders would submit to the Abyssinian kingdom and convert to Christianity by receiving appointments. Yimam Amede Ali (Abba Watew), the son of Queen Mestawot, would be baptised Hailemariam and appointed Dajazmach (Mekuria 1982 Eth. C., p. 200). Similarly, his rival, Yimam Mohammed Ali (son of Ali Abba Bulaa), would be baptised Michael and

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appointed Ras of Wollo (Mekuria, 1982 Eth. C., p. 201). Kubbe of Rayya would also accept Christianity but would revolt shortly. He would, however, submit to Atse Yohannes IV, hoping for a negotiated settlement. Atse Yohannes IV, however, would oversee the decapitation of Kubbe and his men. The forced conversion and submission of the three key Oromo leaders would give the Abyssinians total control over Raayyaa, Yajjuu, and Walloo Oromo.

In Gojjam, the appointment of Ras Ada as Nigus (King) of Gojjam in 1881 and the subsequent encouragement he received from Atse Yohannes IV to conquer the kingdom of Kaffa beyond the western Maccaa Oromo opened up a new battlefield on the Oromo. Adal Tesemma defeated and killed the appointee of Atse Yohannes, Desta Tedla Gualu, in 1874. Nonetheless, he became an ardent supporter of the Atse. By the blessing of the Atse, he became Ras of Gojjam. Ras Adal immediately started the ambitious mission of expanding his territories into the Maccaa Oromo south of Gojjam. Soon, he was crowned Nigus (king) Tekle Haimanot on 20th January 1881. Though himself a descendant of the Oromo rulers of Gojjam, Nigus Tekle Haimanot made the Oromo an enemy and further suppressed the Gojjam Oromo, whose power had been broken after the deposition of Goshu Zewdie in 1852 by his son Birru and the subsequent death of Birru in 1868. His ambition to conquer the kingdom of Kaffa for his master and his zeal to expand his kingdom induced an Oromo descendent to wage war against his kin, the Maccaa Oromo, who inhabited the vast region between the Kingdom of Kaffa and Gojjam, using predisposed Oromo as a frontline.

Around the same time, the Agew people were used as front-line boundary enlargers of the kingdom of Abyssinia against the Benishangul-Gumuz people. This strategic use of the Anglo people by the Abyssinian rulers was not the first one. When the Amhara cut the Agew nation into two from the south (Beke, 1845, p. 91), the Agew of Agew Mider had been used

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to expand Abyssinian territory in the southwest. Reclus (1892) has captured the recent use of the Agew people for the same purpose very well:

East of the Gumus [Gumuz], the plains covered with low hills which stretch towards the offshoots of Damot and Agaumeder are beginning to be peopled by Agau [Agaw] immigrants, who, arriving in the country in isolated families, settle down in the clearings, at a few miles distance from each other. They do not fear the hostility of the natives, as they know they are protected by the prestige of the great military Empire of Abyssinia, by which any wrong done to them would soon be avenged by a war of extermination. Thus, the boundaries of Abyssinia are being yearly enlarged by the immigration of new colonies; from an independent nation, the Gumus [Gumuz] have almost changed into a tributary people. (p. 227)

Under the leadership of Ras Adal Tesemma, later Negus Telke Haimanot, the cultural and political hegemony of the Oromo in Gojjam faded away. Negus Tekle Haimanot was not an Abyssinian. He was an Oromo. But he flavoured being identified as Amhara and promoted Amharic and Abyssinian identity rather than the Oromo language and Oromo identity. As a result, he actively suppressed the Oromo in Gojjam. These rendered the Gojjam Oromo powerless to resist the rise of Abyssinian cultural and political hegemony. Abyssinian identity flourished at the cost of the erosion of Oromo identity among the nobles and the commons of Gojjam.

In Shewa (the present North Shewa Zone of Amhara State), the militarily and diplomatically emboldened Menelik became an expansionist by embracing some Oromo leaders on the one hand and by dividing some Oromo lineage groups and clans on the other. He persuaded several Shewan and Walloo Oromo chiefs to join him in his cause of rising to

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Abyssinian power, preaching unity and peace between the Oromo and the Abyssinians. This tricked the peace-loving Oromo leaders into convincing themselves to join Menelik. The Oromo, Warqitu, and Gobana helped Menelik against the de facto king of Shewa, Bezabeh until the latter was overwhelmed and submitted but soon revolted and killed. Furthermore, Menelik tactically promoted the Oromo leaders who had Abyssinian blood or related to the Shewan Amhara in marriage. He wisely used these Oromo who had decided to follow him against those who refused to abandon the Gadaa government and remained independent. In some instances, he used the existing division among Tuulamaa communities to his advantage by enticing them and siding with one of them based on his strategic goal of dividing, weakening, and attacking the Oromo who opposed him.

Like Negus Tekle Haimanot of Gojjam, Negus Menelik of Shewa was also engaged in massive territorial expansion. The difference was that the latter was more aggressive than the former. Menelik's first target was controlling the Walloo Oromo and the rest of the Shewan Oromo. After he had settled the control of Wollo (province) with Atse Yohannes IV in the 1878 peace deal that made his claim to Shewa official as its king with the title of "Nigus Menelik of Shewa," Menelik was highly encouraged to control more territories to the south and the west of Amharan Shewa (the present North Shewa Zone of Amhara State). This was the beginning of the plan for the massive expansion of the Shewan Amhara insertion into the vast Tuulamaa Oromo territory in the Maccaa and Tuulamaa (central Booranaa Oromo) country and the Arsii and Karrayyuu territories in the major Baarentuu Oromo country. This required Menelik to engage with the Oromo in an armed confrontation on multiple fronts. Menelik's war chiefs, the most powerful of them being Oromo themselves, became busy raiding the Oromo countries, taking the fertile central Oromo land, and making the inhabitants serfs and enslaved people.

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The kings of Shewa and Gojjam (Menelik and Tekle Haimanot) entered an armed confrontation with profound consequences. They have vied with each other for some time because of their ambitions for expansion into the Oromo country and to become the second most crucial monarch of the kingdom next to Atse Yohannes IV. Finally, they decided to battle each other. In June 1882, the two engaged with each other's massive forces in the Oromo country at the battle of Embababo in Guduruu in northeast Wallagga. The latter was wounded and captured. As punishment for entering war with each other, the Atse punished the local kings (Mekuria, 1982 Eth. C., p. 224). First, Nigus Tekle Haimanot was deposed, and his kingdom was given to Ras Alula (but he was later reinstated). Second, the then province of Wollo was taken from Nigus Menelik, divided, and given to Ras Ar'aya and Ras Michael.

The reaction of the Walloo Oromo to the relinquishing of power in Wollo by Menelik to the son of Atse Yohannes IV, Ras Ar'aya, resulted in the rebellion of some Oromo Chiefs of Wollo. Abbaa Jabal and Abbaa Waato in 1883, on the one hand, and Shaykh Tallhah and Shaykh Tola Jaafar in the mid-1880s against both Atse Yohannes and Nigus Menelik, on the other hand, continued. These resistances, however, appear to be low-scale and highly localised. They had little significance in overthrowing either the Atse or the Nigus.

The loss of Wollo was a painful experience in Menelik's expansionist psyche. He decided to take more territories from the Oromo and other southern kingdoms and peoples. His aggressive expansion and raids into the Oromo country continued. His right-hand war chief, Goobana Daccii, had recently subdued most of his Oromo countrymen of Maccaa and Tuulamaa up to Limmuu, Goomma and Geera of the Gibie states for him. Still, Menelik, by the end of the year, wished to have more and more of the country to the south of his Shewan

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kingdom. He had the ambition to build a kingdom that would rival the remainder of the Abyssinian kingdom already before the death of Atse Yohannes IV.

His indebted service to Great Britain brought Atse Yohannes IV to his death. Atse Yohannes IV was a wise man skilled in serving outsiders for his gain of authority. In addition to serving the British expedition against Atse Tewodros II before his ascendancy to the Abyssinian throne, Yohannes IV continued to serve Great Britain's interest after becoming the Atse of Abyssinia. He was seeking continued favour from Great Britain. Since 1882, the British had controlled Egypt. In 1884, the British signed a treaty with Atse Yohannes IV in which the former ceded the walled city of Harar to Nigus Menelik in exchange for assistance from the latter against the Mahdist forces in Sudan. Menelik occupied the town in 1887. Encouraged by his old friendship from the time of the British military expedition to Maqdala in 1868, Atse Yohannes IV helped the enemy of the Mahdist, the British-controlled Egyptians, in not only allowing them to escape through his territories of Tigre but also accompanied them (for protection) (Mekuria, 1982 Eth. C., 1983 Eth. C). Retaliation from the Mahdist came soon. They sacked Gondar but retreated. He had hoped that the British would help him in his venture to fight the Mahdist Sudanese. In the fight at the battle of Gallabat near Matamma, he had no British support. The Mahdist avenged his support and protection for the British-ruled Egyptians who caused suffering to them by killing him in 1889.

After the news of the death of Atse Yohannes IV reaches Shewa, it took the most powerful king of the time, Menelik of Shewa, no time to declare himself "king of kings of Abyssinia." By then, the southern Oromo were being attacked from the center from Shewa by Menelik and from the northwest from Gojjam by Tekle Haimanot. The Northern Oromo of Yajjuu, Walloo, and Raayyaa's power was under Abyssinia's control with fading resistances

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only in pocket strongholds. The resistance of the Tuulamaa and Maccaa Oromo had been broken. He had subdued most of the central and western regions of the Oromo country. The Arsii were facing an enormous war campaign from the warlords of Menelik. He had occupied the ancient city of Harar. In this background, the new Atse Menelik II emerged as the most potent monarch to declare himself “king of kings” in the history of Abyssinia.

Eastern Oromo and Egyptian Occupation of Harar

During the reign of Atse Yohannes IV, the Oromo were under attack from several fronts. While the rest of the Oromo were being attacked by Abyssinian military expeditions and imperial war campaigns from multiple directions from the west across Blue Nile River from Gojjam, from the centre in several directions from Entoto [ent’ot’o:] (Shewa) and from farther north in Wollo, the eastern Oromo was facing a different type of attack. Here, they were facing threats from expanding Turkish and Egyptian contending powers to occupy them and the city-state of Harar.

Harar was a multinational commercial city-state surrounded and protected by the Oromo, whom its citizens (Geyusu) swindled constantly for a living. The enfeebled town maintained its autonomy from the near and distant forces thanks to the tolerance and fierce defence of the Oromo, respectively. Richard Burton (1856 [2012]), who visited the city in the 1850s, observed: “[“The Oromo] would oppose an invader with a strong force of spearmen, the approaches to the city are difficult and dangerous, but it is commanded from the north and west, and the walls would crumble at the touch of a six-pounder. Three hundred Arabs and two galloper guns would take Harar in an hour.” Yet, “its citizens live, like those of Zayla, by systematically defrauding [the Oromo], and the Amir has made it a penal offence to buy by weight and scale” (Chap. VIII, Ten days at Harar)

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The Egyptians occupying an army of 1200 strong led by Muhammad Rauf Pasha, disguised as a scientific expedition, occupied Harar on 11 October 1875 (Trimingham, 1965; Zewde, 2001). The Eastern Oromo had the Walled City under check and control from the mid-16th century until 1875. The walled city had a friendly relationship with the Ottoman Empire since the 16th century, where the latter extended remote and faint protection until 1818. The occupying Egyptian army had no resistance on its travel from Zeila to Harar except from the Oromo, who resisted the invasion and denied the Egyptians to expand and occupy more districts outside of Harar City (Rubenson, 1976, p. 317). After the occupation, the Oromo could cut off the Egyptians from Zeila. As a result, Harar became a separate province with no connection to the coast in late 1878. The Egyptians were forced to increase the number of their troops to over 3,400 “due to threats from the hostile Oromo surrounding the city” (Dill, 1991, pp. 28–29). According to Reclus (1892, p. 202), the occupying force was between four and five thousand. Regardless of their number and discipline, the Oromo warriors fought the Egyptian army, who were equipped with firearms only with swords and daggers, and they “occasionally put them to flight” (Reclus, 1890, p. 401).

The resistance of the Oromo against the Egyptians brought similar disaster to the Oromo and the Geyusu. The Egyptians waged multiple war campaigns on the Ituu and Hubannaa Oromo in the east during their occupation of the walled city of Harar. The Ituu and Hubannaa Oromo gracefully resisted the Egyptian invasion for years without succumbing to the battle fatigues. Nevertheless, they were defeated mainly owing to the superiority of the Egyptian firearms over their spears, swords, and arrows. The eastern Oromo of Harar district, in general, refused to accept foreign Egyptians as masters, and the Egyptian officials were reduced to only tax collectors (Reclus, 1890, p. 401). Even though the Oromo cut off the city from the coastal region in 1878, the occupation significantly weakened the eastern Oromo’s

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military, institutional, and political power. The Egyptian army further exhausted the Oromo by oppression and plunder (Reclus, 1892, p. 202). The devastation was not very much different for the people who inhabited the walled city: they lost their independence, the population dwindled, and much of their property was lost (Reclus, 1892, pp. 203-204).

Out of the defeat, great humiliation came to the Ituu and Hubannaa. Instead of facing the humiliation, some preferred death:

The Oromo of the region had tried to resist the invaders, but after various fights in which their primitive lances were of little avail against the firearms of the Egyptians, they had to submit. The Egyptians managed to decoy their chiefs into Harar and threw them into prison, then forced them to dissolve their parliament, deliver their abba Bokku [Abbaa Bokkuu], cut off their unfurl or long hair, and submit to circumcision. A significant number proffered to be killed rather than be thus humiliated, but after three or four years, they were reduced to such misery that the majority submitted. (J. S. Trimmingham, 1963, quoted in Bokku, 2011, p. 68)

The defeat of the eastern Oromo by the Egyptians exposed them to forceful submission to Islam and the expansion of the Somali into their territories. In the process, Egyptians empowered their co-religious Somalis. The Somalis occupied the region north of the Harar Mountains during this time. The Oromo were “obliged to abandon their fertile plains and settled habitations” due to Somali aggression (Reclus, 1890, p. 400). During the occupation, the Egyptians made large-scale Islamization of the Oromo their primary goal. For this purpose, religious educators and preachers were sent out to the Oromo with the goal of mass conversion. Several Mosques were built, and in areas where there was resistance to conversion, the Oromo were forcibly converted and became Muslims abandoning

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Waaqeffannaa. The Egyptians were able to convert the prisoner Abbaa Gadaas to Islam. One such convert was Orfo Jilo Biko of Afran Qalloo Oromo, the last elected Abbaa Gadaa in 1872 (Hassen, 2008, p. 45) who had resisted the Egyptian occupation of Harar as one of the commanders of the Oromo army that was eventually defeated by the terror of howitzer cannons and rocket, which were owned only by the Egyptian military.

The Egyptians used Orfo Jilo to convert the Oromo to Islam in a similar way that Atse Menelik used Gobana to subdue the Oromo.

After converting their famous prisoner, Orfo Jilo, to Islam, the Egyptians gave him the name of Umar. They restored him to power in the Gara Mulata area located about 60 to 90 kilometres southwest of Harar, not as the president of African also coffee assembly but as an agent of the Egyptian colonial administration. (Mohammed Hasen, 1990, quoted in Bokku, 2011, p. 68)

Orfo Jilo became an ardent campaigner for the Islamization of the Oromo. His devotion to his new religion, Islam, could not let him have regard for his earlier faith of Waaqeffannaa, nor did he any more have respect for the noble Gadaa Government. He became the instrument for the Egyptian project of Islamization and the face of colonial rule of the Oromo in the east.

After his conversion, Orfo became the main instrument for the Egyptian proselytisation, particularly in the Gara Mulata area. He punished or confiscated the property of those who did not observe the Muslim prayer. To this day, people literally say, ‘Salata Orfo soda cotton Allahu Akibar’. ‘Orfo’s prayer for the fear of the axe: Allah is great.’ (Mohammed Hassen, 1990, quoted in Bokku, 2011, p. 68)

In late 1884, the Egyptians left Harar after a decade of occupation because of the Mahdist threat. Great Britain hesitated to occupy the city but became its protectorate for some

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years while Ali Abd ash-Shakur was installed as its governor. The Oromo were weakened during the decade not only because of the destruction of their Gadaa System but also because of the intensive Islamization projects. This created a superpower vacuum in Harar. The Egyptians left Harar in 1885.

In the subsequent years (from 1885–1887), Amir Abdallahi attempted to rule Harar as an independent city-state under a loose British protectorate. Great Britain had just occupied Egypt. However, in 1886, Nigus Menelik of Shewa decided to settle Harar by force following the 1884 Hewett Treaty signed between Atse Yohannes IV, Egypt, and Great Britain. The British ceded the walled city to Nigus Menelik in exchange for Atse Yonannes IV's assistance against the Sudan Mahdist forces. The assistance was needed, as mentioned above, to rescue the Egyptian forces trapped in Sudan through northern Abyssinia. Atse Yohannes IV was pleased that Nigus Menelik would annex Harar and his empire would continue to expand.

This was an opportunity for Menelik to add one more historical territory, however small, to his expanding empire of Shewa. Immediately after the Egyptians had left, Menelik of Shewa had started planning to take the city since. For his campaign of 1886-7, Menelik first sent Aleka Atsme Giorgis, future judge and councillor in Harar but later Shewan Amhara and Oromo historian, to the Harar city to collect intelligence, disguising himself as a Muslim and speaking Arabic (Zewde, 2002, p. 65). After some preparation, he marched on Harar following the refusal of Amir Abdullahi and the eastern Oromo to submit peacefully. He, however, faced resistance from the combined force of the Amir of the city-state (which included some Somali) and the eastern Oromo at the battle of Calanqoo in January 1887. Menelik was victorious after the massacre of thousands of people. He occupied Harar with a punitive expedition (Trimingham, 1952, p. 129). After the battle of Calanqoo, Harar city and its immediate surroundings became part of the territories of the kingdom of Abyssinia.

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The Turko–Egyptian and Adare [a:dere:] alliance against the Oromo (Jalata, 2005) would finally be replaced by the more conniving Abyssinia and Adare alliance. This would make the lousy self-identification and self-governance situation of the eastern Oromo under the former coalition worse with the looming total conquest of the Oromo by Atse Menelik II that would fundamentally change their identity, culture, and traditional Gadaa democracy. Just a few years before the conquest of Harar by Menelik of Shewa, Reclus (1890) recorded that, the eastern Oromo maintained their republican Gadaa government (p. 401) even though Menelik of Shewa had already conquered some of them who inhabit the region west of Harar highland and east of Shewan plateau.

Based on his limited understanding at the time, Reclus explains the functioning of the republican Gadaa government among the eastern Oromo extensively:

The community is organised on republican principles. The administration of the commune is invariably entrusted to a council of elders [Gadaa Council], whose *moti* [Mootii], or president [Abbaa Gadaa], is charged with the executive functions. With him are associated the treasurer [Abbaa Horii], the high priest [Qaalluu], and the *boku* or director of the general assembly [Abbaa Bokkuu], these ministers-being usually chosen [elected] for a period of eight years. The director or “speaker,” [Abbaa Bokkuu] who presides over the public discussions, holding a wooden mace as the sign of his office, is required to keep the debate open until absolute unanimity is arrived at. All have the right of veto, as in the old Polish Diet, and the consequence is that the deliberations are frequently continued from session to session, the principle of “closure” not having yet been introduced. But once a final decision is reached, the question assumes a sacred character. The forefathers of the tribe [ancient Moieties] are invoked, and in their honour is immolated a

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spotless steer; the boku [Abbaa Bokkuu] imbues his wand with the blood, and the priests [Qaalluu], coiling the entrails [caula fat] round their neck and arms, traverse the land, proclaiming to all the people the resolutions [decisions, new laws, amendments to the law] taken by the national assembly. (Reclus, 1890, p. 401–402)

This well-known French geographer also recorded gleams of how the foreign relations of the Gadaa government worked.

[S]pecial functionaries are despatched [sic] along the caravan routes, in order to gather from foreign traders' tidings of the outer world. Nothing escapes the ears of these public agents which may in any way interest the members of their community. Like the old Greek euxenoi, they are also required to represent the citizens with all strangers, to introduce them into the villages and offer them the bowl of milk, a symbol of hospitality. One of the elders [Abbaa Bokkuu or Abbaa Gadaa or Qaalluu] is also required, by way of blessing, to expectorate after the Masai fashion three times on the clothes of the stranger. (Reclus, 1890, p. 402)

The conquest of Harar by Nigus Menelik of Shewa began the end of the freedom and the republican Gadaa government of the eastern Oromo.

The Oromo and Atse Menelik II: “Unification” of Abyssinia and Colonization of the Oromo

The conquest of the Oromo was multi-phased and multi-directional and involved bloody wars and peaceful submissions. Pankhurst (1989) explains the expansion of Shewa into Oromo territories under the Asfa Wassan and his son and his grandson. The initial attempts by the Shewan rulers to conquer the neighbouring Oromo started in earnest. The

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Amharan Shewa begun to attack the Tuulamaa Oromo under the leadership of Asfa Wassan (1775-1808) (pp. 378-379). Asfa Wassan (boundary (frontier) expander) had fought with the Oromo to take some land. Wassan Saggad (1808-1813), son of Asfa Wassan, also had conducted expeditions against the Tuulamaa Oromo in the northwest and, in collaboration with Ras Walda Selassie of Tigreé, against the Walloo and Yajjuu Oromo in the north. Sahle Selassie (1813–1847), son of Wassan Saggad (literally, the frontier kneels), incorporated Angolola, which was recently taken from the Oromo, into this province of Shewa over which he appointed himself Nigus, king. Nigus Sahle Selassie, though he soon established a dynastic marriage with the Oromo and the Muslims, continued to conduct an expedition to the surrounding Oromo country.

However, the first phase of the formal conquest of the central Oromo started during the reign of Nigus Hayle Malakot (r. 1847–1855) of Shewa. Hayle Malakot faced a massive revolt from the Oromo (Pankhurst, 1989, p. 382). During his father's reign, the insignificant enclave of Shewa had expanded tremendously with the gradual takeover of land from the neighbouring Oromo country. Because of the dynastic marriage and forced incorporation, large Oromo communities had fallen under the loose political control of the Shewan monarchy. Using these backgrounds as momentous beginning Hayle Malakot pushed further into the Oromo country. He, however, met with fierce resistance that denied him gaining any significant territory.

The second phase of the conquest of the Oromo was from 1864-1889. This was when Nigus Menelik (1864-1889) was the only king of Shewa. Around the middle of the reign of Atse Yohannes IV, Nigus Menelik's military power was amplified tremendously. He commanded an organised permanent troop of about a thousand riflemen and about a hundredfold "warriors and plunderers" that swelled his expedition to a hundred thousand

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persons (Reclus, 1892, 215). Employing this increased power, he continued the conquest of the Oromo. He focused his conquest on the Maccaa, Tuulamaa, Arsii, and Walloo Oromo before he became Atse. During this second phase of the conquest, Menelik conquered about half of the Oromo country in the territory that would become modern Ethiopia. Shewa, Wollo, Guma, Gomma, Limmu, Gera, Enarya, Harargie, Macha, part of Wallagga, and Arsi fell under his control during this time. This was a massive addition of territories to the kingdom of Shewa. At the same time, the Oromo faced attacks from the east and the northwest. Nigus Tekle Haimanot of Gojjam waged war on the Maccaa Oromo in the districts south of Gojjam. The two vassals of Atse Yohannes IV were executing the Abyssinian expansion program with the full approval and support of the Atse. They were scrambling on the southwestern territory of the Oromo. Towards the end of the reign of Atse Yohannes IV, the dominion of both the Kingdom of Shewa and the Kingdom of Gojjam he expanded three-fold (Reclus, 1892, p. 184). Similarly, as discussed above, the eastern Oromo around Harar were under attack by the Egyptian occupying force, the Turks, and the British during this second phase of Abyssinian conquest.

Table 5: Some Oromo Territories and Year or Duration of Their Conquest

Kingdom/Region/ Territory	Year/Duration of Conquest
Shewa	1865
Jimma	1882
Borena, Gurafarda	1897
Bako	1898
Walloo	1867–1876
Gumaa	1878–1882
Gommaa	1878–1887
Limu–Enariya, Gera	1879–1887
Tuulamaa (Shewa)	1879–1882
Maccaa, Wallagga, Arsii	1882–1886
Ituu–Harar	1885–1887

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Note. They are compiled from Edward Hamilton (*The Wars in Abyssinia: A brief military history*. London; The Unicorn Press, 1936), and Lapiso G. Delebo (አትዮጵያ የገባር ሥርዓትና ጅምር ካፒታሊዝም: 1900–1966: ሁለተኛ መጽሐፍ: አዲስ አበባ, 1990. (Table 9, p. 94)).

The third phase of the conquest of the Oromo continued after Nigus Menelik became Atse of the kingdom of Abyssinia (1889-1913). During Atse Yohannes IV's reign, Nigus Menelik had grown so powerful militarily and in political influence, including in foreign relations. There was no other apparent contender to the Abyssinian throne. Immediately upon the death of Atse Yohannes IV, Nigus Menelik of Shewa declared himself “king of kings” of Abyssinia. Because he had already grown powerful enough to challenge the Atse, there was little resistance to his claim to the throne of Abyssinia. After becoming Atse, Menelik II focused most of his energy on the unification of Abyssinia. He unified Abyssinia (i.e. Tigre, Begemeder, Lasta, and Gojjam) and Shewa under his leadership by overcoming some local commotions in Tigre and Begemeder. After all the regional kings had submitted to him as their sovereign, Atse Menelik II sanctioned the king of Gojjam, Nigus Tekle Haimanot, to conquer the kingdom of Kaffa. Then, he embarked on conquering the rest of the Oromo and other nations, nationalities, and peoples to the kingdom's south, southwest, and southeast. During this phase, Atse Menelik was able to conquer the southern Booranaa Oromo and the remainder of the southwestern Maccaa Oromoo. For example, the Oromo of Borena, Gurafardaa, and Bakko regions were conquered during this third phase.

During these three phases of the conquest of the Oromo and other nations by the kingdom of Abyssinia, the kingdom enjoyed both peaceful submissions and battle triumphs. Kingdoms of Jimmaa, Leeqaa Qeellam, Leeqaa Naqamtee, and Iluu Abbaa Booraa submitted peacefully after reaching settlements where the Mootiis could rule their kingdom but pay tribute to the kingdom. In so doing, the Mootiis saved the massacre of tens of thousands of

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Oromo. However, they encouraged the enemy on those Oromo who resisted the conquest with arms. The Maccaa and Tuulamaa Oromo of central Oromia (Shewa), and Oromo of Arsi, Harar, and Borana were conquered after fierce resistance. Hundreds of thousands of Oromo were killed in every expedition during the three-decades-long resistance of the Oromo. Figure 8 illustrates the gradual conquest of the Oromo and other nations, nationalities, and peoples in modern Ethiopia by the kingdom of Abyssinia from the late 19th to early 20th century.

Menelik expanded Abyssinia Proper tremendously. Just before Nigus Menelik became Atse in 1889, the territory of the kingdom of Abyssinia—Abyssinia proper and Shewa combined—was less than half of France (Reclus, 1892, p. 124). With the conquest of the vast Oromo country and its south-western “natural geographical dependencies” and eastern “ancient political dependencies” of the kingdom (Reclus, 1892, p. 124), by the end of the century, Atse Menelik had expanded his kingdom four times. He made it almost twice as big as France. The Oromo country constituted close to one-half of the territory that would become modern Ethiopia.

“Unification” Propaganda and Oromia

The justification of the Abyssinian conquest of the Oromo and others was unification, which it was not. Even though exceedingly insignificant parts of the present Oromia State and SNNP State had been part of the Medieval Abyssinia about four centuries ago, the war of conquest of Atse Menelik II was characterised deliberately as the war of “unification” of the former Abyssinian territories. When it comes to the territory that has now become the Oromia State, the propaganda of “unification” of former Abyssinian territories (including Oromia), in conjunction with the equally absurd claim that the Oromo arrived in present central Ethiopia (Central Oromia) in the 16th century, might have convinced some Abyssinian and Western

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historians alike. The conquest was unification, which it was not. The reality is starkly different. Except for those who had been integrated into the kingdom of Abyssinia since the divisive political decisions of the frontier northern minority Oromo groups, the Oromo have since inhabited the present Oromia. They had their decentralised republican Gadaa governments under the Gadaa System until some small Oromo monarchies emerged in the Gibie region and Wallagga in the early decades of the 19th century. Those minority Oromo communities who had joined the kingdom of Abyssinia following the enthronement of Atse Susenyos in the early years of the 17th century were integrated and assimilated into Abyssinian identity. They were ruled by the monarchy, which they also had the opportunity to lead. Even so, most of the vast Oromo nation had continued to govern itself according to the Gadaa System, Gadaa Democracy, until the conquest of Atse Menelik II in the late 19th century. Wishful contradictions and asserting are common in the Abyssinian-Ethiopianist camp.

Three main factors might have awe-struck some Abyssinian Atses and elites (political, religious, and pseudo-historical) into not only presuming but also wittingly asserting that all the Oromo of the present Oromia had been part of the kingdom of Abyssinia at some point in time. These are the habitation of the Oromo in the provinces of Abyssinia Proper, to the north of the present Oromia State, the fact that the Oromo constituted about half of the population of Gojjam, Shewa Lasta, and Wollo, and the effect of the imaginative Portuguese sketch map of the country of Prester John in the 15th century. The first might have led to the misconception that if part of a nation was in the kingdom, the kingdom had dominion over the whole nation. The second might have continued to give the false impression that the integration of the Oromo into the Abyssinian society in Abyssinia Proper was reciprocated throughout the Oromo country by integrating the Abyssinian peoples before the settler

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colonisation of the late 19th century. The last, though utterly wrong, might have profoundly affected the concept of the ancient dominion of Abyssinia. The sketch map attributed absurdly not only modern Ethiopia but also the whole region that includes present Burundi, Djibouti, Eastern Sudan, Eritrea, Kenya, Malawi, northern Mozambique, eastern DRC Congo, Rwanda, Somalia, South Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, and Zimbabwe to the dominion of Prester John by confusing Lake Tana with Lake Victoria. It is located, among others, in Shewa, Gojjam, Quara far below the Equator and, Amhara on the Equator, and Tigrai in the region where the Central Africa Republic is now. Of course, there was no Lake Victoria on the map; Lake Tana was in the place of Lake Victoria. This absurdity has deluded some uninformed Abyssinians, their Atses and dabtaras included, to claim that the kingdom once had such a vast domain that included the country of the Oromo. These misconceived factors might have fuelled the baseless “unification” propaganda.

However, the fact is different. Almost all the Oromo who have inhabited the region that has now become the present Oromia had never been a fully integrated part of the kingdom of Abyssinia. The Oromo in this region governed themselves according to their republican Gadaa System at least since the mid-16th century until some trifling Oromo monarchies started to emerge in the western and southwestern Oromia in the early 19th century. This was after the minority frontier Oromo, who had become part of the Abyssinian kingdom (to the north of Oromia) after the historic political decision in the early 17th century that divided the Oromo and had settled in most of the Zones of the present Amhara State and Southern Zone of Tigray States had become politically dominant in the kingdom. These frontier Oromo gradually developed political influence in the Abyssinian kingdom. In the mid-18th century, the Yajjuu Oromo Dynasty was ruling Abyssinia. Abyssinian remained

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under the northern minority Oromo rule effectively from the mid-18th to the mid-19th century.

The Oromo of Oromia started to become part of the expanding kingdom of Abyssinia after the beginning of the expansion of the kingdom of Shewa into the territories of the Tuulamaa Oromo of central Oromia, in the present North Shewa Zone of Oromia, under Nigus Menelik in the 1870s. The Oromo of Oromia became part of the kingdom of Abyssinia during the reign of Atse Menelik II in the last decades of the 19th century. After the conquest of Oromia, Atse Menelik II and his comforter Abyssinian elites tried to characterise the war of conquest of the Oromo and other nations as the war of “unification” of former territories. This claim was based on a misconception that the frontier minority Oromo communities had already been not only part of the kingdom of Abyssinia since the beginning of the 17th century but also had been its masters until a few decades earlier. However, it was well known that these Oromo were a minority and never stood for the whole Oromo nation. The rest of the Oromo nation estranged these minorities for abandoning the Gadaa System and becoming dependents in the kingdom.

The historical fact that the kingdom had expanded to the present central Oromia region in the late 15th and early 16th centuries and had established some satellite military colonies as far south as Lake Zway before the conquest of Ahmad Gragn in the early 16th century, they were expounded to political propaganda to create a new historical narrative. The narrative was that the present central Oromia and its adjacent territories had been a historic part of the kingdom of Abyssinia.

However, the narrative was partly true: only four centuries ago, only for a brief period, and only for enclave territories. Because as observed by Jesuit missionaries who had converted the kingdom to Roman Catholicism in the early 17th century, the Abyssinian army

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traditionally “take their wives and children with them, and the camp hath its streets, its market places, its churches, courts of justice, judges, and civil officers” (Lobo, 1887 [2007], Part II, Chap. VI). Once the army is stationed, the camps soon appear to be formal residence towns where its inhabitants become a forceful burden for their subsistence on the people, and, hence, quickly turn into a centre of a military colony. Some enclaves in central Oromia had been taken from the Oromo, in particular, by these military colonies during the 13th and 16th centuries. The Oromo reclaimed these former satellite Abyssinian colonies, which were settled by its resident armies, during their offensive-defensive struggle in the 16th century. By the end of the 19th century, they had been part of the more excellent Oromo country for nearly four hundred years. Thus, the narrative has no historical or pragmatic merits but serves only as decisive political propaganda.

The narrative was intended to serve two purposes: as the foundation for laying claim to the territories in the Horn of Africa region in competition to the European scramble for Africa and to justify the war of aggression of Abyssinia against the Oromo and other nations. No doubt that it served its first intended purpose very well. It has also gone far enough in its second intended purpose. However, it has failed as an overall strategy because propaganda may help change perceptions, but it does not have the power to change facts. The nation, nationalities and peoples colonized by the kingdom have histories that have not recorded their unity with Abyssinia before their conquest.

The propagandist narrative of the unification of former territories not only created fixations among its proponents but also has remained a disdainful wildflower in the genuine history of the peoples of modern Ethiopia. There have always been people who chose consciously not to be persuaded by the reality of settler colonisation than the “unification” indoctrination. To date, some Abyssinian political and historical elites are fixated on the mix

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of the propaganda that created the pseudo-history of the kingdom and have remained ardent proponents of this narrative. The reality, however, has been apparent. The mainstream Oromo of Oromia, unlike the frontier minority Oromo who have been wholly and partly assimilated in the present Amhara and the Tigray States, had not been part of the Abyssinian kingdom until the reign of Atse Menelik II. Except for frontier petty Oromo communities, they had been independent but highly decentralised Gadaa republics. They had been governing themselves according to their Gadaa System and excessively decentralized Gadaa governments. They were republican confederacies. The pretext that was used for the justification of the settler-colonial campaigns of Atse Menelik II in the present Oromia, SNNP, Gambella, Benishangul-Gumuz, Somali, Harari, and Afar States that has entered the “Ethiopian History” narrative since then, has remained to be a harmful historical weed to the genuine history of the multinational Ethiopia of the 21st century.

Defeat of the Oromo and Rise of Abyssinian Empire

Before their conquest by Atse Menelik II, the Oromo people, except those who were integrated to the kingdom of Abyssinia and those who had formed Mootiis, were independent, democratic, and accommodating to other people’s living among them and neighboring them. They were organized effectively politically using their egalitarian and republican government “to promote their well-being and to maintain their security and sovereignty” (Jalata, 2012, p. 126).

As early as the late 1860s, the northern Tuulamaa (north of Finfinnee (Addis Ababa)) were deceived by their hopeful leader, Gobana Dachi (1821–1889), better known as Gobana. Gobana was born from his Oromo father and Amhara mother. His parents were Christian, and he preferred the Christian language, Amharic, over Afaan Oromoo due to heavy influence of Amharization in his family (Hassen, 1981 cited in Jalata, 2005, p. 71). However, he had

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collected strong Oromo warriors and had become one of the most feared leaders in Shewa. He had opposed Atse Tewodros II because of his anti-Oromo policies and had killed some of Atse Yohannes IV's soldiers who ventured into his stronghold (Jalata, 2005, p. 71). Lured with the prospect of becoming Ras under the self-declared Nigus of Shewa, Menelik, Gobana submitted to the new Nigus betraying the hopes and aspirations of the Tuulamaa Oromo.

The Tuulamaa Oromo had hope of getting back the Oromo who had become part of the Christian kingdom and the aspiration of restoring the unity of the Oromo. As they occupied the territory between Shewa and the kingdom of Abyssinia at the time the Abyssinian Atses were vying to reunite Shewa, a cut-off proxy of the kingdom, with Abyssinia Proper, their immediate objective was to remain independent. To do so, they had to defend themselves from the expansion of the Abyssinian kingdom under Atse Yohannes IV from the north through the territories of the Walloo Oromo on one hand and from the expansion of Shewa, under its new ambitious ruler, Nigus Menelik, from the southeast on the other hand. Despite their hope and aspiration and their immediate need to maintain their independence, their leader submitted voluntarily to Nigus Menelik of Shewa for a motivation that has remained unclear after the latter had declared himself Nigus (king) of Shewa.

Gobana not only suddenly yielded but also would help Nigus Menelik (later Atse) to conquer the rest of the Oromo nation. Through his voluntary submission, he placed the northern Tuulamaa Oromo under Menelik. The unprepared Abbichuu Oromo of northern Tuulamaa, whom Gobana had maintained Abyssinian style feudal lordship over them, had no better alternative but to become part of the then expanding kingdom of Shewa. Gobana also subdued several rising Oromo war chiefs (Abbaa Duulaas) who had begun competing with the elected Abbaa Gadaas for power as per the Oromo republicanism (Baisa, 2004, p. 116). Gobana forced such Oromo chiefs, namely, "Changare Soddise of Bacho, Biratu Gole of

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Metta, Banti Mannie of Sullo and Amaya, Merga Gobana of Chalia, Tufa Munna of Sululta” to submit to Menelik (Baissa, 2004, p. 116). He was conferred the highest title, Ras, by Negus Menelik in 1878. He became the second most powerful man in the kingdom of Shewa next to the king. By all intents and purposes, he had become an Abyssinian aristocrat. As such, he served with full dedication as war general in the subsequent campaigns of Menelik against his own people and other nations. He would secure for Menelik the submission of all the Maccaa Oromo of West Oromia. Personally, Ras Gobana might have felt that he had transformed himself into Abyssinian identity and that his fellow Tuulamaa Oromo should do so.

Gobana became the greatest traitor to the Oromo but the decisive “instrument” of Menelik II to pain the Oromo so greatly. Soon after his submission, he campaigned against the southern Tuulamaa (south of Finfinnee) and broke their defense making it possible for the Amharans to access freely Awash River for the first time. The fellow Tuulamaa Oromo, who decided to follow Gobana and became part of the kingdom of Shewa, fought against the Maccaa Oromo who chose to remain independent. He became the scorn of infighting and caused further division within and between the Maccaa and Tuulamaa Oromo. He became the centre of Menelik’s strategy of turning the Oromo against each other. He succeeded: the Oromo were divided, and some communities fought with each other. In doing so, the Oromo weakened themselves. This was Nigus Menelik’s strategy at work. The only Abyssinian strategy that has ever worked against the Oromo, starting from the reign of Atse Susenyos (r. 1607–1632), has been dividing and weakening the Oromo by turning one Oromo lineage group or community against the other.

Gobana also played a significant role in subduing other southern nations and nationalities and their kingdoms for his master, Nigus Menelik, later Atse Menelik II. A

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Russian volunteer in the army of Menelik II towards the end of the 19th century, Alexander Bulatovich, explains what Gobana had achieved for Menelik:

He conquered for Menelik all the [Oromo] lands to the west from Entotto [near Addis Ababa (Finfinnee)] to Beni-Shangul and to the southwest to the River Baro, to the east and south together with the Emperor he conquered Harar, Arussi [Arsi] and Guragye (Bulatovich, 1897[1971], History of Ethiopia).

Though Gobana had submitted to Menelik and paid tribute, he worked independently for Menelik with asserted authority and accumulated wealth. The power of Gobana, when he was *Ras* of Nigus Menelik, is evident from his own words. In his letter to his master on the eve of the Battle of Embabo, where he was victorious, Gobana made clear his influence and power. With such power and wealth, there is no doubt that Gobana not only played a crucial role in breaking the Oromo and other southern nations and nationalities but also shared the aspiration of Menelik to build an empire carved from the vast region of the Horn of Africa in competition with the European colonisers. After Menelik had become Atse in 1889, the wisdom, brutality, and bravery of Gobana only increased. He became the single most respected war general. The following Amharic folk verse coined following his death stands as testimony to his greatness. It goes, የሚሰጡት ቢያጡ ከድፍን አበሻ፣ ለዐ-ራ-ዔል ሰጡት የጎበኘን ጋሻ. It means, “Because they could not find a successor to Gobana from among Abyssinians, they gave his shield to the church of Archangel St. Uriel.” Gobana held the pinnacle of bravery and military power from among the generals of Atse Menelik II.

After thirty-two years of protracted war (1868–1898), by the end of the 19th century, Atse Menelik II had conquered the whole Oromo land in the present Ethiopian Federation (see Table 5) and destroyed the unity of the Oromo polity with the help of Ras Gobana and

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other Oromo leaders. He conquered Wollo during 1867-77, Liiban, Gullallee, Yaayyaa, Meettaa, Wacacaa from 1868–1878, Tuulamaa, Maccaa, Gommaa, Jimmaa, Limmuu, Geeraa, during 1881-82, Arsi during 1882-1886, Ituu and Wallagga in 1886, Harargie and Iluu Abba Booraa in 1887, Bale in 1891, Booranaa during 1896-1897, and the remaining Oromo land after 1898 onwards (see the invasion route on the illustration by Melbaa (1988, Map 8, p. 61)). In some cases, like in the kingdoms of Jimma, Leeqaa–Naqamtee, and Leeqaa–Qeellam, the Oromo resistance to the brutal Gobana/Abyssinian territorial annexation and subjugation were negotiated finally with Atse Menelik II. The negotiation allowed the kingdoms to retain some autonomy and remain in relative peace after they had acknowledged Atse Menelik II as ‘king of kings’ by subordination and their membership in the new empire employing paying tributes. It is highly likely that by design of the enemy, the Oromo ultimately “split into more than eighty politically independent groups of various sizes” (Haberland, 1992, p. 717). In the end, all the Oromo in modern Ethiopia became highly fragmented and wanted any aspiration of continued resistance or regaining meaningful political unity.

As Atsme Giorgis correctly noted, only Atse Menelik II defeated the Oromo. He remarks, “Even though the Amhara and [the Oromo] fought for 400 years, none of the kings, except Atse Menelik, succeeded in subjugating [the Oromo]” (Tafla, 1987, p. 601).

Nonetheless, there are several reasons why Atse Menelik II successfully conquered the great Oromo nation so fast and, in most cases, so quickly. These include:

Excessive decentralisation of the Gadaa government and Caffees and the decline of the unifying power of the Gadaa System that had resulted in the formation of some Oromo monarchies (Mootiis)

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Internal social divisions among the Oromo, both at sub-moiety, junior sub-moiety, and clan levels, that led to destructive competitions, conflicts, and armed clashes among them, making them vulnerable to external strategic attacks.

Multi-front wars: first with Turko–Egyptian and Adare alliance and then with Abyssinian and Adare alliance in the east; with Mahdist and the people of Benishangul and Gumuz in the west; with Abyssinians first in north Shewa and in Wollo in the north and then in South Shewa, West Shewa, in Wallagga and Gibie regions, in Arsi and Bale in the Oromo heartland, and finally in Boorana in the Oromo heartlands; with British Colonial expansion in the south; and with some of the peoples of the present SNNP from the center

The European colonial support to Abyssinia included support in arms and ammunition, military strategy and training, and diplomatic backing, all done competitively by Great Britain, France, and Italy, who could not lose the strategic cooperation of the kingdom to one another both for their “spheres of influence” at the time and for their strategic preparation for their hopes to take over the territories of the kingdom for themselves in case the kingdom collapses

Lack of modern firearms: Compared to Atse Menelik II, who received 715,000 rifles and 50,000,000 ammunition from European powers during 1868-1900, the Oromo had their traditional weapons; and perhaps an insignificant number of outmoded firearms

The devastations of the “Great Famine” not only killed most of the cattle that the Oromo depended on for most of their subsistence but also forced them to move, allowing the Abyssinians to take parts of southern Oromia freely in search of pastures instead of continuing the battle of resistance.

Lack of modern political organisation and administrative structure to effectively organise the fragmented and dispersed resistance struggles.

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The death of an estimated five million, half of the Oromo population, during the resistance struggle, no doubt, not only deprived the Oromo of fighting forces but also sent a reverberating shock across the Oromo country that probably forced some Oromo resistance groups, particularly those which had established Mootiis, to submit to the Abyssinian warlords without armed resistance.

The Empire of Abyssinian was formed at the end of the 19th century after the subjugation of the Oromo and other nations, nationalities, and peoples who constituted more than three-fourths of the population. The Oromo, whom Martial de Salviac described as a nation who “do not know bowing and prostration; this free people do not bend in front of anyone” (de Salviac, 2005, quoted in Hassen, 2008, p. 43), succumbed to barbaric aggression of kingdom of Abyssinia in few decades. The Oromo were the most significant nation that Atse Menelik had conquered.

Conquering the Oromo was destroying all the nations, nationalities, and peoples that would constitute Ethiopia. Atse Menelik must have known that he would build his dream empire only if he had conquered the Oromo. Adding the Gadaa republican Oromo (Maccaa, Tuulamaa, Gujii, Booranaa, Karrayyuu, Arsii, Baalee, and eastern Oromo of Ituu, Alaa, Noolee, Baabbillee, Jaarsoo, Aniyaa, etc.), the Mootiis of Gibie (Jimma, Gommaa, Gumaa, Limmuu, Geeraa), and the Wallagga (Qeellam, Naqamtee, Arjoo, Sadii, Galaan, Garjaa, Gidaamii, and Sibuu) to the already assimilated northern Oromo (Walloo, Yajjuu, Raayyaa, Asaboo, the Maccaa and Tuulamaa Oromo in Gojjam, Dembia, and Begemededer), he must have believed, the conquests would make a great empire. Also, it was evident that the Oromo occupied the central region to which he had just laid a competitive claim in the European scramble for Africa. He had laid a daring claim to the whole area between the Red Sea and the source of the White Nile in his circular letter to European powers in 1891.

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The claim must have been based on the imaginative Portuguese sketch map of the country of Prester John in the 15th century that locates almost half of modern Ethiopia, including Shewa, Gojjam, Damot, Quara, to the south of Equator and confuses Lake Tana with Lake Victoria and confuses its reader by that much. The map was a product of the sketcher's imagination of the legendary vast Christian kingdom of Prester John, which was later accepted for the Christian kingdom of Abyssinia, where some known names of Abyssinian districts of the time were plotted all over the African sketch map. Yet, it served Atse Menelik II as the pretext for claiming territory. Even today, it finds some naïve people to take it up in false impression for their futile attempt to defend Atse Menelik's conquest of the south, southwest, and southeast as a unification of former Abyssinian territories.

In the letter, among others, Atse Menelik II stated, "I have no intention at all of being an indifferent spectator if the distant Powers hold the idea of dividing up Africa" (Menelik II quoted in Boahen, 1985, p. 4; 1987, p. 25). By then, the Oromo country had been well known for its natural endowments in Europe, and it had become their aspiration for settlement. Krapf had wished it for Europeans (Krapf, 1842, quoted in Jalata, 2005, p. 3), while de Salviac called it a 'garden without boundary.' (de Salviac, 1901[2005], quoted in Jalata, 2011a, p. 11; 2011b, p. 42; 2012, p. 128; 2013, p. 26). Menelik knew that such a 'garden' would not last long in during the Colonial Era and that Europeans had already eyed it. Most importantly, he needed this 'garden without boundary,' the breadbasket of East Africa, for his mission of empire building. In other words, Oromia in the present Ethiopian federation was all that Atse Menelik II needed to build a self-sustaining great empire.

As the Oromo country and the Oromo people constituted at least one-third of both the landmass and the population of the empire from among over eighty ethnic groups, Atse Menelik II must have been sure from the start that his empire-building project was essentially

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the conquest of the Oromo. When he divided the Oromo nation strategically and tactfully and lured its relenting heroes to his side, he was sure that there would be no empire without the conquest of the Oromo. The Oromo had occupied a much larger territory than the present Oromia State at the time, and the Oromo in Abyssinia Proper (in Gojjam, Begemeder, Lasta, Tigre, Wollo, and Shewa) were not yet fully transformed into the Amhara identity to through the would-be instituted Amharan social, cultural, political, and economic hegemony. Furthermore, the Oromo heroes, though they stood on the “wrong” side of the fight and history, played a key role in the conquest of their fellow Oromo and other nations, nationalities, and peoples that have constituted the empire since then. Therefore, it may be said: first, the Oromo were at the center of the Abyssinian Empire building; second, based on the population and landmass of the Oromo in the empire, the Ethiopia Abyssinian-cum-modern Ethiopia has essentially been an Oromo empire governed by the Abyssinian monarchy until 1974. In other words, even though the Oromo were conquered in the late 19th century, modern Ethiopia has been built around the Oromo and the Oromo country by the active participation of some prominent Oromo war leaders.

As such, it may be argued that Ethiopia is principally Oromo and Oromia. It is worth remembering that, by 1914, the Oromo “were dispersed over almost one-half of Ethiopia’s territory” (Akpan, 1985, p. 715), and when the Ethiopian population was about fifty million, the Oromo were about one-half of it (Bassi, 2005, p. 3). Besides, the people of Gojjam and Wollo are majority Oromo. Not less than one-half of the people of the Amhara state have distant Oromo ancestry. The Raya people of Tigray State are undoubtedly Oromo. Harari State is a majority Oromo state. Statistically significant SNNP, Somali, Gambella, and Benishangul-Gumuz States populations are Oromo. The majority of the population of the Dire Dawa City Government is Oromo. If liberated and unmasked from over century-long

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self-denial because of the dehumanisation of the Oromo by the state, more than one-half of the population of Addis Ababa could be Oromo. Similarly, Oromia is the most essential state of Ethiopia. In terms of natural resources, Oromia is the backbone of Ethiopia. In terms of geographical location and national infrastructure networks, Oromia is the nation's only hub. Ethiopia may survive without anyone or some other states, but not without Oromia.

Institutionalisation of Settler Colonialism

The “unification” propaganda, the brute force, and the related pseudo-historical narrative worked well. By the end of the 19th century, the Oromo and other nations were conquered; freedom was lost, and Abyssinia became an Empire in the Horn of Africa region.

The Abyssinian conquest of the Oromo has devastated the Oromo nation. The Oromo, the largest of the nations, and Oromia, the largest of the present states of the Ethiopian Federation, suffered the most. During the multi-phased conquest, the Oromo population was reduced by half. The Oromo lost their land and livelihood and became serfs and enslaved people to the Abyssinian armed settlers, *nafxanyaa*. Abyssinian settlers -- vain, selfish, irritable whose soldiers live by plunder, the monks by alms, disregard of the truth their other national vice, and all the able population carrying arms (Reclus, 1892, pp. 153-154) -- have settled among the Oromo nation in the south, southeast, and southwest as the masters of the land. The settlers continued to expand and receive reinforcements from Abyssinia Proper during the reign of Atse Menelik. They were installed as landed owners and agents of the kingdom throughout the conquered Oromo country. At the end of the conquest, the *nafxanyaa-gabbar* system of settler colonialism was instituted in the Oromo country.

The Abyssinian arrogance that followed the institutionalisation of settler colonisation denied the conquered people their true Ethiopian identity and placed them in second-class citizenship. The Abyssinian noblemen and their descendants (as well as descendants of the

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nafxanyaa, government officials) and the Christian clergy adopted “the worst possible type of ‘colonial’ approach” or racial attitude towards other Ethiopians (including the Oromo) in the conquered and occupied territories (Greenfield, 1965, cited in Akpan, 1985, p. 716). They also prided themselves as retainers and sustainers of the country (Abyssinia) and the owner-builders of an Empire (Empire of Abyssinia-cum-modern Ethiopia) (Greenfield, 1965, cited in Akpan, 1985, p. 716). This approach and arrogance marginalised the non-Abyssinians and placed them in the position of the second citizen in their own country. Even the population of Ethiopia (Empire of Abyssinia] was once presented as composed of 32.2% ‘Ethiopians’ (i.e., Abyssinians (Amhara, Tigre, etc.)), 42.7% [Oromo], 10.1% Sidama, 6.0% Somali, 6.6% Negroids and Nilotes, and 2.0% Afar by some European scholars who chose to be beholden to the perspectives of the Abyssinians, the dominant group (Legesse, 2006, p. 3). Contrary to historical realities, the Abyssinians became “Ethiopians”, and the non-Abyssinians, the genuine Ethiopians, became not only “non-Ethiopians” but also colonies.

In addition to the appropriation of the name “Ethiopia” to themselves and reducing the genuine “Ethiopians” to second citizenship, the Abyssinians adopted the European colonial mentality over the genuine Ethiopians that they have just subjugated. The Abyssinian “colonial approach” was similar to that manifested by the repatriated Americo-Liberians in perceiving themselves as “civilizers” and nation builders; the attitude in both cases was comparable to the flawed “European colonial self-image of the ‘White Man’s Burden’”(Akpan, 1985, p. 716). The instrument of institutionalised settler colonialism not only deprived the Oromo, the main stock of the true Ethiopians, of their identity, culture, and land but also marginalised them from social, political, and economic participation.

These vices of the colonizers would haunt the Oromo for about a century. Through this system, the total and systemic cultural, linguistic, religious, and political dominance of

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the minority Abyssinians in the Oromo country was deeply founded. Newly imposed Abyssinian legendary nationalism replaced Oromo nationalism. These nationalisms have been competing nationalisms in the Horn of Africa region for centuries. The systemic total domination of Abyssinians continued for almost a century, destroying the very fabric of Oromo identity.

Indigenous Governance Principles and Political Economy Outcomes

To connect the historical Oromo leadership and Kushite ethics to the concepts of political economy embedded in the Gada system, I would select four governance principles that demonstrate that the Gada system is not only political, social, spiritual, and ritual but also economic. In doing so, I choose to focus on three principles: consensus-based decision-making, institutional accountability, decentralization of authority, and balanced opposition and a balanced stratified society. These four governance principles connect the Oromo Gada system, Kushite ethics, and the political economy. The findings of the study illustrate Oromo leadership tradition, which is a Gada system of governance, and the Kushite ethical foundations were not only normative or cultural systems, but also a coherent constitutional political economy. The core principles are central mechanisms through which these indigenous governance systems shape economic distribution, political stability, institutional resilience, and social and power balances in society.

A. Consensus-based decision making

Consensus-based decision-making is a constitutional principle in the Gada system. It functioned as a constraint on authority, on arbitrary authority, and this despotism.

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One of the fundamental principles of the Gada system is that every decision must be made based on consensus. There is no singular elected person who can decide on their own. A decision must be made after deliberation, and a consensus has been reached. Collective deliberation across the social strata, including age sets, Gada grades, political parties, and several councils, reduces the likelihood of unilateral extraction. Instead, it facilitates broader participation, including grassroots participation in the political choices. From a political economy perspective, this mechanism allowed for transition costs associated with conflict. I repeat, from a political economy perspective, this mechanism lowered transaction costs associated with conflict. It enhanced compliance with collective decision-making and promoted predictable law-making and rule-setting. In doing so, not only political but also economic decisions that distribute resources are made in consensus after deliberation. The economic implication was greater stability in land use, pastoral mobility, environmental protection, conflict resolution, and protection of society's well-being. This was contributing to sustained productive activities rather than episodic accumulation by ruling elites or capitalists.

B. Institutional accountability

The Gadaa System has several institutions along the age sets, which are divided into eight-year spans. And the Gada grades, which are an eight-year progression for members of the Gada party. All these institutions have elected leaders accountable to their members. This institutional accountability, enforced through fixed terms of office (maximum 8 years) and public evaluation in the form of mid-term evaluations, which could lead to impeachment and removal of the elected leader from office, and the possibility of direct removal, directly shaped the incentive structure within the Gada governance. Leaders were embedded in

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institutions that align authority with social responsibility. Personal accumulation of power or wealth is discouraged and is unacceptable to a person in a leadership position.

This contrasts sharply with extractive governance models in Western systems, in which unchecked tenure enables rent-seeking and coercive redistribution. The findings indicate that the accountability mechanisms of the Gada system enhanced institutional credibility and continuity because the institutions are owned by active participants. This reinforced trust between governing bodies and the governed. In political economy terms, this type of accountability reduced principal-agent problems and strengthened institutional stability over time, as evidenced by the Gada system's institutional stability for at least the last 500 years.

C. Decentralization of authority

The third governance principle of the Gada system is decentralization of authority across territorial and generational units. Authority and power are structured vertically and horizontally in the Gada social stratification. This prevented excessive concentration of political and economic power in one group. Every vertical group in society has its designated power and election systems with measured power and a limited time of office. Horizontally, authority is limited to a designated society, group, or geography. In this system, decision-making authority was distributed across local assemblies. This distribution allowed governance to respond to ecological variations and local economic conditions. Economic improvements are planned locally, not centrally, and planned by the people, not by external expert groups.

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This decentralized structure enabled equitable access to land and resources while preserving the Gada Council's collective oversight. The separation of these decentralized institutions during the expansion of the kingdom of Abyssinia to the South in modern Ethiopia introduced centralized extraction and administrative coercions on the indigenous system. This generated persistent center-periphery inequalities that have persisted for almost 1.5 centuries. And it has proved to be unsustainable and unattainable. The findings of this dissertation, therefore, link the decentralization of power and decision-making not only to political inclusion but also to distributive equality and long-term institutional balance in the Ethiopian state.

D. Balanced opposition and balanced social stratification

In the Gada system of governance, opposition parties are naturally balanced because membership is evenly divided across the five Gada parties. The Gada governance has five Gada parties to which all members of the Oromo polity belong. These five parties divide the society into almost five equal membership groups. Thus, one party has almost the same membership group as the other parties. In terms of resource mobilization and participation, the parties are thus balanced. And if they oppose or support each other, they are also balanced. And the parties are organized so that they take power in a cycle, one after the other, with each party having the opportunity to be in power for 8 years every 40 years. The party in power is in opposition to the party that will replace it as the next ruling party. But it is an ally with the party that will take power eight years after it. This interlinked chain of opposition and allies also creates a strong political balance. Within the same party, the party of the sons' generation and the party of the children's generation are in opposition to each other. Thus, in the same party, the fathers and the children are not allies, but political competitors in the

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same party. This itself forms a balanced opposition. In addition to balanced party opposition, the Oromo society is generally stratified into two equal halves, known as moieties. These equal halves are vertically structured in such a way that they form a balanced opposition. And this vertical balanced opposition is checked with the cross-sectional balanced opposition of the parties. In this way, the overall stratification of Oromo society politically stands as a vertical column of balanced opposition, with depth in the parties and moieties. This translates into balanced decision-making when it comes to resource allocation or economic decisions.

Thus, the balanced stratification in the Oromo society, politically, is also a balanced stratification of the political economy. This system of governance also translates into the political economy, in which resource allocations are carefully studied, debated, and decided not by a single individual but by the consensus of multiple heads of the polity. Taken together, these four governance principles demonstrate that the Oromo indigenous governance operated as a functional political economy, rather than a symbolic tradition. The replacement or displacement of this political-economic tradition by the central state in Ethiopia disrupted established mechanisms of indigenous decision-making, accountability, resource distribution, and a balanced, polycephalous form of economic decision-making. These produced structural instability in the modern Ethiopian state that has continued to shape Ethiopia's political and economic order.

The analysis of this dissertation, therefore, reframes Oromo marginalization as an institutional outcome with clear political-economic consequences, rather than as peripheral cultural marginalization.

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Summary and Conclusion

During the 17th and 18th centuries, three northern Oromo dynasties (chiefdoms) were formed in north of Ethiopia (Hassen, 1990, pp. 80, 88). These chiefdoms were, however, in no way representative of the whole Oromo. They were formed in present north-central Ethiopia by some Oromo minority groups who had willy-nilly decided to integrate with the Abyssinian kingdom a century earlier, perhaps because of their farther penetration into the territories of Abyssinia Proper of the time. Their chiefdoms/dynasties were modelled after their Abyssinian counterparts. Besides, they had symbiotic relationships with the Amhara and Tigre chiefdoms in the region. They also had strong connections with the Oromo rulers of the province of Gojjam because they were an integral part of the Abyssinian polity. These rulers had also partly integrated with the Abyssinian kingdom during these two centuries. Still, they had maintained friendly relationships with their kinsfolk in the Gadaa republican country of the Oromo, the present Oromia, across the Blue Nile in the Oromo mainland region.

In these Oromo countries that have become part of the Amhara and Tigray States, accelerated socio-cultural transformations were taking place. These Oromo communities swiftly adopted the Abyssinian culture and political system so much so that by the mid-18th century, they became dominant both in the palace and in the provincial power structure. The Yajjuu Oromo took the Abyssinian throne in Gondar and made the language of the palace Afaan Oromoo and the capital an Oromo town. The northern Oromo ruled the kingdom by installing puppet kings on the throne while they governed the kingdom as they wished throughout the Yajjuu Dynasty (1769–1855), alias Zamane Masafent. The Oromo rule of the kingdom of Abyssinia further integrated and assimilated the northern Oromo into the Abyssinian culture, language, and identity.

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In the early 19th century, more Oromo monarchies (Mootiis) were formed from among the Gadaa republican Oromo. In the Gibie region, the Oromo feudal states of Limmuu, Gumaa, Gommaa, Geeraa, and Jimmaa were included in the early 19th century (Hassen, 1990). Similarly, increasingly feudal-like states were formed in West Oromia in the second half of the century. These include Naqamtee, Arjoo, Sadii, Galaan, Garjaa, Gidaamii, and Sibuu (Gidada, 2016, p. III). These Oromo Mootiis were detached from the northern Oromo monarchies geographically and ideologically. Unlike the north of Oromo aristocracies that probably had emulated the Abyssinian system, they were formed as a result of internal evolution in connection to the weakening power of the republican Gadaa government due to excessive decentralisation and the growth of power and influence of the Abbaa Duulaas, who made themselves Mootiis (kings) against the Gadaa constitution (Gidada, 2016; Hassen, 1990). “The *moti* [Mootii] system was a historical negation to the gada [Gadaa] system in Oromia” [Emphasis in the original] (Jalata, 2005, p. 7). The Mootiis, however, did not abolish the Gadaa System totally: they continued to use it to their advantage, suppressing only its political aspect.

In the remainder of vast regions of the present Oromia, however, the Oromo continued to govern themselves with their republican Gadaa System. The power of their Gadaa System was, however, in continued decline. Also, they soon became under attack from multiple directions. Starting in 1855, northern Oromo began to suffer from the vengeful and tyrannical attacks of Atse Tewodros II. He wanted to drive the Oromo out of present-day North Ethiopia and unite his Abyssinia Proper with the run-away kingdom of Shewa. The Oromo resisted his onslaught, though at a considerable cost of life. The Walloo Queens (Mestawot and Warqitu) played a key leadership role in the resistance. The northern Oromo

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got a brief respite after the death of Atse Tewodros during the reign of Atse Tekle Giorgis II (r. 1868–1871).

Soon, however, Atse Yohannes IV launched a more systemic attack on them. The northern Oromo were forced to accept Christianity, otherwise massacred. In addition, aggressive Abyssinian expansion into the Republican Oromo territories began: The kingdom of Shewa from Central region and Gojjam from the southwest began military expeditions into the Oromo heartlands. The Walloo Oromo continued to be pressed both from the north by Atse Yohannes IV and from the south by Nigus Menelik of Shewa. In the east, the eastern Oromo fell under the attack of the expanding Turkish and the occupying Egyptian force before Menelik conquered them. The British colonial conquest had begun in the south, the Oromo country in present north Kenya. Moreover, sporadic fighting between the Oromo and resisting nations and nationalities in the current SNNP State was common. In the second half of the 19th century, the Oromo were under attack almost from every direction: “ploughed by the iron and the fire; flooded with blood and the orgy of pillage,” “the theatre of a great massacre” (De Salviac 2005 [1901], cited in Jalata, 2013, p. 26).

These multi-directional attacks on the Oromo made them highly vulnerable. More than any of the attacks, the attack from the centre by Nigus Menelik was far more devastating to the Oromo. The Oromo traditional weapons and traditional warfare could not stop Menelik, who armed his soldiers very well with up-to-date European firearms and had hundreds of thousands of standing armies. By the time he had become Atse of the kingdom in 1889, he had subdued the central Oromo country. By 1900, he had conquered all of the countries of the Oromo, which is mostly the present Oromia State and had expanded the kingdom of Abyssinia by four folds into the Empire of Abyssinia-cum-Ethiopia.

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The success of Atse Menelik II was undoubtedly the result of the failure of the Oromo resistance (diddaa gabrummaa) struggle. During the first half of the 19th century, the country of the Oromo nation, Ormania, encompassed the present Oromia State in Ethiopia, most of Kenya, eastern Uganda, south and southeast of South Sudan, southwest of Somalia, and northern Tanzania. This vast country of the Oromo has been abundantly rich in almost every aspect. In the mid-19th, the European colonialists and Abyssinian expansionists desired the riches of the Oromo country. Some missionaries, for example, Johann Ludwig Krapf, who called the country the Oromo Ormania, lamented that European enterprises were heading to America and Australia instead of Ormania and wished that the country be settled by Europeans. At the beginning of the second half of the century, the present Oromia was a land coveted by Nigus Menelik of Shewa and the Abyssinian kingdom in general. This had been the case since the kingdom had been formed. This time, however, Menelik had not only his power and determination but also the support of Great Britain, Italy, and France, the division of the Oromo, and the weakening of their Gadaa System to his aid to advance his colonial interest. In addition, he had garnered the support of some Oromo leaders who were methodically convinced by the fiddly idea of building a multinational empire in the Horn of Africa region as a counter-competition to European colonial expansion. These Oromo leaders would not only help Menelik II to subdue the Gadaa republican and the Mootii Oromo countries but also other kingdoms, States, and peoples to the south, southwest, and southeast of the kingdom of Abyssinia. After the war of conquest that was by no means less than genocide against the Oromo people, in the late 19th century, Oromia was conquered, and its surviving people, half of the population, subjugated. By the end of the century, the Oromo struggle had failed; the Abyssinian settler colonialism in most parts of Ormania, now Oromia, had begun. Most of the remainder of Ormania, the Oromo country outside of the present

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Oromia State, had been colonised by Great Britain and had become part of British East Africa.

The conquest of the Oromo and the start of settler colonialism of the Oromo country was pioneered by Atse Menelik II, but most of the work was done by his Oromo associates. Menelik expanded his Shewan kingdom and Abyssinia by conquest, mostly through the armies commanded by his noblemen (negus, beloved, ras, dajazmach, and Fitawrari) (Akpan, 1985, p. 716). Among these nobilities were Oromo, the likes of Ras Gobana Dacie, Fitawrari Habtegiorgis (Qusie) Dinagdie, and others. Atse Menelik II occupied conquered territories, including Oromia, with ‘garrison settlements’ in much the same manner as colonialists from Europe in other parts of Africa (R. Greenfield, 1965, cited in Akpan, 1985, p. 716).

After the failure of the Oromo struggle and their subsequent conquest by the Abyssinian kingdom, the Oromo were reduced to second-class citizens in the newly emerged empire. Socially and economically, the Oromo were reduced to subjects: their language and culture were despised and given inferior positions, and their land was taken from them. Because of this, most of them became servants of the *nafxagna*, and Abyssinian settler colonialism was instituted among them. Administratively, they were distributed to almost all administrative regions (Arsi, Bale, Gojjam, Harargie, Gamu Gofa, Illubabor, Kaffa, Shewa, Sidamo, Tigray, Wallaga, and Wallo) of the Empire “in order to create cultural and perceptual differences among the Oromo” in the process of “Ethiopianization” of the Oromo (Jalata, 2005, p. 185). Politically, only a few prominent Oromo individuals had key powers in the newly carved Empire of Abyssinia. Geographically speaking, the Empire of Abyssinia-cum-Ethiopia has been chiefly the country of the Oromo. This is not only because the present Oromia is the largest and the wealthiest state but also because most of the former Abyssinia Proper, most of Amhara State and part of southern Tigray State, has been inhabited by

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assimilated Oromo who could be about half of the total population. As a result, even though it was formed at the expense of the defeat of the Oromo, it is reasonable to assume that modern Ethiopia is essentially an Oromo country. Yet, the Oromo have been rendered a second class and as periphery to the political power. What resulted in such treatment of the Oromo in the Empire of Abyssinia-cum modern Ethiopia was the conquest of the Oromo.

The fall of the Oromo was the primary reason for the making of modern Ethiopia. The direct consequence of the defeat of the Oromo resistance against Abyssinian colonialism was the institutionalisation of Abyssinian settler colonisation in Oromia and the formation of the Empire of Abyssinia-cum modern Ethiopia. Without the conquest of the Oromo, there would have been no modern Ethiopia. In other words, modern Ethiopia was because of the Oromo. This holds today with all intents and purposes: Ethiopian federation is because Oromia is. Accordingly, the dissertation concludes that the formation of modern Ethiopia would not have been possible without the conquest of the Oromo, the single majority nation from among over seventy nations NNPs, who constitute more than one-third of both its population and the landmass, and therefore, modern Ethiopia is essentially an Oromo nation.

The Oromo are the most populous indigenous people of the Horn of Africa. Throughout history, they have inhabited the region, including northern Ethiopia. Contrary to the Abyssinian claim, their historical expansion in Ethiopia before the 16th century had been from north to south (Gidada, 2016). The assimilation of the Oromo with people of south Arabian origin in present-day northern Ethiopia might have started during the Aksumite time (100–700CE). The assimilation had continued probably during the Zagwean Dynasty after, as some Abyssinian historians claim, the Oromo “arrived” in the kingdom during the reign of Mera Tekle Haimanot in the 10th century (Haile, 2002, pp. 171–172; Gidada, 2016, pp. 53–54). The assimilation of the Oromo to the Abyssinian identity might have started at the time

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of the formation of the kingdom in the late 13th century. It is known that the Galaan and Yaayyaa Oromo, as well as the Jiddaa, Waayyuu, and Ganjii clans of Sayyoo Oromo of Qeellam, had inhabited present central Ethiopia in the 13th and 14th century (Gidada, 2016, pp. 54–64), and the former was converted to Christianity (Tamirat, 1972, cited in Gidada, 2016). Several records of the state Church of Abyssinian (for example, Gedle Tekle Haimanot, Gedle Raguel, and Fikare Iyesus) indicate the habitation of the Oromo in the present North Shewa Zones of Oromia and Amhara States in the 13th century. Indeed, at the beginning of the 16th century, most of the northern Oromo had been converted to Christianity (Reclus, 1892, p. 197).

The presence of the Oromo in Abyssinia Proper (present Amhara and Tigray states) was enhanced by the 16th-century offensive campaigns of the Oromo. During this campaign, the Oromo not only gained significant territory from the expansionist Abyssinian kingdom in the south, but also some northern Oromo communities moved farther north into the kingdom's heartland beyond the Blue Nile in the west and beyond Amara in the east. By the early 17th century, Abyssinian had no place where the northern Oromo had not "invaded" except Tigre (Tafla, 1987, p. 165). Soon, however, some Oromo north and the kingdom of Abyssinia established peaceful co-existence under the leadership of Atse Susenyos (r. 1607–1632), who was himself an adopted Oromo followed by some northern Oromo communities as their Gadaa leader (Tafla, 1987, p. 197). A century later, these northern Oromo communities could control the kingdom's political power during the so-called Zamane Masafent (1769–1855), which, in effect, was the Dynasty of the Yajjuu Oromo.

During the centuries that the Oromo interacted and intermingled with the Abyssinians in northern Ethiopia, massive assimilation of the Oromo occurred. This massive assimilation of the Oromo in Abyssinia Proper can be classified into total assimilation and cultural

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assimilation. Cultural assimilation also manifests in urban settlements across the present Oromia State, other states, and the two city governments. The total assimilation has occurred in Gojjam, Gondar, Wollo, and Tigray provinces. The scale of the complete assimilation was pervasive, particularly after 1855. Due to the total assimilation, the Oromo who once inhabited these provinces have lost the outward manifestation of their Oromummaa identity. In Gojjam, Wollo, and Southern Tigray, where the population was Oromo at some point, the outward manifested identity has become Amharan or Tigrie. Nor does the city of Gondar, which was an Oromo town “with all intents and purposes” at its height, show any significant trace of Oromo identity. Similarly, due to aggressive state-sanctioned cultural assimilation that has been going on, particularly after the late 19th century, some Oromo have become “Amhara” in Shewa (including in Addis Ababa), Arsi, Harar, and some urban settlements in many parts of Oromia. In addition, some Oromo communities have been totally or culturally assimilated in other regions of modern Ethiopia (for example, in Somali, Benishangul–Gumuz, Afar, Gambella, and the SNNP States) throughout the 19th and 20th centuries. Many districts in Amhara, Tigray, SNNP, Somali, Gambella, and Benishangul–Gumuz states have technical minority Oromo. As a result, even though the Oromo still constitute a significant part of their population (for example, they are even the majority in the case of Harari State and Dire Dawa City Government), the districts are presently not part of Oromia State. They have, however, kept their Oromo names.

The total and cultural assimilation of the Oromo to Abyssinian or non-Oromo identity had been orchestrated by the social policies of the successive kingdom governments since 1855. The subjugation of the Oromo in the late 19th century by settler colonialist Abyssinians has significantly impacted the aggravated assimilation of the Oromo to Abyssinian identity. During the imperial rule, the Oromo language and culture were banned, and the people were

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reduced to subjects. They were forced systematically to deny their Oromo identity. The social homogenisation policy of the socialist regime (1974-1991) that promoted Amhara-centred Ethiopian identity only affirmed the Abyssinian total assimilationist policy of “one nation-state” building started by Atse Menelik II.

As a result, though they are Oromo, an estimated several million people in modern Ethiopia identified as non-Oromo during the National Regional State formation in the early 1990s. Some of these Oromo have recently achieved cultural awakening, and their aspiration for Oromummaa has manifestly increased. Some Oromo who had identified as Amhara or stated Amharic as their mother tongue for purely instrumental purposes have now rectified their identity. In doing so, they have added their part to the paradox of the so-called 2.5 million “missed” Amhara or “missed” people with Amharic mother tongue in the recent national population statistics.

It is self-evident that perhaps most of the people of the present Amhara State are, in essence, descendants of assimilated Oromo. This is even more so for the people of East and West Gojjam Zones and North and South Wollo Zones. The people of these are fundamentally Oromo. Descendants of the Oromo also constitute a sizable portion of the population of North Gondar and South Gondar Zones. The Oromo Nationalities Special Zone people, negligently cut off from Oromia since the early 1990s, are officially Oromo. It is also self-evident that the people of the Southern Zone of Tigray State are Oromo. These Oromo in the two States have adopted the Abyssinian language, culture, religion, and outward identity because of many centuries of sustained total assimilation programs of the successive Atses of the kingdom of Abyssinia.

Likewise, hundreds of thousands of Oromo who now profess Abyssinian identity in urban centres across Oromia and Harar State have been the victims of relatively recent

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Abyssinian cultural assimilation. Even though it had not been as aggressive and was not backed with political power, such cultural assimilation has also masked the Oromo identity of tens of thousands of Oromo in Somali, Benishangul-Gumuz, Gambella, and SNNP States of the Ethiopian federation. Even though the Oromo themselves have ethnographically integrated some minority alien cultures into the Oromo communities in the 16th and 17th centuries, during their active offensive-defensive military campaigns, the total number of Oromo that has been assimilated to Abyssinian and other identities is incomparable to their number. The former may be estimated to be an inconsequential few hundred thousand.

The centuries of total and cultural assimilation of the Oromo in Abyssinia Proper have robbed millions of their Oromo identity (Oromummaa). They happened before the conquest of the Oromo at the end of the 19th century and during the subsequent systematic and aggressive assimilation program of the empire. The latter lasted for over a century (and has continued since the formation of the Ethiopian Federation in the early 1990s). This has heavily masked their present descendants with phoney Abyssinian, mainly Amhara, identities. Under this heavy mask, however, these millions of people have remained intrinsically Oromo. Millions of Oromo are masked with the veil of Amharic name, Tabbot Christianity, and the so-called “Habasha culture” and “Habasha dress.” Recently, some have already started to uncover the reprehensible false identity mask and come out as delighted Oromo. Thus, considering both the fully and partially assimilated Oromo in Ethiopia, it is highly likely that the Oromo constitute not one-third but more than one-half of the population of the Ethiopian Federation. In other words, modern Ethiopia is essentially Oromia, and modern Ethiopians are essentially the ancient Kush, the genuine Ethiopians.

Surely, “the Oromo, as ancient Rome, have faith in their future greatness”

(D’Abbadie, 2007 [1880], p. 134).

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Chapter 6. Conclusion: Towards New Order in East Africa

This concluding remark shall first attempt to repudiate the ill-conceived notions that (a) the Oromo are not Ethiopians, (b) secession is the best course of action for the Oromo nation, and (c) the Oromo narrative is a tripartite (Colonialist, Traditionalist, and Ethiopianist) narrative. Then, it shall present the summary of the dissertation's propositions as an argument and the new narrative that the dissertation proposes for the Oromo nation. In the end, it shall enumerate a tentative framework in the form of startup recommendations for the peaceful and democratic promotion of the Oromo nation to the political centre in modern Ethiopia in particular and to coalescing leadership of the Kushite nations in the Horn of Africa region in general.

The Ancient Kushite Ethiopianist Narrative

This dissertation adopted neither of the above narratives. Instead, it developed a new, broader narrative encompassing elements of the suggested narratives. It did so by extending further the focus of the history of the Oromo in northeast and east Africa to antiquity and by concentrating on the Kushite-Semite dichotomy of the origin of peoples of modern Ethiopia. Going further back to antiquity, to the period when the ancient Kushites, the originator of the Egyptian civilisation, ruled three continents (Houston, 1926 [2004]), helped to focus on the historical ancient empire of Kush in upper Egypt. The people of the historical ancient kingdom of Kush, who rivalled ancient Egypt and, at times, ruled united Upper and Lower Egypt, were the Kushites of northeast Africa, the true ancient Ethiopians. Being one of the indigenous nations of the region, the Oromo are undoubtedly the true ancient Ethiopians. Emphasising the emergence of the Semite peoples who formed the core of the Abyssinian identity in the first century BCE has helped to make the necessary distinction that the Semite cultural and linguistic foundation in Abyssinia Proper was the result of partial Semitization of

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the indigenous Kushite peoples because of the sustained political influence of the minority Semite core who themselves gradually adopted Kushite identities.

This distinction was necessary to build a broader narrative that would embrace Abyssinian peoples who misguidedly claim Semite descents but are only culturally and linguistically Semitized Kushites. This cultural and linguistic Semitization could be because of two factors: first, their disposition to Sabaeen culture and language through the agency of Semite peoples of southern Arabian origin who crossed from across the Red Sea and established the kingdom of Aksum around the turn of the Common Era; second, through the agency of Christianity and associated Abyssinian orientalist legend. To build a broader, unifying, and visionary narrative of the Oromo in the Horn of Africa region that can also accommodate those who claim Semite descent and have developed Habasha identity, the dissertation finds it appropriate to adopt a new narrative, which may be referred to as the ancient Kushite Ethiopianist narrative. The narrative may also be called the true Ethiopianist narrative.

The Ancient Kushite Ethiopians narrative may include all the Kushite nations in Ethiopia and the Horn of Africa. Hence, it consists of the Oromo, Agew, Bejja, Nuba, Sidama, Kembata, Hadiya, Afar, Somali, Rendille, Gato, Maasai, Erbore, Magogodo, Bayla, Konso, Kebena, Mareko, Tigreweji, Warazi, Gawada, Tsemey, Dasenech, Saho, Tembaro, Alaba, Gedeo, Burji, Bilen, Woyto, etc. In this narrative, some of these peoples (for example, Somali, Afar, Rendille, Maasai, Bejja) may be considered as a recent offshoot of the Oromo, the main stock of the Kushites. In contrast, the rest may be regarded as minority ancient Kushite nations in the narrative. Consequently, the narrative would be a socio-political and historical narrative for all the Kushite nations.

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At this junction, it is essential to note that the Abyssinians (mainly Amhara and Tigre) who confess Semite descent are neither ancient Kushites nor ancient Ethiopians. Ancient Ethiopia existed before the alleged establishment of the mythical Solomonic kingdom in modern northern Ethiopia in the 10th century BCE or before the establishment of the kingdom of Aksum by Semitic settlers from southern Arabia around the 1st century CE. The claim of the priesthood of the Christian kingdom of Abyssinia to the name Ethiopia was motivated purely by religious fantasy rather than reality. The newly emerging 21st-century myth of the common origin of the Amhara and the Oromo peoples, which some proponents of the “Ethiopianist narrative” would like everyone to entertain, is simply wishful thinking. If anything, it is an attempt to assess the waters in search of ground for promoting friendship and cooperation among the uninformed public of both sides. Modern Ethiopia, if not because of the Kushite peoples, may be considered as, as some have already suggested, “Fake Ethiopia.” More profoundly, if not because of the Kushites, such as Agew, Kimant, Oromo, Bejja, Gafat, Quara, etc., that have intermingled and integrated with the Semitic elements through the centuries-long linguistic, cultural, and religious process of the building of Habasha identity, Abyssinia Proper could be considered indeed “Fake Ethiopia.” So could be the Abyssinian-centered Ethiopian nationalism and Abyssinian Ethiopianist narrative of modern Ethiopia. In other words, Abyssinians (people in northern Ethiopia who confess Semite or oriental descent) have only become Abyssinian Ethiopians who have become the northern part of the modern Ethiopian state; they were not the ancient Ethiopians of antiquity. This, however, does not make them less or more of modern Ethiopians. The true ancient Ethiopians of antiquity are the indigenous Cushitic peoples. They are aptly the ancient Kush, the true Ethiopians. Among them, forty per cent of the Ethiopian population, more than 40 million, is Oromo.

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Main Argument Recapitulated

This dissertation has illustrated that the Oromo are the indigenous people of northeast Africa: the ancient Kush, the true ancient Ethiopians. As such, they were connected to the ancient Egyptians in many ways (in philosophy, cosmology, belief system, core culture, physical features, and language). Scholars have noted that the modern Oromo people are the best physical and racial representations of Egypt's pre-dynastic and dynastic peoples. In antiquity, the Agaw, Afar, Somali, and Beja nations were related closely to the Oromo: perhaps they all descended from the same ancestry. The ethnogenesis of the Somali people from the Oromo nation, in particular, appears to be a relatively recent phenomenon.

It has also illustrated that during their long habitation of northeast Africa, the Oromo gradually moved south in antiquity from southern Egypt to the present East Africa region. Then, some of their communities organised themselves in Gadaa-based defensive and offensive military campaigns and returned to the northerly general direction during the medieval period in the region that has now become modern Ethiopia. First, the formation of the kingdom of Aksum, then the formation of Muslim principalities and the aggressive expansion of the kingdom of Abyssinia, and finally, their quest to recover their liberty and territory guided their moves in the region in the Common Era. During this move, the Oromo not only lost a section of their population through centuries of assimilation and religious conversion to the expanding Christian and Muslim powers but also imparted their Luba leadership of the Gadaa tradition on the Semite Aksumites and the Kushite Zagwean monarchies.

Also, the dissertation recounted that by the mid-15th century, Abyssinian domination of the Oromo in present central Ethiopia, in particular, had become an existential threat, prompting the Oromo to challenge and defeat and gradually become the master of the

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kingdom of Abyssinia. They reformed their Gadaa System during the Gadaa of the fathers of Gadaa Jibbenaa (1450-1458) at Madda Walaabuu. They began their Gadaa-based offensive-defensive military campaigns against the Christian and Islamic forces. The campaign, however, gained national momentum in the early 16th century. It was neither migration nor aggressive expansion, as some might have portrayed, but a concerted effort of the Oromo to defend themselves from alien domination and progressively reclaim ancestral territories that had been taken from them over many centuries. Through this campaign, the Oromo reclaim lost territories from the Christian kingdom of Abyssinia, the Muslim kingdom of Adal, and the frontier clans of Somali people. Also, the assimilated northern and mainstream south-central Oromo were united and restored their ancient joint politico-religious centres in central modern Ethiopia. Subsequently, they further expanded in the region that has become southwestern Ethiopia. The momentum of the Oromo campaigns was slowed down and dissipated in the early 17th century when Atse Susenyos, an adopted Oromo, managed to divide the frontier northern Oromo into his opponents and supporters. Those Oromo communities, who joined the kingdom of Abyssinia despite being a minority, ruled the Abyssinia Proper effectively for many decades by establishing the “Yajju Dynasty” during Zamane Masafent. Since the mid-19th century, however, these Oromo were ousted from state power and despised as a people by consequent Abyssinian Atses and Debteras. In the following decades, Atse Menelik II conquered brutally not only the northern politically integrated Oromo but also the independent southern, eastern, and western Oromo of modern Ethiopia. This conquest was the key to the formation of modern Ethiopia. Atse Menelik II institutionalised settler colonialism in the Oromo country, the effect of which is still evident throughout Oromia in its faint form even though it was abolished in 1974.

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The dissertation argues that modern Ethiopia is an Oromo country for all intents and purposes. The Oromo have been continuously assimilated and integrated into Abyssinia Proper (modern northern Ethiopia, Amhara, and Tigray States) for centuries. Their assimilation and integration must have started during the formation of the kingdom of Aksum. Both willful and forced massive assimilation and integration of the Oromo in Abyssinia Proper during the last five decades has been a historical phenomenon. As a result, they make up almost half of the population of Amhara State in general and most of the population of some Zones of the state in particular. Millions of culturally and linguistically veiled Oromo exist in Amhara and Tigray States, Abyssinia Proper. Indeed, the same is true in contiguous neighbouring districts in other neighbourly states. In other words, modern Ethiopia is fundamentally Oromo, and Ethiopia is because Oromo are.

As such, the dissertation further argues that the Oromo cannot be, in any way, 'peripheral' to modern Ethiopia or the Horn of Africa region. They are the rightful 'centre' in every intent and purpose. They have all it takes and deserve to be the centre of modern Ethiopia culturally, economically, politically, and historically. Though misguided, Oromo elites have had no less of a share even in the building and the defence of modern Ethiopia, nor are the present generation of Oromo contributing any less of a share in any way than any other nation of the federation. The very conception of considering the single majority nation, which occupies the central geography of a nation, as the periphery makes no sense, nor does the deliberate and systematic marginalisation of the Oromo from Abyssinian history-cum-failed Ethiopian history. Also, the political position that claims the Oromo are not Ethiopians is old-fashioned and has no genuine historical ground. Incorporeality, the Oromo are true Ethiopians than Abyssinians. They have always been Ethiopians, and the Abyssinians have only become Ethiopians. The present Oromo generation must claim modern Ethiopia's

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political “centre” and fully restore the Kaawoo Oromo dream. The Oromo are the legitimate and rightful nation to do so democratically. Besides, they are duty-bound to unify and lead the Kushite nations of the Horn of Africa region. Genuine Kushite Ethiopian nationalism and Kushite Ethiopia are the future of modern Ethiopia and the Horn of Africa. In other words, the future leadership of the peoples of modern Ethiopia and the Kushites of the Horn of Africa should be in the hands of the Oromo nation, the ancient Kush, the true Ethiopians.

In summary, the central proposition of this dissertation, which is also the main argument, is the following:

- Ancient Ethiopians are indigenous Kushite peoples of northeast Africa. The single largest Kushite nation in northeast Africa is the Oromo. The Oromo nation is, therefore, ancient Ethiopia.
- The Semite Abyssinians arrived in northeast Africa from Arabia. They are not indigenous. They are not Kushites. They are not ancient Kushite Ethiopians. Most people who confess Abyssinian identities today are, however, assimilated Kushites.
- Modern Ethiopia has appropriated the ancient name of the Kushites, Ethiopia, to itself. The Oromo are the single largest Kushite nation in modern Ethiopia. The Oromo are, therefore, the proper modern Ethiopians.
- The Oromo (the ancient Kushite, the ancient Ethiopians, the proper modern Ethiopians, the true Ethiopians) must take centre stage in contemporary Ethiopia. To do so, the Oromo must revisit their historical and socio-political narratives. They must have a visionary and unifying narrative rooted in their history in northeast and east Africa. A new Oromo narrative, an ancient

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Ethiopian narrative, should serve the progression of the Oromo to the political centre and their collective leadership in modern Ethiopia.

- The Oromo should also unite all Kushite nations of the Horn of Africa. As the single largest Kushite nation in Africa, they have sociological legitimacy to represent all the Kushite peoples, all the true ancient Ethiopians.
- The Oromo have all it takes to bring about a new order in the Horn of Africa. They should take the leading role in creating and leading the political movement of the Kushite peoples, uniting all the Kushite brothers of the Horn of Africa, and rebuilding great ancient Ethiopia as a commonwealth of the peoples of East Africa.

Political Blueprinting: Recommendations for Democratic Renewal

The following are tentative recommendations for the peaceful and democratic promotion of the Oromo to modern Ethiopia's political centre and the Kushite peoples' leadership in the Horn of Africa. The recommendations are informed by the precedents of the political history of the Oromo nation in the region, as discussed above.

Uphold True Ancient Ethiopia and Abandon Periphery Politics

This dissertation concluded that the Oromo are genuine ancient Ethiopians. It also has illustrated how the Oromo have given up on their rightful true Ethiopia-ness and veered to the political periphery in modern Ethiopia. The Abyssinians, who only have become Ethiopians, have appropriated the ancient name of the Kushite of the Horn of Africa to themselves. They have positioned themselves as the "historical" Ethiopians through their political and religious propaganda. Furthermore, using the opportunity of their total domination since the formation of modern Ethiopia in the last decades of the 19th century, they have succeeded, at least until recently, in demoting the true ancient Ethiopian nations to second-class citizenship. Instead of

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reclaiming what rightfully belongs to them, the Oromo have also enabled and allowed the Abyssinians to continue to portray them as strangers and second-class citizens, as less of Ethiopians and more of newcomers or strangers. This has resulted in the Oromo's social, cultural, and political marginalisation in modern Ethiopia. Most importantly, the Oromo have been consistently marginalised from the political centre, where they are the true ancient Ethiopians. To make matters worse, some Oromo scholars and politicians have fallen into this Abyssinian entrap and have been promoting the strange claim that the Oromo are not Ethiopians and the spurious idea that secession is the only best course of action for the Oromo of modern Ethiopia. This might have led to the proposition of some ill-conceived and divisive narratives for the Oromo. The dissertation hypothesises that the Oromo themselves have enabled the Abyssinians to marginalise them politically, historically, socially, and linguistically. This is because they have failed to assert that they are the true ancient Ethiopians, who constitute not only the majority in modern Ethiopia but also the legitimate nation to take the central political leadership of the country peacefully and democratically.

Compose the Official Socio-Political History of the Oromo Nation.

The failed "Ethiopian History" hardly represents the history of the Oromo. Every entry that mentions Oromo in this "history" is more distortion than representation. The comprehensive socio-political history of the Oromo nation has not been composed. It is high time to write the official social and political history of the Oromo nation. This involves a comprehensive review of the extant records on the Oromo nation's political history and social transformations and transcribing the rich Oromo oral history, *argaa-dhageettii*. The undertaking should be a national project, and every scholar in the relevant fields should be invited. The outcome would be an authoritative and comprehensive socio-political history of the Oromo.

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Reform and Promote the Gadaa System as the System of Constitutional Model of Ancient Kush, the True Ethiopia.

Gadaa System, the Oromo democracy, and the UNESCO intangible heritage of humanity have far-reaching benefits to the Oromo in particular and the Kushite people of the Horn of Africa in general. It is the measure of the advances of the Oromo socio-political sophistication. It, however, should be reformed, strengthened, and further standardised. The Oromo have learned a great lesson from the excessive decentralisation and gradual weakening of their Gadaa government. The compunction of abandoning or neglecting the Gadaa System runs deep in the blood of every informed Oromo. However, the Gadaa System must be addressed by the federal and state governments in Ethiopia and allowed to implode gradually. This must not continue. It is high time to deepen reform and systemically preserve the Gadaa System. The reform should aim at making Gadaa System the practicable form of Government for Oromia in the short run, that of modern Ethiopia in the medium run, and that of the Horn of Africa region in the end.

The reform should include:

- (1) Promoting and codifying the Gadaa Constitution
- (2) Establishing a national Gadaa Center in Addis Ababa, regional Gadaa Centers in the capitals of each Zone, and municipal Gadaa centres in all major cities and towns of Oromia
- (3) Instituting a geographical moiety system throughout Oromia and associating contiguous nations with the Oromo through the co-formation of a dual moiety system
- (4) Instituting Gadaa System as one of the higher learning fields of study and promoting the universal research of Gadaa laws

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- (5) Reinstating the age-set system as rigorous and highly disciplined physical training and self-defence system, including in the army training.
- (6) Translating key literature on the Gadaa System to major local and international languages and promoting Gadaa democracy as the heritage of humanity
- (7) Reinstating and strengthening the age-set system, the Foollee, the regional Bokkuus, the Jilaa, and Muudaa
- (8) Developing standard references and guidebooks on Gadaa System

Promote Kaawoo as “Oromo Dream”, Vision of National Renewal

Kaawoo is one of the complex concepts of Oromo philosophy. With simplification, this study has defined it as a purposeful, dignified, peaceful, and happy life and living. It has also been described as the Oromo Dream. As such, Kaawoo shares elements with the famous American Dream. Others have associated it strongly with prosperity and peace. At the national level, it measures the national pride and glory of the Oromo nation. At a personal level, it is the measure of personal glory, dignity, freedom, sense of fulfilment, and satisfaction of an Oromo person. Achieving it has always been the dream of every Oromo. It, however, needs to be revived, promoted, and institutionalised as the “Oromo Dream” that could serve as the “Kushite Dream” and, perhaps, ultimately, as the “African Dream.”

Promote the Ancient Ethiopian narrative as the Narrative of the Oromo Nation but Inclusive of all the Kushite nations of the Horn of Africa.

As a nation, the Oromo ought to have a visionary and broad socio-political and historical narrative. The ancient Kushite Ethiopianist narrative that this dissertation proposes would serve this purpose. It is founded on the phronesis that the Oromo are the largest Kushite nations; hence, the modern representation of the ancient Kush, the genuine ancient

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Ethiopians, and the political history of the Oromo nation in northeast and east Africa. The effectiveness of the narrative may depend on how and how much the Oromo promotes it.

The promotion should include the following assertions and claims:

- (1) The Kushites are the genuine ancient Ethiopians
- (2) The Oromo are the ancient Ethiopians
- (3) Modern Ethiopia is because the Oromo are and modern Ethiopia is essentially Oromia,
- (4) The Oromo are the legitimate sociological representative of the Kushites of the Horn of Africa, the ancient Ethiopians
- (5) The Oromo are well-prepared and well-positioned to unite and lead both the Kushite and non-Kushite nations of the Horn of Africa

The promotion should be intensive, and Oromo scholars, the media, schoolteachers, politicians, and relevant state bodies should instil the narrative among the Oromo and other nations of the Horn of Africa.

Engage and Unite Kushite Peoples

The Oromo should reorient their political views towards unifying and leading the Kushite peoples of the Horn of Africa. In other words, they should take leadership responsibilities for the Kushites of Ethiopia and the rest of the continent of Africa. Such engagements should emphasise that the Oromo nation, as the largest Kushite nation, is the legitimate social leader of the Kushite nations and the key to the peace and stability of the Horn of Africa region. In addition, the Oromo must build good people-to-people relationships in modern Ethiopia with Abyssinians who are pretentious that they are Semite and with the minority non-Kushite Ethiopians. At the same time, they must ensure the rights of minorities in Oromia and throughout Ethiopia. Enforcement of the Constitution is invaluable to do so.

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Similarly, outside of modern Ethiopia, they must build good people-to-people relationships with Kushites and with other peoples in the East Africa region. This requires that brotherhood between the Oromo and the Sidama, Guragie, Hadiya, Agew, etc. in Ethiopia, the Somali people of both Ethiopia, Somalia, and Djibouti, the Afar people of Ethiopia, Djibouti, and Eritrea, the Kushites peoples of Sudan and South Sudan, and their descendants in Great Lakes region (in Kenya, Uganda, Rwanda, and northern Tanzania) must be further strengthened. This could be done through (a) people-to-people diplomacy, (b) institutionalisation of diplomacy by the establishment of, for example, the Institute of Kushite Studies, and (c) the formation of a confederation of the Kushite nations that could be transformed, in the end, into a federation of the nations.

Promote Key Oromo Heritages and Values as Remnants of the Heritages and Values of the Ancient Kushites

The Oromo have exceedingly rich socio-political and cultural values. Nevertheless, they have yet to be well known in Ethiopia and abroad. The Oromo have many heritages that should become the heritage of humanity, just like the Gadaa System. Among others, the Oromo should:

1. Promote the ilaa-fi-ilaamee philosophical thinking and the principles of the Gadaa System,
2. Promote the Gadaa System as the heritage of all Kushite peoples.
3. Relate Nagaa, Finna, and Kaawoo as a holistic socio-economic system
4. (d)Recognize and institutionalise Waaqeffannaa as the ancient universal religion of humanity, the religion of ancient Kush, and the present religion of the Oromo nation

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5. Revive the Moggaasaa system of ethnographical and social integration of minorities and promote the modernised institution of Meedhachaa and Kooluu
6. Reinstatement of the Oromo Equestrian Fellowship
7. Institute Oromo national holidays (Irreechaa, Mijuu, Addooyyee, Shinoyyee, Ukee, Taboree, Jila, Muudaa, Baallii, Gubaa, etc.)
8. Institutionalize a regular promotion of Oromo culture (customs, language, art, music, etc.) in Finfinnee (Addis Ababa)
9. Work extensively on registration of more Oromo natural, cultural, social, political, and spiritual heritages at UNESCO as a representative of the Kushite nations.

Winning the Political Centre in Ethiopia

The Oromo must exploit their majority in the Ethiopian Federation and the ruling party to advance their interest and that of the other NNPs of modern Ethiopia. In the history of modern Ethiopia, the Oromo have wasted the political advantage of being the majority several times. It must not be wasted anymore. Every Oromo must start to demand a fairer distribution of federal authority. The OPDO also must demand what is due to the Oromo people through its majority representatives in both houses of the Ethiopian federation. The leadership of the OPDO also must start to stand against the TPLF dictatorship and, if possible, implode EPRDF, aiming for new alignment within it that would allow unreserved promotion of the tenets of the Oromo nation. Young and well-educated members of OPDO must take the lead and start to organise the public, particularly the youth, for the rightful demands of the Oromo to take the political centre. Political leaders and legal scholars also must exploit the Constitutional provisions that would allow a peaceful and democratic rise of the Oromo to the political centre. The Oromo politicians, both in the government and in

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opposition, must be ready to exploit any change in the EPRDF, political or ideological, primarily to the benefit of the Oromo nation and Oromia in its quest to take centre stage for the good of all the NNPs of Ethiopia. No opportunity should be wasted, including costly ones, if the greater good is greater than the cost.

The preparation should include:

- (1) Renewing Kakuu Oromoo in a Grand National Ceremony and institutionalizing it
- (2) Uniting all the Oromo political parties under a single national political program and vision
- (3) Increasing grassroots political participation in Oromia
- (4) Encouraging Oromo scholars to join politics, accept political positions, and lead political institutions
- (5) Supporting interested Oromo in higher learning in the areas of political economy, international relations and diplomacy, and governance
- (6) Training social and political leaders in large numbers
- (7) Introducing reformed civic education in primary and secondary schools
- (8) Introducing affirmative sectorial economic policies and action in Oromia that would support and strengthen the economic participation of the Oromo and boost their influence in the economy of Oromia and the federation
- (9) Reforming school curriculum for all relevant lessons at all levels of schools

Take Symbolic Actions that Associate the Oromo with the Political Centre in

Modern Ethiopia

Mandated visibility, standing representations, and public symbolism are associated with the political centre. The Oromo are far behind in this regard. They must take fundamental, emblematic actions. This may include, but is not limited to,

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- (a) engaging in extensive public relations works to make Afaan Oromo the co-working language of the federal government,
- (b) promoting the naming of the Federal Parliament as Caffee,
- (c) promoting imprinting of Odaa or Abbaa Gadaa on some of the national currency notes and coins,
- (d) restructuring and renaming the Zones and districts of Oromia after the predominant Oromo lineages that inhabit it,
- (e) legislating 'Finfinnee' as the official alternate co-name of Addis Ababa,
- (f) reinstating the old Oromo names of the districts and outlets (karra) of Finfinnee,
- (g) building landmark Oromo national monuments on higher grounds in Finfinnee (for example, city towers in the shape of decorated Horooroo and Siiqqee) and encouraging every major city in the country to have some landmarks named after Gadaa system, the cultural heritage of the country,
- (h) naming and renaming some of the streets, squares, train stations, airports, public buildings, public parks, convention centres, community centres, landmarks, etc., of significant cities in Oromia (including Finfinnee) after 'forgotten' Oromo heroes, historic Abbaa Gadaas, and sentimental Oromo values such as safuu, nagaa, araara, qixxee, birmaduu, etc. and encouraging and sponsoring other cities across the country to do so,
- (i) installing modern, standardized, and decorated monuments of Gadaa, Horooroo, Siiqqee, etc., in every city centre, major parks, and community centres of the cities in Oromia and naming the main squares and streets of the cities as suggested above under (h), and

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- (j) encouraging builders and high-rise building owners in Oromia and across the country to include aesthetic values connected to the Oromo culture and consider naming it after the Oromo name of the area or any sentimental Oromo names.

Take Indomitable Initiatives to Organize and Unite the Kushite Peoples of the Horn of Africa

First, take the initiative to organise consultative conferences of the Kushite peoples of Ethiopia. Engaging these nations' apolitical elders and traditional leaders in the first round may help promote people-to-people relations. The next step could be committing the nations' scholars who might design a program of continued engagement and framework of cooperation. The central and guiding issue for political engagement could be the idea of ancient Kushites and authentic ancient Ethiopia.

Second, take the initiative to organise such consultative and cooperative conferences of the Kushite peoples of the Horn of Africa region. In addition to the central guiding issue mentioned above, peacebuilding and development cooperation could be added. The experiences from the conferences of the Ethiopian Kushites could be shared with the Kushites of the neighbouring nations. Thus, a united and concerted political movement of the Kushite peoples of the Horn of Africa may begin; with it, the renaissance of Kush, the true ancient Ethiopia, may dawn. Scholars and experts may develop policies and plan for such engagements in consultation with the traditional leaders of the respective peoples.

Third, take the initiative to institutionalise such engagements in such a way that it would lead progressively to the formation of Greater Ethiopia of the ancient Kushite nations of the Horn of Africa. This may take the form of a cultural commonwealth, the cultural commonwealth of Kushite nations. The glorious Ancient Kush may be restored with it. The commonwealth may also incubate a genuine union of African nations that could ultimately

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save the continent from the new East-West ravenousness scramble for its resources and potential.

Policy and Scholarly Implications

- The dissertation demonstrates that indigenous constitutional systems such as Gadaa offer viable institutional templates for governance reform in Africa, particularly in federal design, decentralised authority, and mechanisms of political accountability rooted in local legitimacy rather than administrative coercion.
- By reintroducing indigenous republican governance into institutional political economy, the dissertation challenges prevailing development models that equate institutional quality with externally derived state forms, and instead foregrounds historical continuity, endogenous legitimacy, and distributive balance as determinants of institutional stability.
- The findings invite a reorientation of African governance debates away from technocratic reform and toward historically grounded institutional reconstruction, with implications for state-building, conflict regulation, and equitable resource governance across postcolonial African polities.

Final Reflection

This dissertation makes original contributions in the form of historical rectification, reconceptualisation, sociological realignment, political blueprint, and epistemic decolonisation. It exposes the constructed nature of “Ethiopian history” as an Abyssinian-centred political project and advances the Ancient Kushite Ethiopianist Narrative as a new and unifying historiographical paradigm. By interpreting the Gadaa system as a fully fledged deliberative republican polity, the dissertation demonstrates that Oromo constitutional thought and practice not only predate but also exceed in complexity and inclusivity the early

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formations of Western constitutionalism. Ethiopia is thereby reclaimed as Cushitic in its civilizational foundations, while the Oromo are repositioned from the political periphery to the rightful center of the Ethiopian polity. In doing so, the dissertation articulates a model for Oromo-led democratic federalism within Ethiopia and extends this vision towards a Kushite commonwealth across East Africa. It models a decolonial methodology for historiography itself, showing that the recovery of marginalized indigenous narratives can provide normative resources for postcolonial statecraft. Collectively, these interventions fill a critical lacuna in both Ethiopian Studies and African political thought.

The analysis has dismantled the distortions embedded in Ethiopian historiography and restored the Oromo as the true ancient Ethiopians. The dominant Abyssinian narrative, by claiming Ethiopia as its exclusive inheritance, relegated the Oromo to the status of latecomers or outsiders. Constructed through conquest, selective memory, and epistemic violence, this narrative systematically obscured the cultural, political, and philosophical depth of the Oromo nation. By confronting these myths and recovering the republican ethos embedded in Gadaa, the transcendental vision of Kaawoo, and the monotheistic foundations of Waaqeffannaa, this dissertation has restored the memory and dignity of the Oromo nation. The Oromo are not marginal actors but the first nation of Ethiopia: the custodians of its name, the authors of its republican institutions, and the guardians of its deepest

In advancing the New Oromo Ethiopian Approach, this dissertation has rejected the false binary that Oromo identity must either dissolve into Abyssinian nationalism or retreat into secessionist detachment. Instead, it has argued for reclamation: Ethiopia must be repossessed as a Kushite inheritance and reconstituted as a modern, pluralist, and republican project. This reclamation is not an exercise in nostalgia but a strategic reorientation of the Ethiopian state towards its most enduring foundations. Ethiopia can only achieve viability

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when its political center is restored to the Oromo; absent this, the polity remains condemned to recurrent crises of legitimacy and cohesion.

The broader significance of this work lies in its projection beyond Ethiopia. By recovering the Oromo as ancient Ethiopians and exposing the colonial foundations of Abyssinian rule, the dissertation opens intellectual and political space for a more inclusive East African order. The Oromo struggle is not only about correcting a miswritten history; it is about charting a future where democratic pluralism, indigenous republicanism, and cultural integrity constitute the principles of statehood. The Oromo heritage, embodied in Gadaa, Kaawoo, and Waaqeffannaa, offers a normative vocabulary for re-founding Ethiopia and re-imagining a Kushite commonwealth across the Horn of Africa.

The task, however, remains unfinished. The entrenched distortions of history continue to exert power, and the forces invested in their perpetuation remain formidable. Yet by reclaiming the Oromo narrative and repositioning it at the center of Ethiopian and regional politics, this work signals the possibility of renewal. The survival of Ethiopia as more than a fragile empire depends upon rediscovering its Oromo foundations. The flourishing of the Oromo as a nation depends upon embracing their role not as periphery but as Ethiopia's

The challenge ahead is clear: to transform historical recovery into political praxis, to turn memory into emancipatory power, and to rebuild Ethiopia upon its oldest and most resilient ground—the republican ethos of the Oromo and the civilizational ethics of the Kushites.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Transliteration

In this work, it was necessary to use Oromo names and words in their Oromo transliteration in *qubee*. In addition, it was necessary to transliterate Oromo words from English or Amharic into *Afaan Oromoo* using *qubee* (Alphabets of the Oromo language). Furthermore, key Oromo words and phrases and common Oromo expressions that do not have direct equivalences in English in the given context are given in *Qubee*. Similarly, important Amharic words and phrases are also employed as are with introductions. These Oromo and Amharic words and phrases are included in the glossary. These names, words, or phrases are given in italic for distinction.

The following basic information about the *qubee* and their respective phonemes may help better understanding.

- *Afaan Oromoo* has ten vowels. They are divided into five short and five long phonemes that are represented by single and double vowels, respectively. However, the latter group is not considered as an independent *qubee* but as an elongated phoneme of the first.
- In *Afaan Oromoo*, geminate consonant phonemes are represented by doubling the *qubee*. Both, length of the vowel phonemes and geminate of the phonemes determine meanings. For example, the word *aadaa* (culture) and *adda* (forehead; unique; different; and front) give very different meanings because of long vowel phoneme in the former and geminate of the consonant in the latter.
- *Afaan Oromoo* has six digraph phonemes, which are represented by paired *qubee*. They are *ch* [tʃ] (palatal, affricate), *ny* [ɲ] (palatal, nasal), *ph* [pʰ] (bilabial, ejective),

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sh [ʃ] (palatal, fricative), and *dh* [ɖ] (alveolar, implosive). The last is uniquely Oromo. In geminate diagraphs, the first *qubee* is repeated.

- *Afaan Oromoo* also has three consonantal phonemes that differ from their English version. These are *c* [tʃʼ] (palatal, affricate), *q* [kʼ] (velar) and *x* [tʼ] (alveolar).
- In addition, *Afaan Oromoo* has a symbolic separator (equivalent to tilde, glottal stop) represented by [ʔ] and named *hudhaa* [hʊɖɑː]. It is used only in writings to separate consecutive vowel phonemes. It is, however, not considered officially as one of the *qubee*.

Table 6 presents the *qubee* and their respective phonemes with reference to International Phonetic Alphabet (IPA).

Table 6: Oromo Alphabets (Qubee), Phonemes and English Examples

Vowels (<i>Dubbachiiftuu</i>)													
A	aa	E	ee	I	ii	O	oo	U	uu				
[ə]	[ɑː]	[ɛ]	[eː]	[ɪ]	[iː]	[ɔ]	[oː]	[ʊ]	[uː]				
<i>sum</i>	<i>dam</i>	<i>exam</i>	<i>agent</i>	<i>if</i>	<i>teeth</i>	<i>offer</i>	<i>boring</i>	<i>suit</i>	<i>moon</i>				
Consonants (<i>Dubbifamaa</i>)													
B	C	Ch	D	D	F	G	H	J	K	L	M	N	Ny
[b]	[tʃʼ]	[tʃ]	[d]	[ɖ]	[f]	[g]	[h]	[ɕ]	[k]	[l]	[m]	[n]	[ŋ]
<i>bag</i>	Close to very hard <i>ch</i>	<i>church</i>	<i>dam</i>	hollowed and implosive <i>d</i>	<i>fact</i>	<i>God</i>	<i>happy</i>	<i>judge</i>	<i>can</i>	<i>lamp</i>	<i>man</i>	<i>now</i>	Like Italian <i>signore</i>
P	Ph	Q	R	S	Sh	T	V	W	X	Y	Z	‘	
[p]	[pʼ]	[k]	[r]	[s]	[ʃ]	[t]	[v]	[w]	[tʼ]	[j]	[z]	[ʔ]	
<i>purpose</i>	Very hard and explosive <i>p</i>	Like very hard <i>k</i> in <i>Qur’an</i>	<i>rust</i>	<i>sand</i>	<i>sharp</i>	<i>taxi</i>	<i>virus</i>	<i>wax</i>	Very hard but dental <i>t</i>	<i>Europe</i>	<i>zap</i>	Like glottal stop in <i>Qur’an</i>	

Note: Adapted from <http://www.omniglot.com/writing/oromo.htm>

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Appendix B: Glossary of Oromo Words and Phrases

Aadaa [a:da:] — customs, tradition, and culture

Abbaa Alangaa [ɛbba:ɛlɛŋga:] — prosecutor general.

Abbaa Bokkuu [ɛbba:bɔkku:] — elected non-executive head of state, president.

Abbaa Dubbii [ɛbba:dubbi:] — speaker of the assembly or council.

Abbaa Duulaa [ɛbba:du:la:] — commander in chief of the army.

Abbaa Gadaa [ɛbba:gɛda:] — an elected executive of the Gadaa government; head of the Gadaa government at local, regional or pan-Oromo level; sometimes, it refers to all men in Gadaa Stage (*Luba*).

Abbaa Seeraa [ɛbba:se:ra:] — chief Justice, Justice.

Abbaa Muudaa [ɛbba:mu:da:] — Head of the Oromo spiritual institution, leader of the *Qaalluu*.

Argaa-dahgeetti [ɛrga:-ɖɛge:tti:] — Oromo oral literature; ‘what has been seen and heard.’

Ayyaana [ɛjja:nɛ] — an abstract particle of *Waaqa*.

Baallii [ba:lli:] — insignia of power in the form of the best of ostrich tail feather, a token symbol of authority of the Gadaa government.

Baarentuu [ba:rɛntu:] — one of the junior Oromo main sub-moieties.

Birmadummaa [bɪrmɛdʊmma:] — *liberty*; sovereignty

Booranaa [bo:rɛna:] — one of the senior Oromo sub-moieties.

Buttaa [bʊtta:] — a ceremony that precedes power transfer.

Caffee [tʃɛffe:] — the Oromo national Assembly of the multitude; Oromo legislature.

Gaadii [ga:di:] — Oromo Guerrilla warfare of the 16th century.

Gabbaroo [gɛbbɛro:] — captives, those who have submitted; non-slave aliens with limited political rights; the other half of the *Booranaa-Gabbaroo* dual moieties of Southwestern Oromo.

Gadaa [gɛda:] — sixth stage of the Gadaa grades; republican democracy; a form of government; etc.

Galaa [gɛla:] — (a) food provision (subsistence) for a military campaign or for travel in old days; (b) returnee; (c) a deserter, someone who takes refuge as dependent in somebody’s home, family, clan, or country.

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Gogeessa [gɔge:ssɐ]/*Miseensa* [mise:nsɐ] — membership to the Gadaa (party) of one's father by birth; Gadaa party.

Gosa [gɔsɐ] — tribe or clan; ethnic group.

Guddifachaa [gʊddɪfɛʃa:] — the adoption of persons.

Hayyuu [hɛjju:] — scholar, expert, wise, erudite, enlightened; judges.

Heera [he:rɐ] — Oromo constitution.

Hiriyaa [hɪrɪja:] — Oromo age-set membership group.

Ilaa-fi-ilaamee [ɪla:-fi:-ɪla:me:] — facts-and-premises.

Ilmaan gosaa [ɪlma:n g ɔsa:] — sons of the tribe or the clan.

Irreecha [ɪrre:ʃɐ] — Oromo thanksgiving.

Kaawoo [ka:wo:] — purposeful, dignified, peaceful, and happy life and living; 'prosperity and peace.'

Luba [lʊbɐ] — the sixth grade of Gadaa System; genealogical generation of Gadaa; all Oromo in Gadaa grade, or all the Oromo between age 44 and 52 and in power in a staggered succession if an ideally right born son.

Maccaa [mɛttʃa:] — the senior sub-moiety of the *Booranaa*.

Moggaaasa [mɔgga:sɐ] — voluntary ethnographic integration of aliens into the Oromo nation.

Mootii [mo:ti:] — Oromo monarchy.

Odaa [ɔda:] — a giant Sycamore tree; a consecrated assembly place of Oromo legislature.

Ormaa [ɔrma:] — an individual, a group, or a nation that has become distinct and free by becoming independent by its own initiative; those who rose to independence.

Oromummaa [ɔrɔm ʊmma:] — the deep state of Oromo identity.

Qaalluu [k'a:llu:] — Oromo spiritual and ritual leader.

Qixxee [k'ɪtt'e:] —equality (of humanity).

Qondaala [k'ɔnda:lɐ] — the third stage of the Gadaa grades.

Safuu [sɛfu:] — Oromo moral economy; an applied philosophy of all-inclusive ethics.

Seera [se:ra:] — Laws (both natural and man-made).

Tuulamaa [tu:lɛma:] — junior sub-moiety of the *Booranaa*, the dual moiety of *Maccaa*.

Uumaa [u:ma:] — creation or creator.

Waaqa [wa:k'ɐ] — God of the Oromo, ultimate Divinity.

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Waaqeffataa [wa:k'effeta:] — “Child” of *Waaqa*; Obedient of *Waaqa*.

Walaabuu [wɛla:bu:] — primordial substance; the origin of life; sovereign/free; geographical place in southern Ethiopia.

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Appendix C: Glossary of Amharic Words and Phrases

Abun [a:bu:n] — *Archbishop*

Atse [a:tse:] — emperor, “king of kings.”

Dabtara [dɛbtɛra:] — itinerant cantors of the Abyssinian Church who are involved in divination, exorcism, “healing” and literary work.

Dajazmach [dɛdʒa:zma:tʃ] — senior general; an immediate subordinate of a *Ras* or a *Nigus*

Etege [ite:ge:] — Empress; Queen.

Habasha [Ha:bɛʃa:]— Semitic language speaking peoples (mainly Amhara and Tigre) of northern Ethiopia; former Abyssinia Proper, present Amhara, Tigray states, and southern Eritrea.

Fetha Nagast [fɛta:nɛgɛst] — literally, justice of kings; an adapted compilation of temporal and spiritual laws of the kingdom of Abyssinia.

Gabbar [gɛbba:r] — tenant in the conquered regions who paid taxes and tributes to the *nafxanyaa* and the state; semi-slave non-Abyssinians.

Kebra Nagast [kɪbrɛ nɛgɛst] — literally, Glory of Kings; an adapted Abyssinian book of collection of myth and legends on the origin of the kingdom of Abyssinia (Ethiopia) and its kings.

Mekwanenet [mɛkɯwa:nɛnt] — “ruling junta of *Rases*,” governing warlords.

Nafxanyaa [nɛft'ɛna:] — settler soldiers; colonists.

Nigus [nɪgu:s] — king; semi-independent governor; immediate subordinate of *Atse*.

Ras [ra:s] — the highest order of non-imperial title in Abyssinian kingdom; field marshal; immediate subordinate of a king or an emperor.

Rist [rɪst] — property, inherited or endowed by the imperial order, an inherited land.

Zamane Mesafent [zɛmɛnɛ mɛsa:fɪnt] — ‘Era of Princes;’ the *Yajjuu* Oromo Dynasty.

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